

Creative Magic Squares: Single Digit Representations

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Abstract

*This paper brings traditional magic squares of orders 3 to 10 in terms of **single digit**. In this case, the magic squares are written separately for each digit, i.e., for the digits 1 to 9. This has been done for all the orders 3 to 10. In case of orders 8 and 9 there are two possibilities, i.e, one as normal magic squares and another as **bimagic** squares. In case of magic square of order 10, two different ways are written. One as a general magic square without any block. Another as **block-bordered** magic squares with inner magic square of order 8. Again the inner magic square can be written in two ways, i.e., one just **pandiagonal** and another **pandiagonal** and **bimagic**. In case of **single digit** the representations of numbers are not uniform. Writing in terms of single letter "a" we can get uniformity in representations of numbers. It is done in another work [7].*

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1 Introduction

In recent works [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6], the author worked with **single digit** representations of natural numbers. See below few examples.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{717} &:= (1 + 1)^{11} - 11^{(1+1+1)} \\ &:= 22^2 + 222 + 22/2 \\ &:= 3^{(3+3)} - 3 - 3 \times 3 \\ &:= 4 \times (4 \times 44 + 4) - 4 + 4/4 \\ &:= (55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5 + 5)/5 \\ &:= (6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6 - 6 - 6 \\ &:= 777 - 7 \times 7 - 77/7 \\ &:= 8 \times 88 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8 \\ &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{786} &:= ((1 + 1 + 1)^{(1+1+1)} + 1)^{(1+1)} + 1 + 1 \\ &:= (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2 \\ &:= 33 \times (3^3 - 3) - 3 - 3 \\ &:= 4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4) + 4) + (4 + 4)/4 \\ &:= 5 + (5^5 - 5/5)/(5 - 5/5) \\ &:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - 6 \\ &:= 777 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 \times (88 + 8) + 8 + (88 - 8)/8 \\ &:= 9 \times 99 - 99 - 9 + (9 + 9 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{995} &:= (11 - 1)^{(1+1+1)} - (11 - 1)/(1 + 1) \\ &:= 22 + 2 \times (22^2 + 2) + 2/2 \\ &:= 3 \times 333 - 3 - 3/3 \\ &:= 4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4) + 4 - 4/4 \\ &:= 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 \\ &:= 666 + 6 \times 66 - 66 - 6/6 \\ &:= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 + 7 + 7/7 \\ &:= 888 + 88 + 8 + 88/8 \\ &:= 999 - (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)/9. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1000} &:= (11 - 1)^{(1+1+1)} \\ &:= 2 \times (22^2 + 2^{(2+2)}) \\ &:= (3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3 \\ &:= 4 \times (4^4 - 4) - 4 - 4 \\ &:= 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\ &:= ((66 - 6)/6)^{(6 \times 6/(6+6))} \\ &:= (7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7) \times (7 \times 7 + 7/7) \\ &:= 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 \\ &:= 999 + 9/9. \end{aligned}$$

The first work up to 1000 natural numbers is done by author in 2015 [1]. For its extension to 20000 in four parts refer Taneja [2, 3, 4, 5]. The whole work is up to 1.000.000 (.txt file). For some patterned work refer Taneja [6].

2 Single Digits Magic Squares

In recent works [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14], the author worked with **magic squares**. These works include **block-wise** and **block-bordered** magic square from order 3 to 47. Summarized work on magic square can be seen in [15]. Below are basic magic squares of orders 3 to 10, and their representations for the single digit representations.

2.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Example 1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 3 is given by*

			15
8	1	6	15
3	5	7	15
4	9	2	15
15	15	15	15

The 9 magic squares given below represents the same magic square given in Example 1, but of them is written with single digits:

Example 2. *According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 3 given in Example 1 in terms of single digit 1:*

$(1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$	1	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
1 + 1 + 1	1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1	1 + $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
1 + 1 + 1 + 1	11 - 1 - 1	1 + 1

Example 3. *According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 3 given in Example 1 in terms of single digit 2:*

$2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2/2$	$2 + 2 + 2$
$2 + 2/2$	$2 + 2/2 + 2$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$
$2 + 2$	$(2/2 + 2)^2$	2

Example 4. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 3 given in Example 1 in terms of single digit 3:

$3 \times 3 - 3/3$	$3/3$	$3 + 3$
3	$3 + 3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 3/3$
$3 + 3/3$	3×3	$3 - 3/3$

Example 5. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 3 given in Example 1 in terms of single digit 4:

$4 + 4$	$4/4$	$4 + (4 + 4)/4$
$4 - 4/4$	$4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 - 4/4$
4	$4 + 4 + 4/4$	$(4 + 4)/4$

Example 6. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 3 given in Example 1 in terms of single digit 5:

$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5/5$	$5 + 5/5$
$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	5	$5 + (5 + 5)/5$
$5 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5$	$(5 + 5)/5$

Example 7. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 3 given in Example 1 in terms of single digit 6:

$6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6/6$	6
$6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 - 6/6$	$6 + 6/6$
$6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$(6 + 6)/6$

Example 8. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 3 given in Example 1 in terms of single digit 7:

$7 + 7/7$	$7/7$	$7 - 7/7$
$(7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 - (7 + 7)/7$	7
$77/7 - 7$	$7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$(7 + 7)/7$

Example 9. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 3 given in Example 1 in terms of single digit 8:

8	$8/8$	$8 - (8 + 8)/8$
$88/8 - 8$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$	$8 - 8/8$
$8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + 8/8$	$(8 + 8)/8$

Example 10. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 3 given in Example 1 in terms of single digit 9:

$9 - 9/9$	$9/9$	$9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$
$(9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 - (9 + 9)/9$
$(9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	9	$(9 + 9)/9$

The magic sum of 9 Examples 2–10 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{S}_{3 \times 3} &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 = 2 + 2 + 22/2 = 3 + 3 + 3 \times 3 \\
 &:= 4 + 44/4 &= 5 + 5 + 5 &= 6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6) \\
 &:= 7 + 7 + 7/7 &= 8 + 8 - 8/8 &= 9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 1. Using the values given in Appendix 4, write the following magic square of order 3 in single digits 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9:

			66
21	33	12	66
13	22	31	66
32	11	23	66
66	66	66	66

2.2 Magic Square of Order 4

Example 11. According to values given Appendix 4, let's consider a **pan magic square** of order 4.

		34	34	34	34
	7	12	1	14	34
34	2	13	8	11	34
34	16	3	10	5	34
34	9	6	15	4	34
	34	34	34	34	34

Example 12. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 4 given in Example 11 in terms of single digit 1:

$1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$1 + 11$	1	$1 + 1 + 1 + 11$
$1 + 1$	$1 + 1 + 11$	$(1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$	11
$(1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$1 + 1 + 1$	$11 - 1$	$1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1$
$11 - 1 - 1$	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11$	$1 + 1 + 1 + 1$

Example 13. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 4 given in Example 11 in terms of single digit 2:

$2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$	$2/2$	$2^{2+2} - 2$
2	$2 + 22/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2)$	$22/2$
2^{2+2}	$2 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 + 2/2 + 2$
$(2/2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2 + 2$	$2 + 2 + 22/2$	$2 + 2$

Example 14. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 4 given in Example 11 in terms of single digit 3:

$3 + 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3$	$3/3$	$3 + 33/3$
$3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3 - 3/3$	$33/3$
$3^3 - 33/3$	3	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 - 3/3$
3×3	$3 + 3$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 + 3/3$

Example 15. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 4 given in Example 11 in terms of single digit 4:

$4 + 4 - 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4$	$4/4$	$4 + (44 - 4)/4$
$(4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$	$4 + 4$	$44/4$
4×4	$4 - 4/4$	$(44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4/4$
$4 + 4 + 4/4$	$4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 44/4$	4

Example 16. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 4 given in Example 11 in terms of single digit 5:

$5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$(55 + 5)/5$	$5/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$
$(5 + 5)/5$	$(55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55/5$
$5 + 55/5$	$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5$	5
$5 + 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5$	$5 - 5/5$

Example 17. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 4 given in Example 11 in terms of single digit 6:

$6 + 6/6$	$6 + 6$	$6/6$	$6 + 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
$(6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6$	$6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66/6$
$6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$(66 - 6)/6$	$6 - 6/6$
$6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	6	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 - (6 + 6)/6$

Example 18. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 4 given in Example 11 in terms of single digit 7:

7	$(77 + 7)/7$	$7/7$	$7 + 7$
$(7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7/7$	$77/7$
$7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$(7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$(77 - 7)/7$	$7 - (7 + 7)/7$
$7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7/7$	$77/7 - 7$

Example 19. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 4 given in Example 11 in terms of single digit 8:

$8 - 8/8$	$(88 + 8)/8$	$8/8$	$8 + 8 - (8 + 8)/8$
$(8 + 8)/8$	$(88 + 8 + 8)/8$	8	$88/8$
$8 + 8$	$88/8 - 8$	$8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$
$8 + 8/8$	$8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$

Example 20. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 4 given in Example 11 in terms of single digit 9:

$9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$(99 + 9)/9$	$9/9$	$9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$
$(9 + 9)/9$	$(99 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 - 9/9$	$99/9$
$9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$(9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9/9$	$(9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$
9	$9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

The magic sum of 9 Examples 12–20 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) = 2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2} && = 3/3 + 33 \\
 &:= 44 + (4 - 44)/4 && = 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5 && = 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7 && = 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8 && = 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 2. Using the values given in Appendix 4, write the following **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in single digits 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9:

		110	110	110	110
	23	34	11	42	110
110	12	41	24	33	110
110	44	13	32	21	110
110	31	22	43	14	110
	110	110	110	110	110

2.3 Magic Square of Order 5

Example 21. Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 is given by

		65	65	65	65	65
	1	9	12	20	23	65
65	17	25	3	6	14	65
65	8	11	19	22	5	65
65	24	2	10	13	16	65
65	15	18	21	4	7	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

Example 22. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 5 given in Example 3 in terms of single digit 1:

1	11 - 1 - 1	1 + 11	(1 + 1) × (11 - 1)	1 + 11 + 11
1 + (1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹⁺¹	1 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 11)	1 + 1 + 1	(1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)	1 + 1 + 1 + 11
(1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹	11	(1 + 1) × (11 - 1) - 1	11 + 11	1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1
(1 + 1) × (1 + 11)	1 + 1	11 - 1	1 + 1 + 11	(1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹⁺¹
1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11	(1 + 1) × (11 - 1 - 1)	11 + 11 - 1	1 + 1 + 1 + 1	1 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)

Example 23. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 5 given in Example 3 in terms of single digit 2:

2/2	(2/2 + 2) ²	2 × (2 + 2 + 2)	22 - 2	22 + 2/2
2/2 + 2 ²⁺²	2 + 22 + 2/2	2 + 2/2	2 + 2 + 2	2 ²⁺² - 2
2 × (2 + 2)	22/2	22 - 2/2 - 2	22	2 + 2/2 + 2
2 + 22	2	2 + 2 × (2 + 2)	2 + 22/2	2 ²⁺²
2 + 2 + 22/2	2 + 2 ²⁺²	22 - 2/2	2 + 2	2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2

Example 24. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 5 given in Example 3 in terms of single digit 3:

$3/3$	3×3	$3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 \times 3 + 33/3$	$3^3 - 3 - 3/3$
$3 + 33/3 + 3$	$3^3 - 3 + 3/3$	3	$3 + 3$	$3 + 33/3$
$3 \times 3 - 3/3$	$33/3$	$3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$33 - 33/3$	$3 + 3 - 3/3$
$3^3 - 3$	$3 - 3/3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3^3 - 33/3$
$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 3/3$

Example 25. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 5 given in Example 3 in terms of single digit 4:

$4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4$	$4 + 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44/4$
$4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 - 4/4$	$4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (44 - 4)/4$
$4 + 4$	$44/4$	$4 + 4 + 44/4$	$44 \times 4 / (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4/4$
$4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$(4 + 4)/4$	$(44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$	4×4
$4 + 44/4$	$4 \times 4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	4	$4 + 4 - 4/4$

Example 26. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 5 given in Example 3 in terms of single digit 5:

$5/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5$	$(55 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5$	$5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
$5 + (55 + 5)/5$	5×5	$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$
$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5$	$(55 + 55)/5$	5
$5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$(5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5$	$(55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55/5$
$5 + 5 + 5$	$5 + (55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55/5 + 5$	$5 - 5/5$	$5 + (5 + 5)/5$

Example 27. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 5 given in Example 3 in terms of single digit 6:

$6/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 + 6$	$6 + (6 + 6) / 6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + 6 + 66/6$
$6 + 66/6$	$6 \times 6 - 66/6$	$6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	6	$6 + 6 + (6 + 6) / 6$
$6 + (6 + 6) / 6$	$66/6$	$6 + 6 / 6 + 6 + 6$	$(66 + 66) / 6$	$6 - 6 / 6$
$6 + 6 + 6 + 6$	$(6 + 6) / 6$	$(66 - 6) / 6$	$6 + 6 / 6 + 6$	$6 + (66 - 6) / 6$
$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 + 6$	$6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) / (6 + 6)$	$6 - (6 + 6) / 6$	$6 + 6 / 6$

Example 28. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 5 given in Example 3 in terms of single digit 7:

$7/7$	$7 + (7 + 7) / 7$	$(77 + 7) / 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 - 7 / 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7) / 7$
$7 + (77 - 7) / 7$	$7 + 7 + 77 / 7$	$(7 + 7 + 7) / 7$	$7 - 7 / 7$	$7 + 7$
$7 + 7 / 7$	$77 / 7$	$7 + (7 + 77) / 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 / 7$	$7 - (7 + 7) / 7$
$7 + (77 - 7) / 7 + 7$	$(7 + 7) / 7$	$(77 - 7) / 7$	$7 + 7 - 7 / 7$	$7 + 7 + (7 + 7) / 7$
$7 + 7 + 7 / 7$	$7 + 77 / 7$	$7 + 7 + 7$	$77 / 7 - 7$	7

Example 29. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 5 given in Example 3 in terms of single digit 8:

$8/8$	$8 + 8/8$	$(88 + 8) / 8$	$8 + (88 + 8) / 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$
$8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$88/8 - 8$	$8 - (8 + 8) / 8$	$8 + 8 - (8 + 8) / 8$
8	$88/8$	$8 + 88/8$	$(88 + 88) / 8$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$
$8 + (8 + 8)$	$(8 + 8) / 8$	$8 + (8 + 8) / 8$	$(88 + 8 + 8) / 8$	$8 + 8$
$8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + (8 + 8) / 8$	$8 + (88 + 8 + 8) / 8$	$8 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$8 - 8/8$

Example 30. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 5 given in Example 3 in terms of single digit 9:

$9/9$	9	$(99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 99/9$	$(99 + 99 + 9)/9$
$9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$(9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$
$9 - 9/9$	$99/9$	$9 + 9/9 + 9$	$(99 + 99)/9$	$(9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$
$9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$	$(9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9/9$	$(99 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$
$9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9$	$9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 - (9 + 9)/9$

In all the Examples 22 – 30, the magic square is always **pandiagonal** and **magic sum** is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{S}_{5 \times 5} &:= 1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)} = 2/2 + 2^{2+2+2} = (3/3 + 3)^3 + 3/3 \\
 &:= (4^4 + 4)/4 &= 5 + 5 + 55 &= 66 - 6/6 \\
 &:= 77 - (77 + 7)/7 &= 8/8 + 8 \times 8 &= 9 + (999 + 9)/(9 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 3. Using the values given in Appendix 4, write the following **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in single digits 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9:

		165	165	165	165	165
	11	22	33	44	55	165
165	43	54	15	21	32	165
165	25	31	42	53	14	165
165	52	13	24	35	41	165
165	34	45	51	12	23	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165

2.4 Magic Square of Order 6

Example 31. Let's consider a magic square of order 6.

						111
1	35	34	33	2	6	111
30	8	28	9	11	25	111
24	23	15	16	20	13	111
18	14	21	22	17	19	111
7	26	10	27	29	12	111
31	5	3	4	32	36	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

Example 32. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 6 given in Example 31 in terms of single digit 1:

1	$1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	1 + 1	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
$(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$	$1 + (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$	$11 - 1 - 1$	11	$1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$
$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$	$1 + 11 + 11$	$1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11$	$(1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)$	$1 + 1 + 11$
$(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)$	$1 + 1 + 1 + 11$	$11 + 11 - 1$	$11 + 11$	$1 + (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1$
$1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$	$11 - 1$	$(1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$	$(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1$	$1 + 11$
$1 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1$	$1 + 1 + 1$	$1 + 1 + 1 + 1$	$11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1$	$(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$

Example 33. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 6 given in Example 31 in terms of single digit 2:

$2/2$	$2 + 22/2 + 22$	$2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$22 + 22/2$	2	$2 + 2 + 2$
$22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 + 22 + 2 + 2$	$(2/2 + 2)^2$	$22/2$	$2 + 22 + 2/2$
$2 + 22$	$22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 + 22/2$	2^{2+2}	$22 - 2$	$2 + 22/2$
$2 + 2^{2+2}$	$2^{2+2} - 2$	$22 - 2/2$	22	$2/2 + 2^{2+2}$	$22 - 2/2 - 2$
$2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$	$2 + 22 + 2$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 + 22 + 2/2 + 2$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$
$22 + (2/2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2/2 + 2$	$2 + 2/2$	$2 + 2$	$2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$(2 + 2 + 2)^2$

Example 34. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 6 given in Example 31 in terms of single digit 3:

$3/3$	$3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3/3 + 33$	33	$3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3$
$3 + 3^3$	$3 \times 3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 3/3$	3×3	$33/3$	$3^3 - 3 + 3/3$
$3^3 - 3$	$3^3 - 3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$	$3^3 - 33/3$	$3 \times 3 + 33/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$
$3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + 33/3$	$3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$33 - 33/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3$	$3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$
$3 + 3 + 3/3$	$3^3 - 3/3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$	3^3	$3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3$
$3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 - 3/3$	3	$3 + 3/3$	$33 - 3/3$	$3 + 33$

Example 35. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 6 given in Example 31 in terms of single digit 4:

$4/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$44 + (4 - 44)/4$	$4/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$(4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (4 + 4)/4$
$4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4$	$44 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + 4/4$	$44/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$
$4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 + 44/4$	4×4	$4 + 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$
$4 \times 4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 44/4$
$4 + 4 - 4/4$	$4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$(44 - 4)/4$	$4 \times 4 + 44/4$	$44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + 4$
$4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$4 + 4/4$	$4 - 4/4$	4	$4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$

Example 36. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 6 given in Example 31 in terms of single digit 5:

$5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$(5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5/5$
$5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5$	$55/5$	5×5
$5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 + 5$	$5 + 55/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5$	$(55 + 5 + 5)/5$
$5 + (55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$	$5 + 55/5 + 5$	$(55 + 55)/5$	$5 + (55 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5$
$5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$5 + 5$	$5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$(55 + 5)/5$
$5 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5$	5	$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 - 5/5$	$((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 \times 5 + 55/5$

Example 37. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 6 given in Example 31 in terms of single digit 6:

$6/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$(6 + 6)/6$	6
$6 \times 6 - 6$	$6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + (66 + 66)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$66/6$	$6 \times 6 - 66/6$
$6 + (6 + 6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 + 66/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 + ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6)$	$6 + 6/6 + 6$
$6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6)$	$(66 + 66)/6$	$6 + 66/6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6 + 6$
$6 + 6/6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 - 66)/6$	$(66 - 6)/6$	$66 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 6$	$6 \times 6 - 6 - 6/6$	$6 + 6$
$6 \times 6 + 6/6 - 6$	$6 - 6/6$	$6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 - 6$	6×6

Example 38. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 6 given in Example 31 in terms of single digit 7:

$7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$(7 + 7)/7$	$7 - 7/7$
$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$77/7$	$7 + 7 + 77/7$
$7 + ((77 - 7)/7 + 7)$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 - 7/7$
$7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7$	$7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 + (7 + 77)/7$
7	$7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$(77 - 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$(77 + 7)/7$
$7 \times 7 - 7 - 77/7$	$7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$(7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$77/7 - 7$	$7 + 77/7 + 7 + 7$	$7/7 + (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7))$

Example 39. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 6 given in Example 31 in terms of single digit 8:

$8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$(8 + 8)/8$	$8 - (8 + 8)/8$
$8 + (88 + 88)/8$	8	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8/8$	$88/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$
$8 + (8 + 8)$	$8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8$	$8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$(88 + 8 + 8)/8$
$8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$(88 + 88)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 88/8$
$8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$(88 + 8)/8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$	$88/8 - 8$	$8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$(8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$

Example 40. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 6 given in Example 31 in terms of single digit 9:

$9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$99 \times 9 / (9 + 9 + 9)$	$(9 + 9)/9$	$9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$
$9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	9	$99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$
$9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$	$(99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 99/9$	$(99 + 9 + 9)/9$
$9 + 9$	$9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$(99 + 99)/9$	$9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9/9 + 9$
$9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9$	$9 + 9 + 99/9$	$(99 + 9)/9$
$9 + (99 + 99)/9$	$(9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$(9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + (99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9$

In all the Examples 32 – 40, the magic square sum is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 111 = 222/2 = 333/3 \\
 &:= 444/4 = 555/5 = 666/6 \\
 &:= 777/7 = 888/8 = 999/9
 \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 4. Using the values given in Appendix 4, write the following magic square of order 6 in single digits 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9:

						231
11	65	64	63	12	16	231
56	22	54	23	25	51	231
46	45	33	34	42	31	231
36	32	43	44	35	41	231
21	52	24	53	55	26	231
61	15	13	14	62	66	231
231	231	231	231	231	231	231

2.5 Magic Square of Order 7

Example 41. Let's consider a **pandiagonal** of order 7 is given by

		175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175
175	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

Example 42. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 7 given in Example 41 in terms of single digit 1:

1	11 - 1 - 1	1 + (1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹⁺¹	1 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 11)	11 × (1 + 1 + 1)	1 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 1) × (11 - 1)	1 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 1) × (1 + 11)
(1 + 1) × (1 + 1) × (11 - 1)	(1 + 1) × (1 + 1) × (1 + 11)	1 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)	(1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹	(1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹⁺¹	(1 + 1) × (1 + 11)	11 × (1 + 1 + 1) - 1
1 + 11 + 11	1 + (11 - 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)	(1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 11)	1 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 11 + 11)	(1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)	1 + 1 + 1 + 11	1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11
1 + 1 + 11	11 + 11 - 1	11 + 11	(11 - 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)	1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)	(1 + 1) × (1 + 11 + 11)	1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1
1 + (1 + 1) × (11 + 11)	1 + 1 + 1 + 1	1 + 11	(1 + 1) × (11 - 1)	1 + (1 + 1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹	(11 - 1) × (1 + 1 + 1) - 1	111/(1 + 1 + 1)
1 + 1 + 11 × (1 + 1 + 1)	(1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + 11)	(1 + 1) × (11 + 11)	1 + 1 + 1	11	(1 + 1) × (11 - 1) - 1	(1 + 1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹
(1 + 1) × (11 - 1 - 1)	(1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 11)	1 + 11 × (1 + 1 + 1)	(1 + 1) × (11 + 11 - 1)	(1 + 1) × (11 + 11) - 1	1 + 1	11 - 1

Example 43. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 7 given in Example 41 in terms of single digit 2:

2/2	(2/2 + 2) ²	2/2 + 2 ²⁺²	2 + 22 + 2/2	22 + 22/2	2/2 + 2 × (22 - 2)	2/2 + 2 × (22 + 2)
2 × (22 - 2)	2 × (22 + 2)	2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2	2 × (2 + 2)	2 ²⁺²	2 + 22	2 × 2 ²⁺²
22 + 2/2	22 + (2/2 + 2) ²	2 × (22 - 2) - 2/2	2 + 2 × 22 + 2/2	2 + 2 + 2	2 ²⁺² - 2	2 + 2 + 22/2
2 + 22/2	22 - 2/2	22	22 + 2 × (2 + 2)	2 + (2 + 2 + 2) ²	2 + 2 × 22	2 + 2/2 + 2
2 × 22 + 2/2	2 + 2	2 × (2 + 2 + 2)	22 - 2	2 + 22 + 2 + 2	2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2	2/2 + (2 + 2 + 2) ²
2 + 22/2 + 22	(2 + 2 + 2) ²	2 × 22	2 + 2/2	22/2	22 - 2/2 - 2	2 + 22 + 2/2 + 2
2 + 2 ²⁺²	2 + 22 + 2	2 + 2 × 2 ²⁺²	2 × 22 - 2	2 × 22 - 2/2	2	2 + 2 × (2 + 2)

Example 44. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 7 given in Example 41 in terms of single digit 3:

$3/3$	3×3	$3 + 33/3 + 3$	$3^3 - 3 + 3/3$	33	$3 + 33/3 + 3^3$	$3^3 + 33 - 33/3$
$3 + 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 33$	$3 + 3 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3 - 3/3$	$3^3 - 33/3$	$3^3 - 3$	$33 - 3/3$
$3^3 - 3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 33$	$3 + 33/3 + 33$	$3 + 3$	$3 + 33/3$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$
$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$33 - 33/3$	$3 + 3^3$	$3^3 + 33/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 + (3 + 3)/3$
$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33$	$3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 \times 3 + 33/3$	$3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 33 + 3/3$
$3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3 + 33$	$33 + 33/3$	3	$33/3$	$3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	3^3
$3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3^3 - 3/3$	$3/3 + 33$	$3 \times 3 + 33$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3 + 33$	$3 - 3/3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$

Example 45. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 7 given in Example 41 in terms of single digit 4:

$4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$44 - 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 44 + 4/4$
$44 - 4$	$4 + 44$	$4 + 4 - 4/4$	$4 + 4$	4×4	$4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$4 \times (4 + 4)$
$4 + 4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$44 - 4 - 4/4$	$4 + 44 - 4/4$	$4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 44/4$
$4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$	$4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4$	$44 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4$	$44 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4/4$
$44 + 4/4$	4	$4 + 4 + 4$	$4 + 4 \times 4$	$44 - 4 \times 4$	$44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4$
$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	44	$4 - 4/4$	$44/4$	$4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 \times 4 + 44/4$
$4 \times 4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$44 + (4 - 44)/4$	$44 - (4 + 4)/4$	$44 - 4/4$	$(4 + 4)/4$	$(44 - 4)/4$

Example 46. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 7 given in Example 41 in terms of single digit 5:

$5/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5$	$5 + (55 + 5)/5$	5×5	$5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 55/5$	$55 - 5 - 5/5$
$5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$55 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$((5 + 5)/5)^5$
$5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$55 - 5 - 55/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$	$5 + 5 + 5$
$(55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55/5 + 5$	$(55 + 55)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + 5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5 - 5$	5
$55 - 5 - 5$	$5 - 5/5$	$(55 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55/5$	$55 - 55/5$	$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5$	$5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$
$5 + (55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5$	$55 - (55 + 5)/5$	$(5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5$

Example 47. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 7 given in Example 41 in terms of single digit 6:

$6/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 + 66/6$	$6 \times 6 - 66/6$	$66 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$
$6 + 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6$	$6 + 6/6$	$6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 + (6 + 6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 - 6$
$6 + 6 + 66/6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6 - 6$	$6 + 66 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 + 66/6$	6	$6 + 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$
$6 + 6/6 + 6$	$6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) / (6 + 6)$	$(66 + 66)/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 - 6/6$
$666/6 - 66$	$6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6$	$6 + (6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + (66 + 66)/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6 - 6/6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6$
$6 \times 6 - 6/6$	6×6	$6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$66/6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6 + 6$	$66 \times 6 / (6 + 6) - 6$
$6 + 6 + 6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 - 66)/6$	$6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$(6 + 6)/6$	$(66 - 6)/6$

Example 48. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 7 given in Example 41 in terms of single digit 7:

$7/7$	$7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7/7$	7×7
$7 \times 7 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7/7$	7	$7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + ((77 - 7)/7 + 7)$	$7 + 77/7 + 7 + 7$
$7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 77/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7$	$7 + 7 + 7/7$
$7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 - (7 + 7)/7$
$7 + 7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$77/7 - 7$	$(77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7$
$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7$	$7/7 + (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7))$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$(7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$77/7$	$7 + (7 + 77)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$
$7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7$	$7 \times 7 + 7/7 - 7$	$(7 + 7)/7$	$(77 - 7)/7$

Example 49. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 7 given in Example 41 in terms of single digit 9:

$8/8$	$8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + 8/8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8$	$8 - 8/8$	8	$8 + 8$	$8 + (8 + 8)$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8$
$8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - 8/8$
$(88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$(88 + 88)/8$	$8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - (88 - 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$
$8 \times 8 - 8 - 88/8$	$8 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$(88 + 8)/8$	$8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$888 / (8 + 8 + 8)$
$8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$(8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$88 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$88/8 - 8$	$88/8$	$8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 + 88/8$
$8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 88)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$(8 + 8)/8$	$8 + (8 + 8)/8$

Example 50. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 7 given in Example 41 in terms of single digit 9:

$9/9$	9	$9+9-9/9$	$9+9+9-(9+9)/9$	$99 \times 9/(9+9+9)$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9)/(9+9)$	$(9 \times 99-9)/(9+9)$
$(9 \times 9 \times 9-9)/(9+9)$	$9+9+9+9+(99+9)/9$	$9-(9+9)/9$	$9-9/9$	$9+9-(9+9)/9$	$9+((9-((9+9+9)/9))+9)$	$9+(99+99+9)/9$
$(99+99+9)/9$	$9+(99+99)/9$	$9+9+9+(99+9)/9$	$9+9+9+9+99/9$	$9-(9+9+9)/9$	$9+(9 \times 9+9)/(9+9)$	$9+9-(9+9+9)/9$
$(99+9+9)/9$	$9+(99+9)/9$	$(99+99)/9$	$9+9+(99+9)/9$	$9+9+9+99/9$	$9+9+9+9+9+9/9$	$(9 \times 9+9)/(9+9)$
$9+9+9+9+9$	$(9 \times 9-9)/(9+9)$	$(99+9)/9$	$9+99/9$	$9+9+9+9/9$	$9+9+99/9$	$9+9+9+9+9/9$
$9+9+9+9-9/9$	$9+9+9+9$	$9+9+9+9+9-9/9$	$(9+9+9)/9$	$99/9$	$9+9/9+9$	$9+9+9$
$9+9$	$9+9+9-9/9$	$9+9+9+9-(9+9)/9$	$9+99 \times 9/(9+9+9)$	$9+9+9+9+9-(9+9)/9$	$(9+9)/9$	$9+9/9$

In all the Examples 42–50, the magic square sum is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 11 \times (1+1)^{1+1+1+1} - 1 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2/2 = 333/3 + (3/3 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= 4 \times 44 - 4/4 &= 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5) &= 6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 6 \\
 &:= 77 + 7 \times (7 + 7) &= 8 \times 8 + 888/8 &= 9 \times (9 + 9) + (99 + 9 + 9)/9
 \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 5. Using the values given in Appendix 4, write the following magic square of order 7 in single digits 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9:

		308	308	308	308	308	308	308
	11	22	33	44	55	66	77	308
308	65	76	17	21	32	43	54	308
308	42	53	64	75	16	27	31	308
308	26	37	41	52	63	74	15	308
308	73	14	25	36	47	51	62	308
308	57	61	72	13	24	35	46	308
308	34	45	56	67	71	12	23	308
	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308

2.6 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 8

Example 51. Let's consider a **pan magic square** of order 8 is given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	25	48	1	56	26	47	2	55	260
260	8	49	32	41	7	50	31	42	260
260	64	9	40	17	63	10	39	18	260
260	33	24	57	16	34	23	58	15	260
260	27	46	3	54	28	45	4	53	260
260	6	51	30	43	5	52	29	44	260
260	62	11	38	19	61	12	37	20	260
260	35	22	59	14	36	21	60	13	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

Example 52. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 51 in terms of single digit 1:

$1 + (1+1) \times (1+11)$	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11)$	1	$(1+111)/(1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$1 + (1+1) \times (1+11+11)$	1+1	$(111-1)/(1+1)$
$(1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$1 + (1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11)$	$11 \times (1+1+1) - 1$	$1 + (1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11-1)$	$1 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1)$	$(11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$1 + (11-1) \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11+11-1)$
$(1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$	11-1-1	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11-1)$	$1 + (1+1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$(1+1+1) \times (11+11-1)$	11-1	$(1+1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$(1+1) \times (11-1-1)$
$11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (1+11)$	$1 + (1+111)/(1+1)$	$(1+1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$1+11 \times (1+1+1)$	1+11+11	$1+1+(1+111)/(1+1)$	1+1+1+1+11
$(1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$(1+1) \times (1+11+11)$	1+1+1	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1$	$1 + (1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$1 + (1+1) \times (11+11)$	1+1+1+1	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1-1$
$(1+1) \times (1+1+1)$	$1 + (11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$(11-1) \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11+11)-1$	1+1+1+1+1	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$(11-1) \times (1+1+1)-1$	$(1+1) \times (11+11)$
$1 + (1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	11	$1 + 111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11-1)-1$	$(1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	1+11	$111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11-1)$
$1+1+11 \times (1+1+1)$	11+11	$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)-1$	1+1+1+11	$(1+1+1) \times (1+11)$	11+11-1	$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)$	1+1+11

Example 53. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 51 in terms of single digit 2:

$2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2/2$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)$	$2 + 22 + 2$	$2 + 2 \times 22 + 2/2$	2	$22/2 + 2 \times 22$
$2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$22 + (2/2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times 22 - 2$
2^{2+2+2}	$(2/2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2/2 + 2^{2+2}$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 \times (22 - 2) - 2/2$	$2 + 2^{2+2}$
$22 + 22/2$	$2 + 22$	$2 + 22/2 + 2 \times 22$	2^{2+2}	$2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$22 + 2/2$	$22 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2 + 22/2$
$2 + 22 + 2/2 + 2$	$2 + 2 \times 22$	$2 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$2 + 22 + 2 + 2$	$2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$
$2 + 2 + 2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2) + 2/2$	$22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 \times 22 - 2/2$	$2 + 2/2 + 2$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2$	2×22
$2^{2+2+2} - 2$	$22/2$	$2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22 - 2/2 - 2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2 - 2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$	$2/2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22 - 2$
$2 + 22/2 + 22$	22	$22/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2^{2+2} - 2$	$(2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22 - 2/2$	$2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)$	$2 + 22/2$

Example 54. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 51 in terms of single digit 3:

$3^3 - 3 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 33$	$3/3$	$(333 + 3)/(3 + 3)$	$3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 33$	$3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 3^3 + 3/3$
$3 \times 3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 33 - 33/3$	$33 - 3/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3^3$	$3 + 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 33/3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3 + 33$
$(3/3 + 3)^3$	3×3	$3 + 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3$	$3 + 33 + 3^3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 33$	$3 \times (3 + 3)$
33	$3^3 - 3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3^3$	$3^3 - 33/3$	$3/3 + 33$	$3^3 - 3 - 3/3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$
3^3	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 + 3/3$	3	$3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33$	$3 + 3/3$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3/3$
$3 + 3$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3$	$3 + 3^3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3 + 33$	$3 + 3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 3/3 - 3 + 3^3$	$3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$33 + 33/3$
$3 + 33 - 3/3 + 3^3$	$33/3$	$3^3 + 33/3$	$3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3$	$3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3 + 33/3$
$3 + 33 - 3/3$	$33 - 33/3$	$3^3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3 + 33/3$	$3 + 33$	$3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3^3 + 33$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$

Example 55. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 51 in terms of single digit 4:

$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 44$	$4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44$	$4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$4 + 44 - 4/4$	$(4 + 4)/4$	$44 + 44/4$
$4 + 4$	$4 + 44 + 4/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4)$	$44 - 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 - 4/4$	$4 + 44 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$44 - (4 + 4)/4$
$4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + 4/4$	$44 - 4$	$4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$(4^4 - 4)/4$	$(44 - 4)/4$	$44 - 4 - 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + (4 + 4)/4$
$4/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$4 + (4^4 - 44)/4$	4×4	$44 + (4 - 44)/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44/4$	$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 - 4$	$4 + 44/4$
$4 \times 4 + 44/4$	$44 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 - 4/4$	$44 + (44 - 4)/4$	$44 - 4 \times 4$	$44 + 4/4$	4	$(4^4 - 44)/4$
$4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 + 44 - 4/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4$	$44 - 4/4$	$4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 44$	$44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4$	44
$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4$	$44/4$	$44 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 + 44/4$	$(4^4 + 4)/4 - 4$	$4 + 4 + 4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4$	$4 + 4 \times 4$
$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$(4^4 - 4)/4 - 4$	$4 + (44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + 44$	$4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$

Example 56. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 51 in terms of single digit 5:

5×5	$55 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5/5$	$55 + 5/5$	$5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$(5 + 5)/5$	55
$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 5 - 5/5$	$((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 55/5$	$5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times (5 + 5)$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5$
$5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + (55 + 5)/5$	$(5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$	5 + 5	$55 - 5 - 55/5$	$5 + (55 + 5 + 5)/5$
$5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$	5 + 5 + 5
$5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5 - 5$	$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 5 - 5$	$5 - 5/5$	$55 - (5 + 5)/5$
$5 + 5/5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5$	$5 + 5 \times 5$	$55 - (55 + 5)/5$	5	$55 - 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$55 - 55/5$
$5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$55/5$	$5 + 5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 55 + 5/5$	$(55 + 5)/5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 \times 5 - 5$
$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$(55 + 55)/5$	$5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55/5$	$5 + 55/5 + 5$	5 + 55	$(55 + 5 + 5)/5$

Example 57. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 51 in terms of single digit 6:

$6 \times 6 - 66/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6$	$6/6$	$66 + (6 - 66)/6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 - 66)/6$	$6 \times 6 + 66/6$	$(6 + 6)/6$	$66 - 66/6$
$6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 - 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$6 + 6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6 - 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6$
$((6 + 6)/6)^6$	$6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 66/6$	$66 - 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$(66 - 6)/6$	$6 + 66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 + 6$
$66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + (6 + 6 + 6)$	$66 + (6 + 6 - 66)/6$	$6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 + 66/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
$66 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 6$	$6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$66 - 6 - 6$	$6 + (66 + 66)/6$	$666/6 - 66$	$6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 66/6$
6	$6 - 66 + 666/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 - 6/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6 - 6$	$6 \times 6 - 6 - 6/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
$66 - 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66/6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6 + 6$	$66 + 6/6 - 6$	6 + 6	$6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 + ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6)$
$6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$(66 + 66)/6$	$66 - 6/6 - 6$	$6 + 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	6×6	$6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6)$	$66 - 6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6$

Example 58. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 51 in terms of single digit 7:

$7 + 7 + 77/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7$	$7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$(7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$
$7 + 7/7$	7×7	$7 + 77/7 + 7 + 7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7/7$	7	$7 \times 7 + 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 77/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7$
$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 + 7/7$	$7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7$	$(77 - 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7$	$7 + 77/7$
$7 + 7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 + ((77 - 7)/7 + 7)$	$7 + 7/7 + 7 \times 7$	$7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7/7$
$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$(7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$77/7 - 7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + 77/7$
$7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + 7/7 - 7$	$7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$77/7$	$7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$7 + (7 + 77)/7$	$7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$(77 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$
$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 \times 7 + (77 - 7)/7$	7 + 7	$7/7 + (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7))$	7 + 7 + 7	$7 \times 7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 - 7/7$

Example 59. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 51 in terms of single digit 8:

$8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8$	$8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$(8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8/8$
8	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 88)/8$
8×8	$8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8/8$	$8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + (8 + 8)$	$8/8 + 8 \times 8 - 8$	$8 + 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - 8/8$
$8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - (88 - 8)/8$	$88/8 - 8$	$8 \times 8 + (8 - 88)/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 88/8$	$8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 \times 8 - 88/8$
$8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$	$8 + 88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
$8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$88/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 - 88/8$	$(88 + 8)/8$	$888/(8 + 8 + 8)$	$8 + (88 + 8)/8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$(88 + 88)/8$	$8 \times 8 + 88/8 - 8 - 8$	$8 + 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$(8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$(88 + 8 + 8)/8$

Example 60. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 51 in terms of single digit 9:

$9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9/9$	$(999 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	$(9 + 9)/9$	$(999 - 9)/(9 + 9)$
$9 - 9/9$	$(9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + (99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + (99 + 99)/9$	$9 + 99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$
$9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	9	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9$
$99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$	$((9 + 9)/9)^9 + 9/9/9$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$(99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$
$9 + 9 + 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$(9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9$	$(9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$
$9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 \times (9 + 9) - 999/9$	$9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$
$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$	$99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 + 9/9 + 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$(99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 + 99/9$
$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$(99 + 99)/9$	$9 + (9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9$	$9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - (99 + 9)/9$	$(99 + 9 + 9)/9$

Example 61. Let's consider a **pandiagonal** and **bimagic** square of order 8 given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	16	41	36	5	27	62	55	18	260
260	26	63	54	19	13	44	33	8	260
260	1	40	45	12	22	51	58	31	260
260	23	50	59	30	4	37	48	9	260
260	38	3	10	47	49	24	29	60	260
260	52	21	32	57	39	2	11	46	260
260	43	14	7	34	64	25	20	53	260
260	61	28	17	56	42	15	6	35	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

In this case, the above magic square of order 8 is **bimagic** with **bimagic** sum $Sb_{8 \times 8} := 11180$. Each 2×4 blocks is with equal sum entries as of magic square, i.e., 260

Example 62. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 61 in terms of single digit 1:

$(1+1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11-1)$	$(1+1+1) \times (1+11)$	$1+1+1+1+1$	$(1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$1+(1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	$(111-1)/(1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11-1-1)$
$(1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$(1+1+1) \times (11+11-1)$	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1$	$(1+1) \times (11-1)-1$	$1+1+11$	$(1+1) \times (11+11)$	$11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1)^{1+1+1}$
1	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11-1)$	$1+(1+1) \times (11+11)$	$1+11$	$11+11$	$1+(11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$1+1+(1+111)/(1+1)$	$1+(11-1) \times (1+1+1)$
$1+11+11$	$(11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)-1$	$(11-1) \times (1+1+1)$	$1+1+1+1$	$111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11)$	$11-1-1$
$1+111/(1+1+1)$	$1+1+1$	$11-1$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+11+11)$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11)$	$(1+1) \times (1+11)$	$(11-1) \times (1+1+1)-1$	$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)$
$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$11+11-1$	$11 \times (1+1+1)-1$	$1+(1+111)/(1+1)$	$(1+1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$1+1$	11	$(1+1) \times (1+11+11)$
$(1+1) \times (11+11)-1$	$1+1+1+11$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+1+1)$	$1+11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+11)$	$(1+1) \times (11-1)$	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1-1$
$(1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	$1+(1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$1+(1+1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$(1+111)/(1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11+11-1)$	$1+1+1+1+11$	$(1+1) \times (1+1+1)$	$1+1+11 \times (1+1+1)$

Example 63. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 61 in terms of single digit 2:

2^{2+2}	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$(2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2/2 + 2$	$2 + 22 + 2/2 + 2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2$	$22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$2 + 2^{2+2}$
$2 + 22 + 2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$22 - 2/2 - 2$	$2 + 22/2$	2×22	$22 + 22/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2)$
$2/2$	$2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$	22	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2) + 2/2$	$22 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22 + (2/2 + 2)^2$
$22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$22/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 + 2$	$2/2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times (22 + 2)$	$(2/2 + 2)^2$
$2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 + 2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 22$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)$
$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$22 - 2/2$	$2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$2 + 22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$2 \times (22 - 2) - 2/2$	2	$22/2$	$2 + 2 \times 22$
$2 \times 22 - 2/2$	$2^{2+2} - 2$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2}$	2^{2+2+2}	$2 + 22 + 2/2$	$22 - 2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$
$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2 - 2$	$2 + 22 + 2 + 2$	$2/2 + 2^{2+2}$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)$	$2 \times 22 - 2$	$2 + 2 + 22/2$	$2 + 2 + 2$	$2 + 22/2 + 22$

Example 64. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 61 in terms of single digit 3:

$3^3 - 33/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3^3$	$3 + 33$	$3 + 3 - 3/3$	3^3	$3 + 33 - 3/3 + 3^3$	$3^3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3 \times (3 + 3)$
$3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 33 + 3^3$	$3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$33 + 33/3$	33	$3 \times 3 - 3/3$
$3/3$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33$	$3 + 3 \times 3$	$33 - 33/3$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3/3$
$3^3 - 3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 33/3$	$3^3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3 + 3^3$	$3 + 3/3$	$3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 33$	3×3
$3^3 + 33/3$	3	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 33$	$3^3 + 33 - 33/3$	$3^3 - 3$	$3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 33$
$3^3 + 3/3 - 3 + 3^3$	$3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$33 - 3/3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3^3$	$3 + 3 + 33$	$3 - 3/3$	$33/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 + 3/3$
$3 \times 3 + 3/3 + 33$	$3 + 33/3$	$3 + 3 + 3/3$	$3/3 + 33$	$(3/3 + 3)^3$	$3^3 - 3 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3 + 33/3$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3/3$
$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3$	$3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3$	$(333 + 3)/(3 + 3)$	$3 \times 3 + 33$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 + 3$	$3 + 33 - 3/3$

Example 65. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 61 in terms of single digit 4:

4×4	$44 - 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + 44/4$	$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4$	$44 + 44/4$	$4 \times 4 + (4 + 4)/4$
$4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$(4^4 - 4)/4$	$44 + (44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$	44	$4/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4$
$4/4$	$44 - 4$	$44 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4$	$44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 + 44 - 4/4$	$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 - 4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$
$4 + 4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 + 44 + (4 + 4)/4$	$(4^4 - 4)/4 - 4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4$	4	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4$	$4 + 44$	$4 + 4 + 4/4$
$44 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4$	$4 - 4/4$	$(44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 44 - 4/4$	$4 + 44 + 4/4$	$4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 \times 4 + 44$
$4 + 4 + 44$	$4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + (4^4 - 44)/4$	$44 - 4 - 4/4$	$(4 + 4)/4$	$44/4$	$44 + (4 + 4)/4$
$44 - 4/4$	$4 + (44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4 - 4/4$	$44 + (4 - 44)/4$	$4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 \times 4$	$(4^4 - 44)/4$
$(4^4 + 4)/4 - 4$	$44 - 4 \times 4$	$4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44$	$44 - (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 44/4$	$4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$

Example 66. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 61 in terms of single digit 5:

$5 + 55/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 55/5$	$5 \times 5 + 55/5$	5	$5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5$	55	$5 + (55 + 5 + 5)/5$
$5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$(5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$	$55 - 5/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5$	$(55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 55/5$	$5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
$5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$55 - 5 - 5$	$(55 + 5)/5$	$(55 + 55)/5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5$	$5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5$
$5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times (5 + 5)$	$5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 - 5/5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$55 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5$
$5 + 5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$55 - 5 - 5/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 55$
$55 - 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55/5 + 5$	$((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 5 - 55/5$	$(5 + 5)/5$	$55/5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5 - 5$
$55 - (55 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$	$5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$	5×5	$5 \times 5 - 5$	$55 - (5 + 5)/5$
$5 + 55 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + (55 + 5)/5$	$55 + 5/5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5$	$5 + 5 + 5$	$5 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$

Example 67. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 61 in terms of single digit 6:

$6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - 6/6$	6×6	$6 - 6/6$	$66 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 6$	$66 - 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66 - 66/6$	$6 + 6 + 6$
$6 \times 6 + (6 - 66)/6$	$66 - 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$66 - 6 - 6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + (6 + 6)/6$
$6/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$666/6 - 66$	$6 + 6$	$(66 + 66)/6$	$6 - 66 + 666/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6 - 6$
$6 + 6 + 66/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66 - 6/6 - 6$	$6 \times 6 - 6$	$6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$(66 - 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 + 66/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 + 6$	$6 \times 6 - 6 - 6/6$	$66 - 6$
$((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6 - 6$	$6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 - 6$	$66 + (6 + 6 - 66)/6$	$6 + 66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$(6 + 6)/6$	$66/6$	$6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6$
$6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 + 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6/6$	$6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6$	$6 \times 6 - 66/6$	$6 + (6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 66/6$
$66 + 6/6 - 6$	$6 + (66 + 66)/6$	$6 + 66/6$	$66 + (6 - 66)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	6	$6 \times 6 - 6/6$

Example 68. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 61 in terms of single digit 7:

$7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7/7 + (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7))$	$7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 77/7$
$7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + (7 + 77)/7$	$7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7/7$
$7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$(77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 77/7$
$7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + 7/7$	$7 \times 7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$77/7 - 7$	$7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 + (7 + 7)/7$
$7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$(7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$(77 - 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	7×7	$7 + ((77 - 7)/7 + 7)$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 \times 7 + 77/7$
$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + 77/7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + 7/7 + 7 \times 7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7$	$(7 + 7)/7$	$77/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
$7 \times 7 + 7/7 - 7$	$7 + 7$	7	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + 77/7$
$7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7$	$7 \times 7 - 7$	$7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7$

Example 69. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 61 in terms of single digit 8:

$8 + 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$(8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$	$8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 + (8 - 88)/8$	$8 + 88/8$	$(88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	8
$8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 88/8$	$(88 + 8)/8$	$(88 + 88)/8$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$
$8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 + 88/8 - 8 - 8$	$8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$888/(8 + 8 + 8)$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8$	$8 + 8/8$
$8 + 8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$88/8 - 8$	$8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
$8 + 88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8/8 + 8 \times 8 - 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$(8 + 8)/8$	$88/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - (88 - 8)/8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	8×8	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 88/8$
$8 + 8 \times 8 - 88/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 88)/8$	$8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$

Example 70. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 8 given in Example 61 in terms of single digit 9:

$9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9$	$(9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$	$(999 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9$
$9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 + 9/9 + 9$	$(99 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 - 9/9$
$9/9$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9$	$(99 + 9)/9$	$(99 + 99)/9$	$9 \times (9 + 9) - 999/9$	$9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + (99 + 99)/9$
$(99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + (9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	9
$9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	$(9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	$(9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - (99 + 9)/9$
$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 + (99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$((9 + 9)/9)^9 + 9/9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$(9 + 9)/9$	$99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$
$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 99/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$
$9 \times 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9 - 9/9$	$(999 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$

In all the Examples 52 – 70, the magic square sum is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11) := 2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2 &= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 33)/3 + 3 \\
 &= 4 + 4^4 &= 5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) + 5 &= 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + (6 + 6)/6 \\
 &:= 7/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77 - 7 &= (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8) = 99 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9/9
 \end{aligned}$$

In all the Examples 62 – 70, the **bimagic** sum is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{Sb}_{8 \times 8} &:= (11 - 1) \times ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 111) - 1 - 1) \\
 &:= 2 + (22 + 2/2) \times (22^2 + 2) \\
 &:= 3 + 33333/3 + 33 + 33 \\
 &:= (4^4 + 4) \times (44 - 4/4) \\
 &:= (5 - 5/5) \times (5 \times (555 + 5) - 5) \\
 &:= (66 - 6)/6 \times ((6666 + 6)/6 + 6) \\
 &:= 7 + (7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 \times 77 - 7) + 7/7 \\
 &:= 8 \times 8/(8 + 8) + (88 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8)) \\
 &:= 9 \times 9 + 99/9 \times (999 + 9/9 + 9).
 \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 6. Using the values given in Appendix 4, write the following magic square of order 3 in single digits 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9:

		396	396	396	396	396	396	396	396
	45	58	11	84	35	68	21	74	396
396	14	81	48	55	24	71	38	65	396
396	88	15	54	41	78	25	64	31	396
396	51	44	85	18	61	34	75	28	396
396	46	57	12	83	36	67	22	73	396
396	13	82	47	56	23	72	37	66	396
396	87	16	53	42	77	26	63	32	396
396	52	43	86	17	62	33	76	27	396
	396	396	396	396	396	396	396	396	396

2.7 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 9

Example 71. Let's consider a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 9 is given by

		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
369	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** (sum of only rows and columns) with equal magic sums.

Example 72. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 1:

$11 + 11$	$(1 + 11)^{1+1}/(1 + 1) - 1$	$(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$	$(1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$	$11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1$	$(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)$	$(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11)$	$1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
$1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$11 + 11 - 1$	$1 + (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$1 + (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$	$1 + 11 + 11$	$(1 + 11)^{1+1}/(1 + 1)$	$11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$	$1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$
$(1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$1 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))$	$(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$	$(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1$	$(11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 11$	$(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1$	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$
$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)$	$(1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$	$1 + (1 + 1) \times 111/(1 + 1 + 1)$	$1 + (1 + 1) \times (11 + 11)$	1	$11 \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))$	$1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$(11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1 - 1$
$(11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1$	$(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$	$1 + 1 + 1 + 1$	$1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}/(1 + 1)$	$1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)$	$11 - 1 - 1$	$111 - 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1) \times (11 + 11) - 1$	1 + 1
1 + 1 + 1	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1))$	$(1 + 1) \times (11 + 11)$	1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1	$(11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$	$111/(1 + 1 + 1)$	$1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1) \times 111/(1 + 1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)$
$1 + 1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)$	$(111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1$	1 + 11	$(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)$	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11)$	1 + 1 + 1 + 11	$(1 + 111)/(1 + 1)$	$1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}/(1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$
$1 + (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)$	$1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$	11 - 1	$(11^{1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1$	$(111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1$	1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11	$(1 + 11^{1+1})/(1 + 1)$	$1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$	1 + 1 + 11	$1 + (1 + 11^{1+1})/(1 + 1)$	$(11 - 1)^{1+1}/(1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)$	$(111 - 1)/(1 + 1)$	$(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$	11	$(11^{1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1)$

Example 73. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 2:

22	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 - 2/2$	$22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 + 22 + 2/2 + 2$	2^{2+2+2}	$2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$22 - 2$	$(2/2 + 2) \times (22 + 2/2)$	$2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2}$
$2 + 22/2 + 22$	$22 - 2/2$	$2 + 2^{2+2+2} + 2/2$	$2 + 22 + 2 + 2$	$22 + 2/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22 + 22/2$	$2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2/2 + 2^{2+2+2}$
$2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$22 + (2/2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 22 + 2$	$2 + 2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$(2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22 - 2/2 - 2$	$22 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 22$
$2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2 \times (2 + 2)$	$22/2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2/2$	$2 \times 2 \times 22 - 22/2$	$2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2 + 2$	$(2/2 + 2)^{2+2} - 2$
$2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2 \times (22 - 2) - 2/2$	$2 + 2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$(2/2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2) - 2$	$2 \times 22 - 2/2$	2
$2 + 2/2$	$2 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)$	2×22	$2 + 2/2 + 2$	$(2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$	$2/2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times 22 - 2$
$22 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times 22$	$2^{2+2} - 2$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2) + 2/2$	2^{2+2}
$2/2 + 2^{2+2}$	$2 + 22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$22/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$2 + 2 + 22/2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2 - 2$	$2 + 2 \times 22 + 2/2$
$2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 22/2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 2^{2+2}$	$22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$22/2$	$2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)$

Example 74. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 3:

$33 - 33/3$	$((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3$	$3 + 3^3$	3^3	$(3/3 + 3)^3$	$33 - 3/3$	$3 \times 3 + 33/3$	$3 + 33 + 33$	$3/3 + 33$
$3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$	$3^3 + 3/3$	$3^3 - 3 - 3/3$	$3 \times (3^3 - 3)$	33	$3^3 - 3 + 3/3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 + 3/3$
$33 + 33$	$3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3^3 - 3/3$	$((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 - 3$	$3 + 33$	$3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + (3/3 + 3)^3 + 3$	$3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$3^3 - 3$
$3 + 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times (3^3 - 3)$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33$	$3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3/3 - 3$	$3^3 + 33/3$	$3 + 3$	$3 \times 3^3 + 3/3 - 3$
$3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 33$	$3 + 3/3$	$((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3^3$	3×3	$3 \times 3^3 - 3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3 + 33$	$3 - 3/3$
3	$3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3$	$33 + 33/3$	$3 + 3 - 3/3$	3×3^3	$3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 3/3$	$3 + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3$	$3 \times 3 + 33$
$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 + 33 + 3^3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 + 33/3$	$(333 + 3)/(3 + 3)$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3$	$3^3 - 33/3$
$3 + 33/3 + 3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3^3$	$3^3 + 33 - 33/3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3^3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3$	$3 + 33/3 + 33$
$3 \times 3^3 - 33$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 33 - 3/3 + 3^3$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 33/3$	$3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3^3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3^3 + 3/3 - 3 + 3^3$	$33/3$	$3^3 + 33$

Example 75. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 4:

$44 \times 4 / (4 + 4)$	$4 + (4^4 - 4) / 4 + 4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4) / 4$	$4 \times 4 + 44 / 4$	$4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 \times 4$	$4 + (4^4 + 4) / 4$	$44 + (4 - 44) / 4$
$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4 / 4$	$4 + 4 \times 4 + 4 / 4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4) / 4$	$44 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44 / 4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4 / 4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4 / 4$	$(4^4 + 4) / 4$
$(4^4 + 4 + 4) / 4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - 4 / 4$	$4 + 44 \times 4 / (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 + 44 / 4$	$4 + (4^4 + 4 + 4) / 4$	$44 + 4 / 4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$
$44 - 4$	$4 + 4$	$(44 + 4^4) / 4$	$44 + 4 / 4$	$4 / 4$	$(4 - 4 / 4)^4 - 4$	$44 - 4 - (4 + 4) / 4$	$4 + (4 + 4) / 4$	$4 + (44 + 4^4) / 4$
$4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$44 - 4 - 4 / 4$	4	$4 + (4^4 + 4) / 4 + 4$	$44 - 4 + 4 / 4$	$4 + 4 + 4 / 4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4 + 44) / 4$	$44 - 4 / 4$	$(4 + 4) / 4$
$4 - 4 / 4$	$44 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	44	$4 + 4 / 4$	$(4 - 4 / 4)^4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4 / 4$	$4 + 4 - 4 / 4$	$(4^4 + 44 - 4) / 4$	$44 - (4 + 4) / 4$
$(4^4 - 4 - 4) / 4 - 4$	$(4^4 - 44) / 4$	$4 + 4 + 4$	$(4^4 - 4) / 4$	$44 + (4 + 4) / 4$	$4 + (44 - 4) / 4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44$	$4 + 4 + 44 - 4 / 4$	4×4
$4 \times 4 + 4 / 4$	$4 + (4^4 - 44) / 4$	$4 + 44 + 4 / 4$	$(44 - 4) / 4$	$(4^4 - 4) / 4 - 4$	$44 + (44 - 4) / 4$	$4 + 44 / 4$	$(4^4 + 4) / 4 - 4$	$4 + 44 - 4 / 4$
$4 + 44$	$4 + 4 / 4 + 4 + 4$	$(4^4 - 4 - 4) / 4$	$4 + 44 + (4 + 4) / 4$	$4 \times 4 + (4 + 4) / 4$	$44 + 44 / 4$	$4 + 4 + 44$	$44 / 4$	$4 \times 4 + 44$

Example 76. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 5:

$(55 + 55) / 5$	$5 + 55 + 55 / 5$	$5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 \times 5 + (5 + 5) / 5$	$5 + 5 + 55 - 5 / 5$	$((5 + 5) / 5)^5$	$5 \times 5 - 5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + 55 - 5 / 5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5 / 5$
$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + 55 / 5 + 5$	$55 + (55 + 5) / 5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5) / 5$	$5 \times 5 - (5 + 5) / 5$	$5 + 55 + (55 + 5) / 5$	$5 / 5 + ((5 + 5) / 5)^5$	5×5	$5 + 5 + 55$
$55 + 55 / 5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 5 / 5$	$5 \times 5 + 5 / 5$	$5 + (5^5 / 5 + 5) / (5 + 5)$	$5 \times 5 + 55 / 5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 - 5 / 5$	$5 + 55 + 5 + 5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - 5 / 5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 / 5$
$5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + 5 - (5 + 5) / 5$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)$	$55 - 5 - 5$	$5 / 5$	$55 + (55 + 55) / 5$	$5 + 5 / 5 + ((5 + 5) / 5)^5$	$5 + 5 / 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 - 5 / 5$
$5 \times 5 + 55$	$55 - 5 - 55 / 5$	$5 - 5 / 5$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (5 + 5) / 5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 55 / 5$	$5 + 5 - 5 / 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 - (5 + 5) / 5$	$55 - (55 + 5) / 5$	$(5 + 5) / 5$
$5 - (5 + 5) / 5$	$5 / 5 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)$	$55 - 55 / 5$	5	$5 \times 5 + 55 + 5 / 5$	$5 + ((5 + 5) / 5)^5$	$5 + (5 + 5) / 5$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 / 5$	$5 + ((5 + 5) / 5)^5 + 5$
$5 + 55 - (5 + 5) / 5$	$55 - (5 + 5) / 5$	$(55 + 5) / 5$	$(5^5 / 5 + 5) / (5 + 5)$	$55 + 5 / 5 - 5 - 5$	$5 + 5 - 5 / 5 + 5$	$55 + 5 / 5$	$55 + 5 / 5 - 5$	$5 + 55 / 5$
$5 + (55 + 5) / 5$	$55 + (5 + 5) / 5$	$55 - 5 - 5 / 5$	$5 + 5$	$5 + 55 - 5 / 5$	$55 - 5 / 5$	$5 + 5 + 5$	$5 + 55 + 5 / 5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + ((5 + 5) / 5)^5$
$55 + 5 - (5 + 5) / 5$	$(55 + 5 + 5) / 5$	$5 + 55 + (5 + 5) / 5$	$5 \times (5 + 5)$	$5 + (55 + 5 + 5) / 5$	55	$55 - 5 + (5 + 5) / 5$	$55 / 5$	$5 + 55$

Example 77. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 6:

$(66 + 66) / 6$	$6 + 66 - 6 / 6$	$6 \times 6 - 6$	$66 \times 6 / (6 + 6) - 6$	$((6 + 6) / 6)^6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6) / 6 - 6$	$6 + (6 + 6) / 6 + 6 + 6$	$66 + 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 - (6 + 6) / 6$
$6 \times 6 - 6 / 6$	$6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) / (6 + 6)$	$66 + 6 / 6$	$6 + (66 + 66) / 6$	$6 + 6 + 66 / 6$	$6 + 66$	$66 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 - 66 / 6$	$66 - 6 / 6$
66	$6 \times 6 + 6 / 6 - 6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 - 66) / 6$	$66 + (6 + 6) / 6$	6×6	$6 + 6 / 6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + ((6 + 6) / 6)^6$	$6 \times 6 - 6 - 6 / 6$	$6 + 6 + 6 + 6$
$6 + 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6) / 6$	$6 + (6 + 6) / 6$	$666 / 6 - 6 \times 6$	$666 / 6 - 66$	$6 / 6$	$66 + 66 / 6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6) / 6$	6	$6 + 6 + 66 + 6 / 6$
$6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6) / 6$	$6 + 66 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 - (6 + 6) / 6$	$6 + 66 + 6 / 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - 6 / 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 + 66 + 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 6 / 6$	$(6 + 6) / 6$
$6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 + ((6 + 6) / 6)^6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6) / 6$	$6 - 6 / 6$	$6 + 666 / 6 - 6 \times 6$	$6 \times 6 + 6 / 6$	$6 + 6 / 6$	$6 + 66 + (6 + 6) / 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6$
$((6 + 6) / 6)^6 - 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 66 / 6$	$6 + 6$	$66 - 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 + (66 - 6) / 6$	$6 + 6 + (6 + 6) / 6$	$66 + (6 - 66) / 6$	$6 - 66 + 666 / 6$	$6 + (66 - 6) / 6$
$6 + 66 / 6$	$66 + (6 + 6 - 66) / 6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6 / 6$	$(66 - 6) / 6$	$66 - 6 / 6 - 6$	$66 - 6 - 6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$	$66 + 6 / 6 - 6$	$6 \times 6 + 66 / 6$
$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6$	$6 + 6 / 6 + 6$	$66 - 6 + (6 + 6) / 6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6) / 6$	$6 + 6 + 6$	$66 - 66 / 6$	$((6 + 6) / 6)^6 - 6 - 6$	$66 / 6$	$66 - 6$

Example 78. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 7:

$7+7+7+7/7$	$7/7+77-7$	$7+7+7+7+(7+7)/7$	$7+7+7+7-7/7$	$7+7+7\times 7+7/7$	$7+77/7+7+7$	$7+7+7-7/7$	$77-7-7/7$	$7\times 7-7-7-7/7$
$7\times 7-7-7$	$7+7+7$	$7+7\times 7+77/7$	$7+7+7+7$	$7+7+7+(7+7)/7$	$77+(7+7)/7-7$	$7+7+7+(77+7)/7$	$7+7+77/7$	$77-(77+7)/7$
$77-77/7$	$7\times 7-7-77/7$	$7+7+(77+7)/7$	$77-7-(7+7)/7$	$7/7+(7\times 7-(7+7))$	$7+(7+77)/7$	$77-7$	$7+7+7+7+7/7$	$7+(77-7)/7+7$
$7\times 7-7-(7+7)/7$	$7+7/7$	$77-(7+7)/7$	$7+7\times 7-77/7$	$7/7$	77	$7\times 7-77/7$	$7-7/7$	$77+(7+7)/7$
$77+(7+7+7)/7$	$7\times 7+(7-77)/7$	$77/7-7$	$7+77-77/7$	$7\times 7-7-7/7$	$7+(7+7)/7$	$7/7+77$	$7\times 7+7/7-7$	$(7+7)/7$
$(7+7+7)/7$	$77-7/7$	$7\times 7-7+(7+7)/7$	$7-(7+7)/7$	$77-7+77/7$	$7\times 7-(77+7)/7$	7	$77-(7+7+7)/7$	$7\times 7-7$
$7+7\times 7+(7+7)/7$	$7\times 7-7+77/7$	$(77+7)/7$	$7+7+7\times 7$	$7\times 7-(7+7+7)/7$	$7+7$	$7+7\times 7$	$7\times 7+(7+7)/7$	$7+7+(7+7)/7$
$7+(77-7)/7$	$7+7/7+7\times 7$	7×7	$(77-7)/7$	$7\times 7+(77-7)/7$	$7+7\times 7-(7+7)/7$	$7+7+7/7$	$7\times 7+(77+7)/7$	$7\times 7-(7+7)/7$
$7\times 7-7/7$	$7+7-7/7$	$7+7+7\times 7-7/7$	$7\times 7+7/7$	$7+77/7$	$7+7\times 7-7/7$	$7\times 7+(7+7+7)/7$	$77/7$	$7\times 7+77/7$

Example 79. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 8:

$(88+88)/8$	$8+8\times 8-8/8$	$8+(88+88)/8$	$8+8+88/8$	8×8	$8+8+8+8$	$8+(88+8)/8$	$88-8-88/8$	$8+8+8+8+(8+8)/8$
$8+8+8+88/8$	$8+(88+8+8)/8$	$8\times 8-8+88/8$	$8+8+(88+8)/8$	$8+8+8-8/8$	$8+8\times 8$	$8+8+8+8+8/8$	$8+8+8+8/8$	$8/8+8\times 8$
$8\times 8+(8+8)/8$	$8+8+8+8-8/8$	$8+8+8+(8+8)/8$	$8\times 8+8\times 8/(8+8)$	$(8\times 8+8)\times 8/(8+8)$	$8+88/8$	$8+8\times 8-(8+8)/8$	$8+8+(88+8+8)/8$	$8+(8+8)$
$8+8+8+8+8$	8	$8\times 8+88/8$	$8\times 8-8-88/8$	$8/8$	$88-88/8$	$8+8+(88+88)/8$	$8-(8+8)/8$	$88-8-8/8$
$88-8$	$8+8+8+8+8-8/8$	$8\times 8/(8+8)$	$8+8/8+8\times 8$	$8+8+8+8+8+8/8$	$8+8/8$	$88+(8-88)/8$	$8+8+8+8+88/8$	$(8+8)/8$
$88/8-8$	$8\times 8+(88+8)/8$	$88\times 8/(8+8)$	$8+8-88/8$	$8/8+88-8$	$888/(8+8+8)$	$8-8/8$	$8\times 8+8+(8+8)/8$	$8\times 8-(88+88)/8$
$8\times 8-8+(8+8)/8$	$8\times 8-88/8$	$(88+8)/8$	$8\times 8-8/8$	$8\times 8-8-(88-8)/8$	$8+8-(8+8)/8$	$8\times 8-8$	$8\times 8-(88+8+8)/8$	$8+8$
$8+8+8/8$	$8/8+8\times 8-8$	$8\times 8-8-8+8/8$	$8+(8+8)/8$	$8\times 8+88/8-8-8$	$8\times 8+(8-88)/8$	$8+8-8/8$	$8+8\times 8-88/8$	$8\times 8-8-8-8/8$
$8\times 8-8-8$	$(88+8+8)/8$	$8\times 8-(8+8)/8$	$8\times 8-8-8+(8+8)/8$	$8+8+(8+8)/8$	$8\times 8-8-8/8$	$8+88\times 8/(8+8)$	$88/8$	$8\times 8-8\times 8/(8+8)$

Example 80. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 9:

$(99+99)/9$	$9\times 9-9/9-9$	$9+9+(99+9)/9$	$9+9+9$	$9/9+9\times 9-9-9$	$9+(99+99+9)/9$	$9+99/9$	$9\times 9-(99+9)/9$	$9+9+9+9-(9+9)/9$
$9+9+9+9-9/9$	$9+(99+9)/9$	$9+9+(9\times 99-9)/(9+9)$	$9+9+9+9/9$	$(99+99+9)/9$	$9\times 9-9$	$99\times 9/(9+9+9)$	$9+9+9-(9+9)/9$	$9+(999+9)/(9+9)$
$(9+9)\times 99/(9+9+9)$	$9+(99+99)/9$	$9+9+9-9/9$	$9\times 9-(99+9+9)/9$	$9+9+9+9$	$9+9/9+9$	$9\times 9-99/9$	$9+9+99/9$	$9+9+9-(9+9+9)/9$
$(9\times 9\times 9-9)/(9+9)$	$9-9/9$	$9\times 9+(9+9+9)/9-9$	$9+9+9+9+9$	$9/9$	$9\times 9+(9-9\times 9)/(9+9)$	$9+9+9+99/9$	$9-(9+9+9)/9$	$9\times 9-(9+9)/9$
$9\times 9-9/9$	$9+9+9+(99+9)/9$	$(9\times 9-9)/(9+9)$	$9/9+9\times 9-9$	$(9\times 9\times 9+9)/(9+9)$	9	$9\times 9-(9+9+9)/9$	$9+9+9+9+9-(9+9)/9$	$(9+9)/9$
$(9+9+9)/9$	$9\times 9+(9-99)/(9+9)$	$9+9+9+9+9-9/9$	$(9\times 9+9)/(9+9)$	9×9	$9+9+9+9+9/9$	$9-(9+9)/9$	$9\times 9-9+(9+9)/9$	$9+99\times 9/(9+9+9)$
$9+(9\times 99-9)/(9+9)$	$9\times 9-9-9-9-9/9$	$(99+9)/9$	$9\times 9-9-9$	$9+9+9+9+9+9/9$	$9+(9\times 9+9)/(9+9)$	$(999+9)/(9+9)$	$9\times (9+9)-999/9$	$9+9-(9+9)/9$
$9+9-9/9$	$((9+9)/9)^9+9/9/9$	$(9\times 99-9)/(9+9)$	$9+9/9$	$9+(9\times 99+9)/(9+9)$	$9\times 9-9-9-9$	$9+9-(9+9+9)/9$	$9\times 9-9-99/9$	$9+9+9+9+99/9$
$9+9+9+9+(99+9)/9$	$(99+9+9)/9$	$9\times 9-9-9-9/9$	$(9\times 99+9)/(9+9)$	$9+9$	$(999-9)/(9+9)$	$9\times 9-9-9-99/9$	$99/9$	$9\times 9-9-(99+9)/9$

Example 81. Let's consider a **bimagic** square of order 9 given by

									369
1	18	23	35	40	48	60	65	79	369
33	38	52	55	72	77	8	13	21	369
62	67	75	6	11	25	28	45	50	369
27	5	10	49	30	44	74	61	69	369
47	34	42	81	59	64	22	3	17	369
76	57	71	20	7	15	54	32	37	369
14	19	9	39	53	31	70	78	56	369
43	51	29	68	73	63	12	26	4	369
66	80	58	16	24	2	41	46	36	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, the above magic square of order 9 is **bimagic** with **bimagic** sum $Sb_{9 \times 9} := 20049$. Each 3×3 block is with equal sum entries as of magic square i.e., 369.

Example 82. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 1:

1	$(1+1) \times (11-1-1)$	$1+11+11$	$1+1+11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11-1)$	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11)$	$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)$	$1+(1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}-1-1$
$11 \times (1+1+1)$	$1+111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$(111-1)/(1+1)$	$(1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$11 \times (1+(1+1) \times (1+1+1))$	$(1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$1+1+11$	$11+11-1$
$1+(1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	$1+(1+1) \times 11 \times (1+1+1)$	$1+(1+1) \times 111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (1+1+1)$	11	$1+(1+1) \times (1+11)$	$1+(1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$1+(1+1) \times (11+11)$	$(11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$
$(1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$1+1+1+1+1$	11-1	$1+(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11)$	$(11-1) \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11+11)$	$(1+1) \times 111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	$(1+1+1) \times (1+11+11)$
$1+(1+1) \times (1+11+11)$	$1+11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11+11-1)$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}$	$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)-1$	$(1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$	11+11	1+1+1	$1+(1+1)^{1+1+1+1}$
$(1+1) \times (1+111/(1+1+1))$	$1+(1+111)/(1+1)$	$(1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1)-1$	$(1+1) \times (11-1)$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+1+1)$	$1+1+1+1+11$	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1$	$11 \times (1+1+1)-1$	$111/(1+1+1)$
$1+1+1+11$	$(1+1) \times (11-1)-1$	11-1-1	$(1+1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1-1$	$1+(11-1) \times (1+1+1)$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}-11$	$111-11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+111)/(1+1)$
$(1+1) \times (11+11)-1$	$1+(11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$(11-1) \times (1+1+1)-1$	$(1+1) \times (1+11 \times (1+1+1))$	$1+(1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$(1+1+1) \times (11+11-1)$	1+11	$(1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$1+1+1+1$
$(1+1) \times 11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}-1$	$1+1+(1+111)/(1+1)$	$(1+1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$(1+1) \times (1+11)$	1+1	$1+(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11-1)$	$(1+1) \times (1+11+11)$	$(1+1+1) \times (1+11)$

Example 83. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 2:

$2/2$	$2 + 2^{2+2}$	$22 + 2/2$	$2 + 22/2 + 22$	$2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)$	$2/2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$(2/2 + 2)^{2+2} - 2$
$22 + 22/2$	$2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times 2 \times 22 - 22/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 + 22/2$	$22 - 2/2$
$2^{2+2+2} - 2$	$2 + 2^{2+2+2} + 2/2$	$22/2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2 + 2 + 2$	$22/2$	$2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 22 + 2 + 2$	$2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$
$2 + 22 + 2/2 + 2$	$2 + 2/2 + 2$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	2×22	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2 - 2$	$(2/2 + 2) \times (22 + 2/2)$
$2 + 2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$2 \times 22 - 2$	$(2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$	$22/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	2^{2+2+2}	22	$2 + 2/2$	$2/2 + 2^{2+2}$
$2 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)$	$2 + 22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 - 2/2$	$22 - 2$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 + 22/2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$2/2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$
$2^{2+2} - 2$	$22 - 2/2 - 2$	$(2/2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times (22 - 2) - 2/2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$22 + (2/2 + 2)^2$	$22 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2) - 2$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)$
$2 \times 22 - 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2) + 2/2$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2/2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$	$2 + 22 + 2$	$2 + 2$
$2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$22 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	2^{2+2}	$2 + 22$	2	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2 + 2 \times 22$	$(2 + 2 + 2)^2$

Example 84. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 3:

$3/3$	$3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3^3 - 3 - 3/3$	$3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 33$	$3^3 + 33$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 + 3/3 - 3$
33	$3^3 + 33/3$	$3^3 + 3/3 - 3 + 3^3$	$3^3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3 \times (3^3 - 3)$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3/3 - 3$	$3 \times 3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$
$3 + 33 - 3/3 + 3^3$	$3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$	$3 + 3 \times (3^3 - 3)$	$3 + 3$	$33/3$	$3^3 - 3 + 3/3$	$3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 33/3$
3^3	$3 + 3 - 3/3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3^3 + 33 - 33/3$	$3 + 3^3$	$33 + 33/3$	$3 + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3$	$3 + 33 + 33$
$3 + 33/3 + 33$	$3/3 + 33$	$3 \times 3 + 33$	3×3^3	$3^3 + 33 - 3/3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3$	$33 - 33/3$	3	$3 + 33/3 + 3$
$3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3^3$	$((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3$	$3 \times 3 + 33/3$	$3 + 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$33 - 3/3$	$3 + 33 + 3/3$
$3 + 33/3$	$3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	3×3	$3 + 3 + 33$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + (3/3 + 3)^3 + 3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3$	$(333 + 3)/(3 + 3)$
$3 \times 3 + 3/3 + 33$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3$	$3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 - 3$	$((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3$	$3 + 33 + 3^3$	$3 + 3 \times 3$	$3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3/3$
$33 + 33$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3$	$3^3 - 33/3$	$3^3 - 3$	$3 - 3/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3^3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 + 33$

Example 85. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 4:

$4/4$	$4 \times 4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$44 - 4$	$4 + 44$	$4 \times 4 + 44$	$(4^4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (44 + 4^4)/4$
$4/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$44 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 + 44$	$44 + 44/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$	$(4 - 4/4)^4 - 4$	$4 + 4$	$4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$	$4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$
$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4)/4$	$(44 + 4^4)/4$	$4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$44/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$44 - 4 \times 4$	$44 + 4/4$	$4 + 44 + (4 + 4)/4$
$4 \times 4 + 44/4$	$4 + 4/4$	$(44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 44 + 4/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4$	44	$(4^4 + 44 - 4)/4$	$(4^4 + 4)/4 - 4$	$4 + (4^4 + 4)/4$
$4 + 44 - 4/4$	$44 + (4 - 44)/4$	$44 - (4 + 4)/4$	$(4 - 4/4)^4$	$(4^4 - 4)/4 - 4$	$4 \times 4 \times 4$	$44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$4 - 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + 4/4$
$44 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + (4^4 - 44)/4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4)/4 + 4$	$4 + 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 - 4/4$	$4 + 44/4$	$44 + (44 - 4)/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4$
$4 + (44 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 + 4 + 4/4$	$44 - 4 - 4/4$	$(4^4 - 44)/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$4 + (4^4 + 4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4 + 44)/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44$
$44 - 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 44 - 4/4$	$44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4 + (4^4 + 4)/4 + 4$	$(4^4 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4 + 4$	$4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	4
$(4^4 + 4 + 4)/4$	$4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 - 4$	4×4	$4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$(4 + 4)/4$	$44 - 4 + 4/4$	$44 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$

Example 86. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 5:

$5/5$	$5 + (55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$55 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55$	$5 + 5 + 55$	$5 \times 5 + 55 - 5/5$
$5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$55 - 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	55	$5 + 55 + (55 + 5)/5$	$55 + (55 + 55)/5$	$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$(55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55/5 + 5$
$5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$55 + (55 + 5)/5$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)$	$5 + 5/5$	$55/5$	5×5	$5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 5 - 5$	$5 \times (5 + 5)$
$5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	5	$5 + 5$	$55 - 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5$	$55 - 55/5$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5/5$	$5 + 55 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$
$5 + 5 + 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 + 5/5$	$5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$	$(55 + 55)/5$	$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + (55 + 5)/5$
$5/5 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)$	$55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55 + 55/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5$	$5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 + 5$	$55 - 5/5$	$((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
$5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5$	$55 - 5 - 55/5$	$55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$5 + 55 + 5 + 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 + 5/5$
$55 - (55 + 5)/5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 + (5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (5 + 5)/5$	$(5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$	$(55 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$5 - 5/5$
$55 + 55/5$	$5 \times 5 + 55$	$5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$(5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 55/5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5 - 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55/5$

Example 87. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 6:

$6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + 6 + 66/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6$	$66 - 6$	$66 - 6/6$	$6 + 6 + 66 + 6/6$
$66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6 - 6$	$66 - 66/6$	$6 + 66$	$66 + 66/6$	$6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6$	$6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6)$
$66 - 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66 + 6/6$	$666/6 - 6 \times 6$	6	$66/6$	$6 \times 6 - 66/6$	$6 + (66 + 66)/6$	$666/6 - 66$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
$66 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 6$	$6 - 6/6$	$(66 - 6)/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66 + 6/6 - 6$	$66 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
$6 \times 6 + 66/6$	$6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6$	$6 + 666/6 - 6 \times 6$	$66 - 6/6 - 6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6$	$(66 + 66)/6$	$6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 66/6$
$6 + 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$	$66 + (6 + 6 - 66)/6$	$6 + 66 - 6/6$	$6 + ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6)$	$6 + 6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$66 - 6 - 6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 - 6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6$
$6 + 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 66/6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6 - 6$	$6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$	$6 + 66 + 6$	$66 + (6 - 66)/6$
$6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 - 66 + 666/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6 - 6/6$	$66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 66 + 6/6$	$66 - 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 - 66)/6$	$6 - (6 + 6)/6$
66	$6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6$	$6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 + (6 + 6 + 6)$	$(6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6$	6×6

Example 88. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 7:

$7/7$	$7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 + 77/7$	$77 - (77 + 7)/7$	$77 + (7 + 7)/7$
$7 + 7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$77 + (7 + 7)/7 - 7$	77	$7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7$
$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 + 77/7$	$77 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 - 7/7$	$77/7$	$7 + 7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$7 \times 7 + 7/7$
$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$(77 - 7)/7$	7×7	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$77 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$77 - 7 - 7/7$
$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7$	$77 - 7 + 77/7$	$7 \times 7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$(7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + (77 - 7)/7$
$77 - 7/7$	$7 + 7/7 + 7 \times 7$	$7/7 + 77 - 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	7	$7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 77/7 + 7 + 7$	$7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7$
$7 + 7$	$7 + (7 + 77)/7$	$7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + 77/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 77/7$	$77 - 7$	$7/7 + 77$	$7 + 7 \times 7$
$7 \times 7 + 7/7 - 7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$77 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 77 - 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7$	$(77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$77/7 - 7$
$77 - 77/7$	$77 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + ((77 - 7)/7 + 7)$	$(7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7/7 + (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7))$

Example 89. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 8:

$8/8$	$8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8/8 + 8 \times 8$	$88 - 8 - 8/8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$8 + 88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 \times 8$	$88 - 88/8$	8	$(88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
$8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 + 88/8$	$8 \times 8 + 88/8$	$8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$88/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
$8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$	$8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + 8/8$	$8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 \times 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 - 88/8$	$88 - 8 - 88/8$
$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 88)/8$	$8/8 + 88 - 8$	$8 \times 8 + 88/8 - 8 - 8$	8×8	$(88 + 88)/8$	$88/8 - 8$	$8 + 8 + 8/8$
$8 \times 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8/8 + 8 \times 8 - 8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 - 8/8$	$8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 + (8 - 88)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$888/(8 + 8 + 8)$
$8 + 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 88/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$88 + (8 - 88)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + 8/8 + 8 \times 8$	$8 \times 8 - 8/8$	$(88 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
$8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$88 - 8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8$	$8 + 8 + 8$	$(8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - (88 - 8)/8$	$(8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$

Example 90. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 9 given in Example 71 in terms of single digit 9:

$9/9$	$9 + 9$	$(99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - (99 + 9)/9$	$9 + (999 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)/9$
$99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$(999 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - 9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 - 9/9$	$(99 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + (99 + 9)/9$
$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 + (9 + 9 + 9)/9 - 9$	$9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9$	$(9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$
$9 + 9 + 9$	$(9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9/9$	$(9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 + (9 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9$
$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$	9×9	$9 + (9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	$(99 + 99)/9$	$(9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 - 9/9$
$9 \times 9 + (9 - 99)/(9 + 9)$	$((9 + 9)/9)^9 + 9/9/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9/9 - 9$	$9 + 99/9$	$9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 + (99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$
$9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9/9 + 9$	9	$9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$	$9 + (99 + 99)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 99/9$	$9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$(999 + 9)/(9 + 9)$
$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 \times (9 + 9) - 999/9$	$9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 \times 9 - (99 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	$(99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$(9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$
$(9 + 9) \times 99/(9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - 9/9$	$9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$	$(9 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9$

In all the Examples 72 – 90, the magic square sum is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11^{1+1})) &= (2/2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 + 2) &= 3 + (333 + 33) \\
 &:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - 4^4 &= (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - (5/5 + 5) &= 6 + 66 \times 66 / (6 + 6) \\
 &:= 7 + (((77 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7) + 7) &= 8 + ((88/8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8}) &= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)).
 \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 7. Write the following **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 in numbers:

		495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495
	34	88	43	39	81	45	32	86	47	495
495	48	33	84	41	35	89	46	37	82	495
495	83	44	38	85	49	31	87	42	36	495
495	54	18	93	59	11	95	52	16	97	495
495	98	53	14	91	55	19	96	57	12	495
495	13	94	58	15	99	51	17	92	56	495
495	74	68	23	79	61	25	72	66	27	495
495	28	73	64	21	75	69	26	77	62	495
495	63	24	78	65	29	71	67	22	76	495
	495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495

2.8 Magic Squares of Order 10

Example 91. Let's consider a magic square of order 10 is given by

										505
1	80	65	97	39	22	48	86	53	14	505
98	12	9	66	90	74	55	33	41	27	505
47	81	23	79	16	35	94	60	62	8	505
70	57	88	34	2	91	29	15	76	43	505
84	99	52	11	45	68	73	7	30	36	505
13	38	44	10	77	56	82	21	95	69	505
75	46	40	83	28	19	67	92	4	51	505
59	24	96	42	61	3	20	78	37	85	505
26	5	17	58	93	50	31	64	89	72	505
32	63	71	25	54	87	6	49	18	100	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 92. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 91 in terms of single digit 1:

1	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}-1$	$1+(1+1)^{(1+1)\times(1+1+1)}$	$111-11-1-1-1$	$(1+1+1)\times(1+1+11)$	$11+11$	$(1+1)\times(1+1)\times(1+11)$	$(1+1)\times((1+1)\times(11+11))-1$	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1-1$	$1+1+1+11$
$111-11-1-1-1$	$1+11$	$11-1-1$	$(1+1)\times 11\times(1+1+1)$	$(11-1)\times(11-1-1)$	$(1+1)\times 111/(1+1+1)$	$(111-1)/(1+1)$	$11\times(1+1+1)$	$1+(1+1)\times(1+1)\times(11-1)$	$(1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$
$1+(1+1)\times(1+11+11)$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}$	$1+11+11$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}-1-1$	$(1+1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$1+1+11\times(1+1+1)$	$1+((1+1)^{11-1}-1)/11$	$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)$	$1+(1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	$(1+1)^{1+1+1}$
$(11-1-1)^{1+1}-11$	$1+(1+111)/(1+1)$	$11\times(1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$1+11\times(1+1+1)$	$1+1$	$1+(11-1)\times(11-1-1)$	$(11-1)\times(1+1+1)-1$	$1+1+1+1+11$	$(1+1)\times(1+111)/(1+1+1)$	$(1+1)\times(11+11)-1$
$1+1+1+(11-1-1)^{1+1}$	$11\times(11-1-1)$	$(1+1)\times(1+1)\times(1+1+11)$	11	$1+(1+1)\times(11+11)$	$(1+1)\times(1+11\times(1+1+1))$	$1+(1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$1+(1+1)\times(1+1+1)$	$(11-1)\times(1+1+1)$	$(1+1+1)\times(1+11)$
$1+1+11$	$1+111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+1)\times(11+11)$	$9+9+9+9+9-9/9$	$11\times(1+(1+1)\times(1+1+1))$	$(1+111)/(1+1)$	$1+(11-1-1)^{1+1}$	$11+11-1$	$111-(1+1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$(1+1+1)\times(1+11+11)$
$1+(1+1)\times 111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+1)\times(1+11+11)$	$(1+1)\times(1+1)\times(11-1)$	$1+1+(11-1-1)^{1+1}$	$1+(1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$(1+1)\times(11-1)-1$	$1+(1+1)\times 11\times(1+1+1)$	$11+(11-1-1)^{1+1}$	$1+1+1+1$	$1+(11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$
$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)-1$	$(1+1)\times(1+11)$	$(1+11)\times(1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$(1+1)\times(11+11-1)$	$(1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	$1+1+1$	$(1+1)\times(11-1)$	$111-11\times(1+1+1)$	$111/(1+1+1)$	$111-(1+1)\times(1+1+11)$
$(1+1)\times(1+1+11)$	$1+1+1+1+1$	$1+(1+1)^{1+1+1+1}$	$1+1+(1+111)/(1+1)$	$((1+1)^{11-1}-1)/11$	$(11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$1+(11-1)\times(1+1+1)$	$(1+1)^{(1+1)\times(1+1+1)}$	$111-11-11$	$(1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1)$
$11\times(1+1+1)-1$	$(1+1+1)\times(11+11-1)$	$(1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1)-1$	$1+(1+1)\times(1+11)$	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1$	$111-(1+1)\times(1+11)$	$(1+1)\times(1+1+1)$	$1+(1+1)\times(1+1)\times(1+11)$	$(1+1)\times(11-1-1)$	$(11-1)^{1+1}$

Example 93. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 91 in terms of single digit 2:

$2/2$	$2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2/2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2/2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 \times (22 - 2) - 2/2$	22	$2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$2^{2+2} - 2$
$2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$	$(2/2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$22 + 22/2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2 + 22 + 2/2 + 2$
$2 + 2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$(2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$	$22 + 2/2$	$(2/2 + 2)^{2+2} - 2$	2^{2+2}	$2 + 22/2 + 22$	$2 + 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$	$2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2$	$2 \times (2 + 2)$
$22 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$2 \times 2 \times 22$	$2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2}$	2	$2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 + 22/2$	$2 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)$	$2 \times 22 - 2/2$
$2 \times (2 \times 22 - 2)$	$(22/2)^2 - 22$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	22/2	$2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2/2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$	$22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$(2 + 2 + 2)^2$
$2 + 22/2$	$2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	2×22	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 \times 2 \times 22 - 22/2$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)$	$2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$22 - 2/2$	$222/2 - 2^{2+2}$	$(2/2 + 2) \times (22 + 2/2)$
$22/2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2 + 2 \times 22$	$2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$	$2 + 22 + 2 + 2$	$22 - 2/2 - 2$	$2 + 2^{2+2+2} + 2/2$	$2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$	2 + 2	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2) + 2/2$
$22/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	2 + 22	$2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 \times 22 - 2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2 - 2$	$2 + 2/2$	22 - 2	$2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2) - 2$	$2/2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$
$2 + 22 + 2$	$2 + 2/2 + 2$	$2/2 + 2^{2+2}$	$22 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2/2 + 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$22 + (2/2 + 2)^2$	2^{2+2+2}	$2/2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$
$2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 - 2/2$	$2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2/2$	2 + 2 + 2	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 2^{2+2}$	$(2 \times (2 + 2) + 2)^2$

Example 94. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 91 in terms of single digit 3:

$3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 + 3/3$	$3/3 + 3 \times 33 - 3$	$3 + 3 + 33$	$33 - 33/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 33$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 33/3$
$3 \times 33 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3$	3×3	$33 + 33$	$3 \times (3^3 + 3)$	$3 + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3$	$3^3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	33	$3 + 33/3 + 3^3$	3^3
$3 + 33/3 + 33$	3×3^3	$3^3 - 3 - 3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 + 3/3 - 3$	$3^3 - 33/3$	$3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 3) + 3/3$	$3^3 + 33$	$3 + 33 - 3/3 + 3^3$	$3 \times 3 - 3/3$
$3 + (3/3 + 3)^3 + 3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3^3$	$3 \times 33 - 33/3$	$3/3 + 33$	$3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$	$3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3 + 33$
$3 + 3 \times 3^3$	3×33	$3^3 + 3/3 - 3 + 3^3$	$33/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33$	$((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 - 3$	$((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3$	$3 + 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3^3$	$3 + 33$
$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3^3 + 33/3$	$33 + 33/3$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3/3 - 3$	$(333 + 3)/(3 + 3)$	$3/3 + 3 \times 3^3$	$3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 \times 33 - 3 - 3/3$	$3 + 33 + 33$
$3 + 3 \times (3^3 - 3)$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 3/3$	$3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$	$3 \times 3^3 + 33/3$	$3 + 3/3$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3$
$3^3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3^3 - 3$	$3 \times 33 - 3$	$3 \times 3 + 33$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3$	3	$3 \times 3 + 33/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3$	$3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3^3 + 3/3$
$3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 - 3/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3$	$3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 3)$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 33/3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3$	$3 \times (3^3 + 3) - 3/3$	$3 \times (3^3 - 3)$
$33 - 3/3$	$3 + 33 + 3^3$	$((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3$	$3^3 - 3 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + 3 \times 3^3 + 3$	3 + 3	$3^3 + 33 - 33/3$	$3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3/3 + 3 \times 33$

Example 95. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 91 in terms of single digit 4:

$4/4$	$4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$(4^4 + 4)/4$	$4 \times 4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$	$44 - 4 - 4/4$	$44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$4 + 44$	$4 + (4 - 4/4)^4 + 4/4$	$(4^4 - 44)/4$	$4 + (44 - 4)/4$
$4 + (444 - 4)/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + 4$	$4 + 4 + 4/4$	$(4^4 + 4 + 4)/4$	$44 + ((4 + 4)/4 + 44)$	$(4^4 + 44 - 4)/4$	$44 + 44/4$	$4/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$44 - 4 + 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + 44/4$
$4 + 44 - 4/4$	$(4 - 4/4)^4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 + (44 + 4^4)/4$	4×4	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$(444 - 4)/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 \times 4 + 44$	$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4$
$4 + (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4)$	$4 + (4^4 - 44)/4$	$44 + 44$	$44 + (4 - 44)/4$	$(4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 44 + 44 - 4/4$	$44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 44/4$	$44 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$44 - 4/4$
$4 + 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$4 - 4 \times 4 + 444/4$	$4 + 4 + 44$	$44/4$	$44 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4 + (4^4 + 4)/4 + 4$	$4 + 4 - 4/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$
$4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$	$44 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4$	44	$(44 - 4)/4$	$(4 - 4/4)^4 - 4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44$	$4/4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$	$4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$444/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + (4^4 + 4)/4$
$(44 + 4^4)/4$	$44 + (4 + 4)/4$	$44 - 4$	$4 + (44 + 4^4)/4 + 4$	$44 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4)/4$	$4 + 44 + 44$	4	$4 + 4 + 44 - 4/4$
$(4^4 - 4)/4 - 4$	$4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4 + 4)$	$44 - (4 + 4)/4$	$(4^4 + 4)/4 - 4$	$4 - 4/4$	$4 + 4 \times 4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4 + 44)/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4$	$4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$
$4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$4 + 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 - 4$	$((4 + 4)^4 - 4)/44$	$4 + 44 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$
$4 \times (4 + 4)$	$(4^4 - 4)/4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4)/4 + 4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$44 + (44 - 4)/4$	$44 + 44 - 4/4$	$4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 44 + 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4 + 4)$

Example 96. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 91 in terms of single digit 5:

$5/5$	$5 \times 5 + 55$	$5 + 5 + 55$	$5 + 5 + 55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$55 - 5 - 55/5$	$(55 + 55)/5$	$55 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$555/5 - 5 \times 5$	$55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$
$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - (5 + 5)/5$	$(55 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5$	$55 + 55/5$	$5 + (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5)$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5/5$	55	$5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 55/5$	$5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$
$5 + 5 + 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 + 5/5$	$5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 + 55/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 55$	$5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
$5 + 55 + 5 + 5$	$55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 + (5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$(5 + 5)/5$	$5 - 5 \times 5 + 555/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5$	$5/5 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)$	$55 - (55 + 5)/5$
$5 + (55 - 5/5) + 5 \times 5$	$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5$	$55 - 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$55/5$	$55 - 5 - 5$	$5 + (5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55/5$
$(55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$55 - 55/5$	$5 + 5$	$55 + (55 + 55)/5$	$55 + 5/5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55/5 + 5$	$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$
$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)$	$55 + 5/5 - 5 - 5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + 55 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5$	$55 + (55 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 - 5/5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5$
$5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5$	$5 + 55 + 5/5$	$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 55$
$5 \times 5 + 5/5$	5	$5 + (55 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 \times 5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 \times (5 + 5)$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 55/5$	$+55 + (55 + 5)/5$
$((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$(5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$	$5 + 55 + 55/5$	5×5	$55 - 5/5$	$55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5/5$	$55 - 5 - 5/5$	$5 + (55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$

Example 97. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 91 in terms of single digit 6:

$6/6$	$6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66 - 6/6$	$6 \times 6 + 66 - 6 + 6/6$	$6 + 66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$(66 + 66)/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6$	$6 + 6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 66/6$	$6 + 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
$(666 - 6)/6 - 6 - 6$	$6 + 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	66	$6 + ((66 + 6 + 6) + 6)$	$6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66 - 66/6$	$66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$66 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 6$
$6 \times 6 + 66/6$	$6 + 666/6 - 6 \times 6$	$6 + 6 + 66/6$	$6 + 6 + 66 + 6/6$	$6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^5 - 6$	$66 - 6$	$66 - 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + (6 + 6)/6$
$6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^5$	$66 + (6 + 6 - 66)/6$	$66 + (66 + 66)/6$	$6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$(6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 + 66 - 66/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6 - 6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^5$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$
$6 + 66 + 6 + 6$	$666/6 - 6 - 6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^5 - 6 - 6$	$66/6$	$666/6 - 66$	$66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 66 + 6/6$	$6 + 6/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6$	6×6
$6 + 6/6 + 6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$(66 - 6)/6$	$66 + 66/6$	$66 + (6 - 66)/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^5$	$6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 + 66 - 6 - 6/6$	$66 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
$666/6 - 6 \times 6$	$6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 66/6 + 66$	$6 + (66 + 66)/6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6 + 6$	$66 + 6/6$	$6 \times 6 + 66 + (6 - 66)/6$	$6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 - 66 + 666/6$
$66 - 6/6 - 6$	$6 + (6 + 6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 + 66 - 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6$	$66 + 6/6 - 6$	$6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6)$	$6 + 66 + 6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 + 66 + 6/6$
$6 \times 6 + (6 - 66)/6$	$6 - 6/6$	$6 + 66/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^5 - 6$	$666/6 - 6 - 6 - 6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6 - 6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^5$	$6 + 66 + 6 + 66/6$	$6 + 66$
$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 - 6$	$66 - 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 66 - 6/6$	$6 \times 6 - 66/6$	$66 - 6 - 6$	$6 + 666/6 - 6 \times 6 + 6$	6	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6$	$6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^5$

Example 98. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 91 in terms of single digit 7:

$7/7$	$77 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$77 - (77 + 7)/7$	$7 \times (7 + 7) - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 + (7 + 7)/7 + 77$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7$
$7 \times (7 + 7)$	$(77 + 7)/7$	$7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$77 - 77/7$	$7 + (77 - 7/7 + 7)$	$77 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$
$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$77 - 7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$77 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7$	$7 + 77 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7/7$
$77 - 7$	$7 + 7/7 + 7 \times 7$	$77 + 77/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$(7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 77 + 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7/7$	$77 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 + 7/7 - 7$
$7 + 77$	$7/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$	$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$77/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$77 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 77 - 77/7$	7	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7/7 + (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7))$
$7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$(77 - 7)/7$	77	$7 + 7 \times 7$	$7 + 77 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + 77 + 77/7$	$77 - 7 - 7/7$
$77 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 77 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + (7 + 77)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 77 + 7/7$	$77/7 - 7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
$7 \times 7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 + ((77 - 7)/7 + 7)$	$7 \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7$	$7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$(7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7/7 + 77$	$7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 77 + 7/7$
$7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 77 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 + 7/7$	$77 + (77 + 7)/7$	$77 + (7 + 7)/7 - 7$
$7 + 77/7 + 7 + 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7$	$7/7 + 77 - 7$	$7 + 7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$77 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 - 7/7$	7×7	$7 + 77/7$	$(7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$

Example 99. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 91 in terms of single digit 8:

$8/8$	$88 - 8$	$8/8 + 8 \times 8$	$8 + 88 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$(88 + 88)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8$	$88 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 88/8$	$8 + 8 - (8 + 8)/8$
$8 + 88 + (8 + 8)/8$	$(88 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$88 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 88/8$
$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$8/8 + 88 - 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$88 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 + 88 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	8
$8 + 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8/8 + 8 \times 8 - 8$	88	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$(8 + 8)/8$	$88 + (88/8 - 8)$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$
$88 - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$88 + 88/8$	$8 + 88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$88/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 88/8$	$8 \times 8 + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + 8/8 + 8 \times 8$	$8 - 8/8$	$8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$(8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$
$(88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$88 - 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8$	$88 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 88 - 8/8$	$88 - 8 - 88/8$
$8 \times 8 + 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - (88 - 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 + 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 + 88/8$	$88 + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
$8 \times 8 + 88/8 - 8 - 8$	$8 + (8 + 8)$	$8 + 88$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 88)/8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 - 88/8$	$88/8 - 8$	$8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$88 + (8 - 88)/8$	$888/(8 + 8 + 8)$	$8 + 88 - 88/8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$	$8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 88 + 8 - 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	8×8	$8/8 + 88$	$8 + 8 \times 8$
$8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8 \times 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 + (8 - 88)/8$	$88 - 8/8$	$8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$88 + (88 + 8)/8$

Example 100. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 91 in terms of single digit 9:

$9/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9/9$	$9 + (999 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$99 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$(99 + 99)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$	$9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$
$99 - 9/9$	$(99 + 9)/9$	9	$(9 + 9) \times 99/(9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 \times 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 + (9 + 9)/9$	$(999 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9$
$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	9×9	$(99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$99 + (9 - 99)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - (99 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$	$9 - 9/9$
$9 \times 9 - 99/9$	$((9 + 9)/9)^9 + 9/9/9$	$99 - 99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$(9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 \times 9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 - 99)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$
$9 \times 9 + (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	99	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9$	$9 \times 9 - (99 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9$	$9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9$
$(99 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9/9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)$	$(999 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9/9 + 9 \times 9$	$9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$99 + (9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9$
$9 \times 9 + (9 + 9 + 9)/9 - 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 + (9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 + 9/9 + 9$	$9 + 9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 + 99/9$	$(9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times (9 + 9) - 999/9$
$9 + (9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$	$99 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$(9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 99/9$	$9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$
$9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$(9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 + (99 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + (99 + 99)/9$	$9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 + 9 \times 9 - 9/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9$
$9 + (99 + 99 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9/9 - 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9$	$99 - (99 + 9)/9$	$9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$	$(9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$	$9 + 9$	$9/9 + 99$

In all the Examples 92 – 100, the magic square sum is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{S}_{10 \times 10} &:= (11111 - 1)/(11 + 11) = 22 + 22^2 - 2/2 = 3/3 + (3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3) \\
 &:= ((4 + 4) \times (4^4 - 4) + 4)/4 = 5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) = 6/6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6) \\
 &:= 7 + 7 \times (77 - 7) + 7/7 + 7 = 8/8 + 8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8 = (9 + 9)/9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^9 - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

2.9 Block-Bordered Magic Squares

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 based on magic square of order 8. These are based on the Examples 51 and 61.

Example 101. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88
89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12
11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90
96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5
1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100
93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8
7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94
95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

In this case the 4 blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 202$. The magic square of order 8 is with magic sums $S_{8 \times 8} := 404$

Example 102. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 with inner part as **bimagic** square of order 8 is given by

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	34	59	54	23	45	80	73	36	88
89	44	81	72	37	31	62	51	26	12
11	19	58	63	30	40	69	76	49	90
96	41	68	77	48	22	55	66	27	5
1	56	21	28	65	67	42	47	78	100
93	70	39	50	75	57	20	29	64	8
7	61	32	25	52	82	43	38	71	94
95	79	46	35	74	60	33	24	53	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

In this case, the magic square of order 8 is **pandiagonal** and **bimagic** with **magic** and **bimagic** sums as $S_{8 \times 8} := 404$ and $Sb_{8 \times 8} := 23132$.

Example 103. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 101 in terms of single digit 1:

$1+(11-11) \times (11-1-1)$	$11 \times 11 \times (11+1) \times (11+11-1)$	$11 \times 11^{11+11}$	$1+(1+1) \times (11-1) \times 11^{11}$	$11 \times 11 \times (11-1-1)$	$1+(1+1+1)$	$1+(1+1+1)$	$11-11-1-1$	$1+1$	$11 \times (11-1) \times 11^{11}$
$1+(1+1)$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+11+11)$	$1+(1+1111)/(1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11-1)-1$	$111-11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$(1+1) \times 11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}-11$	$11 \times (1+1)^{11+11}$
$111-11-11$	$11+11$	$1+(1+1) \times 1111/(1+1+1)$	$(11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$(111-1)/(1+1)$	$(11-1) \times (1+1+1)$	$1+(1+1) \times 11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11+11-1)$	$(1+1+1) \times (11+11-1)$	$1+11$
11	$1+(11-1-1)^{1+1}$	$1+11+11$	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1$	$(1+1) \times (11+11)-1$	$(1+1) \times 1111/(1+1+1)$	$1+(11-1) \times (1+1+1)$	$1+(1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	$1+1+11 \times (1+1+1)$	$(11-1) \times (11-1-1)$
$11 \times 111 \times (1+1)^{11+11}$	$1+(11-1)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (1+11+11)$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}-1-1$	$(1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)-1$	$1+1111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1)-1$	$1+11 \times (1+1+1)$	$1+(1+1) \times 1+1$
1	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11)$	$1+(1+1111)/(1+1)$	$(1+1) \times (11-1)$	$11 \times (1+(1+1) \times (1+1+1))$	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11-1)$	$1+(1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$	$1+(1+1+1)^{1+1+1}$	$(1+1+1) \times (1+11+11)$	$(11-1)^{1+1}$
$(11 \times 11^{11+11}-1)/11$	$11+11-1$	$(1+1) \times (1+1111)/(1+1+1)$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+11)$	$(1+111)/(1+1)$	$(11-1) \times (1+1+1)-1$	$(1+1) \times (1+11 \times (1+1+1))$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (11-1)$	$(1+1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$	$11 \times 11^{11+11}$
$1+(1+1) \times (1+1+1)$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}$	$(1+1) \times (1+11)$	$(111-1)/(1+1)-1-1$	$(1+1) \times (11+11)$	$1+(1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$11 \times (1+1+1)-1$	$(1+11^{1+1})/(1+1)$	$(1+1+1) \times (1+11)$	$1+(1+1) \times 11^{11+11}-1/11$
$111-11 \times 11^{11+11}$	$(1+1) \times (1+1) \times (1+1+11)$	$1+(1+1) \times (11+11)$	$(11-1-1)^{1+1}-1$	$1+(1+1) \times (1+11)$	$(11^{1+1}-1)/(1+1)$	$111/(1+1+1)$	$(1+11)^{1+1}/(1+1)$	$11 \times (1+1+1)$	$11+11 \times 11+1+11$
$11-1-1$	$1+(1+1+1+1)$	$111-11 \times 11 \times 1+11$	$1+(1+1) \times 11^{11+11}$	$1+(1+1) \times (1-1)^{1+1}$	$111-11 \times 11 \times 1+11$	$111-11-1-1-1$	$1+1+1$	$11 \times (11-1-1)$	$11-1$

Example 104. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 101 in terms of single digit 2:

$2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2$	2^{2+2}	$2 \times (2 \times 22 - 2)$	$2 + 2^{2+2}$	$2^{2+2} - 2$	$2 + 2$	$2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$	2	$2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$
$2 + 22/2$	$2 + 2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$22 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22 - 2/2 - 2$	$2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2) - 2$	$2 \times (22 - 2) - 2/2$	$2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2 + 22 + 2/2 + 2$	$22 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 \times 2 \times 22$
$2/2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22$	22	$22/2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$	$2 + 2^{2+2+2} + 2/2$	$2 \times 22 - 2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$
$22/2$	$2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$2 \times 22 - 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22 + (2/2 + 2)^2$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2$	$2 + 22/2 + 22$	$2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22$
$2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 2 \times (22 + 2) + 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times 22$	$(2/2 + 2)^{2+2} - 2$	$2 + 22 + 2$	$22/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 - 2/2$	$2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$2 + 2/2 + 2$
$2/2$	$2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 22/2 + 2 \times 22$	$22 - 2$	$2 \times 2 \times 22 - 22/2$	$2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2/2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2 + 22 + 2 + 2$	$(2/2 + 2) \times (22 + 2/2)$	$(2 \times (2 + 2) + 2)^2$
$2/2 + 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$	$22 - 2/2$	$2 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)$	$2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 + 2 + 2^{2+2+2}$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 - 2)$	2^{2+2+2}	$2 \times (2 + 2)$
$2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$	$(2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$	$2 + 22$	$2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	2×22	$2/2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times 2^{2+2}$	$2^{2+2+2} - 2/2 - 2$	$(2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$
$222/2 - 2^{2+2}$	$2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$	$2 \times 22 + 2/2$	$2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)$	$2 + 22 + 2/2$	$2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)$	$2/2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$	$22 + 22/2$	$2 + 2 + 2$
$(2/2 + 2)^2$	$2 + 2 + 22/2$	$2 + 2 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$	$2/2 + 2^{2+2}$	$2 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$	$2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2/2$	$2/2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$	$2 + 2/2$	$(22/2)^2 - 22$	$2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$

Example 105. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 101 in terms of single digit 3:

$3^3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$	$3^3 - 33/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3^3$	$3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + 33/3$	$3 + 3/3$	$3 \times 33 - 3/3$	$3 - 3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 + 33/3$
$3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 33$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3$	$3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3$	$3 + 3 + 33$	$33 + 33$	3^3	$3 + (((3/3 + 3)^3) + 3)$	$3 \times 33 - 33/3$
$3 \times (3^3 + 3) - 3/3$	$33 - 33/3$	$3 + 3 \times (3^3 - 3)$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 33/3$	$3^3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 3^3$	$3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$	$3 \times 3 + 33$	$3 + 33 + 3^3$	$3 + 3 \times 3$
$33/3$	$3/3 + 3 \times 3^3$	$3^3 - 3 - 3/3$	$3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 \times 3 + 3/3 + 33$	$3 + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3$	$3 + 3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 33 - 3/3 + 3^3$	$3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3 \times (3^3 + 3)$
$3 \times 33 - 3$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 + 3/3 - 3$	$3^3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 33 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 33/3$	$((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3$	$3/3 + 33$	$3 + 3 - 3/3$
$3/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 33$	$3 + 3^3 + 3^3$	$3 \times 3 + 33/3$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3/3 - 3$	$3 + 3 + 33 + 3/3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 + 3/3$	$3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 33 + 33$	$3/3 + 3 \times 33$
$3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 3)$	$3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$	$3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3$	$3^3 + 33 - 33/3$	$(333 + 3)/(3 + 3)$	$3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 - 3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3^3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3$	$3 \times 3 - 3/3$
$3 + 3 + 3/3$	3×3^3	$3^3 - 3$	$3^3 + 3^3 - 3/3$	$33 + 33/3$	$((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3$	$33 - 3/3$	$(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3$	$3 + 33$	$3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 3) + 3/3$
$3 \times 33 - 3 - 3/3$	$3^3 + 3/3 - 3 + 3^3$	$3 + 3 \times 3 + 33$	$3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$	$3^3 - 3 + 3/3$	$3^3 + 33$	$3 + 33 + 3/3$	$3 \times (3^3 - 3)$	33	$3 + 3$
3×3	$3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$	$3 + 3 \times 3^3 + 3/3$	$3 + 33/3 + 3$	$3 + 3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$	$3 + 3 \times 3^3 + 3$	$3/3 + 3 \times 33 - 3$	3	3×33	$3 \times 3 + 3/3$

Example 106. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 101 in terms of single digit 4:

$4 + 44 + 44 - 4/4$	$4 + (4 - 4/4)^4 + 4/4$	4×4	$4 + 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$4 \times 4 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (44 - 4)/4$	4	$4 + (444 - 4)/4 - 4 \times 4$	$(4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 44 + 44$
$4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$	$4 + 44 - 4/4$	$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 - 4$	$4 + 4 + 44/4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4 + 44)/4$	$44 - 4 - 4/4$	$(4^4 + 4 + 4)/4$	$4 \times 4 + 44/4$	$4 + (4^4 + 4 + 4)/4$	$44 + 44$
$4 + 4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$	$44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$(44 + 4^4)/4$	$4 + 44 + (4 + 4)/4$	$44 + 44/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4)/4$	$44 - (4 + 4)/4$	$(4^4 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4 + 4$
$44/4$	$4/4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44/4$	$44 + (44 - 4)/4$	$44 - 4/4$	$(4^4 + 44 - 4)/4$	$4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$	$44 + ((4 + 4)/4 + 44)$
$4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 + 44 - 4/4$	$44 + (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (44 + 4^4)/4$	$4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$	$(4^4 - 4)/4 - 4$	$44 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4$	$4 + (4^4 - 4)/4 + 4$	$44 + (4 - 44)/4$	$4 + 4/4$
$4/4$	$4 + 44$	$4 + (4^4 - 44)/4$	$4 + 4 \times 4$	$(4 - 4/4)^4 - 4$	$44 - 4$	$(4^4 + 4)/4$	$44 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + (4^4 + 4)/4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4 + 4)$
$((4 + 4)^4 - 4)/44$	$4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$44 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + 44 + 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 + 44$	$44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$	$44 - 4 + 4/4$	$4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4$
$4 + 4 - 4/4$	$(4 - 4/4)^4$	$4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$(4^4 - 44)/4$	44	$4 + (4^4 + 4)/4 + 4$	$4 \times (4 + 4)$	$(4^4 + 4)/4 - 4$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$(444 - 4)/4 - 4 \times 4$
$444/4 - 4 \times 4$	$4 + 4 + 44$	$44 + 4/4$	$4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + 44$	$4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4$	$4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$	$4/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$	$4 + (4 + 4)/4$
$4 + 4 + 4/4$	$4 + 44/4$	$4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$	$4 \times 4 + 4/4$	$4 + (44 + 4^4)/4 + 4$	$44 + 44 - 4/4$	$4 \times 4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$	$4 - 4/4$	$4 - 4 \times 4 + 444/4$	$(44 - 4)/4$

Example 107. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 101 in terms of single digit 5:

$5 - 5 + 5 + 55/5$	$55/5 - 5 \times 5$	$5 + 55/5$	$5 + (55 - 5/5) + 5 \times 5$	$5 + (55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$	$5 - 5/5$	$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - (5 + 5)/5$	$(5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
$(55 + 5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 5 - 55/5$	$55 + 55/5$	$5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + (55 + 5 + 5)$	$5 \times 5 + (5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 55/5$	$(55 + 55)/5$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)$	$5 \times (5 + 5)$	55	$5 + 5 \times 5$	$55 + (55 + 5)/5$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5$	$(5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$	$(55 + 5)/5$
$55/5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 5/5$	$55 - (55 + 5)/5$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5)$
$5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5$	$55 + 5/5 - 5 - 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 \times 5 + 5/5$	$5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 + 5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 55 + 55/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	5
$5/5$	$55 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5$	$55 + (55 + 55)/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$	$5 + 5 + 55$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 + 5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
$5 \times 5 \times 5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 55/5 + 5$	$5/5 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)$	$55 - 5 - 5/5$	$55 + 5/5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$5 + (5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 55/5$	$5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
$5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times 5 + 55 + 5/5$	$5 \times 5 - 5/5$	$55 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 55/5$	$5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (5 + 5)/5$	$((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 55 + 5/5$	$5 \times 5 + 55/5$	$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 - 5/5$
$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5$	$55 - 5 + (5 + 5)/5$	$55 - 5 - 5$	$5 \times 5 + 55$	5×5	$5 + 55$	$5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 55 + (55 + 5)/5$	$5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5/5$
$5 + 5 - 5/5$	$5 + 5 + 5$	$5 + 5 \times 5 + 55$	$5 + (55 + 5)/5$	$5 + 55 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 + 5 + 55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$	$5 - (5 + 5)/5$	$5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5$	$5 + 5$

Example 108. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 101 in terms of single digit 6:

$6 \times 6 + 66 - 66/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 + 66 + 6 + 6$	$6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$(666 - 6)/6 - 6 - 6$	$(6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 + 66 + (6 - 66)/6$
$6 + 6/6 + 6$	$6 \times 6 + 66/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6$	$6 + 6/6 + 6 + 6$	$6 + 66 + 6$	$6 + 66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	66	$66 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 6$	$6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$	$66 + (66 + 66)/6$
$6 + 66 + 6 + 66/6$	$(66 + 66)/6$	$666/6 - 6 \times 6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$66 - 66/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6$	$66 + 6/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6$	$66 - 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6$
$66/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$	$6 + 6 + 66/6$	$66 - 6 - 6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6 - 6$	$66 - 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$6 + ((66 + 6 + 6) + 6)$
$6 \times 6 + 66 - 6$	$6 - 66 + 666/6$	$6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6$	$6 + 6 + 66 + 6/6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 - 66)/6$	$66 - 6/6 - 6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 66 - 6/6$	$6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$6 - 6/6$
$6/6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6$	$66 + (6 + 6 - 66)/6$	$6 + ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6)$	$66 + 66/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$	$66 - 6/6$	$6 + (66 + 66)/6$	$66 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
$666/6 - 6 - 6 - 6$	$6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$66 + (6 - 66)/6$	$6 \times 6 - 6 - 6/6$	$66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 - 6/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6$	$6 + (6 + 6)/6$
$6 + 6/6$	$6 + 666/6 - 6 \times 6$	$6 + (6 + 6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + 66/6$	$6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 + 66 + 6/6$	$6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 - 6$	$66 + 6/6 - 6$	6×6	$6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6$
$6 \times 6 + 66 - 6 - 6/6$	$((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6 - 6$	$666/6 - 66$	$6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$	$6 \times 6 - 66/6$	$66 - 6$	$6 \times 6 + 6/6$	$6 + 66$	$66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	6
$6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$6 + 6 + 6 + 66 + 6/6$	$6 + 66/6$	$6 + 66/6 + 66$	$6 + 666/6 - 6 \times 6 + 6$	$6 \times 6 + 66 - 6 + 6/6$	$6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$	$666/6 - 6 - 6$	$(66 - 6)/6$

Example 109. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 101 in terms of single digit 7:

$7 + 77 + 7$	$7 + (7 + 7)/7 + 77$	$7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 77$	$7 + 77/7$	$7 + 7$	$77(7 - 7)$	$7 \times (7 + 7)$	$(7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 77 + 7/7$
$7 + 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + (7 + 77)/7$	$7/7 + 77$	$7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7$	$77 - 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	$77 - 7$	$77 + 77/7$
$77 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$77 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 + 77/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7$	$(77 + 7)/7$
$77/7$	$7 + 77 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + 7/7 - 7$	$77 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 77/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7$	$7 + (77 - 7/7 + 7)$
$7 \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$77 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$7/7 + 77 - 7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7 - (7 + 7)/7$
$7/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7/7 + 7 \times 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$	77	$7 \times 7 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$77 - (77 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7$	$77 - 7 - 7/7$	$(7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$
$7 + 77 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7$	$77 - 7/7$	7×7	$7 + 7 \times 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$	$77 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 - 7/7$	$7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 + 7/7$	$7 + 7/7$
7	$77 - 7 + 77/7$	$7 + ((77 - 7)/7 + 7)$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + 77/7$	$7 \times 7 - 7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 77 - 77/7$	$7 + 77/7 + 7 + 7$	$7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7/7 + (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7))$	$7 + 77 + (77 - 7)/7$
$7 + 77 + 77/7$	$7 \times 7 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 \times 7 - 77/7$	$77 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 77/7$	$7 \times 7 + 77/7$	$7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7$	$77 + (7 + 7)/7 - 7$	$7 + 7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$	$7 - 7/7$
$7 + (7 + 7)/7$	$7 + 7 + 7/7$	$7 + 77 + 7/7$	$7 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 + 77 - 7/7$	$77 + (77 - 7)/7$	$7 \times (7 + 7) - 7/7$	$(7 + 7 + 7)/7$	$7/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$	$(77 - 7)/7$

Example 110. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 101 in terms of single digit 8:

$88 + (88/8 - 8)$	$88 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8$	$88 - 8 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$8 + 88 + (8 + 8)/8$	$(8 + 8)/8$	$88 + 8 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$
$(88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 88/8$	$88 + (8 - 88)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	88
$8/8 + 88$	$(88 + 88)/8$	$8 \times 8 + 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 + 88/8$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 88)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8/8$	$(88 + 8)/8$
$88/8$	$88 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 + (8 - 88)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$8 \times 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$	$88 + (8 + 8)/8$
$8 + 88$	$8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - (88 - 8)/8$	$88 - 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 + 88/8 - 8 - 8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 88)/8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$	$8 + 8 - 88/8$
$8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8$	$8/8 + 8 \times 8 - 8$	$8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$88 - 88/8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8/8 + 8 \times 8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$88 - 8 - 88/8$	$88 + (88 + 8)/8$
$8 + 88 + 8 - 88/8$	$8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 + (88 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8$	$8 + 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$	$8 \times 8 + 8 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	8×8	8
$8 - 8/8$	$8/8 + 88 - 8$	$8 + (8 + 8)$	$8 \times 8 - 88/8$	$88 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$8 + 8/8 + 8 \times 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 - 88/8$	$(8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$8 + 88 - (8 + 8)/8$
$8 + 88 - 8/8$	$8 + 88 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$8 \times 8 - 8 - 88/8$	$88 - 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 \times 8 - 8 \times 8 / (8 + 8)$	$888 / (8 + 8 + 8)$	$8 + 8 \times 8$	$8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 - (8 + 8)/8$
$8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 - 8/8$	$8 + 88 - 88/8$	$8 + 8 + 8/8$	$8 + 8 \times 8 + 88/8$	$88 - 8/8$	$8 + 88 + 8/8$	$88/8 - 8$	$88 + 88/8$	$8 + (8 + 8)/8$

Example 111. According to values given Appendix 4, let's write magic of order 10 given in Example 101 in terms of single digit 9:

$9 + 9 \times 9 + 9/9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 \times 9 + 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9) / 9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 + 9 + 9) / 9$	$9 + 9$	$9 + (9 \times 9 + 9) / (9 + 9)$	$(9 \times 9 - 9) / (9 + 9)$	$99 - 9/9$	$(9 + 9) / 9$	$9 \times 9 + 99/9$
$(99 + 9 + 9) / 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 + (9 \times 99 - 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 + 9/9 + 9$	$9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9) / 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9) / 9$	$(9 + 9) \times 99 / (9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9$	$9 \times 9 - 99/9$	$99 - 99/9$
$9 + 9 \times 9 - 9/9$	$(99 + 99) / 9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 + 9 + 9) / 9 - 9$	$(9 \times 99 + 9) / (9 + 9)$	$(999 - 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + (99 + 9) / 9$	$9 + 9 + (9 \times 99 - 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 + 99 \times 9 / (9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	$(99 + 9) / 9$
$99/9$	$9/9 + 9 \times 9$	$(99 + 99 + 9) / 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9) / 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 + (9 + 9) / 9$	$9 + (99 + 99) / 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9 \times 9$
$99 - (9 + 9 + 9) / 9$	$9 \times (9 + 9) - 999/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 \times 9 - (9 + 9) / 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 + (9 \times 99 + 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9/9 - 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9) / 9$	$(9 \times 9 + 9) / (9 + 9)$
$9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9) / 9$	$((9 + 9) / 9)^9 + 9/9 / 9$	$9 + 99/9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 - 9 \times 9) / (9 + 9)$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 + (999 + 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 \times 9 - (99 + 9) / 9$	$9/9 + 99$
$9 \times 9 + (99 + 9) / 9$	$9 + (99 + 9) / 9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 - 99) / (9 + 9)$	$(9 \times 99 - 9) / (9 + 9)$	$(999 + 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 + 99/9$	$9 \times 9 - (99 + 9 + 9) / 9$	$(9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$	$9 - 9/9$
$9 - (9 + 9) / 9$	9×9	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9) / 9 + 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9$	$9 + (99 + 99 + 9) / 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9$	$99 + (9 - 99) / (9 + 9)$
$99 + (9 - 9 \times 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 99/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9/9$	$9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9) / 9$	$9 \times 9 - 9 - (99 + 9) / 9$	$9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$	$9 \times 9 - 9$	$99 \times 9 / (9 + 9 + 9)$	$9 - (9 + 9 + 9) / 9$
9	$9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9) / 9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 \times 9 - 9) / (9 + 9)$	$9 + 9 - 9/9$	$9 \times 9 + (9 + 9) / 9$	$99 - (99 + 9) / 9$	$99 - (9 + 9) / 9$	$(9 + 9 + 9) / 9$	99	$9 + 9/9$

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- Inder J. Taneja, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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• Single Digits Representations

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4 Appendix: Single Digit Representations

Within the magic squares we have used total 1 to 100 numbers for the magic squares of orders 3 to 10. The magic sums vary according to each magic square. Any way, the maximum number is 505. Below are values in single digits from 1 to 1000. The representations below are part of author's work. For more details refer author's work [2, 3, 4, 5].

► **1** := 1

:= 2/2

:= 3/3

:= 4/4

:= 5/5

:= 6/6

:= 7/7

:= 8/8

:= 9/9

► **3** := 1 + 1 + 1

:= 2 + 2/2

:= 3

:= 4 - 4/4

:= 5 - (5 + 5)/5

:= 6 × 6/(6 + 6)

:= (7 + 7 + 7)/7

:= 88/8 - 8

:= (9 + 9 + 9)/9

► **5** := 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1

:= 2 + 2/2 + 2

:= 3 + 3 - 3/3

:= 4 + 4/4

:= 5

:= 6 - 6/6

:= 7 - (7 + 7)/7

:= 8 + 8 - 88/8

:= (9 × 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)

► **2** := 1 + 1

:= 2

:= 3 - 3/3

:= (4 + 4)/4

:= (5 + 5)/5

:= (6 + 6)/6

:= (7 + 7)/7

:= (8 + 8)/8

:= (9 + 9)/9

► **4** := 1 + 1 + 1 + 1

:= 2 + 2

:= 3 + 3/3

:= 4

:= 5 - 5/5

:= 6 - (6 + 6)/6

:= 77/7 - 7

:= 8 × 8/(8 + 8)

:= (9 × 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)

► **6** := (1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)

:= 2 + 2 + 2

:= 3 + 3

:= 4 + (4 + 4)/4

:= 5 + 5/5

:= 6

:= 7 - 7/7

:= 8 - (8 + 8)/8

:= 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9

► **7** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$

:= $2 + 2 + 2 + 2/2$

:= $3 + 3 + 3/3$

:= $4 + 4 - 4/4$

:= $5 + (5 + 5)/5$

:= $6 + 6/6$

:= 7

:= $8 - 8/8$

:= $9 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **10** := $11 - 1$

:= $2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$

:= $3 \times 3 + 3/3$

:= $(44 - 4)/4$

:= $5 + 5$

:= $(66 - 6)/6$

:= $(77 - 7)/7$

:= $8 + (8 + 8)/8$

:= $9 + 9/9$

► **13** := $1 + 1 + 11$

:= $2 + 22/2$

:= $3 + 3 \times 3 + 3/3$

:= $4 + 4/4 + 4 + 4$

:= $(55 + 5 + 5)/5$

:= $6 + 6/6 + 6$

:= $7 + 7 - 7/7$

:= $(88 + 8 + 8)/8$

:= $(99 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **8** := $(1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$

:= $2 \times (2 + 2)$

:= $3 \times 3 - 3/3$

:= $4 + 4$

:= $5 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$

:= $6 + (6 + 6)/6$

:= $7 + 7/7$

:= 8

:= $9 - 9/9$

► **11** := 11

:= $22/2$

:= $33/3$

:= $44/4$

:= $55/5$

:= $66/6$

:= $77/7$

:= $88/8$

:= $99/9$

► **14** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 11$

:= $2^{2+2} - 2$

:= $3 + 33/3$

:= $4 + (44 - 4)/4$

:= $5 + 5 - 5/5 + 5$

:= $6 + 6 + (6 + 6)/6$

:= $7 + 7$

:= $8 + 8 - (8 + 8)/8$

:= $9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **9** := $11 - 1 - 1$

:= $(2/2 + 2)^2$

:= 3×3

:= $4 + 4 + 4/4$

:= $5 + 5 - 5/5$

:= $6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$

:= $7 + (7 + 7)/7$

:= $8 + 8/8$

:= 9

► **12** := $1 + 11$

:= $2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$

:= $3 + 3 \times 3$

:= $4 + 4 + 4$

:= $(55 + 5)/5$

:= $6 + 6$

:= $(77 + 7)/7$

:= $(88 + 8)/8$

:= $(99 + 9)/9$

► **15** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11$

:= $2 + 2 + 22/2$

:= $3 + 3 + 3 \times 3$

:= $4 + 44/4$

:= $5 + 5 + 5$

:= $6 + 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$

:= $7 + 7 + 7/7$

:= $8 + 8 - 8/8$

:= $9 + 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **16** := $(1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$
 := 2^{2+2}
 := $3^3 - 33/3$
 := 4×4
 := $5 + 55/5$
 := $6 + (66 - 6)/6$
 := $7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8$
 := $9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **19** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1$
 := $22 - 2/2 - 2$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $4 + 4 + 44/4$
 := $5 \times 5 - 5 - 5/5$
 := $6 + 6/6 + 6 + 6$
 := $7 + (7 + 77)/7$
 := $8 + 88/8$
 := $9 + 9/9 + 9$

► **22** := $11 + 11$
 := 22
 := $33 - 33/3$
 := $44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $(55 + 55)/5$
 := $(66 + 66)/6$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$
 := $(88 + 88)/8$
 := $(99 + 99)/9$

► **17** := $1 + (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$
 := $2/2 + 2^{2+2}$
 := $3 + 33/3 + 3$
 := $4 \times 4 + 4/4$
 := $5 + (55 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 66/6$
 := $7 + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8/8$
 := $9 + 9 - 9/9$

► **20** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)$
 := $22 - 2$
 := $3 \times 3 + 33/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4$
 := $5 \times 5 - 5$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$
 := $8 + (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 99/9$

► **23** := $1 + 11 + 11$
 := $22 + 2/2$
 := $3^3 - 3 - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 + 4 + 44/4$
 := $5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 6 + 66/6$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$
 := $(99 + 99 + 9)/9$

► **18** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 + 2^{2+2}$
 := $3 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $4 \times 4 + (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + (55 + 5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 6 + 6$
 := $7 + 77/7$
 := $8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9$

► **21** := $11 + 11 - 1$
 := $22 - 2/2$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$
 := $5 + 55/5 + 5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7 + 7$
 := $8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + (99 + 9)/9$

► **24** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 22$
 := $3^3 - 3$
 := $4 + (4 \times 4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 - 5/5$
 := $6 + (6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + ((77 - 7)/7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$

► **25** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 22 + 2/2$
 := $3^3 - 3 + 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 + 4/4$
 := 5×5
 := $6 \times 6 - 66/6$
 := $7 + 7 + 77/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **28** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $2 + 22 + 2 + 2$
 := $3^3 + 3/3$
 := $44 - 4 \times 4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + (66 + 66)/6$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 + 7$
 := $8 + 8 + (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$

► **31** := $1 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $22 + (2/2 + 2)^2$
 := $3 + 3^3 + 3/3$
 := $4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 6/6 - 6$
 := $7 \times 7 - 7 - 77/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$
 := $9 + (99 + 99)/9$

► **26** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 22 + 2$
 := $3^3 - 3/3$
 := $4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 + 5/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + (6 - 66)/6$
 := $7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$

► **29** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1$
 := $2 + 2 + 2 + 22 + 2/2$
 := $3 + 3^3 - 3/3$
 := $44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$
 := $6 \times 6 - 6 - 6/6$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7$
 := $8 + 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 99/9$

► **32** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1$
 := $2 \times 2^{2+2}$
 := $33 - 3/3$
 := $4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6 - 6$
 := $7 + 77/7 + 7 + 7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 + 8$
 := $9 + (99 + 99 + 9)/9$

► **27** := $(1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $2 + 22 + 2/2 + 2$
 := 3^3
 := $4 \times 4 + 44/4$
 := $5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $66 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 6$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 7/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 88/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9$

► **30** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$
 := $3 + 3^3$
 := $4 \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5$
 := $6 \times 6 - 6$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + (88 + 88)/8$
 := $9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$

► **33** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $22 + 22/2$
 := 33
 := $4/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 + (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$
 := $99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$

► **34** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
:= $2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2}$
:= $3/3 + 33$
:= $44 + (4 - 44)/4$
:= $5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 - 5/5$
:= $6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$
:= $7 \times 7 - 7 - 7 - 7/7$
:= $8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
:= $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **37** := $111/(1 + 1 + 1)$
:= $2/2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$
:= $3 + 33 + 3/3$
:= $4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4$
:= $5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
:= $6 \times 6 + 6/6$
:= $7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7$
:= $888/(8 + 8 + 8)$
:= $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$

► **40** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)$
:= $2 \times (22 - 2)$
:= $3 + 3 + 33 + 3/3$
:= $44 - 4$
:= $5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$
:= $6 + 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$
:= $7 \times 7 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$
:= $8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8$
:= $(9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **35** := $1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
:= $2 + 22/2 + 22$
:= $3 + 33 - 3/3$
:= $4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$
:= $5 + 5 + 5 \times 5$
:= $6 \times 6 - 6/6$
:= $7 \times 7 - 7 - 7$
:= $8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$
:= $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$

► **38** := $1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)$
:= $2 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$
:= $3^3 + 33/3$
:= $44 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4$
:= $5 + 5/5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
:= $6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
:= $7 \times 7 - 77/7$
:= $8 + 8 + (88 + 88)/8$
:= $9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$

► **41** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)$
:= $2/2 + 2 \times (22 - 2)$
:= $3 + 33/3 + 3^3$
:= $44 - 4 + 4/4$
:= $5 + 5 \times 5 + 55/5$
:= $6 + 6 \times 6 - 6/6$
:= $7 \times 7 - 7 - 7/7$
:= $8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8/8$
:= $(9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **36** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$
:= $(2 + 2 + 2)^2$
:= $3 + 33$
:= $4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$
:= $5 \times 5 + 55/5$
:= 6×6
:= $7/7 + (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7))$
:= $(8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$
:= $9 + 9 + 9 + 9$

► **39** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
:= $2 \times (22 - 2) - 2/2$
:= $3 + 3 + 33$
:= $44 - 4 - 4/4$
:= $55 - 5 - 55/5$
:= $6 + 66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
:= $7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7$
:= $8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 - 8/8$
:= $9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$

► **42** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)$
:= $2 \times 22 - 2$
:= $3 \times 3 + 33$
:= $44 - (4 + 4)/4$
:= $5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5$
:= $6 + 6 \times 6$
:= $7 \times 7 - 7$
:= $8 \times 8 - (88 + 88)/8$
:= $9 + 99 \times 9/(9 + 9 + 9)$

► **43** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 + 11) - 1$
 := $2 \times 22 - 2/2$
 := $3 \times 3 + 3/3 + 33$
 := $44 - 4/4$
 := $55 - (55 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$
 := $7 \times 7 + 7/7 - 7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **46** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
 := $2 + 2 \times 22$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 + 33 + 3/3$
 := $44 + (4 + 4)/4$
 := $55 + 5/5 - 5 - 5$
 := $6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6$
 := $7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 - (88 - 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$

► **49** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$
 := $2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $3^3 + 33 - 33/3$
 := $4 + 44 + 4/4$
 := $55 - 5 - 5/5$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + 6/6$
 := 7×7
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + 8/8$
 := $(9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **44** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 + 11)$
 := 2×22
 := $33 + 33/3$
 := 44
 := $55 - 55/5$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 \times 7 - 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$

► **47** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
 := $2 + 2 \times 22 + 2/2$
 := $3 + 33/3 + 33$
 := $4 + 44 - 4/4$
 := $5 + 5 + 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66/6$
 := $7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$

► **50** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1}/(1 + 1)$
 := $2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $3 + 3 + 33 + 33/3$
 := $4 + 44 + (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times (5 + 5)$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 \times 7 + 7/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $(9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **45** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (11 + 11)$
 := $2 \times 22 + 2/2$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 + 33$
 := $44 + 4/4$
 := $55 - 5 - 5$
 := $666/6 - 66$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 - 77/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 - 88/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9$

► **48** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$
 := $2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $3 \times 3^3 - 33$
 := $4 + 44$
 := $55 + 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 \times 6$
 := $7 \times 7 - 7/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 - 8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + (99 + 9)/9$

► **51** := $1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}/(1 + 1)$
 := $2 + 2 \times (22 + 2) + 2/2$
 := $3^3 + 3^3 - 3$
 := $4 + 4 + 44 - 4/4$
 := $55 + 5/5 - 5$
 := $6 - 66 + 666/6$
 := $7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - 999/9$

► **52** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3^3 + 3/3 - 3 + 3^3$
 := $4 + 4 + 44$
 := $55 - 5 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6 - 6$
 := $7 \times 7 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 99/9$

► **55** := $(111 - 1)/(1 + 1)$
 := $22/2 + 2 \times 22$
 := $3^3 + 3^3 + 3/3$
 := $44 + 44/4$
 := 55
 := $66 - 66/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 - 8/8$
 := $(999 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **58** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $22 + (2 + 2 + 2)^2$
 := $(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3$
 := $(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 - 4$
 := $5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **53** := $(111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1$
 := $2/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3^3 + 3^3 - 3/3$
 := $(4^4 - 44)/4$
 := $55 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 + 66/6$
 := $7 \times 7 - 7 + 77/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 88/8$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$

► **56** := $(1 + 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $2 \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)$
 := $(333 + 3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $4 + 4 + 4 + 44$
 := $55 + 5/5$
 := $66 + (6 - 66)/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8$
 := $(999 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **59** := $(11^{1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1$
 := $22/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $3^3 + 33 - 3/3$
 := $(4^4 - 4)/4 - 4$
 := $5 + 55 - 5/5$
 := $66 - 6/6 - 6$
 := $7 \times 7 + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 + 88/8 - 8 - 8$
 := $9 + (9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **54** := $(111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1$
 := $2 + 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $44 + (44 - 4)/4$
 := $55 - 5/5$
 := $66 - 6 - 6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 + (8 - 88)/8$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9$

► **57** := $1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $2 + 22/2 + 2 \times 22$
 := $3 + 3^3 + 3^3$
 := $4 + (4^4 - 44)/4$
 := $55 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $66 + (6 + 6 - 66)/6$
 := $7 + 7/7 + 7 \times 7$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times 8 - 8$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 + 9/9/9$

► **60** := $(11^{1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1)$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)$
 := $3^3 + 33$
 := $4 \times 4 + 44$
 := $5 + 55$
 := $66 - 6$
 := $7 \times 7 + 77/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9 - (99 + 9)/9$

► **61** := $(1 + 11^{1+1})/(1 + 1)$
 := $2^{2+2+2} - 2/2 - 2$
 := $(3/3 + 3)^3 - 3$
 := $(4^4 + 4)/4 - 4$
 := $5 + 55 + 5/5$
 := $66 + 6/6 - 6$
 := $7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 - 88/8$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9 - 99/9$

► **64** := $(1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$
 := 2^{2+2+2}
 := $(3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 \times 4 \times 4$
 := $5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$
 := $((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 + 7/7$
 := 8×8
 := $9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$

► **67** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + 2^{2+2+2} + 2/2$
 := $3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 + (4^4 - 4)/4$
 := $55 + (55 + 5)/5$
 := $66 + 6/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 + 77/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 + 88/8$
 := $9 + 9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **62** := $1 + (1 + 11^{1+1})/(1 + 1)$
 := $2^{2+2+2} - 2$
 := $3 + 33 - 3/3 + 3^3$
 := $(4^4 - 4 - 4)/4$
 := $5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $66 - 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 \times 7 - 7/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9 - 9 - 9/9$

► **65** := $1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$
 := $2/2 + 2^{2+2+2}$
 := $(3/3 + 3)^3 + 3/3$
 := $(4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + 5 + 55$
 := $66 - 6/6$
 := $77 - (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times 8$
 := $9 + (999 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **68** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $2 + 2 + 2^{2+2+2}$
 := $((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 - 3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$
 := $5 + (5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $66 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $77 - 7 - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 - (99 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **63** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)$
 := $2^{2+2+2} - 2/2$
 := $3 + 33 + 3^3$
 := $(4^4 - 4)/4$
 := $(5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $66 - 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 \times 7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8/8$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9 - 9$

► **66** := $(1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + 2^{2+2+2}$
 := $33 + 33$
 := $(4^4 + 4 + 4)/4$
 := $55 + 55/5$
 := 66
 := $77 - 77/7$
 := $8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $(9 + 9) \times 99/(9 + 9 + 9)$

► **69** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
 := $(2/2 + 2) \times (22 + 2/2)$
 := $3 + 33 + 33$
 := $4 + (4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + 5 + 5 + 55 - 5/5$
 := $66 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $77 - 7 - 7/7$
 := $88 - 8 - 88/8$
 := $9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{70} &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 11 \\ &:= 22 + 2 \times (22 + 2) \\ &:= 3 + (((3/3 + 3)^3) + 3) \\ &:= 4 + (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4) \\ &:= 5 + (55 + 5 + 5) \\ &:= 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\ &:= 77 - 7 \\ &:= 8 + 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8 \\ &:= 9 \times 9 - 99/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{73} &:= 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}/(1 + 1) \\ &:= 2/2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\ &:= ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3 \\ &:= 4 + (4^4 + 4)/4 + 4 \\ &:= 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (5 + 5)/5 \\ &:= 6 + 66 + 6/6 \\ &:= 7 + 77 - 77/7 \\ &:= 8 + 8/8 + 8 \times 8 \\ &:= 9/9 + 9 \times 9 - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{76} &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)) \\ &:= 2 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2) \\ &:= 3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3 \\ &:= 44 + 4 \times (4 + 4) \\ &:= 5/5 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) \\ &:= 6 + 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 \\ &:= 77 - 7/7 \\ &:= 8 \times 8 + (88 + 8)/8 \\ &:= 9 \times 9 + (9 - 99)/(9 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{71} &:= (1 + 11)^{1+1}/(1 + 1) - 1 \\ &:= 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 - 2/2 \\ &:= ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 \\ &:= 4 + (4^4 - 4)/4 + 4 \\ &:= 5 + 55 + 55/5 \\ &:= 6 + 66 - 6/6 \\ &:= 7/7 + 77 - 7 \\ &:= 8 + 8 \times 8 - 8/8 \\ &:= 9 \times 9 - 9/9 - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{74} &:= (1 + 1) \times 111/(1 + 1 + 1) \\ &:= 2 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\ &:= 3 + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 \\ &:= (4^4 + 44 - 4)/4 \\ &:= 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5/5 \\ &:= 6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6 \\ &:= 77 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 \times 8 + 8 + (8 + 8)/8 \\ &:= 9 \times 9 - 9 + (9 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{77} &:= 11 \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)) \\ &:= 2 \times 2 \times 22 - 22/2 \\ &:= 3 \times 3^3 - 3/3 - 3 \\ &:= (4 - 4/4)^4 - 4 \\ &:= 55 + (55 + 55)/5 \\ &:= 66 + 66/6 \\ &:= 77 \\ &:= 88 - 88/8 \\ &:= 9 \times 9 + (9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{72} &:= (1 + 11)^{1+1}/(1 + 1) \\ &:= 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2 \\ &:= 3 \times (3^3 - 3) \\ &:= 4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 \times 4 \\ &:= 5 + 55 + (55 + 5)/5 \\ &:= 6 + 66 \\ &:= 77 + (7 + 7)/7 - 7 \\ &:= 8 + 8 \times 8 \\ &:= 9 \times 9 - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{75} &:= 1 + (1 + 1) \times 111/(1 + 1 + 1) \\ &:= 22/2 + 2^{2+2+2} \\ &:= 3 + 3 \times (3^3 - 3) \\ &:= (44 + 4^4)/4 \\ &:= 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5) \\ &:= 666/6 - 6 \times 6 \\ &:= 77 - (7 + 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 \times 8 + 88/8 \\ &:= 9 \times 9 + (9 + 9 + 9)/9 - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{78} &:= 111 - 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \\ &:= 2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2) - 2 \\ &:= 3 \times 3^3 - 3 \\ &:= 4 + (4^4 - 4 + 44)/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5 \\ &:= 6 + 66 + 6 \\ &:= 7/7 + 77 \\ &:= 88 + (8 - 88)/8 \\ &:= 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

► **79** := $(11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1 - 1$
 := $(2/2 + 2)^{2+2} - 2$
 := $3 \times 3^3 + 3/3 - 3$
 := $4 + (44 + 4^4)/4$
 := $5 \times 5 + 55 - 5/5$
 := $6 + 6 + 66 + 6/6$
 := $77 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $88 - 8 - 8/8$
 := $9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **82** := $1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times 3^3$
 := $4/4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 \times 5 + 55 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $7 + 77 - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $88 - 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9/9 + 9 \times 9$

► **85** := $111 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 2 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3^3 + 3/3$
 := $4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 + 55$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 + 66 + 6/6$
 := $7 + 77 + 7/7$
 := $8 + 88 - 88/8$
 := $9 \times 9 + (9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **80** := $(11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1$
 := $2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)$
 := $3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$
 := $4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 + 55$
 := $6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $77 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $88 - 8$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9/9$

► **83** := $1 + 1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$
 := $4 + (44 + 4^4)/4 + 4$
 := $5 + 55 + 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 66/6 + 66$
 := $7 + 77 - 7/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 + 88/8$
 := $9 \times 9 + (9 + 9)/9$

► **86** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (11 + 11) - 1)$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2$
 := $3 + 3 + 3 \times 3^3 - 3/3$
 := $4 + (4 - 4/4)^4 + 4/4$
 := $555/5 - 5 \times 5$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 + 66 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + (7 + 7)/7 + 77$
 := $88 - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times 9 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **81** := $(11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $(2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$
 := 3×3^3
 := $(4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 \times 5 + 55 + 5/5$
 := $6 + 666/6 - 6 \times 6$
 := $77 - 7 + 77/7$
 := $8/8 + 88 - 8$
 := 9×9

► **84** := $1 + 1 + 1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times (2 \times 22 - 2)$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3^3$
 := $4 + 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$
 := $5 + (55 - 5/5) + 5 \times 5$
 := $6 + 66 + 6 + 6$
 := $7 + 77$
 := $88 - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **87** := $111 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2/2$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3^3 + 3$
 := $44 + 44 - 4/4$
 := $55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 + 666/6 - 6 \times 6 + 6$
 := $77 + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $88 - 8/8$
 := $99 - (99 + 9)/9$

► **88** := $11 \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 22$
 := $3 \times 33 - 33/3$
 := $44 + 44$
 := $5 \times 5 + (5^5/5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $66 + (66 + 66)/6$
 := $77 + 77/7$
 := 88
 := $99 - 99/9$

► **91** := $1 + (11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2/2$
 := $3^3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 + 44 + 44 - 4/4$
 := $5 - 5 \times 5 + 555/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 - 66/6$
 := $7 + 77 + 7$
 := $88 + (88/8 - 8)$
 := $9 + 9 \times 9 + 9/9$

► **94** := $1 + ((1 + 1)^{11-1} - 1)/11$
 := $2 + 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 3) + 3/3$
 := $(444 - 4)/4 - 4 \times 4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 - 5/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6$
 := $7 + 77 + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $8 + 88 - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $99 + (9 - 99)/(9 + 9)$

► **89** := $111 - 11 - 11$
 := $2/2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22$
 := $3 \times (3^3 + 3) - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 55/5$
 := $6 + 66 + 6 + 66/6$
 := $77 + (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8/8 + 88$
 := $9 + 9 \times 9 - 9/9$

► **92** := $11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$
 := $3 \times 3^3 + 33/3$
 := $4 + 44 + 44$
 := $5 + 55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 + (6 - 66)/6$
 := $7 + 7 + 77 + 7/7$
 := $88 + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + 99/9$

► **95** := $111 - (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$
 := $222/2 - 2^{2+2}$
 := $3 \times 33 - 3 - 3/3$
 := $444/4 - 4 \times 4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 - 6 - 6/6$
 := $7 + 77 + 77/7$
 := $8 + 88 - 8/8$
 := $99 + (9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **90** := $(11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 + 2 \times 2 \times 22$
 := $3 \times (3^3 + 3)$
 := $44 + ((4 + 4)/4 + 44)$
 := $5 + (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5)$
 := $6 + ((66 + 6 + 6) + 6)$
 := $7 + (77 - 7/7 + 7)$
 := $88 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 \times 9$

► **93** := $((1 + 1)^{11-1} - 1)/11$
 := $2/2 + 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 3)$
 := $((4 + 4)^4 - 4)/44$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $666/6 - 6 - 6 - 6$
 := $7 + 77 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 88 + 8 - 88/8$
 := $9 \times 9 + (99 + 9)/9$

► **96** := $(1 + 11) \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $3 \times 33 - 3$
 := $4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4 + 4)$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 - 6$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 88$
 := $99 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **97** := $111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1$
 := $2/2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times 33 - 3$
 := $4 \times 4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 + 5 + 55 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 - 6 + 6/6$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7) - 7/7$
 := $8 + 88 + 8/8$
 := $99 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **100** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $(2 \times (2 + 2) + 2)^2$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times 33$
 := $4 + 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $(7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $88 + (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9/9 + 99$

► **103** := $1 + 1 + 1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + 2222/22$
 := $3 + 3 \times 33 + 3/3$
 := $444/4 - 4 - 4$
 := $5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 + 6/6$
 := $(777 - 7)/7 - 7$
 := $888/8 - 8$
 := $(999 + 9)/9 - 9$

► **98** := $111 - 11 - 1 - 1$
 := $2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $3 \times 33 - 3/3$
 := $4 + (444 - 4)/4 - 4 \times 4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $(666 - 6)/6 - 6 - 6$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 88 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $99 - 9/9$

► **101** := $1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2222/22$
 := $3 + 3 \times 33 - 3/3$
 := $4444/44$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 - 6/6$
 := $7777/77$
 := $8888/88$
 := $99 + (9 + 9)/9$

► **104** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3 + 3 + 3 \times 33 - 3/3$
 := $4 \times 4 + 44 + 44$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/(5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $(666 - 6)/6 - 6$
 := $777/7 - 7$
 := $8 + (88 + 8)$
 := $99 + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **99** := $11 \times (11 - 1 - 1)$
 := $(22/2)^2 - 22$
 := 3×33
 := $4 - 4 \times 4 + 444/4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5$
 := $666/6 - 6 - 6$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $88 + 88/8$
 := 99

► **102** := $1 + 1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2 + 2) + 2)^2$
 := $3 + 3 \times 33$
 := $(444 - 4)/4 - 4 - 4$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66$
 := $7 + 77 + 7 + 77/7$
 := $(888 - 8)/8 - 8$
 := $999/9 - 9$

► **105** := $111 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $222/2 - 2 - 2 - 2$
 := $3 + 3 + 3 \times 33$
 := $4 + 4444/44$
 := $5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $666/6 - 6$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 8 + 88 + 8/8$
 := $9 + 99 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

▶ **106** := $111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1$
 := $2 + 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3 + 3 + 3 \times 33 + 3/3$
 := $(444 - 4)/4 - 4$
 := $555/5 - 5$
 := $(666 + 6)/6 - 6$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 + 7) + 7/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 88 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 99 - (9 + 9)/9$

▶ **109** := $111 - 1 - 1$
 := $222/2 - 2$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times (33 + 3)$
 := $44 + (4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $55 + 55 - 5/5$
 := $6/6 + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $77/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $(888 - 8 - 8)/8$
 := $9 + 99 + 9/9$

▶ **112** := $1 + 111$
 := $(222 + 2)/2$
 := $(333 + 3)/3$
 := $(444 + 4)/4$
 := $(555 + 5)/5$
 := $(666 + 6)/6$
 := $(777 + 7)/7$
 := $(888 + 8)/8$
 := $(999 + 9)/9$

▶ **107** := $111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1$
 := $222/2 - 2 - 2$
 := $3 \times (33 + 3) - 3/3$
 := $444/4 - 4$
 := $(555 + 5)/5 - 5$
 := $6 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6/6$
 := $7 + (7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (88/8 + 88)$
 := $9 + 99 - 9/9$

▶ **110** := $111 - 1$
 := $(222 - 2)/2$
 := $(333 - 3)/3$
 := $(444 - 4)/4$
 := $55 + 55$
 := $(666 - 6)/6$
 := $(777 - 7)/7$
 := $(888 - 8)/8$
 := $99 + 99/9$

▶ **113** := $1 + 1 + 111$
 := $2 + 222/2$
 := $(333 + 3 + 3)/3$
 := $(444 + 4 + 4)/4$
 := $(555 + 5 + 5)/5$
 := $(666 + 6 + 6)/6$
 := $(777 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $(888 + 8 + 8)/8$
 := $(999 + 9 + 9)/9$

▶ **108** := $111 - 1 - 1 - 1$
 := $(222 - 2)/2 - 2$
 := $3 \times (33 + 3)$
 := $44 + 4 \times 4 \times 4$
 := $55 + 55 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7777/77$
 := $8 + 88 + (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 99$

▶ **111** := 111
 := $222/2$
 := $333/3$
 := $444/4$
 := $555/5$
 := $666/6$
 := $777/7$
 := $888/8$
 := $999/9$

▶ **114** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 111$
 := $2 + (222 + 2)/2$
 := $3 + 333/3$
 := $4 + (444 - 4)/4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 - 55/5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7 - 7$
 := $(888 + 88)/8 - 8$
 := $(999 + 9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **115** := 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 111
 := 2 + 2 + 222/2
 := 3 + (333 + 3)/3
 := 4 + 444/4
 := 5 + 55 + 55
 := 6 + 6 × (6 + 6 + 6) + 6/6
 := 77 + 7 × 7 - 77/7
 := 8 + 88 + 8 + 88/8
 := 9 + 9 + 99 - (9 + 9)/9

► **118** := 11¹⁺¹ - 1 - 1 - 1
 := 22 + 2 × 2 × (22 + 2)
 := 3 + 3 + (333 + 3)/3
 := 4 + 4 + (444 - 4)/4
 := 5 + (555 + 5 + 5)/5
 := 6 + (666 + 6)/6
 := 7 + 777/7
 := 8 + (888 - 8)/8
 := 9 + 99 + 9 + 9/9

► **121** := 11 × 11
 := (22/2)²
 := (33/3)^{3-3/3}
 := (44/4)^{(4+4)/4}
 := 5 + 5 + 555/5
 := 66 × 66/(6 × 6)
 := ((7 + 7)/7)⁷ - 7
 := 8 × (8 + 8) - 8 + 8/8
 := 9 + (999 + 9)/9

► **116** := 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 111
 := 2 + 2 + (222 + 2)/2
 := 3 + 3 + (333 - 3)/3
 := 4 + 4 × (44 - 4 × 4)
 := 5 + 555/5
 := 6 + (666 - 6)/6
 := 7 + 7 × (7 + 7) + 77/7
 := 8 × (8 + 8) - (88 + 8)/8
 := 9 + 9 + 99 - 9/9

► **119** := 11¹⁺¹ - 1 - 1
 := (22/2)² - 2
 := 3 × 3 + (333 - 3)/3
 := 4 + 4 + 444/4
 := 5 × 5 × 5 - 5 - 5/5
 := 6 + (666 + 6 + 6)/6
 := 77 + 7 × 7 - 7
 := 8 + 888/8
 := 9 + (99/9 + 99)

► **122** := 111 + 11
 := (222 + 22)/2
 := (333 + 33)/3
 := (444 + 44)/4
 := (555 + 55)/5
 := (666 + 66)/6
 := (777 + 77)/7
 := (888 + 88)/8
 := (999 + 99)/9

► **117** := 111 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)
 := (22/2)² - 2 - 2
 := 3 × (33 + 3 + 3)
 := 4 + ((444 + 4 + 4)/4)
 := 5 + (555 + 5)/5
 := 6 + 666/6
 := 7 + (777 - 7)/7
 := 8 × (8 + 8) - 88/8
 := 9 + (99 + 9)

► **120** := 11¹⁺¹ - 1
 := (2 + 2 + 2) × (22 - 2)
 := 3 + 3 × (33 + 3 + 3)
 := (4 + 4) × (44/4 + 4)
 := 5 × 5 × 5 - 5
 := 6 + 6 + 6 × (6 + 6 + 6)
 := 7 + (777 + 7 + 7)/7
 := 8 × (8 + 8) - 8
 := 9 + 999/9

► **123** := 1 + 1 + 11 × 11
 := 2 + (22/2)²
 := 3³ - 3 + 3 × 33
 := 4 + 4 + 4 + 444/4
 := 5 × 5 × 5 - (5 + 5)/5
 := 6 + 6 + 666/6
 := (777 + 77 + 7)/7
 := (888 + 88 + 8)/8
 := (999 + 99 + 9)/9

► **124** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times 11$
 := $2 \times (2^{2+2+2} - 2)$
 := $3 + (33/3)^{3-3/3}$
 := $4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5/5$
 := $6 + 6 + (666 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + 7 + (777 - 7)/7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 99 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **127** := $111 + (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$
 := $(2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2)/2$
 := $3^3 + (3 \times 33 + 3/3)$
 := $4 \times 4 + 444/4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 66 \times 66/(6 \times 6)$
 := $7/7 + (77 + 7 \times 7)$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9/9$

► **130** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 2 \times 2^{2+2+2}$
 := $3 + 3 \times 33 + 3^3 + 3/3$
 := $(4^4 + 4)/((4 + 4)/4)$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5$
 := $66 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $(7 + 7)/7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 + (999 + 9)/9$

► **125** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times 11$
 := $2 + (22/2)^2 + 2$
 := $(3 - 3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $44 + (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5$
 := $66 + 66 - 6 - 6/6$
 := $7 + 7 + 777/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 88/8$
 := $9 + 99 + 9 + 9 - 9/9$

► **128** := $(1 + 1)^{1+(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$
 := $2 \times 2^{2+2+2}$
 := $3 + (3 - 3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $((6 + 6)/6)^{6+6/6}$
 := $((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$

► **131** := $11 \times (1 + 11) - 1$
 := $2 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)/2$
 := $3 + 3 + (3 + 3 - 3/3)^3$
 := $4 + 444/4 + 4 \times 4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5/5$
 := $66 + 66 - 6/6$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 + (777 - 7)/7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) + 88/8 - 8$
 := $9 + (999 + 99)/9$

► **126** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times 11$
 := $2 \times 2^{2+2+2} - 2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 3 + 33)$
 := $(4^4 - 4) \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5$
 := $66 + 66 - 6$
 := $77 + 7 \times 7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + (99 + 9 + 9)$

► **129** := $11 \times (1 + 11) - 1 - 1 - 1$
 := $(2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)/2$
 := $3 + (3 \times 33 + 3^3)$
 := $4/4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $5 + (5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5/5)$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 + 666/6$
 := $7/7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 9 + 999/9$

► **132** := $11 \times (1 + 11)$
 := $22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$
 := $33 + 3 \times 33$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $66 + 66$
 := $7 + 7 + 7 + 777/7$
 := $88 + 88 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $99 \times (99 + 9)/(9 \times 9)$

► **133** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 11)$
 := $22 + 222/2$
 := $33 + 3 \times 33 + 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4$
 := $5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $66 + 66 + 6/6$
 := $7 + 77 + 7 \times 7$
 := $(8 - 8/8) \times (88/8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - 9 - 9 - 99/9$

► **136** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 2 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times (3/3 + 33)$
 := $4 + 4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 + 555/5$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 66$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8)$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times (9 + 9 - 9/9)$

► **139** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11) - 1$
 := $(2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22)/2$
 := $3^3 + (333 + 3)/3$
 := $44/4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 55/5$
 := $6 + 66 + 66 + 6/6$
 := $77/7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + (999 + 9)/9$

► **134** := $1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3 \times 3 + (3 - 3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 + (4^4 + 4) \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5/5$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6}$
 := $7 + 77 + 7 \times 7 + 7/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99 - 9/9$

► **137** := $111 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2^{2+2} + (22/2)^2$
 := $3^3 + (333 - 3)/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4/4 + 4$
 := $5 \times 5 + (555 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 66 + 66 - 6/6$
 := $77 + 77/7 + 7 \times 7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 8/8$
 := $99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99/9$

► **140** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (22 + 2) + 22)$
 := $3 + (333 - 3)/3 + 3^3$
 := $4 \times (4 \times (4 + 4) + 4) - 4$
 := $5 + 5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6} + 6$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) + (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 + (999 + 99)/9$

► **135** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 22 + 222/2$
 := $3 + 33 + 33 \times 3$
 := $(4 - 4/4) \times (44 + 4/4)$
 := $5 + 5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 666/6$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 99$

► **138** := $111 + (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $(2/2 + 2) \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$
 := $3^3 + 333/3$
 := $4 + (4^4 + 4) \times 4/(4 + 4) + 4$
 := $(5 \times 5 \times 55 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6 + 66 + 66$
 := $77 + 7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 999/9$

► **141** := $(1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1$
 := $22 + (22/2)^2 - 2$
 := $33 + 3 \times (33 + 3)$
 := $4^4 - 4 - 444/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 + 555/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 666/6 - 6$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7$
 := $8 \times 8 + 88 - 88/8$
 := $9 + 99 \times (99 + 9)/(9 \times 9)$

► **142** := $(1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1$
 := $(2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2 - 2$
 := $3 + (333 + 3)/3 + 3^3$
 := $4 \times 4 + (4^4 - 4) \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 + (555 + 5)/5$
 := $(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - 9 - 99/9$

► **145** := $1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (22/2)^2 + 22$
 := $3/3 + (3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3)$
 := $4^4 - 444/4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5$
 := $6/6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 8/8$
 := $9/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 - 9/9)$

► **148** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + 2 + (2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2$
 := $(33 \times 3^3 - 3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $4 + 4 \times (4 \times (4 + 4) + 4)$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + (666 + 6)/6$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $888/(8 - (8 + 8)/8)$
 := $99 + (9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **143** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $22 + (22/2)^2$
 := $33 + (333 - 3)/3$
 := $4 \times (4 + 4) + 444/4$
 := $5 + (5 \times 5 \times 55 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6/6$
 := $77 + 77 - 77/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - 9 - 9 - 9/9$

► **146** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2$
 := $3 + (333 - 3)/3 + 33$
 := $4^4 + (4 - 444)/4$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5$
 := $6 \times 6 + (666 - 6)/6$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7/7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 - 9/9)$

► **149** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (22/2 + 2)^2 - 22$
 := $(33 \times 3^3 + 3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 444/4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5/5$
 := $6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6/6$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7 + 7$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 + 88 - 88/8$
 := $99 + (9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **144** := $(1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $(2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2$
 := $(3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3)$
 := $4 \times (4 \times (4 + 4) + 4)$
 := $(5/5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5/5)$
 := $(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)$
 := $(7/7 + 7) \times (77/7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 8$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 - 9/9)$

► **147** := $1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $(22/2 + 2)^2 - 22$
 := $3 + (3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3)$
 := $4 + 444/4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 + (555 + 55)/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 666/6$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 999/9$

► **150** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $22 + 2 \times 2^{2+2+2}$
 := $3 + (3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3) + 3$
 := $(44 + 4^4)/((4 + 4)/4)$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 77 + 77 - 77/7$
 := $8 \times 8 + 88 - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - (99 + 9)/9$

► **151** := $1 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $22 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)/2$
 := $(3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 33/3$
 := $44 + 444/4 - 4$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6/6$
 := $7 + (7/7 + 7) \times (77/7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 + (88 - 8/8)$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - 99/9$

► **154** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $22 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$
 := $33/3 \times (33/3 + 3)$
 := $44 + (444 - 4)/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5/5$
 := $6 + (666 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 6$
 := $77 + 77$
 := $8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8 + 88$
 := $9/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9$

► **157** := $1 + (1 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 222/2 + 2 \times 22$
 := $3 + 33/3 \times (33/3 + 3)$
 := $4/4 + 4 \times (44 - 4) - 4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 + 6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6/6$
 := $77 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7 + 77$
 := $88 + 88 - 8 - 88/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (9 - 99)/(9 + 9)$

► **152** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11) - 1 - 1$
 := $2 \times 2 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)$
 := $3^3 + (3 - 3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 \times (44 - 4) - 4 - 4$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $77 + 77 - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 + 88$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - 9/9 - 9$

► **155** := $11 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times 22 + 222/2$
 := $3 + (3 - 3/3 + 3)^3 + 3^3$
 := $44 + 444/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $66/6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)$
 := $7/7 + 77 + 77$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9$

► **158** := $(1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 11$
 := $2 \times ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2} - 2)$
 := $33 + (3 - 3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 \times (44 - 4) - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $77/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 88 - (8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **153** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11) - 1$
 := $2 \times 22 + 222/2 - 2$
 := $3 \times (3^3 - 3 + 3^3)$
 := $4 + 4 + 4^4 - 444/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 666/6 + 6 \times 6$
 := $77 + 77 - 7/7$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times 8 + 88$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - 9$

► **156** := $(1 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 \times (2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2) - 2)$
 := $(3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3/3)$
 := $4 \times (44 - 4) - 4$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/(5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6$
 := $77 + 77 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 888/(8 - (8 + 8)/8)$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9)/9 - 9$

► **159** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 11$
 := $222/2 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $(3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3$
 := $4 \times (44 - 4) - 4/4$
 := $(55 + 5^5)/(5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 + 6 + 6 + 666/6$
 := $7 \times 7 + (777 - 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 + 88 - 8/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **160** := $(1 + 1) \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1)$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 2 \times (22 - 2)$
 := $3/3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3$
 := $4 \times (44 - 4)$
 := $5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 + (666 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 6 + 6$
 := $7 \times 7 + 777/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 + 88$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9)/9$

► **163** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $((2^{2+2} + 2)^2 + 2)/2$
 := $3/3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3$
 := $4 + 4 \times (44 - 4) - 4/4$
 := $5 \times 55 - (555 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 66/6 - 6$
 := $7 + 77 + 77 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 + 88 + 88/8$
 := $9/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **166** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 \times ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2} + 2)$
 := $3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3/3$
 := $4 \times 44 + (4 - 44)/4$
 := $55 + 555/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $7 + (777 - 7)/7 + 7 \times 7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 + (888 - 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **161** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1$
 := $((2^{2+2} + 2)^2 - 2)/2$
 := $(3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3/3$
 := $4/4 + 4 \times (44 - 4)$
 := $5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 66/6$
 := $7 + 77 + 77$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 + 88 + 8/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) - 9/9$

► **164** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + 2 \times (2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$
 := $3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times (44 - 4)$
 := $5 \times 55 - 555/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6}$
 := $77 + 77 + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 + 88 + (88 + 8)/8$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **167** := $(1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1$
 := $(22/2 + 2)^2 - 2$
 := $(3 \times 333 + 3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $4 \times 44 - 4 - 4 - 4/4$
 := $55 + (555 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 + 66 - 6/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 + 777/7$
 := $8 \times 8 - 8 + 888/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **162** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times (2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$
 := $(3 + 3) \times 3^3$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + 4 \times (44 - 4)$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 + 6$
 := $7 + 77 + 77 + 7/7$
 := $8 + 88 + 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **165** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 \times 22 + (22/2)^2$
 := $3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3$
 := $4 \times 44 - 44/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $66 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)/(6 + 6)$
 := $77 + 77 + 77/7$
 := $88 + 88 - 88/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **168** := $(1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1$
 := $2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22 - 2)$
 := $3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3$
 := $4 \times 44 - 4 - 4$
 := $55 + (555 + 5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + (66 + 66)$
 := $7 + ((77 + 77) + 7)$
 := $88 + (88 - 8)$
 := $9 + (9 \times (9 + 9) - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))$

► **169** := $(1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $(22/2 + 2)^2$
 := $3 + 3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 44 - 44/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55 - 555/5$
 := $(6/6 + 6 + 6)^{(6+6)/6}$
 := $(7 - 7/7 + 7)^{(7+7)/7}$
 := $8/8 + 88 + 88 - 8$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9)/9$

► **172** := $1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2)$
 := $3 \times 3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3/3$
 := $4 \times 44 - 4$
 := $5 + 55 + (555 + 5)/5$
 := $66 - 6 + (666 + 6)/6$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $88 + 88 - 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) + 9/9$

► **175** := $11 \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1} - 1$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2/2$
 := $333/3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 \times 44 - 4/4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 6$
 := $77 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 + 888/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (99 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **170** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + 2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 22 - 2))$
 := $3 + (3 \times 333 + 3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $4 \times 44 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5) - 5$
 := $66 + (666 - 6)/6 - 6$
 := $7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7$
 := $88 + (8 + 8)/8 - 8 + 88$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9/9$

► **173** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (22/2 + 2)^2 + 2$
 := $(3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 33/3$
 := $4 \times 44 - 4 + 4/4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5) - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 6/6 - 6$
 := $77 + 7 \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 88 + 88 - 88/8$
 := $99/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **176** := $11 \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22$
 := $3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 33/3$
 := 4×44
 := $5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $66 + (666 - 6)/6$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 + 7) + 77$
 := $88 + 88$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times (99 + 99)/9$

► **171** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (22/2 + 2)^2$
 := $3 \times (3^3 + 3^3 + 3)$
 := $4 \times 44 - 4 - 4/4$
 := $5 + 55 + 555/5$
 := $66 + 666/6 - 6$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $(8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **174** := $(1 + 1) \times (111 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2$
 := $3 + (3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3 \times 3$
 := $4 \times 44 - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5 + 5) - 5/5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 6$
 := $77 + 7 \times (7 + 7) - 7/7$
 := $8 \times 8 + (888 - 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (99 + 9)/9$

► **177** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1+1}$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2/2$
 := $3 \times (3^3 + 33) - 3$
 := $4 \times 44 + 4/4$
 := $55 + (555 + 55)/5$
 := $66 + 666/6$
 := $7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $88 + 88 + 8/8$
 := $99 + 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **178** := $(1 + 1) \times (111 - 11 - 11)$
 := $2 + 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 33) - 3$
 := $4 \times 44 + (4 + 4)/4$
 := $55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $66 + (666 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $88 + 88 + 8 + 8/8$
 := $99 + 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **181** := $1 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2/2 + 2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2)$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times (3^3 + 33)$
 := $4 + 4 \times 44 + 4/4$
 := $55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5/5$
 := $6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)$
 := $77 - 7 + 777/7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $9/9 + 99 + 9 \times 9$

► **184** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$
 := $3/3 + (3 + 3)^3 - 33$
 := $4 + 4 + 4 \times 44$
 := $5 + 55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5/5$
 := $6 + 66 + (666 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 + 88 + 88$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9 + (999 + 9)/9$

► **179** := $11 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1$
 := $2 + (2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22) + 2/2$
 := $3 \times (3^3 + 33) - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 44 - 4/4$
 := $55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5/5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 6/6$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 9 \times 9 - 9/9$

► **182** := $(1 + 1 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2)$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - 33 - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 44 + (4 + 4)/4$
 := $55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + 77 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 + (888 - 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) + 99/9$

► **185** := $(1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 11$
 := $2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2) + 2/2$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 - 33 - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 + 4 \times 44 + 4/4$
 := $5 + 55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) - 6/6$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 77/7$
 := $8 + 88 + 88 + 8/8$
 := $9 + (9 - 9/9) \times (99 + 99)/9$

► **180** := $11 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2)$
 := $3 \times (3^3 + 33)$
 := $4 + 4 \times 44$
 := $55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)$
 := $77 + (777 - 7)/7 - 7$
 := $88 + 88 + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 9 \times 9$

► **183** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2) - 2/2$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - 33$
 := $4 + 4 + 4 \times 44 - 4/4$
 := $(5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 55 - 5$
 := $6 + 66 + 666/6$
 := $7 + 77 + 7 \times (7 + 7) + 7/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 + 888/8$
 := $9 \times 9 - 9 + 999/9$

► **186** := $((1 + 1)^{11} - 1 - 1)/11$
 := $2 + 2 \times 2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2)$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 - 33$
 := $4 \times 44 + (44 - 4)/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 + 55 + 5/5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)$
 := $77 + 7 \times (7 + 7) + 77/7$
 := $8 + 88 + 88 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $99 + 99 - (99 + 9)/9$

► **187** := $1 + ((1 + 1)^{11} - 1 - 1)/11$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22 + 22/2$
 := $33 \times (3 + 3) - 33/3$
 := $4 \times 44 + 44/4$
 := $55/5 \times ((55 + 5)/5 + 5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6$
 := $77 + (777 - 7)/7$
 := $88 + 88 + 88/8$
 := $99 + 99 - 99/9$

► **190** := $(11 - 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1)$
 := $222 - 2 \times 2^{2+2}$
 := $3/3 + (3 + 3)^3 - 3^3$
 := $4^4 - (4^4 + 4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5 + 55 + 5$
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 99 + 9 \times 9 + 9/9$

► **193** := $1 + 111 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (22/2 + 2)^2 + 22$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times (3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 \times (44 + 4) + 4/4$
 := $5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 55$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + (999 + 9)/9$

► **188** := $1 + 1 + ((1 + 1)^{11} - 1 - 1)/11$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 22 + 2) + 2)$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - 3^3 - 3/3$
 := $444 - 4^4$
 := $(5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 55$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $77 + 777/7$
 := $88 + 88 + (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 99 + 9 \times 9 - 9/9$

► **191** := $1 + (11 - 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1)$
 := $22 + (22/2 + 2)^2$
 := $3 \times (3/3 + 3)^3 - 3/3$
 := $4^4 - (4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times 5 + 55 + 555/5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) + 66/6$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7 \times 7 + 7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $99 + 9 \times 9 + 99/9$

► **194** := $(1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1$
 := $(2^{2+2} - 2)^2 - 2$
 := $33 \times (3 + 3) - 3 - 3/3$
 := $4^4 + (4 - 4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 55 - 5/5$
 := $66 + ((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6}$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + (999 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **189** := $(11 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)$
 := $((22 - 2)^2 - 22)/2$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - 3^3$
 := $4/4 + 444 - 4^4$
 := $5 \times (55 + 5) - 555/5$
 := $66 + 6 + 6 + 666/6$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88/8$
 := $9 + 99 + 9 \times 9$

► **192** := $111 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $3 \times (3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 \times (44 + 4)$
 := $(5/5 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6) + 6$
 := $7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 77/7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + 999/9$

► **195** := $(1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1$
 := $(2^{2+2} - 2)^2 - 2/2$
 := $33 \times (3 + 3) - 3$
 := $4 + 4^4 - (4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 55$
 := $(6 \times 66 - 6) \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7/7$
 := $8 + 88 + 88 + 88/8$
 := $99 + 99 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **196** := $(1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $(2^{2+2} - 2)^2$
 := $3/3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3$
 := $4 + 4 \times (44 + 4)$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 55$
 := $66 + 66 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 99 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **199** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1} - 1$
 := $((22 - 2)^2 - 2)/2$
 := $3/3 + 33 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $4 + 4 + 4^4 - (4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - 66/6$
 := $77 + (777 + 77)/7$
 := $88 + 888/8$
 := $99 + 99 + 9/9$

► **202** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + 222 - 22$
 := $3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) + 3/3$
 := $4^4 + (4 - 44)/4 - 44$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - 6 - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 \times 9 + (999 + 9)/9$

► **197** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2/2 + (2^{2+2} - 2)^2$
 := $33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4^4 + (4 - 4^4)/4$
 := $5 + (5/5 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $(66 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6)/6$
 := $7/7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)$
 := $88 + (888 - 8 - 8)/8$
 := $99 + 99 - 9/9$

► **200** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $222 - 22$
 := $3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 + 4 \times (44 + 4)$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 + (6 - 66)/6$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 + 77/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 99 + (9 + 9)/9$

► **203** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + ((22 - 2)^2 + 2)/2$
 := $3 + 3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3$
 := $4^4 + (44 - 4^4)/4$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5 + 5) - 5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - 6 - 6/6$
 := $7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $9 \times 9 + (999 + 99)/9$

► **198** := $(1 + 1) \times 11 \times (11 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 + (2^{2+2} - 2)^2$
 := $33 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $4 + 4^4 + (4 - 4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times 66 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $77 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7$
 := $88 + (888 - 8)/8$
 := $99 + 99$

► **201** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $((22 - 2)^2 + 2)/2$
 := $3 + 33 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 - 44 - 44/4$
 := $5/5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $(6 \times 66 + 6) \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8/8$
 := $9 + 9 \times 9 + 999/9$

► **204** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + 2 + 222 - 22$
 := $3 + 33 \times (3 + 3) + 3$
 := $44 + 4 \times (44 - 4)$
 := $5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - 6$
 := $7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7/7$
 := $(88 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $(999/9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)/9$

► **205** := $(1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11}) / (11 - 1)$
 := $2 + 2 + ((22 - 2)^2 + 2) / 2$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - 33 / 3$
 := $((4 + 4)^4 + 4) / (4 \times 4 + 4)$
 := $5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 66 / 6$
 := $77 + ((7 + 7) / 7)^7$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 88 / 8$
 := $9 + 99 + 99 - (9 + 9) / 9$

► **208** := $(1 + 1) \times (111 - 1) - 1 - 11$
 := $2 + 222 - 2^{2+2}$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 - 33 / 3$
 := $4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)$
 := $(5^5 - 5) / (5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 - (6 + 6) / 6$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7) + (777 - 7) / 7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 99 + 99 + 9 / 9$

► **211** := $(1 + 1) \times 111 - 11$
 := $222 - 22 / 2$
 := $3 / 3 + (3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3$
 := $4^4 - 44 - 4 / 4$
 := $55 + (5^5 - 5) / (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 + 6 / 6$
 := $7 + 7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 / 7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88 / 8$
 := $99 + (999 + 9) / 9$

► **206** := $1 + (1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11}) / (11 - 1)$
 := $222 - 2^{2+2}$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 + (3 - 33) / 3$
 := $4^4 + 44 + 4 - (4 + 4) / 4$
 := $5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5 / 5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6 - 66) / 6$
 := $77 + 7 / 7 + ((7 + 7) / 7)^7$
 := $8 + 88 + (888 - 8) / 8$
 := $9 + 99 + 99 - 9 / 9$

► **209** := $11 \times ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1)$
 := $222 - 22 / 2 - 2$
 := $33 / 3 + 33 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $4 / 4 + 4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)$
 := $(5^5 + 5 + 5) / (5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 / 6 - 6$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7) + 777 / 7$
 := $88 / 8 \times (88 / 8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 99 + 99 / 9$

► **212** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times 111 - 11$
 := $222 + ((2 - 22) / 2)$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - (3 / 3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 - 44$
 := $(55 + 5^5) / (5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 + (6 + 6) / 6$
 := $77 + 7 + ((7 + 7) / 7)^7$
 := $(8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88) \times 8 / (8 + 8)$
 := $99 + (999 + 9 + 9) / 9$

► **207** := $11 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 / 2 + 222 - 2^{2+2}$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - 3 \times 3$
 := $4^4 - 4 - 44 - 4 / 4$
 := $(5^5 - 5 \times 5 + 5) / (5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (6 \times 66 + 6) \times 6 / (6 + 6)$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 77 / 7$
 := $8 + 88 + 888 / 8$
 := $9 + 99 + 99$

► **210** := $(11 - 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)$
 := $222 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - 3 - 3$
 := $4^4 - 44 - (4 + 4) / 4$
 := $5 + (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6$
 := $7 + 7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)$
 := $88 + (888 + 88) / 8$
 := $99 + 999 / 9$

► **213** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) - 11$
 := $2 + 222 - 22 / 2$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - 3$
 := $4^4 - 44 + 4 / 4$
 := $5 + (5^5 - 5) / (5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 77 + ((7 + 7) / 7)^7 + 7 / 7$
 := $8 + 88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 88 / 8$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 999 / 9$

► **214** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) - 11$
 := $222 - 2 \times (2 + 2)$
 := $3/3 + (3 + 3)^3 - 3$
 := $4^4 - 44 + (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + (5^5 + 5 + 5)/(5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 77/7$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 \times (99 + 9 - 9/9)$

► **217** := $(1 + 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) - 1$
 := $222 - 2 - 2 - 2/2$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 + 3/3$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 44 + 4/4$
 := $5 + (55 + 5^5)/(5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $6/6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 77$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9)^9$

► **220** := $(1 + 1) \times (111 - 1)$
 := $222 - 2$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 3/3$
 := $44 + 4 \times 44$
 := $55 \times (5 - 5/5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $77/7 \times (7 - 7/7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (888 - 8)/(8 \times 8)$
 := $99/9 \times (99/9 + 9)$

► **215** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111) - 11$
 := $2 + 2 + 222 - 22/2$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 44 - 4/4$
 := $5 \times 55 - 55 - 5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6/6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $((9 + 9) \times (99 + 9) - 9)/9$

► **218** := $(1 + 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1)$
 := $222 - 2 - 2$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 - 3/3$
 := $444 \times 4/(4 + 4) - 4$
 := $(5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 5 \times 5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 77$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 99 + 99 + 99/9$

► **221** := $(1 + 1) \times 111 - 1$
 := $222 - 2/2$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 - 3/3 + 3$
 := $44 + 4 \times 44 + 4/4$
 := $55 \times (5 - 5/5) + 5/5$
 := $6 + (6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6/6)$
 := $(777 + 777 - 7)/7$
 := $(888 - 8 + 888)/8$
 := $99 + (999 + 99)/9$

► **216** := $(1 + 1) \times (111 - (1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $(2 + 2 + 2)^{2/2+2}$
 := $(3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 44$
 := $(5 - 5/5) \times (55 - 5/5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $(7 - 7/7)^{(7+7+7)/7}$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 9 + 99 + 99$

► **219** := $(1 + 1) \times (111 - 1) - 1$
 := $222 - 2/2 - 2$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3$
 := $44 + 4 \times 44 - 4/4$
 := $5 \times 55 - 55 - 5/5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $77 + 7 + 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $9 + 99 + 999/9$

► **222** := $(1 + 1) \times 111$
 := 222
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 3$
 := $444 \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $(5 + 5) \times 555/(5 \times 5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) \times 777/7$
 := $(8 + 8) \times 888/(8 \times 8)$
 := $(9 + 9) \times 999/(9 \times 9)$

► **223** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $2/2 + 222$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 3/3 + 3$
 := $4^4 + 44/4 - 44$
 := $5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 5 \times 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6/6$
 := $7 + (7 - 7/7)^{(7+7+7)/7}$
 := $8 + 88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99/9 - 9$

► **226** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111)$
 := $2 + 222 + 2$
 := $3 \times 3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 3/3$
 := $4 + 444 \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6$
 := $7 \times (7 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8 + 88$
 := $9 + 9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9)^9$

► **229** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 111)$
 := $(22^2 - 22)/2 - 2$
 := $(3^{3+3} - 33)/3 - 3$
 := $4^4 - 44/4 - 4 \times 4$
 := $5 + (5 - 5/5) \times (55 + 5/5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6/6 + 6$
 := $7 + (7 + 7) \times 777/(7 \times 7)$
 := $8 + (888 + 888 - 8)/8$
 := $9 + 99/9 \times (9 + 99/9)$

► **224** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)$
 := $2 + 222$
 := $3 \times 3 + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3/3)$
 := $4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $(5 - 5/5) \times (55 + 5/5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $77 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9) \times (99 + 9) - 9)/9$

► **227** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111)$
 := $2 + 2 + 222 + 2/2$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 + 33/3$
 := $4 - 44 + 4^4 + 44/4$
 := $5 + (5 + 5) \times 555/(5 \times 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + 66/6$
 := $7 + 77/7 \times (7 - 7/7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $((9 + 9) \times (99 + 9) + 99)/9$

► **230** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
 := $222 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 33/3$
 := $4 + 4 + 444 \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $5 + 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5)$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $(77 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7)/7$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times 888/(8 \times 8)$
 := $9 + 99 + (999 + 99)/9$

► **225** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)$
 := $2 + 222 + 2/2$
 := $3 \times 3 + (3 + 3)^3$
 := $4/4 + 4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times (55 - 5 - 5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6) + 6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $(7/7 + 7 + 7)^{(7+7)/7}$
 := $(8 - 8/8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8}$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 99$

► **228** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 111)$
 := $2 + 222 + 2 + 2$
 := $3 + (3 + 3)^3 + 3 \times 3$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $(5 - 5/5) \times ((5 + 5)/5 + 55)$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $(7 - 7/7) \times (7 \times 7 - 77/7)$
 := $(88/8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 99 + 9 + 999/9$

► **231** := $11 \times (11 + 11 - 1)$
 := $(22^2 - 22)/2$
 := $33 + 33 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $44 + 4 \times 44 + 44/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5/5$
 := $66 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6)$
 := $77 + 77 + 77$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) + 888/8 - 8$
 := $9 + (9 + 9) \times 999/(9 \times 9)$

► **232** := $111 + 11^{1+1}$
 := $2 + 222 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$
 := $(3^{3+3} - 33)/3$
 := $4^4 - 4 \times 4 - 4 - 4$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 \times (555/5 + 5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (66 - 6)/6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - 777/7$
 := $88 + 8 + 8 + 8 \times (8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99/9$

► **235** := $11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)$
 := $2 + 222 + 22/2$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} - 33)/3$
 := $4^4 - 4 - 4 \times 4 - 4/4$
 := $5 + 5 + 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5)$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6/6$
 := $7 + (7 - 7/7) \times (7 \times 7 - 77/7)$
 := $(8 \times 8 \times 88 + 8)/(8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9)$

► **238** := $(1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 \times ((22/2)^2 - 2)$
 := $(3^{3+3} + 3)/3 - 3 - 3$
 := $4^4 - 4 \times 4 - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $(5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + (66 + 66)/6$
 := $777 - 7 \times 77$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) + (888 - 8)/8$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9} - 9 - 9$

► **233** := $11 + (1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $222 + 22/2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3) - 3/3$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 4 \times 4 - 44/4$
 := $(5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 5 - 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 66/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 + (8 + 8 - 8/8)^{(8+8)/8}$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9/9 - 9$

► **236** := $1 + 11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 22$
 := $(3^{3+3} - 3)/3 - 3 - 3$
 := $4^4 - 4 \times 4 - 4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 + 555/5$
 := $66 \times 66/(6 + 6 + 6) - 6$
 := $(7 + 777/7) \times (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + (88/8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 + (9 + 9)/9$

► **239** := $(1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) - 1$
 := $(22^2 - 2)/2 - 2$
 := $(3^{3+3} - 3)/3 - 3$
 := $4^4 - 4 \times 4 - 4/4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 55/5$
 := $6 + 6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 66/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 777/7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8) + 888/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + ((9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **234** := $1 + 11 + (1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 22$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)$
 := $4^4 - 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $(5 - 5/5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 + 5/5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6 + 6$
 := $(77 + 7/7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $(8 \times (8 + 8) - 88/8) \times (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9$

► **237** := $11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111)$
 := $(22^2 - 2)/2 - 2 - 2$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)$
 := $4/4 + 4^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 + (555 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 66 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (77 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7)/7$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 88/8 - 8$
 := $99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 999/9$

► **240** := $(1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1)$
 := $22^2/2 - 2$
 := $3 \times 3 \times 3^3 - 3$
 := $4^4 - 4 \times 4$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5/5)$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6 - 6$
 := $(7 - (7 + 7)/7) \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7)$
 := $8 \times 8 + 88 + 88$
 := $(999/9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)/9$

► **241** := $(1 + 1) \times 11^{1+1} - 1$
 := $(22^2 - 2)/2$
 := $(3^{3+3} + 3)/3 - 3$
 := $4/4 + 4^4 - 4 \times 4$
 := $5 + 555/5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 66/6$
 := $7 + (7/7 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times 8 + 88 + 88$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (9 + 9)/9$

► **244** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $2 + 22^2/2$
 := $(3^{3+3} + 3)/3$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 4 \times 4$
 := $5/5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) - 7/7$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9/9$

► **247** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $2 + (22^2 + 2)/2 + 2$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} + 3)/3$
 := $4^4 - 4/4 - 4 - 4$
 := $5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 5/5$
 := $6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6$
 := $(7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7)$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 - 8/8$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9} - 9$

► **242** := $(1 + 1) \times 11^{1+1}$
 := $22^2/2$
 := $(3^{3+3} - 3)/3$
 := $44 \times 44/(4 + 4)$
 := $(5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5 - 5/5$
 := $66 \times 66/(6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $77/7 \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7/7)$
 := $88 \times (88 + 88)/(8 \times 8)$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9/9$

► **245** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $2 + (22^2 + 2)/2$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3$
 := $4^4 - 44/4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 5$
 := $(6 + 6/6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6/6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7)$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 88/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9)/9$

► **248** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $2 + 22^2/2 + 2 + 2$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3 + 3$
 := $4^4 - 4 - 4$
 := $5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 + 66 \times 66/(6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8$
 := $9/9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9} - 9$

► **243** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times 11^{1+1}$
 := $(22^2 + 2)/2$
 := $3 \times 3 \times 3^3$
 := $(4 - 4/4)^{4/4+4}$
 := $(5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $(6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^{6-6/6}$
 := $((7 + 7 + 7)/7)^{7-(7+7)/7}$
 := $(8 + 8/8) \times (8 + 8 + 88/8)$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)$

► **246** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $2 + 22^2/2 + 2$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 \times 3^3$
 := $4^4 + (4 - 44)/4$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7)$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8 - 88)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **249** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $2 + (22^2 + 2)/2 + 2 + 2$
 := $33 + (3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 44/4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 5/5$
 := $6 + (6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^{6-6/6}$
 := $((7 + 7)/7)^{7/7+7} - 7$
 := $8/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8$
 := $9 + (999/9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)/9$

► **250** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))$
 := $2 \times ((22/2)^2 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3 + 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3)/3$
 := $4^4 - 4 - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $(7 - (7 + 7)/7) \times (7 \times 7 + 7/7)$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8 - 8$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (9 + 9)/9$

► **253** := $11 \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
 := $(22^2 + 22)/2$
 := $3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3)/3$
 := $4/4 + 4^4 - 4$
 := $5 + 5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) + 7/7$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 88/8$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9/9$

► **256** := $(1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}}$
 := $2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $(3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3}$
 := 4^4
 := $(5 - 5/5)^{5-5/5}$
 := $((6 + 6)/6)^{(6+6)/6+6}$
 := $((7 + 7)/7)^{7/7+7}$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9}$

► **251** := $11 + (1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1)$
 := $(22^2 + 22)/2 - 2$
 := $3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3$
 := $4^4 - 4/4 - 4$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) - 7/7$
 := $8 + (8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9/9$

► **254** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
 := $2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2$
 := $(3^{3+3} + 33)/3$
 := $4^4 - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) - 5/5$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)$
 := $77 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7 \times 7$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $99/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)$

► **257** := $1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}}$
 := $2/2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} + 33)/3$
 := $4/4 + 4^4$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) - 55$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6/6$
 := $7/7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^{7/7+7}$
 := $8/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)$
 := $9/9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9}$

► **252** := $(1 + 11) \times (11 + 11 - 1)$
 := $2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2 - 2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 - 4$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7)$
 := $(8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)$

► **255** := $111 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2/2$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 - 4/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77/7 - 77$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (99 + 9)/9$

► **258** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}}$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3) + 3$
 := $4^4 + (4 + 4)/4$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 55$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)$
 := $(7 - 7/7) \times ((7/7 - 7) + 7 \times 7)$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **259** := $1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{(1+1)^{1+1+1}}$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2/2$
 := $3 + (3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3}$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 4/4$
 := $5 \times 55 - 55/5 - 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6/6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77 - 7$
 := $88/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8$
 := $99 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9)/9$

► **262** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 11) - 1)$
 := $22^2 - 222$
 := $3 + (3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3} + 3$
 := $4 + (4 + 4)/4 + 4^4$
 := $5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) - 55$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^{(6+6)/6+6}$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times 77 - 7)/(7 + 7) - 7$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) + 99$

► **265** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 11)$
 := $22 + (22^2 + 2)/2$
 := $(33 \times (3^3 - 3) + 3)/3$
 := $4 + 4/4 + 4^4 + 4$
 := $5 \times 55 - 5 - 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6/6 + 6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7 - 77$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8/8$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9}$

► **260** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} + 33)/3 + 3$
 := $4 + 4^4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5) + 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77 - 7$
 := $(8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9/9$

► **263** := $(1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 11) - 1$
 := $22 + (22^2 - 2)/2$
 := $(33 \times (3^3 - 3) - 3)/3$
 := $4 + 4^4 - 4/4 + 4$
 := $5 \times 55 - (55 + 5)/5$
 := $66/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^{7/7+7}$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99/9$

► **266** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 11))$
 := $222 + 2 \times 22$
 := $3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3) - 3)/3$
 := $4^4 + (44 - 4)/4$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times 55 - (5 + 5)$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9} + 9/9$

► **261** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 11) - 1) - 1$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2/2 + 2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3 + 3)$
 := $4 + 4/4 + 4^4$
 := $5 + (5 - 5/5)^{5-5/5}$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 77 + 7 \times 7$
 := $(88/8 - 8) \times (88 - 8/8)$
 := $99 + 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **264** := $(1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 11)$
 := $2 \times 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)$
 := $33 \times (3 \times 3 - 3/3)$
 := $4 + 4^4 + 4$
 := $5 \times 55 - 55/5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7 - 77$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + 999/9 - 9$

► **267** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 11))$
 := $22/2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $3 \times 3 \times (3^3 + 3) - 3$
 := $4^4 + 44/4$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((5 + 5)/5 - 5 - 5)$
 := $666 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 66$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77$
 := $88/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)$
 := $99/9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9}$

► **268** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11))$
 := $2 + 222 + 2 \times 22$
 := $3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3) + 3)/3$
 := $4 + 4^4 + 4 + 4$
 := $5 \times 5 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $(6 - (6 + 6)/6) \times (66 + 6/6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7 - 77$
 := $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9)/9 + 99$

► **271** := $1 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22/2 + 2$
 := $3^3 + (3^{3+3} + 3)/3$
 := $4 + 44/4 + 4^4$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times 55 - 5$
 := $66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 66/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7 - 77$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8/8 + 8$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) + 99 + 9/9$

► **274** := $11 \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)) - 1$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2^{2+2}$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 \times (3^3 + 3) + 3/3$
 := $4 \times 4 + ((4 + 4)/4 + 4^4)$
 := $5 \times 55 - 5/5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77 + 7/7$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8 + 8$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9} + 9$

► **269** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11))$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22/2$
 := $3^3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3$
 := $4 + 4/4 + 4^4 + 4 + 4$
 := $5 \times 55 - (5/5 + 5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 66/6$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times 77 - 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (88/8 - 8) \times (88 - 8/8)$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9/9 + 99$

► **272** := $(1 + 1 + 11) \times (11 + 11 - 1) - 1$
 := $2^{2+2} + 2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3 + 3^3$
 := $4 \times 4 + 4^4$
 := $5 \times 55 + (5 + 5)/5 - 5$
 := $6 + (6/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7 - 77$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8$
 := $99 + 99/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **275** := $11 \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))$
 := $22 + (22^2 + 22)/2$
 := $33 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3$
 := $4 + 44/4 + 4^4 + 4$
 := 5×55
 := $66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6/6 - 6$
 := $77/7 \times (77/7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (999 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **270** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $222 + 2 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $3 \times 3 \times (3^3 + 3)$
 := $4 + (44 - 4)/4 + 4^4$
 := $5 \times 55 - 5$
 := $666 - 6 \times 66$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times 77 + 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) + 99$

► **273** := $(1 + 1 + 11) \times (11 + 11 - 1)$
 := $(22/2 + 2) \times (22 - 2/2)$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 \times (3^3 + 3)$
 := $4 \times 4 + 4/4 + 4^4$
 := $5 \times 55 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 666 \times 6/(6 + 6) - 66$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8/8 + 8$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + 999/9$

► **276** := $(1 + 11) \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
 := $22 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2$
 := $33 + 3 \times 3 \times 3^3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4 + 4^4$
 := $5 \times 55 + 5/5$
 := $66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 77 - 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8) + 8$
 := $(99/9 + 9 \times 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **277** := $1 + (1 + 11) \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
 := $((22 + 2)^2 - 22)/2$
 := $33 + (3^{3+3} + 3)/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4 + 4^4 + 4/4$
 := $5 \times 55 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6 + 6/6$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 77 + 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $(8 - 8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8) - 8$
 := $99 + 99 - (9 + 9)/9 + 9 \times 9$

► **280** := $111 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 + (3/3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4 + 4^4 + 4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7 - 7$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9/9 + 99 + 99 + 9 \times 9$

► **283** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1) - 1$
 := $((22 + 2)^2 - 2)/2 - 2 - 2$
 := $3 + (3/3 + 3)^3 + (3 + 3)^3$
 := $4 \times 4 + 44/4 + 4^4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55 - (5 + 5)/5 + 5$
 := $66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6/6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 77/7$
 := $8 + 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9} + 9 + 9$

► **278** := $(1 + 1111)/(1 + 1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $22 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)/3 + 33$
 := $4^4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4)$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + 66 \times 66/(6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7 - 77$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $99 + 9 \times 9 - 9/9 + 99$

► **281** := $1 + 111 + (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + ((22 + 2)^2 - 22)/2 + 2$
 := $3^3 + (3^{3+3} + 33)/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4 + 4^4 + 4/4 + 4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55 + 5/5$
 := $66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6/6$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7 - 7$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88$
 := $9 + 99/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9) + 99$

► **284** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 \times ((2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2 - 2)$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3$
 := $44 + 4^4 - 4 \times 4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55 - 5/5 + 5$
 := $66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $(7 - 77)/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7)$
 := $(8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9) + (999 + 99)/9$

► **279** := $1 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + ((22 + 2)^2 - 22)/2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 3) + 3)$
 := $4 + 44/4 + 4^4 + 4 + 4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55 - 5/5$
 := $6 \times 66 - 666/6 - 6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7 - 7 - 7$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $99 + 99 + 9 \times 9$

► **282** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22 + 2$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 3) + 3)$
 := $4 + 44 \times 4/(4 + 4) + 4^4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55 + (5 + 5)/5$
 := $66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $77 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 77$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 999/9 + 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **285** := $(1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 11) - 1$
 := $((22 + 2)^2 - 2)/2 - 2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) - 3$
 := $44 + 4/4 - 4 \times 4 + 4^4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55 + 5$
 := $6 \times 66 - 666/6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - (7 + 7)/7 - 7$
 := $(8 - 8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)$
 := $(99 - 9/9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)/9 - 9$

► **286** := $(1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $22 \times (22/2 + 2)$
 := $33/3 \times (3^3 - 3/3)$
 := $44 + 44 \times 44/(4 + 4)$
 := $5 \times 55 + 55/5$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7 - 7$
 := $8 \times 8 + (8 + 8) \times 888/(8 \times 8)$
 := $99 \times (9 - 9/9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **289** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $(2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3)$
 := $44 + 4^4 - 44/4$
 := $5 \times (55 + 5) - 55/5$
 := $6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $(7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7$
 := $(8/8 + 8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8}$
 := $(9 + 9 - 9/9)^{(9+9)/9}$

► **292** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + (22 + 2)^2/2 + 2$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) + 3/3$
 := $4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4^4$
 := $5 + (55 + 5)/5 + 5 \times 55$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $(8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + 8) \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 9 \times 9 + (999 + 9)/9$

► **287** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1} - 1$
 := $((22 + 2)^2 - 2)/2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) - 3/3$
 := $4^4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4$
 := $5 \times 55 + (55 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) - 6/6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7$
 := $88 + 88 + 888/8$
 := $(99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9)/9 - 9$

► **290** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + (22 + 2)^2/2$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) - 3/3$
 := $44 + (4 - 44)/4 + 4^4$
 := $5 + (5 \times 55 + 5) + 5$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 77/7$
 := $8/8 + (8/8 + 8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8}$
 := $(9/9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9 + 9)$

► **293** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2 + 2$
 := $3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3/3 - 3$
 := $4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) + 4^4 + 4/4$
 := $5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5 \times 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) - 6/6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7$
 := $8 + (8 - 8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)$
 := $((9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9/9) - 9)/9$

► **288** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $(22 + 2)^2/2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3)$
 := $4^4 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5 \times 5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88$
 := $9 + (99 + 99) + 9 \times 9$

► **291** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + (2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3)$
 := $4 + 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4 + 4^4$
 := $5 + 5 \times 55 + 55/5$
 := $6 + 6 \times 66 - 666/6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88/8$
 := $99 + 9 \times 9 + 999/9$

► **294** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + (22 + 2)^2/2 + 2 + 2$
 := $3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3$
 := $44 + 4^4 - (4 + 4)/4 - 4$
 := $5 \times (55 + 5) - 5/5 - 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7)$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8) \times 888/(8 \times 8)$
 := $((9 + 9 + 9)/9) \times (99 - 9/9)$

► **295** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1$
 := $2 + (2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2 + 2 + 2$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3$
 := $44 + 4^4 - 4/4 - 4$
 := $5 \times (55 + 5) - 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) + 6/6$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7)$
 := $8 + 88 + 88 + 888/8$
 := $(99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (9 + 9))/9$

► **298** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $2 \times 22 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33$
 := $44 + 4^4 - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $55 + (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $(66 - 6)/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $77/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7$
 := $(88 \times (88/8 + 8 + 8) + 8)/8$
 := $(99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9)/9$

► **301** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + ((22 + 2)^2 + 22)/2$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 + 3/3$
 := $44 + 4/4 + 4^4$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times (55 + 5)$
 := $6/6 + (6 - 66) \times (6/6 - 6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7)$
 := $8 + (8 - 8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8) + 8$
 := $9 \times 9 + (99/9 + 9) \times 99/9$

► **296** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1} - 1$
 := $2 \times ((2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3/3$
 := $44 + 4^4 - 4$
 := $5/5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) - 5$
 := $((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6/6)$
 := $(7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7)$
 := $8 \times 888/(8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $(99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9)/9$

► **299** := $11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $((22 + 2)^2 + 22)/2$
 := $3 + (3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3/3)$
 := $44 + 4^4 - 4/4$
 := $5 \times (55 + 5) - 5/5$
 := $66/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - (7 + 7)/7)$
 := $(8 \times (888 + 8) + 8)/(8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $(99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 + 9)/9$

► **302** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $(2^{2+2} + 2)^2 - 22$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3/3 + 3$
 := $44 + (4 + 4)/4 + 4^4$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times (55 + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6/6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 7/7$
 := $(88 - 8/8 + 8 \times 8) \times (8 + 8)/8$
 := $(9 \times (9 + 9) - 99/9) \times (9 + 9)/9$

► **297** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $((22 + 2)^2 + 22)/2 - 2$
 := $3 \times 3 \times 33$
 := $44 + 4^4 + 4/4 - 4$
 := $5 \times 55 + (55 + 55)/5$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 66/(6 + (6 + 6)/6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + (8/8 + 8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8}$
 := $99 + 99 + 99$

► **300** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times 22 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33$
 := $44 + 4^4$
 := $5 \times (55 + 5)$
 := $(6 - 66) \times (6/6 - 6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7$
 := $(8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88) \times 8/(8 + 8)$
 := $(9/9 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **303** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $222 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2}$
 := $3 + (3 \times 3 \times 33 + 3)$
 := $4 + 44 - 4/4 + 4^4$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5 - 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times 6 \times 66/(6 + (6 + 6)/6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 888/8$
 := $9 + (99 - 9/9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **304** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + (2^{2+2} + 2)^2 - 22$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 + 3/3 + 3$
 := $4 + 44 + 4^4$
 := $5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) - 5/5$
 := $((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 6)$
 := $(7/7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - 77/7)$
 := $(8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 99/9 - 9$

► **307** := $111 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $(22 + 2/2)^2 - 222$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3)$
 := $4 + 44 - 4/4 + 4^4 + 4$
 := $(5^5 - 55)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (6 - 66) \times (6/6 - 6) + 6/6$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7 + 7$
 := $88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $9 + (99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9)/9$

► **310** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + 22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2)$
 := $((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3 - 33$
 := $44 + (44 - 4)/4 + 4^4$
 := $5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) + 5$
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6 - 6 + 66)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (7 + 7)/7 + 7$
 := $88 + (8 + 8) \times 888/(8 \times 8)$
 := $99 + 99 + (999 + 9)/9$

► **305** := $(11 \times 111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + (2/2 + 2)^{2+2} + 222$
 := $333 - 3^3 - 3/3$
 := $4 + 44 + 4^4 + 4/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times (55 + 5)$
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times (66 - 6 + 6/6)$
 := $77/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7)$
 := $8/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 88/8)$
 := $9 + (99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9)/9$

► **308** := $(1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2)$
 := $33/3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33$
 := $4 + 44 + 4^4 + 4$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5$
 := $66 + 66 \times 66/(6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 7$
 := $88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8 + 8)$
 := $99/9 \times (9/9 + 9 + 9 + 9)$

► **311** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $22 + (2^{2+2} + 2/2)^2$
 := $3 + 3 \times 3 \times 33 + 33/3$
 := $44 + 44/4 + 4^4$
 := $55/5 + 5 \times (55 + 5)$
 := $6 + (6 - 6/6) \times (66 - 6 + 6/6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $8 + 888/8 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - (99 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **306** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11) - 1)$
 := $22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2) - 2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3)$
 := $4 + 44 + 4^4 + (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) + 5/5$
 := $6 + (6 - 66) \times (6/6 - 6)$
 := $(7 - 7/7) \times (7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7)$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 88/8)$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 - 9/9)$

► **309** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $22 + ((22 + 2)^2 - 2)/2$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3)$
 := $4^4 + (4^4 - 44)/4$
 := $5 + (5 \times (55 + 5) - 5/5) + 5$
 := $66 + (6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^{6-6/6}$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 7/7 + 7$
 := $8/8 + 88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8 + 8)$
 := $99 + 999/9 + 99$

► **312** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$
 := $(22 + 2) \times (22/2 + 2)$
 := $3 + 3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3) + 3$
 := $4 + 4 + 4 + 44 + 4^4$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6 - 6$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 77/7$
 := $8 + (8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - (99 + 9)/9$

<p>► 313 := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 11)$:= $(2^{2+2} + 2)^2 - 22/2$:= $3 + (3/3 + 3 + 3)^3 - 33$:= $4 + (4^4 - 44)/4 + 4^4$:= $(5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$:= $6 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 66/6$:= $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + (77 + 7)/7$:= $8 + (8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8) + 8/8$:= $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 99/9$</p>	<p>► 316 := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 11)$:= $2 \times (2 \times ((2/2) + 2)^{2+2} - 2)$:= $(3/3 + 3 + 3)^3 - 3^3$:= $4 \times 4 + 44 + 4^4$:= $5 + 5 \times (55 + 5) + 55/5$:= $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$:= $7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 77$:= $8 + 88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8 + 8)$:= $9/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9$</p>	<p>► 319 := $11 \times ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1)$:= $2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2) - 2/2$:= $333 - 33/3 - 3$:= $4^4 + (4^4 - 4)/4$:= $5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 5/5$:= $66 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + 6/6$:= $7 + 7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 77/7$:= $8 \times 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8/8$:= $99/9 \times (99/9 + 9 + 9)$</p>
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<p>► 314 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 11))$:= $2 + (22 + 2) \times (22/2 + 2)$:= $3 \times 33 + (3 + 3)^3 - 3/3$:= $4^4 + (4^4 - 4 - 4)/4 - 4$:= $5/5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$:= $(6 - 6/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6$:= $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7/7 + 77)$:= $8 + (8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8) + (8 + 8)/8$:= $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9/9 - 9$</p>	<p>► 317 := $1 + (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1} - 11)$:= $2 + 22^2 - (22/2 + 2)^2$:= $333 + 33/3 - 3^3$:= $4^4 + (4^4 + 4)/4 - 4$:= $5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5)$:= $66 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) - 6/6$:= $(77/7 + 7)^{(7+7)/7} - 7$:= $8 + 88 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)/(8 + 8) + 8/8$:= $(9 + 9)/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9$</p>	<p>► 320 := $(11 - 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1)$:= $2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2)$:= $333 + (3 - 33)/3 - 3$:= $4 \times 4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$:= $(5 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5$:= $(6 - 6/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6$:= $(7/7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7 - 7)$:= $8 \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8)$:= $(9 - 9/9) \times (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)$</p>
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<p>► 315 := $((1 + 1)^{1+11} - 1)/(1 + 1 + 11)$:= $22^2 - (22/2 + 2)^2$:= $3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3 + 3)$:= $4^4 + (4^4 - 4)/4 - 4$:= $(5 \times 5 + 5^5)/(5 + 5)$:= $(666 - 6 \times 6) \times 6/(6 + 6)$:= $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 77$:= $88/8 + (8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)$:= $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9$</p>	<p>► 318 := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1) - 1 - 11$:= $2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2) - 2$:= $3 + 3 \times 33 + (3 + 3)^3$:= $4^4 + (4^4 - 4 - 4)/4$:= $5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$:= $66 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6)$:= $7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77/7 - 7 - 7$:= $8 \times 8 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$:= $9 + 999/9 + 99 + 99$</p>	<p>► 321 := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1 - 11$:= $2/2 + (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2))$:= $333 - (3 \times 3 + 3)$:= $4^4 + (4^4 + 4)/4$:= $5/5 + ((5 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)$:= $6 \times 6 \times 6 + (666/6 - 6)$:= $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7 + 7 + 7)$:= $8/8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + 8 \times 8)$:= $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$</p>
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► **322** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 11$
 := $((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 2$
 := $333 - 33/3$
 := $4^4 + (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 5)$
 := $(6 \times (66 - (6 + 6))) - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9)/9$

► **325** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1))^{1+1}$
 := $2/2 + ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2)$
 := $3 + (333 - 33/3)$
 := $4 + (((4^4 + 4)/4 + 4^4)$
 := $5 \times (55 + 5 + 5)$
 := $6/6 + (6 \times (66 - (6 + 6)))$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (77/7 + 7)$
 := $(8/8 + 8 \times 8) \times ((8 - 88/8) + 8)$
 := $9/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)$

► **328** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 + (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) + 2)$
 := $3/3 + (333 - (3 + 3))$
 := $4 + (4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4)$
 := $5 + (((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 5) + 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + (666 + 6)/6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + 8 \times 8)$
 := $9 + ((99/9) \times (99/9 + 9 + 9))$

► **323** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 11$
 := $((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 2/2$
 := $333 + ((3 - 33)/3)$
 := $4 + (((4^4 - 4)/4) + 4^4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 5)$
 := $(6 \times (66 - (6 + 6))) - 6/6$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7))$
 := $(8/8 + 8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9/9$

► **326** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) - 1$
 := $2 + ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2)$
 := $333 - ((3/3 + 3) + 3)$
 := $4 + (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4) + 4^4$
 := $5/5 + (5 \times (55 + 5 + 5))$
 := $6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (((7 - 77)/7) - 7)$
 := $8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8 \times 8$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)$

► **329** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1) - 1$
 := $2 + (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) + 2/2) + 2)$
 := $333 - (3/3 + 3)$
 := $4 + (((4^4 + 4)/4 + 4^4) + 4)$
 := $55 + (5 \times 55 - 5/5)$
 := $6 \times 66 - (66 + 6/6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + 8/8) + 8 \times 8$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + ((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **324** := $((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1))^{1+1}$
 := $(2^{2+2} + 2)^2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times (33 + 3))$
 := $4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $(5/5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5)$
 := $6 \times (66 - (6 + 6))$
 := $(77/7 + 7)^{(7+7)/7}$
 := $((((8 + 8)/8) + 8) + 8)^{(8+8)/8}$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)$

► **327** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 + (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) + 2/2)$
 := $333 - (3 + 3)$
 := $4 + (((4^4 - 4)/4) + 4^4) + 4$
 := $5 + (((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 5) + 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + 666/6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (((7 + 7)/7 + 7) + 7)$
 := $8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) - 8/8) + 8 \times 8$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)$

► **330** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1)$
 := $22 \times ((22/2 + 2) + 2)$
 := $333 - 3$
 := $4^4 + (((4^4 - 4) + 44)/4)$
 := $55 + 5 \times 55$
 := $66 \times (6 - 6/6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7))$
 := $88/8 \times ((88 + 88)/8 + 8)$
 := $(999 - 9)/((9 + 9 + 9)/9)$

► **331** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1)$
 := $222 + (222/2 - 2)$
 := $3/3 + (333 - 3)$
 := $4^4 + ((44 + 4^4)/4)$
 := $55 + (5 \times 55 + 5/5)$
 := $6/6 + 66 \times (6 - 6/6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + ((8/8 + 8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8))$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - ((9 + 9)/9))$

► **334** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $2 \times (((22/2 + 2)^2) - 2)$
 := $3/3 + 333$
 := $444 + ((4 - 444)/4)$
 := $5 + ((5 \times 55 - 5/5) + 55)$
 := $6/6 + 666 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7)$
 := $((8 + 8 + 8) \times 888/8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9/9)$

► **337** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)$
 := $((22 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2)/2$
 := $3 + (333 + 3/3)$
 := $4^4 + (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (66 \times (6 - 6/6) + 6/6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7)$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 888/8$
 := $9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9})$

► **332** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1$
 := $2 + (22 \times ((22/2 + 2) + 2))$
 := $333 - 3/3$
 := $4 + ((4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4) + 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 55)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - 77/7$
 := $8 + (((((8 + 8)/8) + 8) + 8)^{(8+8)/8})$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9/9)$

► **335** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $2 + (222/2 + 222)$
 := $3 + (333 - 3/3)$
 := $4 + (((44 + 4^4)/4) + 4^4)$
 := $5 + (5 \times 55 + 55)$
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times (66 + 6/6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7)$
 := $((8 - 8/8)^{88/8-8}) - 8$
 := $99/9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)$

► **338** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times ((22/2 + 2)^2)$
 := $3 + ((333 - 3/3) + 3)$
 := $4/4 + ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4^4)$
 := $5 \times 5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7 - 7)$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + ((8 - 888)/8)$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9))$

► **333** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $222 + 222/2$
 := 333
 := $4^4 + ((4 - 4/4)^4 - 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5)$
 := $666 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (7 - 77)/7$
 := $(88/8 - 8) \times 888/8$
 := $9 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)$

► **336** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 22) - 2)))$
 := $3 + 333$
 := $4 \times ((4 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)) + 4)$
 := $(5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5/5)$
 := $6 + 66 \times (6 - 6/6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7$
 := $88 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) - 8)$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99 + 9)/9$

► **339** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111)$
 := $((22 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)/2$
 := $3 + (333 + 3)$
 := $(4 \times ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4)) - 4/4$
 := $((5^5 - 55)/5) - 5 \times 55$
 := $6 + 666 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (77/7))$
 := $8 + (((8/8 + 8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8)) + 8)$
 := $9 + ((999 - 9)/((9 + 9 + 9)/9))$

► **340** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111)$
 := $2 + (2 \times ((22/2 + 2)^2))$
 := $((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3 - 3$
 := $4 \times ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4)$
 := $5 + ((5 \times 55 + 55) + 5)$
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $((8 \times 88 - 8)/((8 + 8)/8)) - 8$
 := $((9 - 9/9) + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)$

► **343** := $11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1$
 := $222 + (22/2)^2$
 := $((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3$
 := $((4 - 4/4) + 4)^{4-4/4}$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 5 \times 5)$
 := $(6/6 + 6)^{6 \times 6/(6+6)}$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7$
 := $(8 - 8/8)^{88/8-8}$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9/9) + 9)$

► **346** := $1 + 1 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $22 + ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2)$
 := $3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3)$
 := $((4 + 4) \times 44) - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4)$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/5 - (5 \times 55 + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66))$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $88 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9} + 9 \times 9)$

► **341** := $11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1)$
 := $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2)/2$
 := $3 \times 3 + (333 - 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4^4)$
 := $5 + ((5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5/5))$
 := $6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (66 + 6/6))$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + ((88/8 - 8) \times 888/8)$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9/9) + 9)$

► **344** := $11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2))$
 := $333 + 33/3$
 := $44 + (44 + 4^4)$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/5 - (5 \times 55 + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6) + 6)$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7$
 := $88 + ((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8))$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99/9))$

► **347** := $11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)$
 := $2 + (((22/2)^2 + 222) + 2)$
 := $3 + (333 + 33/3)$
 := $((4 + 4) \times 44) - (4/4 + 4)$
 := $(55/5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) - 5$
 := $6 \times (66 - 6) - (6/6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77/7 - 7)$
 := $((8 \times 88 - 8)/((8 + 8)/8)) - 8/8$
 := $9 \times 9 \times (9 + 9) - 9999/9$

► **342** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1 + 111))$
 := $2 \times (((22/2 + 2)^2) + 2)$
 := $3 \times 3 + 333$
 := $(4 - 44)/4 + ((4 + 4) \times 44)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 5 \times 5)$
 := $6 + (66 \times (6 - 6/6) + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7$
 := $88 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) - ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9)$

► **345** := $1 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $2 + ((22/2)^2 + 222)$
 := $3 + (333 + 3 \times 3)$
 := $4 + (((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4^4) + 4)$
 := $5^5 - (5 \times 555 + 5)$
 := $6 + (666 \times 6/(6 + 6) + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8/8 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + 88)$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + ((99 + 9)/9))$

► **348** := $1 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)$
 := $2 \times ((2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22) - 2)$
 := $3 + ((333 + 3 \times 3) + 3)$
 := $((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4$
 := $(5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 55$
 := $6 \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $(8 \times 88 - 8)/((8 + 8)/8)$
 := $((99 + 9)/9) \times (99/9 + 9 + 9)$

► **349** := $11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $(22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2/2 - 2$
 := $3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) + 3$
 := $4/4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4)$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 55$
 := $6 \times (66 - 6) - 66/6$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7)$
 := $8/8 + ((8 \times 88 - 8)/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 + (((9 - 9/9) + 9) \times (99/9 + 9))$

► **352** := $11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1)$
 := $22 \times 2^{2+2}$
 := $3 \times 3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3)$
 := $(4 + 4) \times 44$
 := $55/5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 \times (66 - 6) - ((6 + 6)/6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times (88/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $((9/9 + 9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9}) - 9$

► **355** := $11 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $2 + ((22 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2/2)$
 := $3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) + 3 \times 3$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4)$
 := $55 + (5 \times (55 + 5))$
 := $6/6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) - 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77 + 7)/7$
 := $88 + (((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + (88/8))$
 := $99 + (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9})$

► **350** := $11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111)$
 := $(22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2$
 := $3 + ((333 + 33/3) + 3)$
 := $((4 + 4) \times 44) - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times ((55 + 5 + 5) + 5)$
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7$
 := $((8 + 8)/8) \times (888/8 + 8 \times 8)$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **353** := $1 + 11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1)$
 := $2/2 + (22 \times 2^{2+2})$
 := $3 \times 3 + (333 + 33/3)$
 := $4/4 + ((4 + 4) \times 44)$
 := $((55 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times (66 - 6) - 6/6 - 6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times (88/((8 + 8)/8)))$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99/9)) + 9)$

► **356** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1)) - 1$
 := $2 + ((22 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2)$
 := $3^3 + (333 - (3/3 + 3))$
 := $4 + ((4 + 4) \times 44)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 55)$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) - 6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7) + 7)$
 := $(8 \times 88 + 8)/((8 + 8)/8)$
 := $((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)/(9 + 9) - 9$

► **351** := $11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) - 1$
 := $(22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2/2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times (33 + 3 + 3))$
 := $((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 55$
 := $(666 + 6 \times 6)/((6 + 6)/6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7/7)$
 := $8 + ((8 - 8/8)^{88/8-8})$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9) + 9)$

► **354** := $1 + 1 + 11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1)$
 := $2 + (22 \times 2^{2+2})$
 := $3 + (333 + (3 \times (3 + 3)))$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + ((4 + 4) \times 44)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 55)$
 := $6 \times (66 - 6) - 6$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + 77/7$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (88/((8 + 8)/8)))$
 := $9 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 999/9$

► **357** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1 - 1)$
 := $(2/2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 - 2)$
 := $3^3 + (333 - 3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4/4)$
 := $5 + (55/5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)$
 := $66 \times 66/(6 + 6) - 6$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7)$
 := $8/8 + ((8 \times 88 + 8)/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $((9 - 9/9) + 9) \times (((99 + 9)/9) + 9)$

► **358** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1))$
 := $2 + (((22 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2) + 2)$
 := $3^3 + ((333 - 3) + 3/3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + (4 + 4)/4)$
 := $5 + (((55 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) + 5)/5)$
 := $6 \times (66 - 6) - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7/7) + 7)$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - ((8 + 8)/8 + 88)$
 := $((9 + 9)/9) \times ((9 \times 9 - 9/9) + 99)$

► **361** := $((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)) - 1^{1+1}$
 := $(22 - (2/2 + 2))^2$
 := $3^3 + (333 + 3/3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4/4) + 4)$
 := $5/5 + (5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5)$
 := $6/6 + 6 \times (66 - 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77/7))$
 := $(88/8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8}$
 := $(9/9 + 9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9}$

► **364** := $1 + 11 \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 \times ((2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2)) + 2)$
 := $(33 \times 33 + 3)/3$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4) + 4)$
 := $(5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 55/5$
 := $6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) - ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 88 + 8)/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **359** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) - 1$
 := $((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2) - 2$
 := $3^3 + (333 - 3/3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4) + 4)$
 := $(5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5) - 5/5$
 := $6 \times (66 - 6) - 6/6$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)) + 7)$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (8/8 + 88)$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **362** := $11 \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2)))$
 := $(33 \times 33 - 3)/3$
 := $4^4 + ((444 - 4)/4 - 4)$
 := $55 + (5^5 - 55)/(5 + 5)$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times (66 - 6)$
 := $7 + ((77 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7)$
 := $8/8 + ((88/8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8})$
 := $9/9 + ((9/9 + 9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9})$

► **365** := $1 + 1 + 11 \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + (((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2) + 2)$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 33 - 3)/3)$
 := $(4/4 + 4)^4 - (4^4 + 4)$
 := $5 + (5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5)$
 := $6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) - 6/6)$
 := $7 + (((7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7/7) + 7) + 7)$
 := $888 - (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8)$
 := $((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **360** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1)$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 + 2))$
 := $3^3 + 333$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4)$
 := $(5/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5)$
 := $6 \times (66 - 6)$
 := $7 + (((77 - 7)/7) + 7 \times 7 \times 7)$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 88$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)$

► **363** := $11 \times 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2)$
 := $33 \times 33/3$
 := $4^4 + (444/4 - 4)$
 := $55 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5)$
 := $66 \times 66/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (((7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7) + 7) + 7)$
 := $88/8 + (8 \times (88/((8 + 8)/8)))$
 := $(99 \times 99)/(9 + 9 + 9)$

► **366** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $222 + ((2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))^2)$
 := $33 + 333$
 := $4^4 + (444 - 4)/4$
 := $(5/5 + 5) \times ((55 + 5/5) + 5)$
 := $6 + 6 \times (66 - 6)$
 := $7 + (((7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)) + 7) + 7)$
 := $((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)) + ((888 - 8)/8)$
 := $9/9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)/(9 + 9))$

- **367** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $222/2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 33 + 3)/3)$
 := $4^4 + 444/4$
 := $55 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + 6/6)$
 := $7 + (((77 - 7)/7) + 7 \times 7 \times 7) + 7$
 := $888/8 + ((8 + 8) \times (8 + 8))$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9) \times ((9 \times 9 - 9/9) + 99))$
- **370** := $(1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 22) + 2))))$
 := $3^3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3)$
 := $4 + ((444 - 4)/4 + 4^4)$
 := $(5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 5$
 := $6 \times (66 - 6) + (66 - 6)/6$
 := $77 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) - 7/7)$
 := $(8888 - 8)/(8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9/9 + 9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9})$
- **373** := $(11 + 11)^{1+1} - 111$
 := $22^2 - 222/2$
 := $3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) + 3^3$
 := $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4^4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 55)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (66 - 6) + 6/6) + 6)$
 := $77 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $(8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) - 88/8$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) - 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **368** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 22) + 2)))$
 := $3 + (((33 \times 33 - 3)/3) + 3)$
 := $4 \times (44 + 44 + 4)$
 := $55 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77/7)) + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 88)$
 := $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)) + 9)$
- **371** := $1 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $22^2 - (222/2 + 2)$
 := $3^3 + (333 + 33/3)$
 := $4 + (444/4 + 4^4)$
 := $5/5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 5)$
 := $66/6 + 6 \times (66 - 6)$
 := $77 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7)$
 := $(8 - 8/8) \times (8 \times 8 - 88/8)$
 := $99/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9))$
- **374** := $11 \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $22 + (22 \times 2^{2+2})$
 := $33/3 \times (3/3 + 33)$
 := $(44 \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4))/(4 + 4)$
 := $(5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 5/5$
 := $(66/6) \times (6 \times 6 - ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (77/7 + 7)$
 := $888 - (8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8)$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **369** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11^{1+1}))$
 := $(2/2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 + 2)$
 := $3 + (333 + 33)$
 := $(4/4 + 4)^4 - 4^4$
 := $(5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - (5/5 + 5)$
 := $6 + 66 \times 66/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (((77 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7) + 7)$
 := $8 + ((88/8 + 8)^{(8+8)/8})$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9))$
- **372** := $1 + 1 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 \times ((2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 22) + 2))) + 2)$
 := $3 + ((333 + 33) + 3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4 \times 4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 55)$
 := $6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + 6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7) + 77)$
 := $8 + (((8 \times 88 + 8)/((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)$
 := $9 + ((99 \times 99)/(9 + 9 + 9))$
- **375** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $2 + (22^2 - 222/2)$
 := $3 \times ((3 - 3/3 + 3)^3)$
 := $4 + ((444/4 + 4^4) + 4)$
 := $5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))$
 := $6 + (66 \times 66/(6 + 6) + 6)$
 := $7 + (((7 \times 7 \times 7 + (77/7)) + 7) + 7)$
 := $888 - (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8)$
 := $((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 999/9$

- **376** := $1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $(22 - 2)^2 - (22 + 2)$
 := $33 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3)$
 := $(4 + 4) \times (44 - 4/4 + 4)$
 := $5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)))$
 := $6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + ((66 - 6)/6))$
 := $(7/7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $888 - 8 \times 8 \times 8$
 := $9 \times 9 + ((99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (9 + 9))/9)$
- **377** := $11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $(22/2)^2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $3 + (33/3 \times (3/3 + 33))$
 := $4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4^4) + 4)$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)))$
 := $6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + (66/6))$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7/7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8/8 + (888 - 8 \times 8 \times 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + ((99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9)/9)$
- **378** := $1 + 11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $(22 - 2)^2 - 22$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3^3)$
 := $4^4 + ((444 + 44)/4)$
 := $((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5)$
 := $6 \times 66 - 6 - 6 - 6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7 + 7)$
 := $(8 - (8 + 8)/8) \times (8 \times 8 - 8/8)$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (((99 + 9)/9) + 9)$
- **379** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)) - 1$
 := $2/2 + ((22 - 2)^2 - 22)$
 := $3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3) + 33$
 := $444 - (4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) - 5/5)$
 := $6 \times 66 - ((66/6) + 6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7 + 7))$
 := $8 + ((8 - 8/8) \times (8 \times 8 - 88/8))$
 := $9 \times 99 - (((9 + 9)/9)^9)$
- **380** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $2 + ((22 - 2)^2 - 22)$
 := $3 + ((33/3 \times (3/3 + 33)) + 3)$
 := $444 - 4 \times 4 \times 4$
 := $5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)))$
 := $6 \times 66 + (((6 - 66)/6) - 6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (77 + 7)/7$
 := $(8 \times (88 + 8) - 8)/((8 + 8)/8)$
 := $(9/9 + 9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)$
- **381** := $11 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + (((22 - 2)^2 - 22) + 2/2)$
 := $3 + (3 \times (3 \times 33 + 3^3))$
 := $444 + ((4 - 4^4)/4)$
 := $5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))) + 5/5)$
 := $6 + ((66 \times 66/(6 + 6) + 6) + 6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 77/7$
 := $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) - (88/8))$
 := $9 + (((99 \times 99)/(9 + 9 + 9)) + 9)$
- **382** := $1 + 11 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $(2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2)) - 2$
 := $3333/3 - 3^{3+3}$
 := $4^4 + ((4^4 - 4)/((4 + 4)/4))$
 := $5^5/5 - ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5)$
 := $6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $((7 - 77)/7) + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7)$
 := $(8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9999/9 - 9 \times 9 \times 9$
- **383** := $(1 + 11) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) - 1$
 := $22 + ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2)$
 := $((3 + 3) \times ((3/3 + 3)^3)) - 3/3$
 := $((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)) - 4/4$
 := $5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5))$
 := $6 \times 66 - (6/6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7)$
 := $(8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) - 8/8$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9$
- **384** := $(1 + 11) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1)$
 := $2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2)$
 := $(3 + 3) \times ((3/3 + 3)^3)$
 := $(4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)$
 := $((55 + 5)/5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $(7/7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7)$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))$
 := $((9 + 9)/9) \times (999/9 + 9 \times 9)$

► **385** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $2/2 + (2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2))$
 := $3/3 + ((3 + 3) \times ((3/3 + 3)^3))$
 := $4/4 + ((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4))$
 := $55 \times ((5 + 5)/5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 66 - 66/6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)))$
 := $99/9 \times (((9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9) + 9$

► **388** := $((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} - 1 - 11$
 := $2 \times (((2^{2+2} - 2)^2) - 2)$
 := $3 + (((3 + 3) \times ((3/3 + 3)^3)) + 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4))$
 := $5 \times 55 + (555 + 5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6 + 6)$
 := $((7 \times 777) - 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $(8 \times (88 + 8) + 8)/((8 + 8)/8)$
 := $9 + (9 \times 99 - (((9 + 9)/9)^9))$

► **391** := $(1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 11^{1+1}$
 := $2 + ((22 - 2)^2 - 22/2)$
 := $3^3 + ((33 \times 33 + 3)/3)$
 := $444 + ((44 - 4^4)/4)$
 := $5 + (555/5 + 5 \times 55)$
 := $6/6 + (6 \times 66 - 6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7/7$
 := $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) - 8/8)$
 := $((99/9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9}) - 9$

► **386** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $2 + (2^{2+2} \times (22 + 2))$
 := $3^{3+3} - (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3)$
 := $4^4 + ((4^4 + 4)/((4 + 4)/4))$
 := $5 \times 55 + 555/5$
 := $6 \times 66 + (6 - 66)/6$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7)$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)))$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - ((99 + 9 + 9) + 9)$

► **389** := $((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} - 11$
 := $(22 - 2)^2 - 22/2$
 := $3^3 + ((33 \times 33 - 3)/3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)) + 4/4)$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) - 55/5$
 := $6 \times 66 - 6/6 - 6$
 := $((7 \times 777) + 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $((8 - 8/8) \times 888) + 8)/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9/9 + 9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9))$

► **392** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2)$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times (3 \times 33 - 3/3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)) + 4)$
 := $((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5/5)$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times 66 - 6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)))$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times ((9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **387** := $1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $(22 - 2)^2 - (22/2 + 2)$
 := $3 + ((3 + 3) \times ((3/3 + 3)^3))$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)) - 4/4)$
 := $5 \times 55 + (555 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times 66 + (((6 - 66) + 6)/6)$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7)$
 := $888 + (88/8 - 8 \times 8 \times 8)$
 := $((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 99$

► **390** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} - 11$
 := $(2 \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2)) - 2$
 := $3^3 + (33 \times 33/3)$
 := $((4 + 4)/4 + 4) \times (4^4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + (55 \times ((5 + 5)/5 + 5))$
 := $6 \times 66 - 6$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $(8 - (8 + 8)/8) \times (8/8 + 8 \times 8)$
 := $((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 999)/(9 + 9)$

► **393** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 11) - 1)$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2))$
 := $(33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)) + 4/4) + 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 55)$
 := $6 \times 66 - 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) + 8/8)$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9) \times (999/9 + 9 \times 9))$

<p>▶ 394 := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 11) - 1)$:= $2 + (2 \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2))$:= $3/3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3)$:= $4 + (((4 + 4)/4 + 4) \times (4^4 + 4)/4)$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (5^5/5 + 5)$:= $6 \times 66 - (6 + 6)/6$:= $((7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7)$:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) + ((8 + 8)/8))$:= $9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - (99/9))$</p>	<p>▶ 397 := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$:= $(22 - 2)^2 - 2/2 - 2$:= $3/3 + (33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3))$:= $44 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4/4)$:= $5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times (55 + 5/5))$:= $6/6 + 6 \times 66$:= $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7))$:= $8/8 + ((88 \times (8 \times 8 + 8))/(8 + 8))$:= $((9 + 9) \times (99 + 99) + 9)/9$</p>	<p>▶ 400 := $((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}$:= $(22 - 2)^2$:= $3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) + 3/3)$:= $444 - 44$:= $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55)$:= $6 + (6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6))$:= $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + 7/7)$:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) + 8)$:= $(99/9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9}$</p>
<p>▶ 395 := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11) - 1$:= $(22 - 2)^2 - (2/2 + 2 + 2)$:= $(33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3/3$:= $44 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4)$:= $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) - 5$:= $6 \times 66 - 6/6$:= $7 + (((7 \times 777) - 7)/(7 + 7))$:= $88/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)))$:= $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - (99 + 9 + 9)$</p>	<p>▶ 398 := $((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} - 1 - 1$:= $(22 - 2)^2 - 2$:= $3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3/3)$:= $444 - ((4 + 4)/4 + 44)$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (5^5 + 5)/5$:= $(6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 66$:= $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7/7)$:= $8 + ((8 - (8 + 8)/8) \times (8/8 + 8 \times 8))$:= $((9 + 9)/9) \times ((9/9 + 99) + 99)$</p>	<p>▶ 401 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}$:= $2/2 + (22 - 2)^2$:= $3 + (((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3/3) + 3)$:= $4/4 + (444 - 44)$:= $5/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55)$:= $6 + (6 \times 66 - 6/6)$:= $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7))$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - 888/8$:= $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - 999/9$</p>
<p>▶ 396 := $11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)$:= $22 \times (2^{2+2} + 2)$:= $33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)$:= $44 + ((4 + 4) \times 44)$:= $5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) - 5)$:= 6×66 := $7 + (((7 \times 777) + 7)/(7 + 7))$:= $(88 \times (8 \times 8 + 8))/(8 + 8)$:= $9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9)$</p>	<p>▶ 399 := $((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} - 1$:= $(22 - 2)^2 - 2/2$:= $3 + (33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3))$:= $4 \times 4^4 - (4/4 + 4)^4$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - 5^5/5$:= $6 \times 66 + (6 \times 6/(6 + 6))$:= $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7)$:= $(8 - 8/8) \times ((8/8 - 8) + 8 \times 8)$:= $(9/9 + 9 + 9) \times (((99 + 9)/9) + 9)$</p>	<p>▶ 402 := $1 + 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}$:= $2 + (22 - 2)^2$:= $3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) + 3)$:= $444 + ((4 + 4)/4 - 44)$:= $(5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55)$:= $6 + 6 \times 66$:= $((77 - 7)/7) + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7)$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((8 - 888)/8)$:= $((9 + 9)/9)^9 + ((9 - 999)/9)$</p>

▶ 403 := $1 + 1 + 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}$	▶ 406 := $11 \times 111 / (1 + 1 + 1) - 1$	▶ 409 := $1 + 1 + 11 \times 111 / (1 + 1 + 1)$
:= $2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2/2$	:= $2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2 + 2$	:= $22/2 + (22 - 2)^2 - 2$
:= $3 + (((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) + 3/3) + 3)$	:= $3/3 + (3^3 \times ((3 \times 3 + 3) + 3))$	:= $3 + ((3^3 \times ((3 \times 3 + 3) + 3)) + 3/3)$
:= $4 + (4 \times 4^4 - (4/4 + 4)^4)$	:= $4 + (((4 + 4)/4 - 44) + 444)$	:= $4 + ((4/4 + 4) \times (4 - 4/4)^4)$
:= $5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - (5^5 + 5)/5)$	:= $5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5/5)$	:= $5 + (((5 - 5/5)^5 - 5^5/5) + 5)$
:= $6 + (6 \times 66 + 6/6)$	:= $6 \times 66 + (66 - 6)/6$	:= $6 + ((6 \times 66 + 6/6) + 6)$
:= $77/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7)$	:= $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + 7)$	:= $77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (77/7))$
:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))) + (88/8))$	:= $(8 - 8/8) \times (((8 + 8)/8) - 8) + 8 \times 8$	:= $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 888/8)$
:= $9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - ((9 + 9)/9))$	:= $9/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9)$	:= $9 + ((99/9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9})$
▶ 404 := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}))$	▶ 407 := $11 \times 111 / (1 + 1 + 1)$	▶ 410 := $11 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} - 1$
:= $2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2$	:= $2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2/2 + 2 + 2$	:= $2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2 \times (2 + 2)$
:= $333 + (((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3)$	:= $33 \times 333/3^3$	:= $3 + 33 \times 333/3^3$
:= $4 + (444 - 44)$	:= $4 + ((4 \times 4^4 - (4/4 + 4)^4) + 4)$	:= $((4 + 4)^4 + 4) / ((44 - 4)/4)$
:= $5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - 5^5/5)$	:= $55/5 \times (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5)$	:= $5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5)$
:= $6 + (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 66)$	:= $6 \times 66 + 66/6$	:= $6 + (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 66) + 6)$
:= $7 \times 77 - (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7)$	:= $7 + ((7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + 7/7) + 7)$	:= $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) + (77/7))$
:= $8 + ((88 \times (8 \times 8 + 8)) / (8 + 8))$	:= $8888/8 - 8 \times 88$	:= $8 + (((8 - 888)/8) + 8 \times 8 \times 8)$
:= $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - (99 + 9)$	:= $9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + ((9 + 9)/9))$	:= $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9 - 999/9)$
▶ 405 := $11 \times 111 / (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 - 1$	▶ 408 := $1 + 11 \times 111 / (1 + 1 + 1)$	▶ 411 := $11 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}$
:= $2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 2/2 + 2$	:= $2 \times (2 + 2) + (22 - 2)^2$	:= $22/2 + (22 - 2)^2$
:= $3^3 \times ((3 \times 3 + 3) + 3)$	:= $3 + (3^3 \times ((3 \times 3 + 3) + 3))$	:= $3 \times 3^3 + (333 - 3)$
:= $(4/4 + 4) \times (4 - 4/4)^4$	:= $4 + ((444 - 44) + 4)$	:= $44 + (444/4 + 4^4)$
:= $5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55)$	:= $(5 \times 5 - 5/5) \times (((55 + 5)/5) + 5)$	:= $55/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55)$
:= $6 + ((6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)) + 6 \times 66)$	:= $6 + (6 \times 66 + 6)$	:= $6 + (((6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)) + 6 \times 66) + 6)$
:= $7 + ((7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7) - 7/7) + 7)$	:= $(7/7 + 7) \times ((7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7)$	:= $7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((88/8 + 88) + 8)$	:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8)$	:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8888/88)$
:= $9 \times (((9 + 9 + 9) + 9) + 9)$	:= $(99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 999)/9$	:= $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - ((9 + 9)/9 + 99)$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{412} &:= 1 + 11 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} \\ &:= 2 \times (222 - 2^{2+2}) \\ &:= 3/3 + ((3 \times 3^3 - 3) + 333) \\ &:= 444 - 4 \times (4 + 4) \\ &:= 5 + (55/5 \times (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5)) \\ &:= 6 + (((66 - 6)/6) + 6 \times 66) \\ &:= 77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7)) \\ &:= (888 - 8 \times 8)/((8 + 8)/8) \\ &:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (9/9 + 99) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{415} &:= (1 + 1 + 11) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) - 1 \\ &:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 22/2 + 2 \\ &:= 3/3 + (3 \times 3^3 + 333) \\ &:= 4^4 + (4 \times (44 - 4) - 4/4) \\ &:= 5 + ((5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55) + 5) + 5) \\ &:= 6 + (((6 \times 66 + 6/6) + 6) + 6) \\ &:= 7 + ((7/7 + 7) \times ((7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7)) \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8/8 + 88) + 8) \\ &:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9) + 9/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{418} &:= 11 \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)) \\ &:= 22 \times (22 - 2/2 - 2) \\ &:= 33/3 \times (33/3 + 3^3) \\ &:= 4^4 + (4 \times (44 - 4) + (4 + 4)/4) \\ &:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) \\ &:= 6 \times 66 + ((66 + 66)/6) \\ &:= 7 + (7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7)^7) \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) - (88 + 8)) \\ &:= 9 + (((99/9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9}) + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{413} &:= 1 + 1 + 11 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1} \\ &:= 2 + (22 - 2)^2 + 22/2 \\ &:= 3 \times 3^3 + (333 - 3/3) \\ &:= 44 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4^4) \\ &:= 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\ &:= 6 + (6 \times 66 + (66/6)) \\ &:= 77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7) \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88/8 + 88) \\ &:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{416} &:= (1 + 1 + 11) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1) \\ &:= 2^{2+2} + (22 - 2)^2 \\ &:= 3 + ((333 - 3/3) + 3 \times 3^3) \\ &:= 4^4 + (4 \times (44 - 4)) \\ &:= (55/5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 + 5/5) \\ &:= 6 + (((((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 66) + 6) + 6) \\ &:= ((77 \times 77 - 7)/(7 + 7)) - 7 \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8) \\ &:= 9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99/9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{419} &:= 1 + 11 \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)) \\ &:= (22 - 2/2)^2 - 22 \\ &:= ((3^3 + 3) \times (33/3 + 3)) - 3/3 \\ &:= (44 \times 44 - (4^4 + 4))/4 \\ &:= 555 - (555/5 + 5 \times 5) \\ &:= 6 + ((6 \times 66 + (66/6)) + 6) \\ &:= 77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7) \\ &:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8888/88)) \\ &:= (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9 \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{414} &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}) \\ &:= 2 + 2 \times (222 - 2^{2+2}) \\ &:= 3 \times 3^3 + 333 \\ &:= 4 + ((4 + 4)^4 + 4)/((44 - 4)/4) \\ &:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (555 + 55) \\ &:= 6 + ((6 \times 66 + 6) + 6) \\ &:= 7/7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7) + 77) \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((8 - 88)/8 - 88) \\ &:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{417} &:= 11 \times (1 + 111/(1 + 1 + 1)) - 1 \\ &:= (22 - 2/2)^2 - 22 - 2 \\ &:= 3 + (3 \times 3^3 + 333) \\ &:= 4/4 + (4 \times (44 - 4) + 4^4) \\ &:= ((5^5 + 5^5) + 5)/(5 + 5 + 5) \\ &:= 6 \times 66 + ((6 \times 6 + 6)/((6 + 6)/6)) \\ &:= ((77 \times 77 + 7)/(7 + 7)) - 7 \\ &:= 8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8)) \\ &:= 9 + ((99 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 999)/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{420} &:= (1 + 1) \times (11 - 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1) \\ &:= 22 + (22 - 2)^2 - 2 \\ &:= (3^3 + 3) \times (33/3 + 3) \\ &:= 4 + (4 \times (44 - 4) + 4^4) \\ &:= (55 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \\ &:= 6 \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6) \\ &:= 77 + 7 \times 7 \times 7 \\ &:= 88 \times 88/(8 + 8) - 8 \times 8 \\ &:= ((9 + 9)/9) \times (999/9 + 99) \end{aligned}$$

<p>► 421 := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1} - 11$:= $2 + (((22 - 2/2)^2) - 22)$:= $((3 + 3)^{3/3+3} - 33)/3$:= $4^4 + ((4 \times 44) - 44/4)$:= $5 + ((55/5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 + 5/5))$:= $(6 \times (66 + 6)) - 66/6$:= $7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 77)$:= $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88/8 + 88))$:= $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (9/9 + 99)$</p>	<p>► 424 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times 111 - 11))$:= $2 + ((22 - 2)^2 + 22)$:= $3 \times 3^3 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3)$:= $444 - (4 \times 4 + 4)$:= $(5 - 5/5) \times (555/5 - 5)$:= $6 \times (66 - 6) + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$:= $(77 \times 77 + 7)/(7 + 7)$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88$:= $9/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99)$</p>	<p>► 427 := $1 + (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) - 11)$:= $2 + (((22 - 2/2)^2) - 2^{2+2})$:= $((3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3) + 3)/3$:= $444 - (4 \times 4 + 4/4)$:= $(5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5))$:= $6/6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6)$:= $7 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 77)$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88/8 - (88 + 8))$:= $((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9) - (9 + 9)$</p>
<p>► 422 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times 111 - 11$:= $22 + (22 - 2)^2$:= $3^3 + ((33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3)) - 3/3)$:= $444 - (44/((4 + 4)/4))$:= $5 + (((5^5 + 5^5) + 5)/(5 + 5 + 5))$:= $((6 - 66)/6) + (6 \times (66 + 6))$:= $77 + (7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7))$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8)/8 + 88)$:= $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 99$</p>	<p>► 425 := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times 111 - 11))$:= $((22 - 2/2)^2) - 2^{2+2}$:= $((3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3) - 3)/3$:= $4/4 + (444 - (4 \times 4 + 4))$:= $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5)$:= $(6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6/6 - 6$:= $7 + ((7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7)^7) + 7)$:= $8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88)$:= $99 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + ((9 + 9)/9))$</p>	<p>► 428 := $(11 \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11))) - 1$:= $2 \times (222 - 2 \times (2 + 2))$:= $((3 + 3)^{3/3+3} - 3)/3 - 3$:= $444 - 4 \times 4$:= $(5 - 5/5) \times ((555 + 5)/5 - 5)$:= $(6 + 6)/6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6)$:= $7 \times 77 - 777/7$:= $888/((8 + 8)/8) - 8 - 8$:= $((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9) - (9 + 9)$</p>
<p>► 423 := $1 + (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times 111 - 11)$:= $22 + ((22 - 2)^2 + 2/2)$:= $3 \times ((3 \times (33 + 3)) + 33)$:= $444 - ((4 \times 4 + 4/4) + 4)$:= $55 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 55)$:= $66 + (66 \times 66/(6 + 6) - 6)$:= $(77 \times 77 - 7)/(7 + 7)$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/8 + 88)$:= $99 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 426 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111) - 11$:= $(2 \times (222 + 2)) - 22$:= $(3 + 3) \times (((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3)$:= $444 - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4 \times 4)$:= $5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 55 + 5))$:= $(6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6$:= $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times 7 - 7/7) + 77)$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) - 88)$:= $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (999/9 - 9)$</p>	<p>► 429 := $11 \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11))$:= $(2 \times (222 - 2)) - 22/2$:= $33 + (33 \times (3 \times 3 + 3))$:= $4/4 + (444 - 4 \times 4)$:= $555 - (5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5/5)$:= $66 + 66 \times 66/(6 + 6)$:= $7 \times 77 + ((7 - 777)/7)$:= $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (88/8 + 8)$:= $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - (((9 + 9)/9) + 9 \times 9)$</p>

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{430} &:= ((11 + 11 - 1)^{1+1}) - 11 \\ &:= 2 + (2 \times (222 - 2 \times (2 + 2))) \\ &:= (3 - 3/3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3/3) \\ &:= 4^4 + ((4 \times 44) - (4 + 4)/4) \\ &:= 555 - 5 \times 5 \times 5 \\ &:= (6 \times (66 + 6)) - (6 + 6)/6 \\ &:= 7 + ((77 \times 77 - 7)/(7 + 7)) \\ &:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8)/8 + 88)) \\ &:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (9/9 + 9 \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{433} &:= 1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1}) \\ &:= 2 \times 222 - 22/2 \\ &:= (((3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) + 3)/3 \\ &:= 444 - 44/4 \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5) \\ &:= 6/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6)) \\ &:= 777 - (7 \times 7 \times 7 + 7/7) \\ &:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88) + 8/8) \\ &:= 9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99) + 9/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{436} &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) \\ &:= 2 \times (222 - (2 + 2)) \\ &:= 3 + (((3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) + 3)/3 \\ &:= 444 - 4 - 4 \\ &:= 5 + ((555 - 5 \times 5 \times 5) + 5/5) \\ &:= 6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - ((6 + 6)/6)) \\ &:= 7 + (((7 - 777)/7) + 7 \times 77) \\ &:= 888/((8 + 8)/8) - 8 \\ &:= (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{431} &:= ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1}) - 1 \\ &:= 2 \times 222 - (22/2 + 2) \\ &:= (((3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) - 3)/3 \\ &:= 4^4 + ((4 \times 44) - 4/4) \\ &:= 5/5 + (555 - 5 \times 5 \times 5) \\ &:= (6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6/6 \\ &:= 7 + ((77 \times 77 + 7)/(7 + 7)) \\ &:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/8 + 88)) \\ &:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9 \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{434} &:= 1 + (1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1})) \\ &:= (2 \times (222 - (2 + 2))) - 2 \\ &:= 3 + (((3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) - 3)/3 \\ &:= 444 + (4 - 44)/4 \\ &:= 5 + (555 - (5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5/5)) \\ &:= (6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6)) \\ &:= 777 - 7 \times 7 \times 7 \\ &:= (8 - 8/8) \times (8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8)/8)) \\ &:= 99 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99/9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{437} &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1)) \\ &:= ((22 - 2/2)^2) - 2 - 2 \\ &:= (((3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)) - 3)/3 \\ &:= 4 + (444 - 44/4) \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) \\ &:= 6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6/6) \\ &:= 7 + (((77 \times 77 - 7)/(7 + 7)) + 7) \\ &:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 88/8 \\ &:= (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{432} &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)^{1+1} \\ &:= 2 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^{2/2+2}) \\ &:= 3 \times ((3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3)) \\ &:= 4^4 + (4 \times 44) \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 55)/(5 + 5) \\ &:= 6 \times (66 + 6) \\ &:= ((7 + 7)/7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7) \\ &:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88) \\ &:= 9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{435} &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}) \\ &:= 2 + (2 \times 222 - 22/2) \\ &:= 3 + (3 \times 33 + 333) \\ &:= 444 - ((4/4 + 4) + 4) \\ &:= 5 + (555 - 5 \times 5 \times 5) \\ &:= (6 \times (66 + 6)) + (6 \times 6/(6 + 6)) \\ &:= 7 + (7 \times 77 - 777/7) \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88/8 - 88) \\ &:= (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 999/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{438} &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (111 - 1) - 1) \\ &:= (2 \times (222 - 2)) - 2 \\ &:= (3 + 3) \times (((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) \\ &:= 444 - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4) \\ &:= 5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) \\ &:= 6 + (6 \times (66 + 6)) \\ &:= 7 + (((77 \times 77 + 7)/(7 + 7)) + 7) \\ &:= (8 - 88)/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) \\ &:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (((9 + 9)/9) + 9 \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

► **439** := $((11 + 11 - 1)^{1+1}) - 1 - 1$
 := $((22 - 2/2)^2) - 2$
 := $((3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)) + 3 / 3$
 := $444 - (4/4 + 4)$
 := $555 - (555/5 + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) + 6/6)$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (8/8 + 8)$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (9/9 + 9 \times 9)$

► **442** := $1 + ((11 + 11 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times 222 - 2$
 := $3 \times 33 + (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3)$
 := $444 - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 5 \times 5 \times 5)$
 := $((66 - 6)/6) + (6 \times (66 + 6))$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8)$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times ((9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9)))$

► **445** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times 111)$
 := $2/2 + 2 \times 222$
 := $333 + ((333 + 3)/3)$
 := $4/4 + 444$
 := $555 - (55 + 55)$
 := $6 + (((6 \times (66 + 6)) + 6/6) + 6)$
 := $77/7 + (777 - 7 \times 7 \times 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (88/8))$
 := $((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **440** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (111 - 1)$
 := $2 \times (222 - 2)$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times ((333 - 3)/3)$
 := $444 - 4$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (55 - (55/5))$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) - 7/7$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9 \times 9$

► **443** := $((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times 111) - 1$
 := $2 + ((22 - 2/2)^2)$
 := $333 + ((333 - 3)/3)$
 := $444 - 4/4$
 := $555 - (555 + 5)/5$
 := $66/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6))$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $888/((8 + 8)/8) - 8/8$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99/9)) + 99)$

► **446** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times 111)$
 := $2 + 2 \times 222$
 := $((3 \times (33 \times 3^3)) + 3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $444 + (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + (((55/5 + 5) + 5)^{(5+5)/5})$
 := $6 + (((6 \times (66 + 6)) + ((6 + 6)/6)) + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **441** := $(11 + 11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $(22 - 2/2)^2$
 := $3 \times (((3 + 3) \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3)$
 := $4/4 + (444 - 4)$
 := $((55/5 + 5) + 5)^{(5+5)/5}$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) + (6 \times 6/(6 + 6)))$
 := $7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8)$
 := $9 \times ((9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **444** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times 111$
 := 2×222
 := $333 + 333/3$
 := 444
 := $(5 - 5/5) \times 555/5$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) + 6)$
 := $(77/7 - 7) \times 777/7$
 := $888/((8 + 8)/8)$
 := $(999 \times (9 - 9/9))/(9 + 9)$

► **447** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times 111))$
 := $2 + (2 \times 222 + 2/2)$
 := $3 + (333/3 + 333)$
 := $4 + (444 - 4/4)$
 := $((5^5 - 5/5) + 5)/((5 + 5)/5 + 5)$
 := $((6/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6) - 6/6$
 := $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) - 7/7)$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8/8$
 := $9/9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9))$

- **448** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)$
 := $2 \times (222 + 2)$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times ((333 + 3)/3)$
 := $4 + 444$
 := $(5 - 5/5) \times (555 + 5)/5$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times ((999 + 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **449** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111))$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times (222 + 2))$
 := $3 + (((3 \times (33 \times 3^3)) + 3)/(3 + 3))$
 := $4 + (444 + 4/4)$
 := $5 + ((5 - 5/5) \times 555/5)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) + (66/6))$
 := $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) + 7/7)$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)$
 := $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9 \times 9) + 9)$
- **450** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111))$
 := $2 + (2 \times (222 + 2))$
 := $(3 + 3) \times ((3 \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3)$
 := $4 + (444 + (4 + 4)/4)$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)$
 := $666 - 6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $(7 - 7/7) \times (77 - (7 + 7)/7)$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)$
 := $9 \times ((9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **451** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)))$
 := $2 + ((2 \times (222 + 2)) + 2/2)$
 := $3 + ((3/3 + 3) \times ((333 + 3)/3))$
 := $4 + ((444 - 4/4) + 4)$
 := $5/5 + ((5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5))$
 := $66 + (6 \times 66 - (66/6))$
 := $77/7 \times (7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7))$
 := $88/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8)$
 := $((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 99)/(9 + 9)$
- **452** := $11 + ((11 + 11 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times ((222 + 2) + 2)$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times (((333 - 3)/3) + 3)$
 := $4 + (444 + 4)$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + ((5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5))$
 := $66 + (((6 - 66)/6) + 6 \times 66)$
 := $77/7 + 7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 888/((8 + 8)/8)$
 := $9/9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 99)/(9 + 9))$
- **453** := $1 + (11 + ((11 + 11 - 1)^{1+1}))$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times ((222 + 2) + 2))$
 := $(3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) - 33$
 := $4 + ((444 + 4/4) + 4)$
 := $5 + ((5 - 5/5) \times (555 + 5)/5)$
 := $6 + (((6/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6) - 6/6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + (777 - 7)/7$
 := $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - (88/8)) + 8)$
 := $9 + ((999 \times (9 - 9/9))/(9 + 9))$
- **454** := $11 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times 111) - 1)$
 := $2 + (2 \times ((222 + 2) + 2))$
 := $3/3 + ((3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) - 33)$
 := $444 + (44 - 4)/4$
 := $5 + (((5 - 5/5) \times 555/5) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6/6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times 7 + 777/7$
 := $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **455** := $11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times 111)$
 := $22/2 + 2 \times 222$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 + (((3^{3+3} - 3)/3) - 3)$
 := $444 + 44/4$
 := $5 + ((5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5))$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times (66 - 6/6)$
 := $7 \times 77 - (77 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8/8)$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **456** := $1 + (11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times 111))$
 := $2 \times (((222 + 2) + 2) + 2)$
 := $3 + ((3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) - 33)$
 := $4 + (444 + 4 + 4)$
 := $5 + (((5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)) + 5/5)$
 := $66 + (6 \times 66 - 6)$
 := $(7 - 7/7) \times (77 - 7/7)$
 := $8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)$
 := $(9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 999/9$

<p>► 457 := $11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times 111))$:= $2 + (2 \times 222 + 22/2)$:= $(3 + 3)^3 + (((3^{3+3} + 3)/3) - 3)$:= $4 + (((444 + 4/4) + 4) + 4)$:= $((5 + 5)/5)^{5-5/5+5} - 55$:= $66 + ((6 \times 66 - 6) + 6/6)$:= $7 + ((7 - 7/7) \times (77 - (7 + 7)/7))$:= $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + 8/8)$:= $((9999 + 9)/(9 + 9)) - 99$</p>	<p>► 460 := $(1 + 1) \times ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11))$:= $22^2 - (22 + 2)$:= $(3 + 3)^3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3)/3)$:= $4 \times 4 + 444$:= $5 + (((5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)) + 5)$:= $6 \times 66 + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$:= $7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7 + 77)$:= $8 + (888/((8 + 8)/8) + 8)$:= $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - (((9 + 9)/9)^9)$</p>	<p>► 463 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (11 + 11 - 1)))$:= $22 + ((22 - 2/2)^2)$:= $3/3 + (33 \times (33/3 + 3))$:= $4 + ((444 + 44/4) + 4)$:= $5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$:= $66 + (6 \times 66 + 6/6)$:= $7/7 + (77 \times (7 - 7/7))$:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8/8) + 8)$:= $9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9$</p>
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<p>► 458 := $1 + (11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times 111)))$:= $22^2 - (22 + 2 + 2)$:= $(3 + 3)^3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3)/3)$:= $4 + ((44 - 4)/4 + 444)$:= $(5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 55 - 5)/(5 + 5 + 5)$:= $66 + (((6 + 6)/6 - 6) + 6 \times 66)$:= $7 + (77/7 \times (7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7)))$:= $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + ((8 + 8)/8))$:= $9 + ((((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9 \times 9) + 9) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 461 := $((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (11 + 11 - 1))) - 1$:= $22^2 - (22 + 2/2)$:= $(33 \times (33/3 + 3)) - 3/3$:= $4 \times 4 + (444 + 4/4)$:= $55/5 + ((5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5))$:= $66 + (6 \times 66 - 6/6)$:= $7 \times 77 - (7/7 + 77)$:= $8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$:= $9/9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - (((9 + 9)/9)^9))$</p>	<p>► 464 := $(1 + 1) \times (111 + 11^{1+1})$:= $2 + (22^2 - 22)$:= $3 + ((33 \times (33/3 + 3)) - 3/3)$:= $4 + (444 + 4 \times 4)$:= $(5 - 5/5) \times (555/5 + 5)$:= $66 + (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 66)$:= $7 \times 77 + ((7 + 7)/7 - 77)$:= $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + 8)$:= $9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9$</p>
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<p>► 459 := $11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111))$:= $22/2 + (2 \times (222 + 2))$:= $3 \times (3 \times ((3^3 - 3) + 3^3))$:= $4 + (444 + 44/4)$:= $(5^5 - 555)/5 - 55$:= $66 + (6 \times 66 - (6 \times 6/(6 + 6)))$:= $7 + (7 \times (7 \times 7 + 7 + 7) + (77/7))$:= $88/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8)$:= $(9 + 9 + 9) \times ((9 - 9/9) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 462 := $(1 + 1) \times (11 \times (11 + 11 - 1))$:= $22^2 - 22$:= $33 \times (33/3 + 3)$:= $4 \times 4 + (444 + (4 + 4)/4)$:= $55/5 \times (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5) + 5$:= $66 + 6 \times 66$:= $77 \times (7 - 7/7)$:= $(8 - 8/8) \times (((8 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 8)$:= $99 + ((99 \times 99)/(9 + 9 + 9))$</p>	<p>► 465 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (111 + 11^{1+1}))$:= $2 + ((22^2 - 22) + 2/2)$:= $3 + (33 \times (33/3 + 3))$:= $4 + ((444 + 4 \times 4) + 4/4)$:= $5 \times (5 \times 5 \times 5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5)$:= $66 + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6)) + 6 \times 66)$:= $77 + (((7 \times 777) - 7)/(7 + 7))$:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + 8/8) + 8)$:= $9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 999/9)$</p>
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<p>► 466 := $(1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111)$:= $22 + 2 \times 222$:= $3 + ((33 \times (33/3 + 3)) + 3/3)$:= $444 + (44/((4 + 4)/4))$:= $(5^5 + 5)/5 - (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)$:= $6 + (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6 \times 66)$:= $77 + (((7 \times 777) + 7)/(7 + 7))$:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)$:= $((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - (99/9 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 469 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111)))$:= $2/2 + (22^2 - 2^{2+2})$:= $3/3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3))$:= $4/4 + ((4^4 - 44) + 4^4)$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - 555$:= $6/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6 + 6))$:= $7 + (77 \times (7 - 7/7))$:= $(8 - 8/8) \times ((88/8 - 8) + 8 \times 8)$:= $9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - (((9 + 9)/9)^9))$</p>	<p>► 472 := $(11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 11$:= $22^2 - (2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))$:= $3 + (((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)) + 3/3)$:= $4 + ((4^4 - 44) + 4^4)$:= $55 + (((5^5 + 5^5) + 5)/(5 + 5 + 5))$:= $6 + (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6 \times 66) + 6$:= $7 \times (77 - 7) - (77/7 + 7)$:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + 8) + 8)$:= $9 + (((((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9) + 9)$</p>
<p>► 467 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111))$:= $22 + (2 \times 222 + 2/2)$:= $((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)) - 3/3$:= $4^4 + (4^4 - (44 + 4/4))$:= $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5))$:= $(6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) - 6/6$:= $7 + (7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7 + 77))$:= $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + (88/8))$:= $((9 + 9)/9^9) - (((9 + 9 + 9) + 9) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 470 := $(1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111))$:= $2 + (22^2 - 2^{2+2})$:= $3 + (((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)) - 3/3)$:= $4 + ((44/((4 + 4)/4)) + 444)$:= $(5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)) - 5$:= $(6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6 + 6))$:= $7 + ((77 \times (7 - 7/7)) + 7/7)$:= $8 + ((8 - 8/8) \times (((8 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 8))$:= $(9 + 9)/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (((9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9))$</p>	<p>► 473 := $(11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11$:= $22^2 - 22/2$:= $33/3 + (33 \times (33/3 + 3))$:= $44/4 \times (44 - 4/4)$:= $55/5 \times (55 - ((55 + 5)/5))$:= $6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) - 6/6)$:= $7 \times 77 + (77/7 - 77)$:= $8 + (((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + 8/8) + 8) + 8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9})$</p>
<p>► 468 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111))$:= $22^2 - 2^{2+2}$:= $(3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)$:= $4^4 + (4^4 - 44)$:= $(5 - 5/5) \times ((555 + 5)/5 + 5)$:= $6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)$:= $(7 - 7/7) \times (7/7 + 77)$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88/((8 + 8)/8))$:= $(9 + 9) \times (((9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 471 := $(11 + 11)^{1+1} - (1 + 1 + 11)$:= $22^2 - (22/2 + 2)$:= $3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3))$:= $4 \times 4 + (444 + 44/4)$:= $5/5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)) - 5)$:= $6 \times (66 - 6) + 666/6$:= $7 \times 7 \times 7 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$:= $8 + (((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) - 8/8) + 8) + 8)$:= $9 + (((99 \times 99)/(9 + 9 + 9)) + 99)$</p>	<p>► 474 := $1 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11)$:= $22^2 + ((2 - 22)/2)$:= $(3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3)) - 3$:= $((44 \times (44 - 4/4)) + 4)/4$:= $5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - 555)$:= $6 + (6 \times (66 + 6 + 6))$:= $(7 - 7/7) \times ((7 + 7)/7 + 77)$:= $(8 - (8 + 8)/8) \times (88 - (8/8 + 8))$:= $((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - (99 + 9)/9$</p>

<p>► 475 := $1 + (1 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11))$:= $2 + (22^2 - 22/2)$:= $(3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) - 33/3$:= $444 + (4 \times (4 + 4) - 4/4)$:= $5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)$:= $6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) + 6/6)$:= $7 + ((7 - 7/7) \times (7/7 + 77))$:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 - 8) + (88/8)) + 8)$:= $((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 99/9$</p>	<p>► 478 := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1) - 1)$:= $22^2 - (2 + 2 + 2)$:= $3/3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3))$:= $4^4 + (444/((4 + 4)/4))$:= $5 + (55/5 \times (55 - ((55 + 5)/5)))$:= $((66 - 6)/6) + (6 \times (66 + 6 + 6))$:= $7 + (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7 \times 7 \times 7)$:= $(88 \times 88 - (88 + 8))/(8 + 8)$:= $9/9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 9)$</p>	<p>► 481 := $(11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1$:= $22^2 - 2/2 - 2$:= $3 + ((3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3)) + 3/3)$:= $((44 \times 44 + 4)/4) - 4$:= $(5555 - 5^5)/5 - 5$:= $(6/6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6/6)$:= $7 \times (77 - 7) - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7)$:= $8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8/((8 + 8)/8))))$:= $9 \times 9 + ((99/9 + 9)^{(9+9)/9})$</p>
<p>► 476 := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1)))$:= $22^2 - 2 \times (2 + 2)$:= $(33/3 + 3) \times (3/3 + 33)$:= $444 + 4 \times (4 + 4)$:= $5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5))$:= $(6/6 + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66)$:= $7 \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7)$:= $88 \times 88/(8 + 8) - 8$:= $((9 + 9)/9^9) - ((9 + 9 + 9) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 479 := $((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1)) - 1$:= $22^2 - (2/2 + 2 + 2)$:= $((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 33$:= $((44 \times 44 - 4)/4) - 4$:= $5 + (((5 - 5/5)^5 - 555) + 5)$:= $66/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6 + 6))$:= $7 \times (77 - 7) - 77/7$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8/8 + 8 + 8 + 8) + 8)$:= $(9 + 9)/9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 9)$</p>	<p>► 482 := $(11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1$:= $22^2 - 2$:= $3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 33)$:= $(44 \times 44 - (4 + 4))/4$:= $((5555 - 5^5 + 5)/5) - 5$:= $6 + ((6/6 + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66))$:= $7 \times (77 - 7) - (7/7 + 7)$:= $8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((88 + 88)/8 + 8)$:= $((9 \times ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9)) + 9)/(9 + 9)$</p>
<p>► 477 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1))))$:= $2 + ((22^2 - 22/2) + 2)$:= $3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3)$:= $4 + (44/4 \times (44 - 4/4))$:= $(5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5))$:= $6 + (6 \times (66 - 6) + 666/6)$:= $7/7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7))$:= $(8/8 + 8) \times (8 \times 8 - 88/8)$:= $((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) - 9$</p>	<p>► 480 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1)$:= $22^2 - 2 - 2$:= $3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3))$:= $(4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 + 44)$:= $5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5))$:= $6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) + 6)$:= $(7/7 + 7) \times (77/7 + 7 \times 7)$:= $8 \times (8 \times 8 - (8/((8 + 8)/8)))$:= $(9/9 - 9 \times 9) \times (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - 9)$</p>	<p>► 483 := $(11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1$:= $22^2 - 2/2$:= $(3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) - 3$:= $(44 \times 44 - 4)/4$:= $5 \times 55 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5 + 5))$:= $(6/6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6/(6 + 6) + 66)$:= $7 \times (77 - 7) - 7$:= $88 \times 88/(8 + 8) - 8/8$:= $((9 + 9 + 9)/9) \times (9 \times (9 + 9) - 9/9)$</p>

► **484** := $(11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := 22^2
 := $3/3 + ((3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) - 3)$
 := $44 \times 44/4$
 := $55/5 \times (55 - (55/5))$
 := $((66 + 66)/6)^{(6+6)/6}$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - 7)$
 := $88 \times 88/(8 + 8)$
 := $((99 + 99)/9)^{(9+9)/9}$

► **487** := $1 + (1 + (1 + (11 + 11)^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + 22^2 + 2/2$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3)$
 := $4 + ((44 \times 44 - 4)/4)$
 := $(5555 - 5^5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + ((6/6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6/6))$
 := $7 \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/8 + 8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))$

► **490** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1})))$
 := $2 + 22^2 + 2 + 2$
 := $3 + ((3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) + 3/3)$
 := $4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4) + 4)/4)$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (55 - (5/5 + 5))$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times (77 - 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 88)/8$
 := $((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9) - 9$

► **485** := $1 + (11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2/2 + 22^2$
 := $((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3^3$
 := $(44 \times 44 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + ((5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)) + (66/6))$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (77 - 7) - 7)$
 := $8/8 + 88 \times 88/(8 + 8)$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - (9 + 9 + 9)$

► **488** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + 22^2 + 2$
 := $3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3^3)$
 := $44 + 444$
 := $(5 - 5/5) \times ((555 + 55)/5)$
 := $((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times ((66 - 6) + 6/6)$
 := $7 \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8 - 8 - 8$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))$

► **491** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}))))$
 := $2 + 22^2 + 2/2 + 2 + 2$
 := $3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3^3) + 3$
 := $4 + (((44 \times 44 - 4)/4) + 4)$
 := $5 + (5555 - 5^5)/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + ((6/6 + 6) \times (66 - 6/6))$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (77 - 7)$
 := $8 + (88 \times 88/(8 + 8) - 8/8)$
 := $((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9) - 9$

► **486** := $1 + (1 + (11 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + 22^2$
 := $3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3$
 := $((44 \times 44 + 4) + 4)/4$
 := $(5555 - 5^5)/5$
 := $666 + (6 \times (6 - 6 \times 6))$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - (77/7))$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((8 - 88)/8 - (8 + 8))$
 := $(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)$

► **489** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1})))$
 := $2 + 22^2 + 2/2 + 2$
 := $3 + (3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3)$
 := $4 + ((44 \times 44 + 4)/4)$
 := $555 - (55/5 + 55)$
 := $666 - (666/6 + 66)$
 := $7 \times (77 - 7) - 7/7$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8 + 8))$
 := $((9 + 9 + 9)/9) + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))$

► **492** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11^{1+1})))$
 := $2 \times (2 + 2) + 22^2$
 := $3 + ((3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) + 3)$
 := $4 + (444 + 44)$
 := $5 + ((5555 - 5^5 + 5)/5)$
 := $66 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6)$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times (77 - 7)$
 := $8 + 88 \times 88/(8 + 8)$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - (99/9 + 9)$

► **493** := $11 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1} - (1 + 1))$
 := $22/2 + (22^2 - 2)$
 := $3 + (((3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) + 3/3) + 3)$
 := $4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4)/4) + 4)$
 := $555 + ((5 - 5^5/5)/(5 + 5))$
 := $((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - 66/6$
 := $7 \times (77 - 7) + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88/8 + 8)$
 := $((9 + 9)/9^9) - (9/9 + 9 + 9)$

► **496** := $1 + (11 + (11 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $22^2 + (2 \times (2 + 2 + 2))$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3))$
 := $4 \times (4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4) - 4)$
 := $5/5 + (55 \times (5 - 5/5 + 5))$
 := $((6 + 6)/6)^6 + (6 \times (66 + 6))$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - 7/7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8 - 8$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) + 9/9)$

► **499** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1}/(1 + 1) - 1$
 := $2 + 22/2 + 22^2 + 2$
 := $((3 \times (3 \times 333)) - 3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $4 + 44/4 \times (44 + 4/4)$
 := $555 - (55 + 5/5)$
 := $66 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) + 6/6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
 := $((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **494** := $11 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1)$
 := $2 + 2 \times (2 + 2) + 22^2$
 := $((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - (3 \times (3 + 3))$
 := $((44 \times 44 - 4) + 44)/4$
 := $555 - ((55 + 5/5) + 5)$
 := $((6 - 66)/6) + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6))$
 := $77/7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((8 - 88)/8 - 8)$
 := $((9 + 9)/9^9) - (9 + 9)$

► **497** := $1 + (1 + (11 + (11 + 11)^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + (22/2 + 22^2)$
 := $33/3 + (3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3)$
 := $4/4 + ((4^4 - 4 \times 4) + 4^4)$
 := $555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - (55 + 5))$
 := $66 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6/6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (77 - 7)$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8))$
 := $99/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))$

► **500** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1}/(1 + 1)$
 := $2^{2+2} + 22^2$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times ((3 - 3/3 + 3)^3)$
 := $4 + ((4^4 - 4 \times 4) + 4^4)$
 := $5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $66 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 \times (77 - 7) + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (88 + 8)/8$
 := $((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **495** := $11 + (11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $22/2 + 22^2$
 := $3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3)$
 := $44/4 \times (44 + 4/4)$
 := $55 \times (5 - 5/5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 66 + (666/6 - (6 + 6))$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))$

► **498** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1}/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1$
 := $2^{2+2} + (22^2 - 2)$
 := $3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 + 3))$
 := $4^4 + (44 \times 44/(4 + 4))$
 := $555 - ((5 + 5)/5 + 55)$
 := $66 + (6 \times (66 + 6))$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + 7/7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) - (8 + 8))$
 := $((99 + 9)/9) + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))$

► **501** := $(1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 11$
 := $2/2 + 2^{2+2} + 22^2$
 := $((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3)) - 3$
 := $4^4 + (4^4 - 44/4)$
 := $5/5 + (5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5))$
 := $6 \times 66 + (666/6 - 6)$
 := $77/7 + 7 \times (77 - 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8$
 := $((9 + 9)/9^9) - 99/9$

► **502** := $1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 11$
 := $2 + 2^{2+2} + 22^2$
 := $3 + ((3 \times 3 \times 333 - 3)/(3 + 3))$
 := $4^4 + ((4 - 44)/4 + 4^4)$
 := $555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - 55)$
 := $((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7 \times (77 - 7) + (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 - 88)/8$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - 9/9 - 9$

► **505** := $(11111 - 1)/(11 + 11)$
 := $22 + 22^2 - 2/2$
 := $3/3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3))$
 := $((4 + 4) \times (4^4 - 4) + 4)/4$
 := $5 + (5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5))$
 := $6/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6))$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (77 - 7) + 7/7) + 7)$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8)$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9 - 9)$

► **508** := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + 22^2 + 22$
 := $((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - (3/3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 + (4^4 - 4)$
 := $((5^5 - (555 + 5))/5) - 5$
 := $6 \times 66 + (666 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + (77/7))$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **503** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 11$
 := $22 + 22^2 - (2/2 + 2)$
 := $((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3 \times 3$
 := $((4 + 4) \times (4^4 - 4) - 4)/4$
 := $(5^5 - (555 + 55))/5$
 := $((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - 6/6$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (77 - 7) - 7/7) + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8/8 + 8)$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - 9$

► **506** := $(1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 11 + 11)$
 := $22 + 22^2$
 := $((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - (3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 + (4^4 - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4))$
 := $5 + ((5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) + 5/5)$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6))$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (77 - 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)) + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + (((8 + 8)/8) - 8)$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) + (99/9))$

► **509** := $(1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 1 - 1 - 1$
 := $2 + 22^2 + 2/2 + 22$
 := $((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3$
 := $4/4 + ((4^4 - 4) + 4^4)$
 := $(5^5 - 555)/5 - 5$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - 6/6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + (77 + 7)/7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8)$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **504** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 11) \times (11 + 11 - 1))$
 := $22 + 22^2 - 2$
 := $(3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 + (4^4 - 4 - 4)$
 := $5 + (555 - (55 + 5/5))$
 := $(6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) + 9)$

► **507** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $22 + 22^2 + 2/2$
 := $3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3))$
 := $4^4 + (4^4 - (4/4 + 4))$
 := $((5 + 5)/5)^{5-5/5+5} - 5$
 := $6 \times 66 + 666/6$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + ((77 - 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88/8 - (8 + 8))$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))$

► **510** := $(1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 1 - 1$
 := $2^{(2/2+2)^2} - 2$
 := $3^{3+3} - ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 + (4^4 - (4 + 4)/4)$
 := $5 + ((5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6))$
 := $(7 - 7/7) \times (7/7 + 77 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 - (9 + 9)/9$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{511} &:= (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 1 \\ &:= 2^{(2/2+2)^2} - 2/2 \\ &:= ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3/3 \\ &:= 4^4 + (4^4 - 4/4) \\ &:= 555 + (55/5 - 55) \\ &:= 6 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) + 6/6) \\ &:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - 77 \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8 \\ &:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{514} &:= 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\ &:= 2 + 2^{(2/2+2)^2} \\ &:= 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3/3) \\ &:= 4^4 + ((4 + 4)/4 + 4^4) \\ &:= (5^5 - 555)/5 \\ &:= 6 + ((666 + 6)/6 + 6 \times 66) \\ &:= 7 \times 77 - (77/7 + 7 + 7) \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8 \\ &:= (9 + 9)/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{517} &:= 11 \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11 + 11)) \\ &:= 22 + (22/2 + 22^2) \\ &:= 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3/3 + 3) \\ &:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4^4) + 4^4) \\ &:= 5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^{5-5/5+5} \\ &:= (66/6) \times (66/6 + 6 \times 6) \\ &:= 77/7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7 + 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8) + 8) \\ &:= 9 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{512} &:= (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\ &:= 2^{(2/2+2)^2} \\ &:= (3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3} \\ &:= 4^4 + 4^4 \\ &:= ((5 + 5)/5)^{5-5/5+5} \\ &:= ((6 + 6)/6)^{6 \times 6/(6+6)+6} \\ &:= (7/7 + 7)^{(7+7+7)/7} \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 \\ &:= ((9 + 9)/9)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{515} &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\ &:= 2 + ((2^{(2/2+2)^2}) + 2/2) \\ &:= 3 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) \\ &:= 4 + ((4^4 - 4/4) + 4^4) \\ &:= 5^5/5 - (55 + 55) \\ &:= 66/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) \\ &:= 7 + ((7 \times (77 - 7) + (77/7)) + 7) \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88/8 - 8) \\ &:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{518} &:= (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11 \\ &:= 2 + (2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)) \\ &:= 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 3) \\ &:= 4 + (((4 + 4)/4 + 4^4) + 4^4) \\ &:= 5 + ((5^5 - (555 + 5))/5) \\ &:= 6 + (((6 + 6)/6)^{6 \times 6/(6+6)+6}) \\ &:= 7 \times 77 - (7 + 7 + 7) \\ &:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8)/8)) \\ &:= 9 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{513} &:= 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\ &:= 2/2 + 2^{(2/2+2)^2} \\ &:= 3^{3+3} - (3 + 3)^3 \\ &:= 4/4 + (4^4 + 4^4) \\ &:= (5^5 - (555 + 5))/5 \\ &:= 6 + (666/6 + 6 \times 66) \\ &:= 7/7 + ((7/7 + 7)^{(7+7+7)/7}) \\ &:= 8/8 + 8 \times 8 \times 8 \\ &:= 9/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{516} &:= 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} \\ &:= 2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2) \\ &:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - (3 + 3)^3) \\ &:= 4 + (4^4 + 4^4) \\ &:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - (55 + 55) \\ &:= 6 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) + 6) \\ &:= (7 - 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7 + 77) + 7) \\ &:= 8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8/((8 + 8)/8)) \\ &:= (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + ((9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{519} &:= 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11 \\ &:= 2 + ((2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)) + 2/2) \\ &:= 33 + (3 \times (3 + 3) \times 3^3) \\ &:= (((4 + 4) \times (4^4 + 4)) - 4)/4 \\ &:= 5 + (5^5 - 555)/5 \\ &:= 6 + ((666/6 + 6 \times 66) + 6) \\ &:= 7 + ((7/7 + 7)^{(7+7+7)/7}) \\ &:= 8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) \\ &:= 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - ((9 + 9)/9) \end{aligned}$$

► **520** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 11$
 := $2 \times ((2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2) + 2)$
 := $3 \times 3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((4^4 + 4^4) + 4)$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/(5/5 + 5)$
 := $((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (66 - 6/6)$
 := $7 \times 77 - ((77 + 7)/7 + 7)$
 := $8 + 8 \times 8 \times 8$
 := $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9)$

► **523** := $11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1}$
 := $22/2 + (2^{(2/2+2)^2})$
 := $33/3 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3})$
 := $4^4 + (44/4 + 4^4)$
 := $555 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 + (((66/6) \times (66/6 + 6 \times 6))$
 := $7 \times 77 - (((7 + 7)/7 + 7) + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8$
 := $99/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)$

► **526** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times 11 \times (1 + 11) - 1)$
 := $(22 \times (22 + 2)) - 2$
 := $3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 33/3)$
 := $(44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)) - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5/5)/(5/5 + 5))$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (66 - 6/6))$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times 77 - (7 + 7))$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **521** := $11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - (1 + 1)$
 := $(22/2)^2 + (22 - 2)^2$
 := $3 \times 3 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3})$
 := $((4 + 4) \times (4^4 + 4)) + 4/4$
 := $(5^5 + 5/5)/(5/5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) + (66/6))$
 := $7 \times 77 - (77/7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8)$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)$

► **524** := $1 + 11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1}$
 := $2 \times (22^2 - 222)$
 := $3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 3 \times 3)$
 := $(44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)) - 4$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 555)/5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 66 + (((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6})$
 := $7 \times 77 - (7/7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88 + 8)/8$
 := $(((9 + 9)/9)^9) + (99 + 9)/9$

► **527** := $(1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1 - 1$
 := $((22 + 2/2)^2) - 2$
 := $3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 3 \times 3) + 3)$
 := $(44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)) - 4/4$
 := $555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - (5 \times 5 + 5))$
 := $(66 \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6)) - 6/6$
 := $7 \times 77 - (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **522** := $11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1} - 1$
 := $2 + ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 22^2)$
 := $(3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 + ((44 - 4)/4 + 4^4)$
 := $5 + ((5 + 5)/5)^{5-5/5+5} + 5$
 := $666 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times 77 + (((7 - 77)/7) - 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8)$
 := $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9/9)$

► **525** := $1 + 1 + 11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1}$
 := $((22 + 2/2)^2) - 2 - 2$
 := $3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3 + 3))$
 := $444 + (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5)$
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 - 6)$
 := $7 \times 77 - (7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
 := $(((9 + 9)/9)^9) + ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)$

► **528** := $(1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1$
 := $22 \times (22 + 2)$
 := $33 \times (3^3 - 33/3)$
 := $44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)$
 := $5 + (555 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5)$
 := $66 \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times 77 - 77/7$
 := $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8)$
 := $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - ((9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$

► **529** := $(1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $(22 + 2/2)^2$
 := $(3^3 - 3/3 - 3)^{3-3/3}$
 := $4/4 + (44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4))$
 := $555 - (5 \times 5 + 5/5)$
 := $6/6 + (66 \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6))$
 := $7 \times 77 + (7 - 77)/7$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8) + 8)$
 := $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9) + 9)$

► **532** := $1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (((22 \times (22 + 2)) + 2)$
 := $3 + (((3^3 - 3/3 - 3)^{3-3/3})$
 := $4 + (44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4))$
 := $555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 5)$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times (((((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6) + 6)$
 := $7 \times 77 - 7$
 := $8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 8 \times 8)$
 := $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + (99/9))$

► **535** := $1 + 11 + 11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1}$
 := $2 + (((((22 + 2/2)^2) + 2) + 2)$
 := $(3333 - (3 \times 3 + 3)^3)/3$
 := $(4/4 + 4) \times (444/4 - 4)$
 := $5 + (555 - 5 \times 5)$
 := $6 + ((66 \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6)) + 6/6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 77 - (77/7))$
 := $8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) + 8) + 8)$
 := $((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9) - 9$

► **530** := $1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (22 \times (22 + 2))$
 := $(3 \times (3 + 3)) + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3})$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + (44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4))$
 := $555 - 5 \times 5$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + (66 \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6))$
 := $7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7)$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8) + 8)$
 := $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9)$

► **533** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) + 2)$
 := $3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + (3 \times (3 + 3)))$
 := $4 + ((44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)) + 4/4)$
 := $555 - (55 + 55)/5$
 := $6 + ((66 \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6)) - 6/6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times 77 - 7)$
 := $8 + ((88 + 8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 8 \times 8)$
 := $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + ((99 + 9)/9))$

► **536** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11))$
 := $2 + ((2^{(2/2+2)^2}) + 22)$
 := $3^3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3)$
 := $4 + ((44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)) + 4)$
 := $5 + ((555 - 5 \times 5) + 5/5)$
 := $((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (66 + 6/6)$
 := $7 \times 77 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9) - 9$

► **531** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + ((22 + 2/2)^2)$
 := $3 \times ((3 \times (3^3 + 33)) - 3)$
 := $4 + ((44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)) - 4/4)$
 := $5/5 + (555 - 5 \times 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 - 6))$
 := $7 \times 77 - (7/7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 99)$

► **534** := $11 + 11 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1}$
 := $22 + (2^{(2/2+2)^2})$
 := $3 + (33 \times (3 + 3) + 333)$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 \times (44/4 + 4^4)$
 := $5 + (555 - (5 \times 5 + 5/5))$
 := $6 + (66 \times ((6 + 6)/6 + 6))$
 := $7 \times 77 + ((7 + 7)/7 - 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + (88 + 88)/8$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^9 + ((99 + 99)/9)$

► **537** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 11))$
 := $2 \times (2 + 2) + ((22 + 2/2)^2)$
 := $(3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 33))) - 3$
 := $(4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 44)$
 := $5 + (((5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 5) + 555)$
 := $666/6 + ((6 \times (66 + 6)) - 6)$
 := $7 \times 77 - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8) + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 999/9$

► **538** := $11 + ((1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - (1 + 1))$
 := $22 + (2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2))$
 := $3^3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) - 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((4 + 4)/4 \times (44/4 + 4^4))$
 := $555 - (((55 + 5)/5) + 5)$
 := $666 - (((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6})$
 := $7 \times 77 - 7/7$
 := $8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8) + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 + ((((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9) + 9) + 9)$

► **541** := $1 + (11 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + ((22 \times (22 + 2)) + 22/2)$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 33)))$
 := $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 44))$
 := $5/5 + ((5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5))$
 := $6/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6))$
 := $7 \times 77 + (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times (88 - 8) - (88/8 + 88)$
 := $9 + ((((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + (99/9)) + 9)$

► **544** := $(1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 11$
 := $2 \times (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2^{2+2})$
 := $((((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) - 33)$
 := $(4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4)$
 := $555 - 55/5$
 := $666 - ((666 + 66)/6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8 + 8) + 8)$
 := $((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **539** := $11 + ((1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1} - 1)$
 := $22/2 + (22 \times (22 + 2))$
 := $3^3 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3})$
 := $44/4 + (44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4))$
 := $555 - (55/5 + 5)$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times (66/6 + 66)$
 := 7×77
 := $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8) + 8)$
 := $9 + ((((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9) + 9)$

► **542** := $1 + (1 + (11 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) + 22/2)$
 := $3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 3^3)$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 \times ((44/4 + 4^4) + 4)$
 := $555 - (55 + 5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (66 + 6/6))$
 := $7 \times 77 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + ((88 + 88)/8 + 8 \times 8 \times 8)$
 := $((9999 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9$

► **545** := $(1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) - 11$
 := $2^{2+2} + ((22 + 2/2)^2)$
 := $33 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3})$
 := $4/4 + ((4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4))$
 := $555 - 5 - 5$
 := $6 + ((6/6 + 6) \times (66/6 + 66))$
 := $7 + (7 \times 77 - 7/7)$
 := $8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 8/8) + 8) + 8) + 8)$
 := $((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **540** := $11 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times ((2 \times (22 + 2)) + 222)$
 := $3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 33))$
 := $(4 - 4/4) \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5)$
 := $(6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6)$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times 77$
 := $8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 8 \times 8) + 8)$
 := $(9 + 9 + 9) \times (99/9 + 9)$

► **543** := $(1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 11$
 := $2^{2+2} + (((22 + 2/2)^2) - 2)$
 := $3 + (3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 33)))$
 := $((4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4)) - 4/4$
 := $555 - (55 + 5)/5$
 := $666/6 + (6 \times (66 + 6))$
 := $7 \times 77 + (77/7 - 7)$
 := $8 + (((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) + 8) + 8) + 8)$
 := $((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9/9$

► **546** := $1 + ((1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) - 11)$
 := $222 + ((2^{2+2} + 2)^2)$
 := $(3 + 3)^3 + (333 - 3)$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + ((4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4))$
 := $5/5 + (555 - 5 - 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6))$
 := $7 + 7 \times 77$
 := $(8 - 8/8) \times ((8 - 88)/8 + 88)$
 := $((9999 - 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9$

► **547** := $1 + (1 + ((1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) - 11))$
 := $2 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) + 2^{2+2})$
 := $3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) - 33$
 := $((44 \times 44 - 4) + 4^4)/4$
 := $555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - 5 - 5)$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) + 6/6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 77 + 7/7)$
 := $(8888 - 8)/(8 + 8) - 8$
 := $((9999 + 9)/(9 + 9)) - 9$

► **550** := $(1111 - 11)/(1 + 1)$
 := $22 + (22 \times (22 + 2))$
 := $3/3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 333)$
 := $(4/4 + 4) \times (444 - 4)/4$
 := $(5 + 5) \times 55$
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times ((666 - 6)/6)$
 := $7 \times 77 + 77/7$
 := $(8888 - 88)/(8 + 8)$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 99)$

► **553** := $(1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1$
 := $2 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) + 22)$
 := $((3333 + 3)/(3 + 3)) - 3$
 := $4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4^4) + 4)/4)$
 := $555 - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times (66 + 6/6 + 6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 77 + 7)$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - 88)$
 := $9 + (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **548** := $(1111 - 11)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1$
 := $22^2 + 2^{2+2+2}$
 := $3 + (((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3}) + 33)$
 := $4 + ((4 + 4) \times (4 \times 4 \times 4 + 4))$
 := $555 - ((5 + 5)/5 + 5)$
 := $666 - ((666 + 6)/6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 77 + ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times 8 + 88 \times 88/(8 + 8)$
 := $9 + ((((((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9) + 9) + 9)$

► **551** := $1 + (1111 - 11)/(1 + 1)$
 := $22 + ((22 + 2/2)^2)$
 := $(3333 - 3^3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $444 + (444/4 - 4)$
 := $5/5 + (5 + 5) \times 55$
 := $66/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6))$
 := $7 \times 77 + (77 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times (88 - 8) - (8/8 + 88)$
 := $(9999 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **554** := $(1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1$
 := $((22 + 2)^2) - 22$
 := $(3333 - 3 \times 3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $444 + (444 - 4)/4$
 := $555 - 5/5$
 := $666 - (666 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 77 + 7/7) + 7)$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - 88)$
 := $9 + (((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **549** := $(1111 - 11)/(1 + 1) - 1$
 := $22 + (((22 + 2/2)^2) - 2)$
 := $3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 33)$
 := $((44 \times 44 + 4^4) + 4)/4$
 := $555 - (5/5 + 5)$
 := $666 - (666/6 + 6)$
 := $7 \times 77 + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + 888/(8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 99$

► **552** := $1 + (1 + (1111 - 11)/(1 + 1))$
 := $(22 + 2) \times (22 + 2/2)$
 := $3 + ((3 + 3)^3 + 333)$
 := $44 + ((4^4 - 4) + 4^4)$
 := $555 + ((5 + 5)/5 - 5)$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) + 6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 77 - 7/7) + 7)$
 := $8 \times (88 - 8) - 88$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times (9 \times 9 - ((99 + 9)/9))$

► **555** := $(1111 - 1)/(1 + 1)$
 := $(2222 - 2)/(2 + 2)$
 := $(3333 - 3)/(3 + 3)$
 := $444 + 444/4$
 := 555
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times 666/6$
 := $(7777 - 7)/(7 + 7)$
 := $(8888 - 8)/(8 + 8)$
 := $(9999 - 9)/(9 + 9)$

► **556** := (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1)
 := 2 + (((22 + 2)²) - 22)
 := (3333 + 3)/(3 + 3)
 := 44 + (4⁴ + 4⁴)
 := 5/5 + 555
 := (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6)
 := (7777 + 7)/(7 + 7)
 := (8888 + 8)/(8 + 8)
 := (9999 + 9)/(9 + 9)

► **559** := 1 + (1 + (1 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1)))
 := 2 + (((2222 - 2)/(2 + 2)) + 2)
 := 3 + ((3333 + 3)/(3 + 3))
 := 4 + (444/4 + 444)
 := 5 + (555 - 5/5)
 := 6/6 + (666 - 6 × (6 + 6 + 6))
 := 7 + (((7 × 77 - 7/7) + 7) + 7)
 := 888/8 + 8 × (8 × 8 - 8)
 := 9/9 + ((9 × (9 × 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9)

► **562** := 1 + ((11 + 1111)/(1 + 1))
 := 2 + (((22 + 2)²) - 2²⁺²)
 := ((3 × 3 + 3 + 3)³ - 3)/(3 + 3)
 := ((4 - 4⁴)/4) + (4/4 + 4)⁴
 := 5 + (555 + (5 + 5)/5)
 := 6 + (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6)
 := 7 + ((7777 - 7)/(7 + 7))
 := (8 + 8)/8 + ((8 - 8/8) × (88 - 8))
 := 9 + (((99 × 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9

► **557** := 1 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1)
 := 2 + ((2222 - 2)/(2 + 2))
 := (3333 + 3 × 3)/(3 + 3)
 := 44 + ((4/4 + 4⁴) + 4⁴)
 := 555 + (5 + 5)/5
 := 6/6 + (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6)
 := 7 + (7 × 77 + (77/7))
 := 8 × (8 × 8 + 8) - (88/8 + 8)
 := (9 × (9 × 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9/9 - 9

► **560** := (11 - 1) × (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)
 := ((22 + 2)²) - 2²⁺²
 := (3333 + 3³)/(3 + 3)
 := 4 + ((44 + 4⁴) + 4⁴)
 := 5 + 555
 := (6 - 6/6) × (666 + 6)/6
 := 7 + ((7 × 77 + 7) + 7)
 := (8 - 8/8) × (88 - 8)
 := (9 - 9/9) × (9 × 9 - 99/9)

► **563** := 1 + (1 + ((11 + 1111)/(1 + 1)))
 := ((22 + 2)²) - (22/2 + 2)
 := ((3 × 3 + 3 + 3)³ + 3)/(3 + 3)
 := 4 + ((444/4 + 444) + 4)
 := 5 + ((555 - (5 + 5)/5) + 5)
 := 666 - ((6 × 6 + 66) + 6/6)
 := 7 + ((7777 + 7)/(7 + 7))
 := 8 + (8888 - 8)/(8 + 8)
 := 9 + (((99 × 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9

► **558** := 1 + (1 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1))
 := 2 + (((22 + 2)²) - 22) + 2
 := 3 × (((3 + 3)³ - 33) + 3)
 := 4 + ((444 - 4)/4 + 444)
 := 5 + (555 - (5 + 5)/5)
 := 666 - 6 × (6 + 6 + 6)
 := 7 + ((77 + 7)/7 + 7 × 77)
 := (8/8 + 8) × (8 × 8 - ((8 + 8)/8))
 := (9 × (9 × 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9

► **561** := (11 + 1111)/(1 + 1)
 := (2222 + 22)/(2 + 2)
 := 33 × ((33/3 + 3) + 3)
 := (4/4 + 4)⁴ - 4 × 4 × 4
 := 5 + (555 + 5/5)
 := 6 + ((6 - 6/6) × 666/6)
 := 7 + (((7 × 77 + 7/7) + 7) + 7)
 := 8/8 + ((8 - 8/8) × (88 - 8))
 := (9999 + 99)/(9 + 9)

► **564** := ((1 + 1) × (1 + 11))¹⁺¹ - 1 - 11
 := 22² + (2 × 2 × (22 - 2))
 := (3 × ((3 + 3)³ - 3³)) - 3
 := (4 × (4⁴ - 4)) - 444
 := 5 + (555 - 5/5 + 5)
 := (6 + 6) × (66/6 + 6 × 6)
 := 7 + ((7 × 77 + (77/7)) + 7)
 := 8 + ((8888 + 8)/(8 + 8))
 := 9 + ((9999 - 9)/(9 + 9))

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{565} &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 11 \\ &:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 22/2 \\ &:= ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 33)/3 \\ &:= 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4 \times 4) \\ &:= 5 + 555 + 5 \\ &:= 6/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (66/6 + 6 \times 6)) \\ &:= 7 + (((77 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 77) + 7) \\ &:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 88/8 \\ &:= 9 + ((9999 + 9)/(9 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{568} &:= 1 + (11 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1)) \\ &:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 2 \times (2 + 2) \\ &:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 33)/3) \\ &:= 4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4)) - 444) \\ &:= (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 55 \\ &:= 6 + ((6666 + 6)/(6 + 6) + 6) \\ &:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77 - 7) + 77) \\ &:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8 \\ &:= 9/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{571} &:= 1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111)/(1 + 1)) \\ &:= ((22 + 2)^2) - (2/2 + 2 + 2) \\ &:= (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) - (3 + 3) \\ &:= ((44 \times (44 + 4 + 4)) - 4)/4 \\ &:= (5^5 + 5)/5 - 55 \\ &:= 66 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) + 6/6) \\ &:= 7 + (((7 \times 77 + (77/7)) + 7) + 7) \\ &:= 8 + ((8888 - 8)/(8 + 8) + 8) \\ &:= 9 + (((((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9) + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{566} &:= 11 + (1111 - 1)/(1 + 1) \\ &:= ((2 - 22)/2) + ((22 + 2)^2) \\ &:= (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3^3)) - 3/3 \\ &:= 4 + (((4 - 4^4)/4) + (4/4 + 4)^4) \\ &:= 555 + 55/5 \\ &:= 6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (666 + 6)/6) \\ &:= 77 + (7 \times (77 - 7) - 7/7) \\ &:= (8 - 88)/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\ &:= (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{569} &:= 1 + (1 + (11 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1))) \\ &:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 22/2) + 2 \\ &:= (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) - (3 + 3) \\ &:= 4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4 \times 4) + 4) \\ &:= (5^5 - 5)/5 - 55 \\ &:= 66 + (((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) - 6/6) \\ &:= 7 + (((7777 - 7)/(7 + 7)) + 7) \\ &:= 8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8) \\ &:= (9 + 9)/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{572} &:= 11 + ((11 + 1111)/(1 + 1)) \\ &:= 22 \times (22 + 2 + 2) \\ &:= (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) - 3 \\ &:= 44 + (44 \times ((4 + 4) + 4)) \\ &:= (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 55 \\ &:= (66/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 - (6 + 6)) \\ &:= 7777/7 - 7 \times 77 \\ &:= 88 + 88 \times 88/(8 + 8) \\ &:= 9 + (((((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9) + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{567} &:= 11 + (1 + 1111)/(1 + 1) \\ &:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 22/2) \\ &:= 3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3^3) \\ &:= ((4/4 + 4) + 4) \times ((4^4 - 4)/4) \\ &:= 555 + (55 + 5)/5 \\ &:= 6 + (((6 - 6/6) \times 666/6) + 6) \\ &:= 77 + 7 \times (77 - 7) \\ &:= (8/8 + 8) \times (8 \times 8 - 8/8) \\ &:= 9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{570} &:= (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 111)/(1 + 1) \\ &:= ((22 + 2)^2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \\ &:= 3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3^3)) \\ &:= 444 + ((4^4 - 4)/((4 + 4)/4)) \\ &:= 5^5/5 - 55 \\ &:= 66 + ((6 + 6) \times (6 \times 6 + 6)) \\ &:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (77/7 + 7) \\ &:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8) \\ &:= 9 + ((9999 + 99)/(9 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{573} &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1 \\ &:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 2/2 - 2 \\ &:= ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3/3) - 3 \\ &:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 4 + 4) \\ &:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 55) \\ &:= 66 + (666/6 + 6 \times 66) \\ &:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (7/7 + 7 + 7) \\ &:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 88/8) \\ &:= 9 + (((9999 - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{574} &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1 - 1 \\
 &:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 2 \\
 &:= (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) - 3 \\
 &:= 4^4 + (((4^4 - 4 - 4)/4) + 4^4) \\
 &:= 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 55) \\
 &:= (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) - (6 + 6)/6 \\
 &:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \\
 &:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8 \\
 &:= (9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) \times (9/9 + 9 \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{577} &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} \\
 &:= 2/2 + ((22 + 2)^2) \\
 &:= ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3 \\
 &:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 4) \\
 &:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 55) \\
 &:= 6/6 + (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) \\
 &:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - 77/7 \\
 &:= 8/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
 &:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) + 9/9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{580} &:= (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1})) \\
 &:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2) \\
 &:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) \\
 &:= 4 \times 4^4 - 444 \\
 &:= 5 \times 5 + 555 \\
 &:= (6 - 6/6) \times (((666 - 6)/6) + 6) \\
 &:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - (7/7 + 7) \\
 &:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + (8/((8 + 8)/8)) \\
 &:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{575} &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1 \\
 &:= ((22 + 2)^2) - 2/2 \\
 &:= ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3 \\
 &:= 4^4 + (((4^4 - 4)/4) + 4^4) \\
 &:= 5 + (5^5/5 - 55) \\
 &:= (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) - 6/6 \\
 &:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7)) \\
 &:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8/8 \\
 &:= 9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) - 9/9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{578} &:= 1 + (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1}) \\
 &:= 2 + ((22 + 2)^2) \\
 &:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) \\
 &:= 4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - (44 + 4)) \\
 &:= 5 \times 5 + (555 - (5 + 5)/5) \\
 &:= (6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) \\
 &:= ((7 - 77)/7) + 7 \times (77 + 7) \\
 &:= (8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
 &:= 99/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{581} &:= 1 + ((1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}))) \\
 &:= 2 + (((((22 + 2)^2) + 2/2) + 2) \\
 &:= 3 + (((((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3) + 3) \\
 &:= (4/4 + 4)^4 - 44 \\
 &:= 5 \times 5 + (555 + 5/5) \\
 &:= 6 + ((6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) - 6/6) \\
 &:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - 7 \\
 &:= 8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 88/8) + 8) \\
 &:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{576} &:= ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} \\
 &:= (22 + 2)^2 \\
 &:= (3 \times 3 + 3)^3/3 \\
 &:= 4 \times (4 \times (4 \times (4 + 4) + 4)) \\
 &:= 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 - 55) \\
 &:= 6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66) \\
 &:= (77 + 7)/7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7) \\
 &:= 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) \\
 &:= 9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{579} &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1})) \\
 &:= 2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2/2) \\
 &:= 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3)/3) \\
 &:= 4 \times 4^4 - (444 + 4/4) \\
 &:= 5 \times 5 + (555 - 5/5) \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 \times 6 + 66 \times 66/(6 + 6) \\
 &:= 7 \times (77 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7) \\
 &:= 88/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8) \\
 &:= ((99 + 9)/9) + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{582} &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)^{1+1}))) \\
 &:= 2 + (((((22 + 2)^2) + 2) + 2) \\
 &:= 3 + (((((3 \times 3 + 3)^3)/3) + 3) \\
 &:= 4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44) \\
 &:= 5 \times 5 + (555 + (5 + 5)/5) \\
 &:= 6 + (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) \\
 &:= 7/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - 7) \\
 &:= 8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8) \\
 &:= 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (99/9)
 \end{aligned}$$

<p>► 583 := $11 \times ((111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1)$:= $2 + (((((22 + 2)^2) + 2/2) + 2) + 2)$:= $3 + (((((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) + 3)$:= $44/4 \times ((4^4 - 44)/4)$:= $55/5 \times (55 - (5 + 5)/5)$:= $6 + ((6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66)) + 6/6)$:= $((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (77 + 7) - 7)$:= $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8/8)$:= $9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) \times (9/9 + 9 \times 9))$</p>	<p>► 586 := $11 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1)$:= $2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2 \times (2 + 2))$:= $3 \times 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3)$:= $4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44) + 4/4)$:= $5 + (555 + 5 \times 5 + 5/5)$:= $((((6 + 6)/6)^{6+6}) + 6)/(6/6 + 6)$:= $7 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7)/7$:= $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + ((8 + 8)/8))$:= $9 + (((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) + 9/9) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 589 := $1 + (1 + (11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1}))$:= $2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 22/2)$:= $3 + ((3 \times (33 \times (3 + 3) - 3)) + 3/3)$:= $4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44) + 4)$:= $((5^5 - 55)/5) - 5 \times 5$:= $666 - (66/6 + 66)$:= $7/7 + 7 \times (77 + 7)$:= $88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8)$:= $9 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \times 9$</p>
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<p>► 584 := $1 + 11 \times ((111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1)$:= $2 \times (2 + 2) + ((22 + 2)^2)$:= $3 \times 3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3)$:= $4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 444)$:= $5 + ((555 - 5/5) + 5 \times 5)$:= $((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times (66 + 6/6 + 6)$:= $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - (77/7))$:= $8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8)$:= $9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9$</p>	<p>► 587 := $11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1}$:= $22/2 + ((22 + 2)^2)$:= $((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 33)/3$:= $4 + (44/4 \times ((4^4 - 44)/4))$:= $555 + ((5 + 5)/5)^5$:= $66/6 + (6 \times ((6 \times 6 - 6) + 66))$:= $7 \times (77 + 7) - 7/7$:= $88/8 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8)$:= $9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) + (99/9))$</p>	<p>► 590 := $(11 - 1) \times ((11^{1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1)$:= $2^{2+2} + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2)$:= $3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 33)/3)$:= $(44 - 4)/4 \times (((4^4 - 4)/4) - 4)$:= $5 + ((555 + 5 \times 5) + 5)$:= $666 + (((6 - 66)/6) - 66)$:= $((7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times (77 + 7)$:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8) + 8)$:= $9 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \times 9$</p>
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<p>► 585 := $11 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - (1 + 1))$:= $22/2 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2)$:= $3 \times (33 \times (3 + 3) - 3)$:= $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44)$:= $5 + (555 + 5 \times 5)$:= $(6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 + 6)$:= $7 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$:= $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + 8/8)$:= $9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 588 := $1 + (11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1})$:= $(2/2 + 2) \times ((2^{2+2} - 2)^2)$:= $3 + (3 \times (33 \times (3 + 3) - 3))$:= $4 + ((4 \times 4^4 - 444) + 4)$:= $5 \times 55 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$:= $666 - (66 + 6 + 6)$:= $7 \times (77 + 7)$:= $((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8)$:= $(99 - 9/9) \times (9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))$</p>	<p>► 591 := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 11)^{1+1})$:= $2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 22/2) + 2$:= $3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3$:= $44/4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 444)$:= $5 \times 5 + (555 + (55/5))$:= $6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 + 6))$:= $7 \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7)/7$:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) - 8/8) + 8)$:= $9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - ((9 + 9)/9)$</p>
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- **592** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1} - 1)$
 := $2^{2+2} + ((22 + 2)^2)$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3)$
 := $4 \times ((4 \times (4 \times (4 + 4) + 4)) + 4)$
 := $5 + (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 555)$
 := $6 \times 6 + (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6)$
 := $77/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9$
- **595** := $111 + (11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $22^2 + 222/2$
 := $3/3 + 3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $(44 \times 44 + 444)/4$
 := $5^5/5 - (5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $6/6 + (666 - (66 + 6))$
 := $7 + 7 \times (77 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + (88/8))$
 := $9/9 + (99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)))$
- **598** := $11 + (11 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1})$
 := $22 + ((22 + 2)^2)$
 := $3 + (3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) + 3/3)$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 \times ((44 - 4/4) + 4^4)$
 := $(5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 5$
 := $666 - (((6 + 6)/6) + 66)$
 := $7 \times (77 + 7) + (77 - 7)/7$
 := $88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $99 + (((9 \times 999) - 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **593** := $11 \times ((111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1) - 1$
 := $22^2 + (222/2 - 2)$
 := $3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3$
 := $(4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4)$
 := $5^5/5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $666 - (66 + 6/6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times 88 - 888/8$
 := $9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)$
- **596** := $1 + (111 + (11 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $22 + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2)$
 := $3 + (3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) - 3/3)$
 := $(4 \times (4^4 + 4)) - 444$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/5 - (5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $666 - (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) + 7/7)$
 := $8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8))$
 := $(9999 + 9 \times 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9)$
- **599** := $1111 - (1 + 1)^{11-1-1}$
 := $22 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2/2)$
 := $((33/3)^3) - (3^{3+3} + 3)$
 := $((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4^4)) - 4/4$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/5 - 5 \times 5$
 := $666 - (66 + 6/6)$
 := $77/7 + 7 \times (77 + 7)$
 := $88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8)$
 := $99 + (((9 \times 999) + 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **594** := $11 \times ((111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1)$
 := $2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 2^{2+2})$
 := $3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4))$
 := $55/5 \times (55 - 5/5)$
 := $666 - (66 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - 7/7)$
 := $8 \times 88 + ((8 - 888)/8)$
 := $99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))$
- **597** := $1 + (1 + (111 + (11 + 11)^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + (222/2 + 22^2)$
 := $3 + 3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4))$
 := $(5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - (5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $666 - (6 \times 6/(6 + 6) + 66)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 88/8) + 88)$
 := $999/9 + ((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9))$
- **600** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 22)$
 := $3 + (3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) + 3)$
 := $(4 + 4) \times ((44 + 4^4)/4)$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5)$
 := $666 - 66$
 := $(7/7 + 7) \times (77 - (7 + 7)/7)$
 := $88 + 8 \times 8 \times 8$
 := $99 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - (99/9)$

▶ 601 := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1}$	▶ 604 := $11 \times (111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1$	▶ 607 := $1 + 1 + 11 \times (111 - 1)/(1 + 1)$
:= $2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 22) + 2/2$	:= $2 \times (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 22)$	:= $2 + ((22/2)^2 + 22^2)$
:= $3 + ((3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3) + 3/3) + 3)$	:= $3^3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3)$	:= $3 + ((3 \times (33 \times (3 + 3) + 3)) + 3/3)$
:= $(4/4 + 4)^4 - ((4 \times 4 + 4) + 4)$	:= $4^4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4)$	:= $4^4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4)$
:= $(5^5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 5$	:= $(55 \times 55 - 5)/5$	:= $((55 \times 55 + 5) + 5)/5$
:= $6/6 + (666 - 66)$	:= $6 + (666 - (((6 + 6)/6) + 66))$	:= $6 + ((666 - 66) + 6/6)$
:= $7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7) - 7/7) + 7)$	:= $7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)) + 7)$	:= $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) + (77 + 7)/7)$
:= $8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88)$	:= $88 + ((8/((8 + 8)/8)) + 8 \times 8 \times 8)$	:= $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - 8/8) + 88)$
:= $9 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9) + 9 \times 9)$	:= $9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + (99/9)$	:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (999 + 99)/9$
▶ 602 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)^{1+1})$	▶ 605 := $11 \times (111 - 1)/(1 + 1)$	▶ 608 := $(11 \times 111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1$
:= $2 + (((22 + 2)^2) + 22) + 2$	:= $22^2 + (22/2)^2$	:= $2^{2+2} \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)$
:= $((33/3)^3) - 3^{3+3}$	:= $3 + (((33/3)^3) - 3^{3+3})$	:= $33 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3)$
:= $(4 + 4)/4 \times ((44 + 4^4) + 4/4)$	:= $(4/4 + 4)^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4)$	:= $4^4 + ((4 + 4) \times 44)$
:= $(5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 5 \times 5$	:= $55 \times (55/5)$	:= $((5^5 - (55 + 5))/5) - 5$
:= $666 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6$	:= $6 + (666 - 66 - 6/6)$	:= $6 + (666 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6)$
:= $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) + 7)$	:= $77 + (7 \times 77 - (77/7))$	:= $(7/7 + 7) \times (77 - 7/7)$
:= $88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8)$	:= $8 \times 88 - (88/8 + 88)$	:= $8 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88)$
:= $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9 \times 9$	:= $99/9 \times ((999 - 9)/(9 + 9))$	:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((999 + 9)/9) + 9)$
▶ 603 := $11 \times (111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 1$	▶ 606 := $1 + 11 \times (111 - 1)/(1 + 1)$	▶ 609 := $(11 \times 111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1$
:= $22^2 + ((22/2)^2 - 2)$	:= $2 + (2 \times (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 22))$	:= $2 + (((22/2)^2 + 22^2) + 2)$
:= $3 \times (33 \times (3 + 3) + 3)$	:= $3 + (3 \times (33 \times (3 + 3) + 3))$	:= $33 + ((3 \times 3 + 3)^3/3)$
:= $4 + (((4 + 4) \times (44 + 4^4)) - 4)/4$	:= $4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4))$	:= $(4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4$
:= $(5^5 - (55 + 55))/5$	:= $(55 \times 55 + 5)/5$	:= $((5^5 - 55)/5) - 5$
:= $6/6 + (666 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6)$	:= $6 + (666 - 66)$	:= $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - 6 \times 6/(6 + 6)$
:= $7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7) + 7/7) + 7)$	:= $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) + (77/7))$	:= $77 + (7 \times 77 - 7)$
:= $8 + ((8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + (88/8)) + 8)$	:= $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 88)$	:= $(8 - 8/8) \times (88 - 8/8)$
:= $9 + (99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)))$	:= $9 + (((9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)) + 999/9)$	:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (999/9 + 9)$

► **610** := $(11 \times 111 - 1)/(1 + 1)$
 := $2 + ((2 \times 2^{2+2}) + ((22 + 2)^2))$
 := $33 + (((3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3)$
 := $4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4)$
 := $55 + 555$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times 77 - 7 + 77)$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + (8 + 8)/8) + 88)$
 := $99 + (((((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9/9)$

► **613** := $1 + 1 + (1 + 11 \times 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $22^2 + ((2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 2)/2)$
 := $3/3 + ((3 + 3) \times (3 \times 33 + 3))$
 := $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 \times 4)$
 := $(5^5 - (55 + 5))/5$
 := $6/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7) + (77/7)) + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times 88 - (88/8 + 88))$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9 + 9))$

► **616** := $11 \times ((1 + 111)/(1 + 1))$
 := $2 \times (22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2))$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 33)$
 := $(4 + 4) \times ((4 - 4/4)^4 - 4)$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/5 - 5 - 5$
 := $6 + (6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $77 + 7 \times 77$
 := $88 \times (8 - 8/8)$
 := $99/9 \times ((999 + 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **611** := $(1 + 11 \times 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $22^2 + ((2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2)/2)$
 := $3 \times 33 + ((3 - 3/3)^{3 \times 3})$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4) + 4^4$
 := $5 + ((55 \times 55 + 5)/5)$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - 6/6$
 := $77 + (((7 + 7)/7 - 7) + 7 \times 77)$
 := $88 + (8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8)$
 := $99 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)$

► **614** := $(1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 111))^{1+1} - 11$
 := $(2 \times (22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2))) - 2$
 := $3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - (3/3 + 33)$
 := $(4/4 + 4)^4 - 44/4$
 := $(5^5 - 55)/5$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66)$
 := $77 + (7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times 88 - ((8 + 8)/8 + 88)$
 := $999/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) - 9$

► **617** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $22 + (222/2 + 22^2)$
 := $3^{3+3} - ((333 + 3)/3)$
 := $(4/4 + 4)^4 - 4 - 4$
 := $(5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 5 - 5$
 := $6 + (6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) - 6/6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times 77 + 77)$
 := $8/8 + 88 \times (8 - 8/8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((999 + 9)/9)$

► **612** := $1 + (1 + 11 \times 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $2 \times ((22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2)) - 2)$
 := $(3 + 3) \times (3 \times 33 + 3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) + 4^4)$
 := $(5^5 - (55 + 5 + 5))/5$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 77 - (77/7)) + 77)$
 := $88 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 8 \times 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9 + 9)$

► **615** := $11 \times (1 + 111)/(1 + 1) - 1$
 := $(2/2 + 2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 + 2)$
 := $3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 33$
 := $(4 - 44)/4 + (4/4 + 4)^4$
 := $5^5/5 - 5 - 5$
 := $(66 \times 66 - 666)/6$
 := $77 + (7 \times 77 - 7/7)$
 := $8 \times 88 - (8/8 + 88)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((999 + 9 + 9) + 9)/9)$

► **618** := $1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $2 + (2 \times (22 \times (2^{2+2} - 2)))$
 := $3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 33)$
 := $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44/4)$
 := $(5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 5$
 := $6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66)$
 := $77 + (7 \times 77 + ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + 88 \times (8 - 8/8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 - 999/9$

► **619** := $1 + 1 + 1 + 11 \times (1 + 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $(2 \times 22) + (((22 + 2)^2) - 2/2)$
 := $3^{3+3} + ((3 - 333)/3)$
 := $444 + ((4 \times 44) - 4/4)$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/5 - 5$
 := $6 + (6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) + 6/6)$
 := $77 + (((7 + 7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times 77)$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88/8) + 88)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 - 999)/9)$

► **622** := $11 + (1 + 11 \times 111)/(1 + 1)$
 := $222 + (22 - 2)^2$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3 \times 3))$
 := $4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4)$
 := $(5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 5$
 := $66 + (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 77 - 7/7) + 77)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + ((888 - 8)/8)$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9))$

► **625** := $(1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1}$
 := $(2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}$
 := $(3 - 3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3}$
 := $(4/4 + 4)^4$
 := $5^5/5$
 := $(6 - 6/6)^{6-(6+6)/6}$
 := $(7 - ((7 + 7)/7))^{77/7-7}$
 := $8 + (88 \times (8 - 8/8) + 8/8)$
 := $9 \times 9 + (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **620** := $11 + (11 \times 111 - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1$
 := $(2 \times 22) + ((22 + 2)^2)$
 := $3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - (3^3 + 3/3)$
 := $444 + (4 \times 44)$
 := $5^5/5 - 5$
 := $6 + (6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $77 + ((7 \times 77 - 7) + (77/7))$
 := $8 \times 8 + ((8888 + 8)/(8 + 8))$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 99$

► **623** := $111 + (1 + 1)^{11-1-1}$
 := $((2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) - 2$
 := $3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - (3^3 + 3/3))$
 := $(4/4 + 4)^4 - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $(5^5 - 5 - 5)/5$
 := $66/6 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 66)$
 := $7 + (7 \times 77 + 77)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + 888/8$
 := $999/9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)$

► **626** := $1 + (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1}$
 := $2 + ((22 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2))$
 := $3/3 + ((3 - 3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3})$
 := $4/4 + (4/4 + 4)^4$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/5$
 := $6/6 + ((6 - 6/6)^{6-(6+6)/6})$
 := $(7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - 77/7$
 := $8 + (((8 + 8)/8) - 88) + 8 \times 88$
 := $9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((999 + 9)/9))$

► **621** := $11 + (11 \times 111 - 1)/(1 + 1)$
 := $((2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2}) - 2 - 2$
 := $3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3 \times 3)$
 := $(4/4 + 4)^4 - 4$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/5 - 5$
 := $6 + ((66 \times 66 - 666)/6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 77 - ((7 + 7)/7)) + 77)$
 := $8 \times (88 - 8) - (88/8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)$

► **624** := $(1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1} - 1$
 := $(22 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3 \times 3))$
 := $4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4) - 4)$
 := $(5^5 - 5)/5$
 := $666 - (6 \times 6 + 6)$
 := $(7/7 + 7) \times (7/7 + 77)$
 := $8 + 88 \times (8 - 8/8)$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times (9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))$

► **627** := $11 \times (1 + ((1 + 111)/(1 + 1)))$
 := $2 + ((2/2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2})$
 := $33 + 3 \times 33 \times (3 + 3)$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + (4/4 + 4)^4$
 := $(5^5 + 5 + 5)/5$
 := $666 - ((66 \times 6/(6 + 6)) + 6)$
 := $77 + (7 \times 77 + (77/7))$
 := $88/8 + 88 \times (8 - 8/8)$
 := $9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 999/9)$

<p>▶ 628 := 1 + (11 × (1 + ((1 + 111)/(1 + 1)))) := 22² + ((2 × (2 + 2 + 2))²) := 3 + ((3 - 3/3 + 3)^{3/3+3}) := 4 + (4 × (4 × (44 - 4) - 4)) := 5 + (5⁵ - 5 - 5)/5 := 666 - (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 × 6) := 77 + ((77 + 7)/7 + 7 × 77) := 8 × (88 - 8) - (88 + 8)/8 := 9 × 9 × 9 - ((9 + 9)/9 + 99)</p>	<p>▶ 631 := 1 + ((11 - 1) × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (11 + (11 - 1)))) := 2 + (((2/2 + 2 + 2)²⁺²) + 2) + 2 := 3/3 + (3 × ((3 + 3)³ - (3 + 3))) := 4 + (((4/4 + 4)⁴ + (4 + 4)/4) := 5 + (5⁵ + 5)/5 := 6/6 + (666 - 6 × 6) := 7 + ((7/7 + 7) × (7/7 + 77)) := 8 × (88 - 8) - (8/8 + 8) := 9/9 + (9 × 9 × 9 - 99)</p>	<p>▶ 634 := 1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × 111 - 11)) := 2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)²) - (2 × 22)) := 3 × (3 + 3)³ - (33/3 + 3) := 4 + (((4/4 + 4)⁴ + 4/4) + 4) := 5 + ((5⁵ - 5)/5 + 5) := 6 + (666 - (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 × 6)) := 7 + ((7 × 77 + (77/7)) + 77) := (8 + 8)/8 + (8 × (88 - 8) - 8) := 9 + (((99 × 99) - 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 × 9)</p>
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<p>▶ 629 := 1 + (1 + (11 × (1 + ((1 + 111)/(1 + 1))))) := 2 + (((2/2 + 2 + 2)²⁺²) + 2) := 3³⁺³ - (3 × 33 + 3/3) := 4 + (4/4 + 4)⁴ := 5 + (5⁵ - 5)/5 := 666 - (6 × 6 + 6/6) := (7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) - (7/7 + 7) := 8 × (88 - 8) - 88/8 := 9 × 9 × 9 - (9/9 + 99)</p>	<p>▶ 632 := 11¹⁺¹ + ((1 + 1)¹¹⁻¹⁻¹ - 1) := (22 + 2 + 2)² - 2 × 22 := 3 + (3³⁺³ - (3 × 33 + 3/3)) := (4 × (4 × (44 - 4))) - 4 - 4 := 5 + (5⁵ + 5 + 5)/5 := 666 + (((6 + 6)/6) - 6 × 6) := (7/7 + 7) × ((7 + 7)/7 + 77) := 8 × (88 - 8) - 8 := 9 × 9 × 9 + (((9 + 9)/9) - 99)</p>	<p>▶ 635 := 11 + ((1 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 11))¹⁺¹ - 1) := (((2 + 2 + 2)²⁺²) - 22)/2 - 2 := (3 × ((3 + 3)³ - 3)) - (3/3 + 3) := (4/4 + 4)⁴ + (44 - 4)/4 := 5 + (5⁵/5 + 5) := 6 + (666 - (6 × 6 + 6/6)) := (7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) - (7 + 7)/7 := 8 + (88 × (8 - 8/8) + (88/8)) := 9 × 99 - (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9})</p>
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<p>▶ 630 := (11 - 1) × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (11 + (11 - 1))) := 2 + (((2 × (2 + 2 + 2))²) + 22²) := 3 × ((3 + 3)³ - (3 + 3)) := 4 + ((4/4 + 4)⁴ + 4/4) := 5 + 5⁵/5 := 666 - 6 × 6 := (7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) - 7 := (8 - 8/8) × ((8 + 8)/8 + 88) := 9 × 9 × 9 - 99</p>	<p>▶ 633 := (1 + 1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × 111 - 11) := 2 × (2 + 2) + ((2/2 + 2 + 2)²⁺²) := 3 + (3 × ((3 + 3)³ - (3 + 3))) := 4 + ((4/4 + 4)⁴ + 4) := 5 + ((5⁵ - 5 - 5)/5 + 5) := 666 - (66 × 6/(6 + 6)) := 7 + ((7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) - (77/7)) := 8/8 + (8 × (88 - 8) - 8) := 9 × 9 × 9 + (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - 99)</p>	<p>▶ 636 := 11 + (1 + (1 + 1) × (1 + 11))¹⁺¹ := 2 × ((2²⁺² × (22 - 2)) - 2) := (3 × ((3 + 3)³ - 3)) - 3 := (4 × (4 × (44 - 4))) - 4 := (55 + 5⁵)/5 := 6 + (666 - 6 × 6) := (7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) - 7/7 := 8 × (88 - 8) - (8/((8 + 8)/8)) := 9 × (9 × 9 - 9) - (99 + 9)/9</p>
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- **637** := $1 + (11 + (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1})$
 := $((2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2} - 22)/2$
 := $3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 33/3$
 := $4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4) + 4)$
 := $(55 + 5^5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + ((666 - 6 \times 6) + 6/6)$
 := $7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - (88/8))$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 99/9$
- **640** := $111 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2))$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3))$
 := $4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4))$
 := $5 + (5^5/5 + 5 + 5)$
 := $((66 - 6)/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $(7 - ((7 + 7)/7)) \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 \times (88 - 8)$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9)$
- **643** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 11) - 1$
 := $(22 - 2)^2 + (22^2 + 2)/2$
 := $3 + ((3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) + 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4))) - 4/4)$
 := $5 + (((55 + 5^5 + 5) + 5)/5)$
 := $6/6 + ((6 \times 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)) - 6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - 7/7)$
 := $88/8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - 8)$
 := $99 + (((99 \times 99) - 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **638** := $11 \times (1 + 1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1))$
 := $(2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2))) - 2$
 := $(3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) - 3/3$
 := $(4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4))) - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $((55 + 5^5 + 5) + 5)/5$
 := $(66/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7))$
 := $8 \times (88 - 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9/9 - 9$
- **641** := $1 + 111 + (1 + 11 + 11)^{1+1}$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2)))$
 := $3 + ((3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)) - 3/3)$
 := $4 \times 4 + (4/4 + 4)^4$
 := $5 + ((55 + 5^5)/5)$
 := $666 + ((66/6) - 6 \times 6)$
 := $77/7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) - 7)$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times (88 - 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((99/9) - 99)$
- **644** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 11)$
 := $2 \times (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) - 2)$
 := $3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - (3/3 + 3)$
 := $4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4)))$
 := $5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 5)$
 := $666 - ((66 + 66)/6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7))$
 := $8 \times (88 - 8) + (8/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $99 + (((99 \times 99) + 9)/(9 + 9))$
- **639** := $1 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + (1 + 111)/(1 + 1))$
 := $2 + (((2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2} - 22)/2)$
 := $3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)$
 := $(4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4))) - 4/4$
 := $5 + (((5^5 - 5)/5 + 5) + 5)$
 := $6 + (666 - (66 \times 6/(6 + 6)))$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (77 + 7 + 7))$
 := $8 \times (88 - 8) - 8/8$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9$
- **642** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1 - 11)$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2^{2+2} \times (22 - 2)))$
 := $3 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3))$
 := $4 \times 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4/4)$
 := $5 + ((55 + 5^5 + 5)/5)$
 := $(6 \times 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)) - 6$
 := $777 - (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7)$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (88 - 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((99 + 9)/9) - 99)$
- **645** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 11)$
 := $((2 + 2 + 2)^{2+2} - 2)/2 - 2$
 := $3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 3$
 := $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4 \times 4)$
 := $5 \times 5 + (5^5/5 - 5)$
 := $(6 \times 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6)/((6 + 6)/6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)) + 7/7)$
 := $8 + ((8 \times (88 - 8) - (88/8)) + 8)$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

▶ 646 := (1 + 1) × (1 + (1 + 1 + 1) × 111 - 11)	▶ 649 := 11 × ((11 ¹⁺¹ - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1)	▶ 652 := (1 + 1) × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (111 - 1 - 1) - 1)
:= (2 × ((2 ²⁺² + 2) ²)) - 2	:= (((2 + 2 + 2) ²⁺²) + 2)/2	:= 2 × (((2 ²⁺² + 2) ²) + 2)
:= 3/3 + (3 × (3 + 3) ³ - 3)	:= 3/3 + 3 × (3 + 3) ³	:= 3 + (3 × (3 + 3) ³ + 3/3)
:= 4 + (((4/4 + 4) ⁴ + 4 × 4) + 4/4)	:= 4 + (((4/4 + 4) ⁴ + 4 × 4) + 4)	:= 4 + ((4 + 4) × (4 - 4/4) ⁴)
:= 5 + (((55 + 5 ⁵)/5) + 5)	:= 5 × 5 + (5 ⁵ - 5)/5	:= 5 × 5 + (5 ⁵ + 5 + 5)/5
:= (6 × 6 × (6 + 6 + 6)) - (6 + 6)/6	:= 6/6 + (6 × 6 × (6 + 6 + 6))	:= 666 - ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6)
:= 7 + ((7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) + ((7 + 7)/7))	:= 777 - ((7 + 7)/7) ⁷	:= 7 + (((7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) + 7/7) + 7)
:= 8 + (8 × (88 - 8) - ((8 + 8)/8))	:= 8 + (8 × (88 - 8) + 8/8)	:= ((88 + 8)/8) + 8 × (88 - 8)
:= 9 × (9 × 9 - 9) - (9 + 9)/9	:= 9/9 + 9 × (9 × 9 - 9)	:= 9 × (9 × 9 - 9) + ((9 × 9 - 9)/(9 + 9))

▶ 647 := (1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × (11 - 1 - 1)) ¹⁺¹ - 1	▶ 650 := 1 + 11 × ((11 ¹⁺¹ - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1)	▶ 653 := (11 ¹⁺¹⁺¹ - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1 - 11
:= (((2 + 2 + 2) ²⁺²) - 2)/2	:= 2 + (2 × ((2 ²⁺² + 2) ²))	:= 22 ² + ((22/2 + 2) ²)
:= 3 × (3 + 3) ³ - 3/3	:= 3 + (3 × (3 + 3) ³ - 3/3)	:= 3 + ((3 × (3 + 3) ³ - 3/3) + 3)
:= ((4 + 4) × (4 - 4/4) ⁴) - 4/4	:= (44 - 4)/4 × (4 ⁴ + 4)/4	:= 44 + ((4/4 + 4) ⁴ - 4 × 4)
:= ((55 + 55) + 5 ⁵)/5	:= 5 × (5 × 5 × 5 + 5)	:= 5 + ((5 ⁵ - 5 - 5)/5 + 5 × 5)
:= (6 × 6 × (6 + 6 + 6)) - 6/6	:= 666 + (((6 - 66)/6) - 6)	:= 666 - (6/6 + 6 + 6)
:= 7 + ((7 - ((7 + 7)/7)) × ((7 + 7)/7) ⁷)	:= 7 × 77 + 777/7	:= 7 × 77 + (((7 + 7)/7) ⁷ - (7 + 7))
:= 8 + (8 × (88 - 8) - 8/8)	:= 8 + (8 × (88 - 8) + ((8 + 8)/8))	:= 88 + (8 × (8 × 8 + 8) - 88/8)
:= 9 × (9 × 9 - 9) - 9/9	:= (9 + 9)/9 + 9 × (9 × 9 - 9)	:= 9 × (9 × 9 - 9) + ((9 × 9 + 9)/(9 + 9))

▶ 648 := (1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × (11 - 1 - 1)) ¹⁺¹	▶ 651 := (1 + 1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × (111 - 1 - 1) - 1)	▶ 654 := (1 + 1) × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (111 - 1 - 1))
:= 2 × ((2 ²⁺² + 2) ²)	:= 2 + (((2 + 2 + 2) ²⁺²) + 2)/2	:= ((22 + 2 + 2) ²) - 22
:= 3 × (3 + 3) ³	:= 3 + 3 × (3 + 3) ³	:= 3 + (3 × (3 + 3) ³ + 3)
:= (4 + 4) × (4 - 4/4) ⁴	:= 44/4 + (4 × (4 × (44 - 4)))	:= 4 + ((44 - 4)/4 × (4 ⁴ + 4)/4)
:= 5 × 5 + (5 ⁵ - 5 - 5)/5	:= 5 × 5 + (5 ⁵ + 5)/5	:= 5 + ((5 ⁵ - 5)/5 + 5 × 5)
:= 6 × 6 × (6 + 6 + 6)	:= (6 × 6 × 6 × 6 + 6)/((6 + 6)/6)	:= 666 - 6 - 6
:= 77/7 + (7 × (77 + 7 + 7))	:= 7 + ((7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) + 7)	:= 77 + (7 × (77 + 7) - (77/7))
:= 8 + 8 × (88 - 8)	:= 88/8 + 8 × (88 - 8)	:= 8 + ((8 × (88 - 8) - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)
:= 9 × (9 × 9 - 9)	:= 9 × (9 × 9 - 9) + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)	:= 9 + (9 × (9 × 9 - 9) - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))

▶ 655 := (1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1) × 111 – 11 := 2 + (((22/2 + 2) ²) + 22 ²) := 3 + ((3 × (3 + 3) ³ + 3/3) + 3) := (4 × (4 × (44 – 4) + 4)) – 4/4 := 5 + (5 ⁵ /5 + 5 × 5) := 666 – 66/6 := 7 + ((7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) + (77/7)) := 8 + ((8 × (88 – 8) – 8/8) + 8) := 9 + (9 × (9 × 9 – 9) – ((9 + 9)/9))	▶ 658 := (1 + 1) × (((1 + 1 + 1) × (111 – 1)) – 1) := (22 × (2 × (2 + 2) + 22)) – 2 := 3/3 + (3 × ((3 + 3) ³ + 3)) := 44 + ((4/4 + 4) ⁴ – 44/4) := (5 ⁵ + 5)/5 + ((5 + 5)/5) ⁵ := 666 – ((6 + 6)/6 + 6) := 77 + (7 × (77 + 7) – 7) := 8 + ((8 × (88 – 8) + ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8) := 9 + (9 × (9 × 9 – 9) + 9/9)	▶ 661 := 1 + ((1 + 1) × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (111 – 1))) := 2 + (((2 + 2 + 2) ²⁺²) + 22)/2 := 3 + ((3 × ((3 + 3) ³ + 3)) + 3/3) := 4 + ((4/4 + 4) ⁴ + 4 × (4 + 4)) := 5 × 5 + ((55 + 5 ⁵)/5) := 6/6 + (666 – 6) := 7 × 77 + (777 + 77)/7 := ((88 + 8) × (8 – 8/8)) – 88/8 := 9 × (9 × 9 – 9) + ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)
▶ 656 := 1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1) × 111 – 11) := 2 + (((22 + 2 + 2) ²) – 22) := (3 × ((3 + 3) ³ + 3)) – 3/3 := 4 × (4 × (44 – 4) + 4) := 5 + ((5 ⁵ + 5)/5 + 5 × 5) := 666 + (6 – 66)/6 := 7 + (777 – ((7 + 7)/7) ⁷) := 8 + (8 × (88 – 8) + 8) := 9 + (9 × (9 × 9 – 9) – 9/9)	▶ 659 := ((1 + 1) × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (111 – 1))) – 1 := (((2 + 2 + 2) ²⁺²) + 22)/2 := 33/3 + 3 × (3 + 3) ³ := 4 × 4 × 44 – (44 + 4/4) := ((55 × (55 + 5)) – 5)/5 := 666 – 6/6 – 6 := 777 – (777/7 + 7) := 8 + (8 × (88 – 8) + (88/8)) := 99/9 + 9 × (9 × 9 – 9)	▶ 662 := (1 + 1) × (1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) × (111 – 1))) := 2 + (22 × (2 × (2 + 2) + 22)) := 3 + (3 × (3 + 3) ³ + 33/3) := (4 + 4)/4 + (44 × (44/4 + 4)) := 5 + (((5 + 5)/5) ⁵ + 5 ⁵ /5) := 666 + ((6 + 6)/6 – 6) := 7 + (((7 × (77 + 7 + 7)) + (77/7)) + 7) := 88 + (8 × (8 × 8 + 8) – (8 + 8)/8) := 9 + (((9 × 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 × (9 × 9 – 9))
▶ 657 := (1 + 1 + 1) × (((1 + 1) × (111 – 1)) – 1) := (2/2 + 2) × (222 – (2/2 + 2)) := 3 × ((3 + 3) ³ + 3) := 4 × (4 + 4) + (4/4 + 4) ⁴ := 5 ⁵ /5 + ((5 + 5)/5) ⁵ := 666 + (((6 – 66) + 6)/6) := 7 + (777/7 + 7 × 77) := 8 + ((8 × (88 – 8) + 8/8) + 8) := 9 + 9 × (9 × 9 – 9)	▶ 660 := (1 + 1) × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (111 – 1)) := 22 × (2 × (2 + 2) + 22) := 3 + (3 × ((3 + 3) ³ + 3)) := 44 × (44/4 + 4) := 55 × ((55 + 5)/5) := 666 – 6 := 7 × 77 + (((7 + 7)/7) ⁷ – 7) := 8 × 88 – (88/((8 + 8)/8)) := 9 × (9 × 9 – 9) + (99 + 9)/9	▶ 663 := (1 + 1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × 111 – 1) := 222 + ((22 – 2/2) ²) := 3 + ((3 × ((3 + 3) ³ + 3)) + 3) := 4 + 4 × 4 × 44 – (44 + 4/4) := 5 + ((5 ⁵ + 5)/5 + ((5 + 5)/5) ⁵) := 666 – 6 × 6/(6 + 6) := 7 + ((777 – ((7 + 7)/7) ⁷) + 7) := 88 + (8 × (8 × 8 + 8) – 8/8) := 9 + ((9 × (9 × 9 – 9) – ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)

► **664** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1)$
 := $((2/2 + 2) \times 222) - 2$
 := $(3 - 3/3) \times (333 - 3/3)$
 := $4 + (44 \times (44/4 + 4))$
 := $5 + (((55 \times (55 + 5)) - 5)/5)$
 := $666 - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $77 + (7 \times (77 + 7) - 7/7)$
 := $88 + 8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8)$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times (((9 + 9)/9) + 9 \times 9)$

► **667** := $1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $2/2 + ((2/2 + 2) \times 222)$
 := $((3 + 3) \times 333 + 3)/3$
 := $4444/4 - 444$
 := $555 + (555 + 5)/5$
 := $6/6 + 666$
 := $7 \times 77 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 + ((8 \times (88 - 8) + (88/8)) + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + 9/9) + 9)$

► **670** := $1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times 111))$
 := $2 + (((2/2 + 2) \times 222) + 2)$
 := $3 + (((3 + 3) \times 333 + 3)/3)$
 := $44 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4/4)$
 := $55 + (5^5/5 - (5 + 5))$
 := $6 + (666 - ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) \times (7 \times 7 \times 7 - (7/7 + 7))$
 := $((88 + 8) \times (8 - 8/8)) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + ((99 + 99)/9)$

► **665** := $(11^{1+1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1)$
 := $((22 + 2 + 2)^2) - 22/2$
 := $3^{3+3} - ((3/3 + 3)^3)$
 := $44 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4)$
 := $5 + (55 \times ((55 + 5)/5))$
 := $666 - 6/6$
 := $77 + 7 \times (77 + 7)$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times 8 + 8) + 88)$
 := $9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) - 9/9) + 9)$

► **668** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111)$
 := $2 + ((2/2 + 2) \times 222)$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} - ((3/3 + 3)^3))$
 := $(4 \times ((4 \times 44) - (4 + 4))) - 4$
 := $55 + ((5^5 - (55 + 5))/5)$
 := $666 + (6 + 6)/6$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - (77/7 + 7)$
 := $8 + (8 \times 88 - (88/((8 + 8)/8)))$
 := $9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + (99/9))$

► **671** := $11 \times ((1 + 11^{1+1})/(1 + 1))$
 := $2 + ((2/2 + 2) \times (222 + 2/2))$
 := $33/3 \times (((3/3 + 3)^3) - 3)$
 := $44/4 \times ((4^4 + 4)/4 - 4)$
 := $5 + (555/5 + 555)$
 := $6 + (666 - 6/6)$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - (7/7 + 7 + 7)$
 := $((88 + 8) \times (8 - 8/8)) - 8/8$
 := $99/9 \times (9 \times 9 - (99/9 + 9))$

► **666** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$
 := $(2/2 + 2) \times 222$
 := $3 \times (((3 + 3)^3 + 3) + 3)$
 := $((4 + 4)/4 + 4) \times 444/4$
 := $555 + 555/5$
 := 666
 := $(7 - 7/7) \times 777/7$
 := $(8 - (8 + 8)/8) \times 888/8$
 := $9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + 9)$

► **669** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 1) \times 111)$
 := $(2/2 + 2) \times (222 + 2/2)$
 := $3 + (333 + 333)$
 := $44 + (4/4 + 4)^4$
 := $55 + ((5^5 - 55)/5)$
 := $666 + (6 \times 6/(6 + 6))$
 := $((7 - 77)/7) + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 7)$
 := $8 \times 88 - ((88/8 + 8 + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + ((99 + 9)/9))$

► **672** := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111))$
 := $(2/2 + 2) \times (222 + 2)$
 := $3^3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 3)$
 := $4 \times ((4 \times 44) - (4 + 4))$
 := $(5/5 + 5) \times (555 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + 666$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7)$
 := $(88 + 8) \times (8 - 8/8)$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) + 9 \times 9)$

▶ 673 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)))$	▶ 676 := $((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)))^{1+1}$	▶ 679 := $((1 + 1)^{11} - 11)/(1 + 1 + 1)$
:= $((22 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2 - 2$	:= $(22 + 2 + 2)^2$	:= $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2/2)$
:= $((3^3 - 3/3)^{3-3/3}) - 3$	:= $(3^3 - 3/3)^{3-3/3}$	:= $3 + ((3^3 - 3/3)^{3-3/3})$
:= $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 44)$	:= $4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - (4 + 4)))$	:= $4 + (44/4 + 4) \times (44 + 4/4)$
:= $55 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 5)$	:= $55 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 - 5)$	:= $55 + (5^5 - 5)/5$
:= $6 + (666 + 6/6)$	:= $666 + (66 - 6)/6$	:= $6 + (666 + 6/6 + 6)$
:= $7 + ((7 - 7/7) \times 777/7)$	:= $((7 - 77)/7) + (7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7))$	:= $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 7$
:= $8/8 + ((88 + 8) \times (8 - 8/8))$	:= $8 \times 88 + ((8 - 8 \times 8)/((8 + 8)/8))$	:= $8 \times 88 - (8/8 + 8 + 8 + 8)$
:= $9 + ((9 - 9/9) \times (((9 + 9)/9) + 9 \times 9))$	:= $((9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9)^{(9+9)/9}$	:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9))$

▶ 674 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 111)))$	▶ 677 := $1 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11))))^{1+1}$	▶ 680 := $1 + (((1 + 1)^{11} - 11)/(1 + 1 + 1))$
:= $((22 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2$	:= $2/2 + ((22 + 2 + 2)^2)$	:= $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2)$
:= $3^3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 3/3)$	:= $((3 + 3) \times 333) + 33/3$	:= $33 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 - 3/3)$
:= $4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 + 44) + 4/4)$	:= $4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 + 44) + 4)$	:= $(4 + 4) \times ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4)$
:= $55 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 5)$	:= $55 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 5)$	:= $55 + 5^5/5$
:= $6 + (666 + ((6 + 6)/6))$	:= $666 + 66/6$	:= $6 + ((666 + ((6 + 6)/6)) + 6)$
:= $7 + (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7 \times 77)$	:= $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7)$	:= $7/7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 7)$
:= $8 + ((8 - (8 + 8)/8) \times 888/8)$	:= $8 \times 88 - (88/8 + 8 + 8)$	:= $8 \times 88 - 8 - 8 - 8$
:= $9 \times (9 + 9) + (((9 + 9)/9)^9)$	:= $9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + (99/9)) + 9)$	:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 - 9 \times 99)/(9 + 9))$

▶ 675 := $((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)))^{1+1} - 1$	▶ 678 := $1 + (1 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11))))^{1+1})$	▶ 681 := $((1 + ((1 + 1)^{11}))/((1 + 1 + 1))) - 1 - 1$
:= $((22 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2$	:= $2 + ((22 + 2 + 2)^2)$	:= $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2/2) + 2)$
:= $3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 + 3 \times 3)$	:= $3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 + 3^3)$	:= $33 + 3 \times (3 + 3)^3$
:= $(44/4 + 4) \times (44 + 4/4)$	:= $(4 - 44)/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4))$	:= $4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 + 44) + 4) + 4)$
:= $5 \times ((5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5) + 5)$	:= $55 + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5$	:= $55 + (5^5 + 5)/5$
:= $6 + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6)) + 666)$	:= $6 + (666 + 6)$	:= $66 \times (6 + 6) - 666/6$
:= $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 77/7$	:= $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - (7/7 + 7)$	:= $((7 + 7)/7) + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 7)$
:= $(8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8 \times 8)$	:= $8 \times 88 + ((8 - 88)/8 - (8 + 8))$	:= $8/8 + (8 \times 88 - (8 + 8 + 8))$
:= $9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - 9) + 9) + 9)$	:= $999/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)))$	:= $9 \times 99 - (999/9 + 99)$

- **682** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (1 + 1) / (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2) + 2$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 + 33)$
 := $44/4 \times ((4^4 - 4 - 4)/4)$
 := $55 + (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + ((66 - 6)/6 + 666)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - (77/7))$
 := $8 \times 88 - (88 + 88)/8$
 := $99/9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9/9 + 9 + 9))$
- **683** := $(1 + ((1 + 1)^{11})) / (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $22^2 + (((22 - 2)^2 - 2)/2)$
 := $((33/3)^3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)^3$
 := $(4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - (4/4 + 4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 55)$
 := $6 + (666 + (66/6))$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + ((8/8 + 8) \times (88/8 + 8 \times 8))$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)$
- **684** := $1 + ((1 + ((1 + 1)^{11})) / (1 + 1 + 1))$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (((22/2 + 2)^2) + 2))$
 := $3 + (3 \times (3 + 3)^3 + 33)$
 := $(4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - 4$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 + 55)$
 := $6 + ((666 + 6) + 6)$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 \times 88 - (((88 + 8)/8) + 8)$
 := $(99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9)/9))) - 9$
- **685** := $1 + (1 + ((1 + ((1 + 1)^{11})) / (1 + 1 + 1)))$
 := $22/2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2)$
 := $3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 33)$
 := $4 \times 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 44)$
 := $5 + (5^5/5 + 55)$
 := $6 + ((666 + 6/6 + 6) + 6)$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 7/7$
 := $8 \times 88 - (88/8 + 8)$
 := $9 + (((9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9)^{(9+9)/9}$
- **686** := $(11 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - 1)) / (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 \times ((22/2)^2 + 222)$
 := $(3 - 3/3) \times (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3)$
 := $(4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 + 55)$
 := $6 + (((666 + ((6 + 6)/6)) + 6) + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 88 + ((8 - 88)/8 - 8)$
 := $(99 - 9/9) \times (9 - ((9 + 9)/9))$
- **687** := $11 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)))^{1+1})$
 := $22/2 + ((22 + 2 + 2)^2)$
 := $3^{3+3} - (3 \times 3 + 33)$
 := $(4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - 4/4$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 + 55)$
 := $((6 \times 6 / (6 + 6))^6) - (6 \times 6 + 6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7))$
 := $8 \times 88 - (8/8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9 \times (9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))) + 999/9)$
- **688** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111)$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (2 \times (2 \times 2 \times 22 - 2)))$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 33))$
 := $4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)$
 := $(5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 55 + 5) / (5 + 5)$
 := $666 + ((66 + 66)/6)$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7))$
 := $8 \times 88 - 8 - 8$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9) / (9 + 9))$
- **689** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111))$
 := $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 22/2)$
 := $3 + ((3 - 3/3) \times (((3/3 + 3) + 3)^3))$
 := $4/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4))$
 := $5 + (((5^5 - 5)/5 + 55) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((666 + (66/6)) + 6)$
 := $777 - (77/7 + 77)$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times 88 - (8 + 8))$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 - 9 \times 9 \times 9) / (9 + 9))$
- **690** := $11 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - 11) / (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $2 + (((2/2 + 2) \times 222) + 22)$
 := $33 + (3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 + 3))$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4))$
 := $5 + ((5^5/5 + 55) + 5)$
 := $6 + (((666 + 6) + 6) + 6)$
 := $77/7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 7)$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times 88 - (8 + 8))$
 := $(9/9 + 9) \times (9 \times 9 - ((99 + 9)/9))$

<p>▶ 691 := $((1 + 1)^{11-1}) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 111$:= $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 22/2) + 2$:= $3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 3^3)$:= $4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) - 4/4)$:= $55 + ((55 + 5^5)/5)$:= $6 \times 6 + (666 - 66/6)$:= $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - ((7 + 7)/7))$:= $8 \times 88 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((99/9 + 9 + 9) + 9)$</p>	<p>▶ 694 := $11 + ((1 + ((1 + 1)^{11}))/ (1 + 1 + 1))$:= $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2^{2+2})$:= $3/3 + (33 \times ((3 \times (3 + 3)) + 3))$:= $(4 - 44)/4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44$:= $5 + (((5^5 - 5)/5 + 55) + 5) + 5$:= $6 + (((66 + 66)/6) + 666)$:= $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + 7/7)$:= $8 \times 88 + (8 - 88)/8$:= $9/9 + (99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9)/9)))$</p>	<p>▶ 697 := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + 11^{1+1})$:= $(22/2)^2 + ((22 + 2)^2)$:= $3/3 + (3^{3+3} - 33)$:= $4 + (44/4 \times ((4^4 - 4)/4))$:= $5 + (((55 + 5^5 + 5)/5) + 55)$:= $6 \times 6 + ((666 - 6) + 6/6)$:= $77/7 + (7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7))$:= $8/8 + (8 \times 88 - 8)$:= $9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)))$</p>
<p>▶ 692 := $(11 \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + (11 - 1)))) - 1$:= $2 \times (((2^{2+2} + 2)^2) + 22)$:= $3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 33 + 3)$:= $4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4))$:= $55 + ((55 + 5^5 + 5)/5)$:= $6 \times 6 + (((6 - 66)/6) + 666)$:= $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) - 7/7)$:= $8 \times 88 - (88 + 8)/8$:= $99 + (((9 + 9)/9)^9) + 9 \times 9$</p>	<p>▶ 695 := $1 + 11 + (1 + (1 + 1)^{11}) / (1 + 1 + 1)$:= $222 + (22^2 - 22/2)$:= $3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 33)$:= $4^4 + (444 - (4/4 + 4))$:= $5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 55$:= $6 \times 6 + (666 - 6/6 - 6)$:= $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + ((7 + 7)/7))$:= $8 \times 88 - (8/8 + 8)$:= $9 + ((99 - 9/9) \times (9 - ((9 + 9)/9)))$</p>	<p>▶ 698 := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111) - 1$:= $22 + ((22 + 2 + 2)^2)$:= $3 + (3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 33))$:= $4^4 + (444 - (4 + 4)/4)$:= $(5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5$:= $((66/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6) - 6$:= $777 - ((7 + 7)/7 + 77)$:= $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times 88 - 8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((99 + 99)/9) + 9)$</p>
<p>▶ 693 := $11 \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + (11 - 1)))$:= $(2/2 + 2) \times ((22^2 - 22)/2)$:= $33 \times ((3 \times (3 + 3)) + 3)$:= $44/4 \times ((4^4 - 4)/4)$:= $5 + ((5 \times 5 \times 5 \times 55 + 5)/(5 + 5))$:= $((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6 \times 6$:= $7 + (7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7))$:= $8 \times 88 - 88/8$:= $99 \times (9 - ((9 + 9)/9))$</p>	<p>▶ 696 := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + 11^{1+1})$:= $2 \times (2 \times ((2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 22) - 2))$:= $3^{3+3} - 33$:= $4^4 + (444 - 4)$:= $5 + (((55 + 5^5)/5) + 55)$:= $6 \times 6 + (666 - 6)$:= $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + (77 - 7)/7$:= $8 \times 88 - 8$:= $(9 - 9/9) \times (99 - ((99 + 9)/9))$</p>	<p>▶ 699 := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111)$:= $2 + ((22/2)^2 + ((22 + 2)^2))$:= $3 + (3^{3+3} - 33)$:= $4^4 + (444 - 4/4)$:= $(5^5 - 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))$:= $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6 \times 6)$:= $777 - (7/7 + 77)$:= $88/8 + (8 \times 88 - (8 + 8))$:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 999/9$</p>

▶ 700 := $1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111)$	▶ 703 := $(11 \times ((1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)})) - 1$	▶ 706 := $1 + 1 + 11 \times ((1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)})$
:= $2 \times ((22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2)$	:= $(2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2})) - 2/2$	:= $222 + 22^2$
:= $3 + ((3^{3+3} - 33) + 3/3)$	:= $3/3 + (3^{3+3} - 3^3)$	:= $3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3^3) + 3/3)$
:= $4^4 + 444$	:= $4 \times 4 \times 44 - 4/4$	:= $(4 + 4)/4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44$
:= $5 \times (((5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5) + 5) + 5)$	:= $5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 55)$	:= $5 \times 5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 + 55)$
:= $6 \times 6 + (666 - ((6 + 6)/6))$	:= $6 \times 6 + (666 + 6/6)$	:= $6 + ((666 - ((6 + 6)/6)) + 6 \times 6)$
:= $777 - 77$	:= $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + ((77 - 7)/7))$	:= $7 + (777 - (7/7 + 77))$
:= $8 \times 88 - (8/((8 + 8)/8))$	:= $8 \times 88 - 8/8$	:= $(8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 88$
:= $(9/9 + 9) \times (9 \times 9 - 99/9)$	:= $9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9))$	:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((99 + 99 + 9)/9)$

▶ 701 := $1 + 1 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + (1 + 1) \times 111)$	▶ 704 := $11 \times ((1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)})$	▶ 707 := $(11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 11 - 11$
:= $2/2 + (2 \times ((22 \times 2^{2+2}) - 2))$	:= $2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2})$	:= $2/2 + (222 + 22^2)$
:= $3^{3+3} - (3^3 + 3/3)$	:= $33/3 \times ((3/3 + 3)^3)$	:= $3 + (33/3 \times ((3/3 + 3)^3))$
:= $4/4 + (444 + 4^4)$	:= $4 \times (4 \times 44)$	:= $4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 - 4/4$
:= $(5^5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))$	:= $5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 + 55)$	:= $5 \times 5 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 + 55)$
:= $6 \times 6 + (666 - 6/6)$	:= $(66/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6$	:= $6 + ((666 - 6/6) + 6 \times 6)$
:= $7/7 + (777 - 77)$	:= $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + (77/7))$	:= $7 + (777 - 77)$
:= $8 + (8 \times 88 - (88/8))$	:= 8×88	:= $88/8 + (8 \times 88 - 8)$
:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9/9 + 9 + 9) + 9)$	:= $(9 - 9/9) \times (99 - (99/9))$	:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((99 + 99)/9)$

▶ 702 := $(1 + 1) \times ((11 \times ((11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)) - 1)) - 1)$	▶ 705 := $1 + 11 \times ((1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)})$	▶ 708 := $(1 + 11) \times ((11^{1+1} - 1)/(1 + 1) - 1)$
:= $(2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2})) - 2$	:= $2/2 + (2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2}))$	:= $2 + (222 + 22^2)$
:= $3^{3+3} - 3^3$	:= $3 + (3^{3+3} - 3^3)$	:= $3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3^3) + 3)$
:= $4 \times 4 \times 44 - (4 + 4)/4$	:= $4/4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44$	:= $4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44$
:= $55 + (((55 + 55) + 5^5)/5)$	:= $5 \times 5 + (5^5/5 + 55)$	:= $((55 + 5)/5) \times (55 - 5/5 + 5)$
:= $6 \times 6 + 666$	:= $((66 \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6) + 6)/6$	:= $6 + (666 + 6 \times 6)$
:= $((7 + 7)/7) + (777 - 77)$	:= $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + (77 + 7)/7)$	:= $7 + ((777 - 77) + 7/7)$
:= $8 \times 88 - (8 + 8)/8$	:= $8/8 + 8 \times 88$	:= $8 \times 88 + (8/((8 + 8)/8))$
:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)$	:= $9 + ((9 - 9/9) \times (99 - ((99 + 9)/9)))$	:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (((99 + 9)/9) + 9)$

<p>▶ 709 := $11 \times 111 - (1 + 1)^{11-1-1}$:= $2 + ((222 + 22^2) + 2/2)$:= $3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 3 \times 3)$:= $4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + 4/4$:= $5 + (((5^5 - 5)/5 + 55) + 5 \times 5)$:= $6 + ((666 + 6/6) + 6 \times 6)$:= $7 + (((7 + 7)/7 - 77) + 777)$:= $8 + ((8 \times 88 - (88/8)) + 8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99/9 + 9)$</p>	<p>▶ 712 := $1 + (1111 - (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}))$:= $2 \times (((22 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2) + 2)$:= $3/3 + (3^{3+3} - (3 \times (3 + 3)))$:= $4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + 4$:= $55 + (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5^5/5)$:= $6 \times 6 + ((66 - 6)/6 + 666)$:= $777 + ((77 + 7)/7 - 77)$:= $8 + 8 \times 88$:= $9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9))$</p>	<p>▶ 715 := $11 \times (1 + ((1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}))$:= $22/2 + (2 \times (22 \times 2^{2+2}))$:= $3^{3+3} - (33/3 + 3)$:= $44/4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44$:= $55 \times (55 + 5 + 5)/5$:= $(66/6) \times (66 - 6/6)$:= $7 + (((777 - 77) + 7/7) + 7)$:= $88/8 + 8 \times 88$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 - 99)/(9 + 9)) - 9)$</p>
<p>▶ 710 := $(11 - 1) \times ((1 + 11)^{1+1}/(1 + 1) - 1)$:= $2 + ((222 + 22^2) + 2)$:= $3^{3+3} - ((3 \times (3 + 3)) + 3/3)$:= $4 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + (4 + 4)/4$:= $5 + ((5^5/5 + 55) + 5 \times 5)$:= $6 + ((66/6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6)$:= $777 + (((77 - 7)/7) - 77)$:= $8 + (8 \times 88 - ((8 + 8)/8))$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9/9 + 9 + 9)$</p>	<p>▶ 713 := $(1 + 11 + 11) \times (1 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))$:= $((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) - 2^{2+2}$:= $3^{3+3} + (33/3 - 3^3)$:= $4 + (4 \times 4 \times 44 + 4/4) + 4$:= $(55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) - (5 + 5))/5$:= $6 \times 6 + (666 + (66/6))$:= $7 + ((777 - (7/7 + 77)) + 7)$:= $8 + (8 \times 88 + 8/8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9) - (9 + 9))$</p>	<p>▶ 716 := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (1 + 11^{1+1+1})$:= $2 + ((2 + 2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 - 2))$:= $3^{3+3} + (((3 - 33)/3) - 3)$:= $(4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4$:= $(55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5)/5$:= $((66 \times (66 - 6/6)) + 6)/6$:= $7 \times (77 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$:= $8 \times 88 + (88 + 8)/8$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)$</p>
<p>▶ 711 := $1111 - ((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}$:= $(2222/2) - (22 - 2)^2$:= $3^{3+3} - (3 \times (3 + 3))$:= $4 + (4 \times 4 \times 44 - 4/4) + 4$:= $((555 + 5^5)/5) - 5 \times 5$:= $((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6 - 6 - 6$:= $77/7 + (777 - 77)$:= $8 + (8 \times 88 - 8/8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)$</p>	<p>▶ 714 := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1)))$:= $(2 + 2 + 2) \times ((22/2)^2 - 2)$:= $3 + (3^{3+3} - (3 \times (3 + 3)))$:= $4 \times 4 \times 44 + (44 - 4)/4$:= $(55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) - 5)/5$:= $(6 + 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6$:= $7 + ((777 - 77) + 7)$:= $8 + ((8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 88)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - (9 + 9))$</p>	<p>▶ 717 := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - 11^{1+1+1}$:= $222 + (22/2 + 22^2)$:= $3^{3+3} - (3 \times 3 + 3)$:= $4/4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4)$:= $((55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5) + 5)/5$:= $((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6 - 6$:= $777 - (77/7 + 7 \times 7)$:= $8 \times 88 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9$</p>

<p>► 718 := $(11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 11$:= $2 \times (((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2) - 2)$:= $3^{3+3} - 33/3$:= $(4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - (4 + 4)/4$:= $5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - ((5 + 5)/5)^5$:= $(6 + 6) \times (66 - 6) - (6 + 6)/6$:= $7 + ((77/7 - 77) + 777)$:= $8 + ((8 \times 88 - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - 99/9$</p>	<p>► 721 := $(111 + 11^{1+1+1})/(1 + 1)$:= $((((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)^2) - 2)/2$:= $3 + (3^{3+3} - 33/3)$:= $4/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4))$:= $((55 + 5)^{(5+5)/5} + 5)/5$:= $6/6 + (6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)$:= $777 - (7 \times 7 + 7)$:= $8 + ((8 \times 88 + 8/8) + 8)$:= $9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9)$</p>	<p>► 724 := $(1 + 1) \times ((11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))) - 1)$:= $2 + (2 \times ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2))$:= $3/3 + (3^{3+3} - (3 + 3))$:= $4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4))$:= $(5^5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$:= $(66 \times 66 - 6 - 6)/6$:= $(7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - 77/7$:= $8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))$</p>
<p>► 719 := $1 + ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 11)$:= $((22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2$:= $3^{3+3} + ((3 - 33)/3)$:= $(4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4/4$:= $((55 + 5)^{(5+5)/5} - 5)/5$:= $(6 + 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6/6$:= $777 - (((7 + 7)/7 + 7 \times 7) + 7)$:= $8 + ((8 \times 88 - 8/8) + 8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9 - 9$</p>	<p>► 722 := $(1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)) - 1)^{1+1}$:= $2 \times ((22 - (2/2 + 2))^2)$:= $3^{3+3} - ((3/3 + 3) + 3)$:= $(4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4))$:= $((55 + 5)^{(5+5)/5} + 5) + 5)/5$:= $(6 + 6)/6 + (6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)$:= $7/7 + (777 - (7 \times 7 + 7))$:= $8 + (((8 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88) + 8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9) - 9)$</p>	<p>► 725 := $((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)))) - 1$:= $22^2 + (22^2 - 2)/2$:= $3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 3)$:= $4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) + 4/4)$:= $5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5)$:= $(66 \times 66 - 6)/6$:= $777 - (((7 + 7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times 7)$:= $8 + ((88 + 8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 88)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))$</p>
<p>► 720 := $(1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1))$:= $(22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$:= $3^{3+3} - 3 \times 3$:= $4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)$:= $(5/5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 \times 5 - 5)$:= $(6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)$:= $777 - ((7/7 + 7 \times 7) + 7)$:= $8 + (8 \times 88 + 8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9$</p>	<p>► 723 := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times 11^{1+1}) - 1)$:= $(2/2 + 2) \times (22^2 - 2)/2$:= $3^{3+3} - (3 + 3)$:= $4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4/4)$:= $5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5$:= $((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6$:= $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7) + ((7 + 7)/7)^7)$:= $8 + (88/8 + 8 \times 88)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - 9)$</p>	<p>► 726 := $(1 + 1) \times (11 \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)))$:= $22 \times (22/2 + 22)$:= $3^{3+3} - 3$:= $44/4 \times (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4)$:= $5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5))$:= $66 \times (66/6)$:= $(7 - 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7)$:= $8 \times 88 + (88 + 88)/8$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$</p>

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{727} &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 \\ &:= ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) - 2 \\ &:= 3/3 + (3^{3+3} - 3) \\ &:= 4 + (((4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) - 4/4) + 4) \\ &:= (5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5)) \\ &:= (66 \times 66 + 6)/6 \\ &:= 777 - (7/7 + 7 \times 7) \\ &:= 8 + (((8 \times 88 - 8/8) + 8) + 8) \\ &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (9 + 9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{730} &:= 1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} \\ &:= 2/2 + ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) \\ &:= 3/3 + 3^{3+3} \\ &:= 4 + (44/4 \times (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4)) \\ &:= 5 + (5 \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5)) \\ &:= 6/6 + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) \\ &:= ((7 + 7)/7) + (777 - 7 \times 7) \\ &:= 8 + (((((8 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88) + 8) + 8) \\ &:= 9/9 + 9 \times 9 \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{733} &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}))) \\ &:= 2 + (((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) + 2) \\ &:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3/3) \\ &:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4)^{4+(4+4)/4}) \\ &:= 55 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 55) \\ &:= 6 + ((66 \times 66 + 6)/6) \\ &:= (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - (7 + 7)/7 \\ &:= 8 + (((88 + 8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 88) + 8) \\ &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{728} &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 \\ &:= 2 + (22^2/2 + 22^2) \\ &:= 3^{3+3} - 3/3 \\ &:= 4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) + 4) \\ &:= (55 + 5/5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)/5 \\ &:= ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6/6 \\ &:= 777 - 7 \times 7 \\ &:= 8 + (8 \times 88 + 8 + 8) \\ &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{731} &:= 1 + (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}) \\ &:= 2 + ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) \\ &:= 3 + (3^{3+3} - 3/3) \\ &:= 44/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) + 4)) \\ &:= ((555 + 5^5)/5) - 5 \\ &:= 6 + ((66 \times 66 - 6)/6) \\ &:= 7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - (77/7)) \\ &:= 8 + ((88/8 + 8 \times 88) + 8) \\ &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9)/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{734} &:= (1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}))) \\ &:= 222 + (2^{(2/2+2)^2}) \\ &:= 3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3/3) + 3) \\ &:= (4 + 4)/4 \times (444/4 + 4^4) \\ &:= 5 + ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^{5/5+5}) \\ &:= 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6/6) \\ &:= (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - 7/7 \\ &:= 8 + ((88 + 88)/8 + 8 \times 88) \\ &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{729} &:= (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} \\ &:= (2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2} \\ &:= 3^{3+3} \\ &:= (4 - 4/4)^{4+(4+4)/4} \\ &:= (5 - (5 + 5)/5)^{5/5+5} \\ &:= (6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6 \\ &:= 7/7 + (777 - 7 \times 7) \\ &:= (8/8 + 8)^{88/8-8} \\ &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{732} &:= 1 + (1 + (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1})) \\ &:= (2/2 + 2) \times (22^2/2 + 2) \\ &:= 3 + 3^{3+3} \\ &:= 44 + (4 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)) \\ &:= (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5) - 5 \\ &:= 66 + 666 \\ &:= 77/7 + (777 - (7 \times 7 + 7)) \\ &:= 8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88) + 8) \\ &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{735} &:= (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11^{1+1}))) \\ &:= 2 + (((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) + 2) + 2) \\ &:= 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3) \\ &:= (4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 - 44/4) \\ &:= 55 + (5^5/5 + 55) \\ &:= 6 + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) \\ &:= 7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7) \\ &:= 8 + (((8 \times 88 - 8/8) + 8) + 8) + 8) \\ &:= 9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) \end{aligned}$$

► **736** := $111 + (1 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))^{1+1}$
 := $2^{2+2} \times ((2 \times 22) + 2)$
 := $3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3/3) + 3)$
 := $4 \times (((4 \times 44) + 4) + 4)$
 := $(555 + 5^5)/5$
 := $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6/6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7))$
 := $8 + ((8 \times 88 + 8 + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9))$

► **739** := $11 + ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1)$
 := $22^2 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)} - 2/2)$
 := $3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} + 3/3)$
 := $4^4 + ((44 \times 44 - 4)/4)$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 55)/5)$
 := $6 + (((66 \times 66 + 6)/6) + 6)$
 := $77/7 + (777 - 7 \times 7)$
 := $8 + (((88/8 + 8 \times 88) + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9/9)$

► **742** := $1 + (1 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}))$
 := $2 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22^2)$
 := $3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3/3) + 3 \times 3)$
 := $4^4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4) + 4)/4)$
 := $5 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5)$
 := $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6/6) + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7))$
 := $8 + (((88 + 88)/8 + 8 \times 88) + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)$

► **737** := $11 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))))$
 := $2/2 + (2^{2+2} \times ((2 \times 22) + 2))$
 := $3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} - 3/3)$
 := $4/4 + (4 \times (((4 \times 44) + 4) + 4))$
 := $((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5$
 := $(66/6) \times (66 + 6/6)$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7))$
 := $8 + ((8/8 + 8)^{88/8-8})$
 := $9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9)$

► **740** := $11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $22^2 + 2^{2 \times (2+2)}$
 := $3^{3+3} + 33/3$
 := $4 + (4 \times (((4 \times 44) + 4) + 4))$
 := $5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5 - 5$
 := $66/6 + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times 88 + ((8 \times 8 + 8)/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99/9)$

► **743** := $1 + (1 + (1 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1})))$
 := $2 + ((2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22^2) + 2/2)$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} + 33/3)$
 := $4 + (((44 \times 44 - 4)/4) + 4^4)$
 := $5 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5) + 5)/5)$
 := $6 + ((66/6) \times (66 + 6/6))$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) + 7/7)$
 := $888/8 + (8 \times (88 - 8) - 8)$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \times 9 \times 9)$

► **738** := $1 + (11 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))))$
 := $2 + (2^{2+2} \times ((2 \times 22) + 2))$
 := $3 \times 3 + 3^{3+3}$
 := $4^4 + ((44 \times 44 - (4 + 4))/4)$
 := $((555 + 5^5) + 5) + 5)/5$
 := $6 + (666 + 66)$
 := $777 + (((77 - 7)/7) - 7 \times 7)$
 := $(8/8 + 8) \times (((8 + 8)/8) - 8) + 88)$
 := $9 + 9 \times 9 \times 9$

► **741** := $1 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1})$
 := $2/2 + (2^{2 \times (2+2)} + 22^2)$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} + 3 \times 3)$
 := $4^4 + ((44 \times 44 + 4)/4)$
 := $5 + ((555 + 5^5)/5)$
 := $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - 7/7)$
 := $8 \times 88 + 888/(8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99 + 9)/9$

► **744** := $(1 + 11) \times (1 + ((1 + 11^{1+1})/(1 + 1)))$
 := $(2 \times 22^2) - (222 + 2)$
 := $3 + ((3^{3+3} + 3 \times 3) + 3)$
 := $44 + (444 + 4^4)$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 5)$
 := $6 + ((666 + 66) + 6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) + ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 \times (88 + 8) - 8 - 8 - 8$
 := $9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$

<p>► 745 := $(1 + (1 + (1 + ((1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))))/11$:= $2^{2+2} + ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2})$:= $3^3 + (3^{3+3} - 33/3)$:= $4 + (((44 \times 44 + 4)/4) + 4^4)$:= $5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5) - 5$:= $6 + (((66 \times 66 + 6)/6) + 6) + 6$:= $777 - ((77/7 + 7 + 7) + 7)$:= $8 + (((8/8 + 8)^{88/8-8}) + 8)$:= $9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 748 := $(1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))))$:= $22 \times ((2 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2)$:= $3/3 + (3^{3+3} + (3 \times (3 + 3)))$:= $44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44$:= $5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5$:= $(66/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66)$:= $7 + (((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - 7/7) + 7)$:= $8 \times 88 + (88/((8 + 8)/8))$:= $9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9/9) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 751 := $11 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1})$:= $22 + ((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2})$:= $33 + (3^{3+3} - 33/3)$:= $(4 \times (4^4 - 4)) - (4/4 + 4^4)$:= $5/5 + 5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5)$:= $6 \times 6 + ((66/6) \times (66 - 6/6))$:= $777 - ((77 + 7)/7 + 7 + 7)$:= $888/8 + 8 \times (88 - 8)$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((99 + 99)/9)$</p>
<p>► 746 := $(1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - 111)$:= $(2 \times 22^2) - 222$:= $3 + ((3^{3+3} + 33/3) + 3)$:= $44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 - (4 + 4)/4$:= $5 + (((555 + 5^5)/5) + 5)$:= $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + (66/6))$:= $77/7 + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7))$:= $8 \times (88 + 8) - (88 + 88)/8$:= $9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9) + 9)$</p>	<p>► 749 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))))$:= $22 + (((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) - 2)$:= $3 \times 3 + (3^{3+3} + 33/3)$:= $44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + 4/4$:= $5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 - 5)/5$:= $6 + (((66/6) \times (66 + 6/6)) + 6)$:= $7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) + 7)$:= $8 \times (88 + 8) - (88/8 + 8)$:= $9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99/9))$</p>	<p>► 752 := $1 + (11 + (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}))$:= $2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - (22 + 2))$:= $3^3 + (3^{3+3} - (3/3 + 3))$:= $4 \times (444 - 4^4)$:= $5 \times 5 \times 5 + (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5$:= $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + (66/6)) + 6$:= $777 - (77/7 + 7 + 7)$:= $8 \times (88 + 8) - 8 - 8$:= $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((99 + 99 + 9)/9)$</p>
<p>► 747 := $((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))))$:= $2/2 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 222)$:= $3 \times ((3 + 3)^3 + 33)$:= $44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 - 4/4$:= $((555 + 55) + 5^5)/5$:= $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6) + 6$:= $(77 + 7)/7 + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7))$:= $(8/8 + 8) \times ((88/8 + 8 \times 8) + 8)$:= $9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 750 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (11 \times (1 + (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))))$:= $2 + (22 \times ((2 \times 2^{2+2}) + 2))$:= $3 + (3^{3+3} + (3 \times (3 + 3)))$:= $44 + 4 \times 4 \times 44 + (4 + 4)/4$:= $5 \times 5 \times (5 \times 5 + 5)$:= $66 \times (6 + 6) - (6 \times 6 + 6)$:= $(7/7 + 7 + 7) \times (7/7 + 7 \times 7)$:= $(8 - 88)/8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) - 8)$:= $9 + (((99 + 9)/9) + 9 \times 9 \times 9)$</p>	<p>► 753 := $((1 + 11)^{1+1+1})/(1 + 1) - 111$:= $2 + (((2/2 + 2)^{2+2+2}) + 22)$:= $3^3 + (3^{3+3} - 3)$:= $4/4 + (4 \times (444 - 4^4))$:= $5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 5 \times 5)$:= $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6) + 6) + 6$:= $7 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) + (77/7))$:= $8/8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8))$:= $9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9) + 9)$</p>

▶ 754 := 1 + (((1 + 11) ¹⁺¹⁺¹)/(1 + 1)) - 111	▶ 757 := 1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) × ((1 + 11) × (11 + (11	▶ 760 := 1 + (11 × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + (11 + 11))))
:= (2 × ((22 - 2) ² - 22)) - 2	:= 2/2 + (2 × ((22 - 2) ² - 22))	:= 2 × (((22 - 2) ² - 22) + 2)
:= 3 ³ + ((3 ³⁺³ - 3) + 3/3)	:= 3 ³ + (3 ³⁺³ + 3/3)	:= 3 + ((3 ³⁺³ + 3/3) + 3 ³)
:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4 × (444 - 4 ⁴))	:= 4/4 + ((4 - 4/4) × (4 ⁴ - 4))	:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4) × (4 ⁴ - 4))
:= 5 + ((5 ⁵ - 5)/5 + 5 × 5 × 5)	:= 5 + (5 × 5 × (5 × 5 + 5) + ((5 + 5)/5))	:= 5 + (5 × 5 × (5 × 5 + 5) + 5)
:= 6 + ((66/6) × (((6 + 6)/6) + 66))	:= 6/6 + (6 × ((66 - 6) + 66))	:= 6 × 6 + ((66 × 66 - 6 - 6)/6)
:= 777 - (((7 + 7)/7 + 7) + 7) + 7)	:= 7/7 + (777 - (7 + 7 + 7))	:= 777 + (((7 - 77)/7) - 7)
:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 × (88 + 8) - (8 + 8))	:= 8 × (88 + 8) - 88/8	:= 8 × (88 + 8) - 8
:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) + 9) + 9)	:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 + 9/9) + 9) + 9)	:= 9 + (((99 + 99)/9) + 9 × 9 × 9)

▶ 755 := 11 ¹⁺¹⁺¹ - (((1 + 1) × (1 + 11)) ¹⁺¹)	▶ 758 := (11 × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + (11 + 11)))) - 1	▶ 761 := 1 + (1 + (11 × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + (11 + 11))))))
:= (2 × ((22 - 2) ² - 22)) - 2/2	:= 2 + (2 × ((22 - 2) ² - 22))	:= 2 + ((2/2 + 2) × ((22 ² + 22)/2))
:= 3 ³ + (3 ³⁺³ - 3/3)	:= 3 + ((3 ³⁺³ - 3/3) + 3 ³)	:= 33 + (3 ³⁺³ - 3/3)
:= ((4 - 4/4) × (4 ⁴ - 4)) - 4/4	:= (4 + 4)/4 + ((4 - 4/4) × (4 ⁴ - 4))	:= ((4 - 4/4) × (4 ⁴ - 4/4)) - 4
:= 5 + 5 × 5 × (5 × 5 + 5)	:= 5 + (((5 ⁵ - 5 - 5)/5 + 5 × 5 × 5) + 5)	:= 5 × 5 + ((555 + 5 ⁵)/5)
:= 66 × (6 + 6) - (6 × 6 + 6/6)	:= (6 + 6)/6 + (6 × ((66 - 6) + 66))	:= 6 × 6 + ((66 × 66 - 6)/6)
:= 777 - (7/7 + 7 + 7 + 7)	:= 777 - ((77 + 7)/7 + 7)	:= 777 - (((7 + 7)/7 + 7) + 7)
:= 8 × (88 + 8) - (88 + 8 + 8)/8	:= (8 - 88)/8 + 8 × (88 + 8)	:= 8/8 + (8 × (88 + 8) - 8)
:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9)	:= 9 + ((9 × 9 × 9 + (99/9)) + 9)	:= ((99/9) × (9 × 9 - (99/9))) - 9

▶ 756 := (1 + 1 + 1) × ((1 + 11) × (11 + (11 - 1)))	▶ 759 := 11 × ((1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + (11 + 11)))	▶ 762 := (1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + (11 × (1 + (11 + 11))))
:= 2 × ((22 - 2) ² - 22)	:= (2/2 + 2) × ((22 ² + 22)/2)	:= (2/2 + 2) × (2 ^{2×(2+2)} - 2)
:= 3 ³ + 3 ³⁺³	:= 3 + (3 ³⁺³ + 3 ³)	:= 33 + 3 ³⁺³
:= (4 - 4/4) × (4 ⁴ - 4)	:= (4 - 4/4) × ((4/4 - 4) + 4 ⁴)	:= (4 - 4/4) × (4 ⁴ - (4 + 4)/4)
:= 5 + (5 × 5 × (5 × 5 + 5) + 5/5)	:= 5 + (((5 ⁵ - 5)/5 + 5 × 5 × 5) + 5)	:= 5 × 5 + (((555 + 5 ⁵) + 5)/5)
:= 6 × ((66 - 6) + 66)	:= 6 × 6 + (((6 × 6/(6 + 6)) ⁶) - 6)	:= 6 + (6 × ((66 - 6) + 66))
:= 777 - (7 + 7 + 7)	:= 777 - (77/7 + 7)	:= 777 - (7/7 + 7 + 7)
:= 8 × (88 + 8) - (88 + 8)/8	:= 8 × (88 + 8) - (8/8 + 8)	:= (8 + 8)/8 + (8 × (88 + 8) - 8)
:= 9 + ((9 × 9 × 9 + 9) + 9)	:= 9 × (9 × 9 - 9) + 999/9	:= 9 × 9 × 9 + (99/((9 + 9 + 9)/9))

▶ 763 := (111 - 1 - 1) × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)))	766 := (111 × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)))) - 1	▶ 769 := 1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + 1) ^{(1+1)×(1+1+1)})
:= 2/2 + ((2/2 + 2) × (2 ^{2×(2+2)} - 2))	:= (2 × (2 ²⁺² × (22 + 2))) - 2	:= 2/2 + (2 × (2 ²⁺² × (22 + 2)))
:= 3/3 + (3 ³⁺³ + 33)	:= 3 + ((3 ³⁺³ + 3/3) + 33)	:= 3 + (((3 ³⁺³ + 3/3) + 33) + 3)
:= 4 × 4 ⁴ - ((4/4 + 4 ⁴) + 4)	:= 4 × 4 ⁴ - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4 ⁴)	:= 4/4 + (4 × (4 × (44 + 4)))
:= 555 + ((5 ⁵ - 5)/(5 + 5 + 5))	:= 5 + (((555 + 5 ⁵)/5) + 5 × 5)	:= (5 × (5 - 55)) + ((5 - 5/5) ⁵ - 5)
:= 6 × 6 + ((66 × 66 + 6)/6)	:= 6 × 6 + (((6 × 6/(6 + 6)) ⁶) + 6/6)	:= 6/6 + ((6 + 6) × ((6 + 6)/6) ⁶)
:= 777 - (7 + 7)	:= 777 - 77/7	:= 777 - (7/7 + 7)
:= 88/8 + (8 × (88 + 8) - (8 + 8))	:= 8 × (88 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8	:= 8/8 + 8 × (88 + 8)
:= (9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) × (9/9 + 99 + 9)	:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 + 9/9) + 9) + 9) + 9	:= 9 × 9 × 9 + ((9 × 9 × 9 - 9)/(9 + 9))

▶ 764 := 1 + ((111 - 1 - 1) × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1))))	767 := ((1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + 1) ^{(1+1)×(1+1+1)}) - 1	▶ 770 := 11 × ((11 - 1 - 1) ¹⁺¹ - 11)
:= 2 × ((2 ²⁺² × (22 + 2)) - 2)	:= (2 × 2 × 222) - (22/2) ²	:= 2 + (2 × (2 ²⁺² × (22 + 2)))
:= 3 + ((3 ³⁺³ - 3/3) + 33)	:= 3 ³ + (3 ³⁺³ + 33/3)	:= 3 + ((3 ³⁺³ + 33/3) + 3 ³)
:= 4 × 4 ⁴ - (4 ⁴ + 4)	:= 4 × 4 ⁴ - (4/4 + 4 ⁴)	:= (4 + 4)/4 + (4 × (4 × (44 + 4)))
:= 5 × (5 × 5 + 5) + ((5 ⁵ - 55)/5)	:= 5 + (((555 + 5 ⁵) + 5)/5) + 5 × 5	:= 55 × ((5 - 5/5 + 5) + 5)
:= 6 × 6 + (((6 × 6/(6 + 6)) ⁶) - 6/6)	:= ((6 + 6) × ((6 + 6)/6) ⁶) - 6/6	:= (6/6 + 6) × ((666 - 6)/6)
:= 7/7 + (777 - (7 + 7))	:= 777 + (7 - 77)/7	:= 777 - 7
:= 8 × (88 + 8) - (8/((8 + 8)/8))	:= 8 × (88 + 8) - 8/8	:= (8 + 8)/8 + 8 × (88 + 8)
:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 - 9/9) + 9) + 9) + 9	:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 + (99/9)) + 9) + 9)	:= 99/9 × (9 × 9 - 99/9)

▶ 765 := (1 + 1 + 1) × (111 + ((1 + 11) ¹⁺¹))	▶ 768 := (1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + 1) ^{(1+1)×(1+1+1)}	▶ 771 := 1 + (11 × ((11 - 1 - 1) ¹⁺¹ - 11))
:= (2/2 + 2) × (2 ^{2×(2+2)} - 2/2)	:= 2 × (2 ²⁺² × (22 + 2))	:= 22 ² + (((22 + 2) ²) - 2)/2
:= 3 + (3 ³⁺³ + 33)	:= 3 + ((3 ³⁺³ + 33) + 3)	:= 3 × 3 + (3 ³⁺³ + 33)
:= (4 - 4/4) × (4 ⁴ - 4/4)	:= 4 × (4 × (44 + 4))	:= (4 - 4/4) × (4/4 + 4 ⁴)
:= 5 + ((5 × 5 × (5 × 5 + 5) + 5) + 5)	:= (5 × 5 - 5/5) × ((5 + 5)/5) ⁵	:= 5/5 + (55 × ((5 - 5/5 + 5) + 5))
:= 6 × 6 + ((6 × 6/(6 + 6)) ⁶)	:= (6 + 6) × ((6 + 6)/6) ⁶	:= 6 + (((6 × 6/(6 + 6)) ⁶) + 6 × 6)
:= 777 - (77 + 7)/7	:= (7 - 7/7) × ((7 + 7)/7) ⁷	:= 7/7 + (777 - 7)
:= 8 + (8 × (88 + 8) - (88/8))	:= 8 × (88 + 8)	:= 88/8 + (8 × (88 + 8) - 8)
:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 + 9) + 9) + 9)	:= 9 + (9 × (9 × 9 - 9) + 999/9)	:= 9 × 99 - (999/9 + 9)

▶ 772 := 1 + (1 + (11 × ((11 - 1 - 1) ¹⁺¹ - 11)))	▶ 775 := 1111 - ((1 + 1 + 1) × (1 + 111))	▶ 778 := 1 + (111 × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1))))
:= 2 × ((2 ²⁺² × (22 + 2)) + 2)	:= 2 + (((2 ²⁺² + 2/2) ²) + 22 ²)	:= (2 × (22 - 2) ²) - 22
:= 3 × 3 + ((3 ³⁺³ + 3/3) + 33)	:= 3333/3 - (333 + 3)	:= 3333/3 - 333
:= 4 + (4 × (4 × (44 + 4)))	:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4) × (4/4 + 4 ⁴))	:= 4 + ((4 - 4/4) × ((4 + 4)/4 + 4 ⁴))
:= (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) × 555/5) - 5	:= 5 × (5 × (5 × 5 + 5) + 5)	:= ((5 ⁵ - 5)/(5 - 5/5)) - (5 + 5)/5
:= 666 + ((666 + 6)/6 - 6)	:= 66 × (6 + 6) - ((66/6) + 6)	:= 666 + (666 + 6)/6
:= ((7 + 7)/7) + (777 - 7)	:= 777 - (7 + 7)/7	:= 7/7 + 777
:= 8 × (88 + 8) + (8/((8 + 8)/8))	:= 8 + (8 × (88 + 8) - 8/8)	:= 8 + (8 × (88 + 8) + ((8 + 8)/8))
:= 9 × 99 + (((9 - 999)/9) - 9)	:= ((9 - 9/9) × (99 - 9/9)) - 9	:= 9 × 9 × 9 + ((9 × 99 - 9)/(9 + 9))

▶ 773 := ((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹)) ¹⁺¹) - 11	▶ 776 := (111 × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)))) - 1	▶ 779 := 1 + (1 + (111 × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)))))
:= (2 × 22) + ((2/2 + 2) ²⁺²⁺²)	:= 2 × (2 × (((2 ²⁺² - 2) ²) - 2))	:= 2/2 + ((2 × (22 - 2) ²) - 22)
:= 33 + (3 ³⁺³ + 33/3)	:= 3 + ((3 ³⁺³ + 33/3) + 33)	:= (33 × 3 ³) - ((333 + 3)/3)
:= 4 + ((4 × (4 × (44 + 4))) + 4/4)	:= 4 + ((4 × (4 × (44 + 4))) + 4)	:= 44/4 + (4 × (4 × (44 + 4)))
:= 5 + ((5 × 5 - 5/5) × ((5 + 5)/5) ⁵)	:= 5/5 + (5 × (5 × (5 × 5 + 5) + 5))	:= ((5 ⁵ - 5)/(5 - 5/5)) - 5/5
:= 6 + (((6 + 6) × ((6 + 6)/6) ⁶) - 6/6)	:= 666 + (666 - 6)/6	:= 66 × (6 + 6) - (6/6 + 6 + 6)
:= 7 + (777 - (77/7))	:= 777 - 7/7	:= ((7 + 7)/7) + 777
:= 8 + ((8 × (88 + 8) - (88/8)) + 8)	:= 8 + 8 × (88 + 8)	:= 88/8 + 8 × (88 + 8)
:= 99 + (((9 + 9)/9) ⁹) + 9 × (9 + 9)	:= (9 - 9/9) × (99 - ((9 + 9)/9))	:= 9 × 99 - ((999 + 9)/9)

▶ 774 := 1 + (((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹)) ¹⁺¹) - 11)	▶ 777 := 111 × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)))	▶ 780 := (11 - 1) × (111 - (11 × (1 + 1 + 1)))
:= (2/2 + 2) × (2 ^{2×(2+2)} + 2)	:= 222/2 × ((2/2 + 2 + 2) + 2)	:= 2 + ((2 × (22 - 2) ²) - 22)
:= 3 + ((3 ³⁺³ + 33) + 3 × 3)	:= (3 ³ × (3 ³ + 3)) - 33	:= (3 ³ + 3) × (3 ³ - 3/3)
:= (4 - 4/4) × ((4 + 4)/4 + 4 ⁴)	:= (4 - 4/4) × ((4 ⁴ - 4/4) + 4)	:= (4 - 4/4) × (4 ⁴ + 4)
:= (5 × (5 - 55)) + (5 - 5/5) ⁵	:= ((5 + 5)/5 + 5) × 555/5	:= (5 ⁵ - 5)/(5 - 5/5)
:= 6 + ((6 + 6) × ((6 + 6)/6) ⁶)	:= 666 + 666/6	:= (6 + 6) × (66 - 6/6)
:= 777 - (7 + 7 + 7)/7	:= 777	:= 777 + (7 + 7 + 7)/7
:= 8 + (8 × (88 + 8) - ((8 + 8)/8))	:= 8 + (8 × (88 + 8) + 8/8)	:= ((88 + 8)/8) + 8 × (88 + 8)
:= 9 × 99 - (99 + 9 + 9)	:= (9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) × 999/9	:= 9 × 99 - 999/9

<p>► 781 := $11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1}) / (1 + 1)) - 1$:= $((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2 - 2$:= $33/3 \times (((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3)$:= $4/4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 + 4))$:= $(5^5 - 5/5) / (5 - 5/5)$:= $66 \times (6 + 6) - 66/6$:= $77/7 + (777 - 7)$:= $88 + (8 \times 88 - (88/8))$:= $9 \times 99 + ((9 - 999)/9)$</p>	<p>► 784 := $(1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1}$:= $(22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2$:= $(3^3 + 3/3)^{3-3/3}$:= $4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4)$:= $(55/5 + 5^5) / (5 - 5/5)$:= $(6/6 + 6) \times (666 + 6)/6$:= $7 + 777$:= $8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) + 8)$:= $(9 - 9/9) \times (99 - 9/9)$</p>	<p>► 787 := $111 + (((1 + 1) \times (1 + (1 + 11)))^{1+1})$:= $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2/2)$:= $3 + ((3^3 + 3/3)^{3-3/3})$:= $4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times ((4/4 + 4^4) + 4))$:= $5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times 555/5) + 5$:= $6/6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - 6)$:= $777 + (77 - 7)/7$:= $8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) + (88/8))$:= $9999/9 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)$</p>
<p>► 782 := $1 + (11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1}) / (1 + 1)) - 1)$:= $((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2$:= $3^3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3/3) + 3^3)$:= $(4 + 4)/4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 + 4))$:= $5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times 555/5)$:= $((6 - 66)/6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)$:= $7 + (777 - ((7 + 7)/7))$:= $8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8) - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)$:= $9 \times 99 - (9/9 + 99 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 785 := $1 + ((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1})$:= $2/2 + ((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2)$:= $3/3 + ((3^3 + 3/3)^{3-3/3})$:= $4/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4))$:= $5 + ((5^5 - 5) / (5 - 5/5))$:= $66 \times (6 + 6) - 6/6 - 6$:= $7 + (777 + 7/7)$:= $8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8) + 8/8) + 8)$:= $9 + ((9 - 9/9) \times (99 - ((9 + 9)/9)))$</p>	<p>► 788 := $11 + (111 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))))$:= $2 + (((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) + 2)$:= $(33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - (3/3 + 3)$:= $4 + (4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4))$:= $5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5^5) + 5) / (5 - 5/5)$:= $(6 + 6)/6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - 6)$:= $77/7 + 777$:= $8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times (88 + 8))$:= $9 + (9 \times 99 - ((999 + 9)/9))$</p>
<p>► 783 := $((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1}) - 1$:= $((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2$:= $3 \times (3 \times (3 \times 3^3 + 3 + 3))$:= $(4 - 4/4) \times ((4/4 + 4^4) + 4)$:= $((5 + 5)/5 + 5^5) + 5 / (5 - 5/5)$:= $6 + (666/6 + 666)$:= $7 + (777 - 7/7)$:= $(8/8 + 8) \times (88 - 8/8)$:= $9 \times 99 - (99 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 786 := $1 + (1 + ((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1}))$:= $2 + ((22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2)$:= $(33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - (3 + 3)$:= $(4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4))$:= $5 + ((5^5 - 5/5) / (5 - 5/5))$:= $66 \times (6 + 6) - 6$:= $7 + (((7 + 7)/7) + 777)$:= $8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8) + ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)$:= $9 + ((9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) \times 999/9)$</p>	<p>► 789 := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + 11)))) - 1$:= $(2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 22/2$:= $(33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3$:= $4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4)) + 4/4)$:= $5 + ((55/5 + 5^5) / (5 - 5/5))$:= $66 + (((6 \times 6 / (6 + 6))^6) - 6)$:= $777 + (77 + 7)/7$:= $888 - (88/8 + 88)$:= $9 + (9 \times 99 - 999/9)$</p>

<p>► 790 := $(1 + 1) \times ((11 \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)))$:= $(22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2$:= $3/3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3)$:= $4 + ((4 \times ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + 4)) + (4 + 4)/4)$:= $5 + (((5^5 - 5)/(5 - 5/5)) + 5)$:= $66 \times (6 + 6) - (6 + 6)/6$:= $7 + ((777 - 7/7) + 7)$:= $88 + (8 \times 88 - ((8 + 8)/8))$:= $9 \times 99 - ((9 + 9)/9 + 99)$</p>	<p>► 793 := $1 + (11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1)))$:= $2/2 + (22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2)$:= $3/3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3))$:= $4/4 + (44 \times ((4 + 4)/4 + 4 \times 4))$:= $555 + (((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) - 5)$:= $6/6 + 66 \times (6 + 6)$:= $7 + (((7 + 7)/7) + 777) + 7)$:= $8/8 + (8 \times 88 + 88)$:= $9/9 + (99 \times (9 - 9/9))$</p>	<p>► 796 := $(1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}) - (1 + 1)$:= $2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 2)$:= $3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3/3)$:= $444 + ((4 + 4) \times 44)$:= $5 + (((555 + 5^5)/5) + 55)$:= $6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - ((6 + 6)/6))$:= $7 + ((77 + 7)/7 + 777)$:= $88 + ((8/((8 + 8)/8)) + 8 \times 88)$:= $9 + (9999/9 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9))$</p>
<p>► 791 := $(11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1))) - 1$:= $(22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2$:= $(33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3/3$:= $44/4 + ((4 - 4/4) \times (4^4 + 4))$:= $55 + ((555 + 5^5)/5)$:= $66 \times (6 + 6) - 6/6$:= $7 + (777 + 7)$:= $88 + (8 \times 88 - 8/8)$:= $9 \times 99 - (9/9 + 99)$</p>	<p>► 794 := $1 + (1 + (11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1))))$:= $2 + (22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2)$:= $3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3/3)$:= $444 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - (4 + 4)/4)$:= $(5 \times (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)) - (5/5 + 5)$:= $(6 + 6)/6 + 66 \times (6 + 6)$:= $7 + (((77 - 7)/7) + 777)$:= $88 + ((8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times 88)$:= $(9 + 9)/9 + (99 \times (9 - 9/9))$</p>	<p>► 797 := $((11 \times (1 + ((1 + 11)^{1+1}))) - 1)/(1 + 1)$:= $2/2 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 2))$:= $3 + (((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3/3) + 3)$:= $(4 \times 44) + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4)$:= $5 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5) + 55)$:= $6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - 6/6)$:= $7 + (((777 - 7/7) + 7) + 7)$:= $8 + (888 - (88/8 + 88))$:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)$</p>
<p>► 792 := $11 \times (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1))$:= $22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$:= $33 \times (3^3 - 3)$:= $44 \times ((4 + 4)/4 + 4 \times 4)$:= $55 + (((555 + 5^5) + 5)/5)$:= $66 \times (6 + 6)$:= $7 + ((777 + 7/7) + 7)$:= $88 + 8 \times 88$:= $99 \times (9 - 9/9)$</p>	<p>► 795 := $11 + ((1 + ((1 + 1 + 1)^{1+1+1}))^{1+1})$:= $(2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 2)) - 2/2$:= $3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3))$:= $444 + (((4 + 4) \times 44) - 4/4)$:= $(55 + 5^5)/(5 - 5/5)$:= $66 + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6)$:= $7 + (77/7 + 777)$:= $8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8) + (88/8)) + 8)$:= $9 \times 99 + (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - 99)$</p>	<p>► 798 := $(1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}) - 1$:= $(2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 2$:= $3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3)$:= $(4 - 4/4) \times ((44 - 4)/4 + 4^4)$:= $555 + ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5)$:= $6 + 66 \times (6 + 6)$:= $7 + (777 + 7 + 7)$:= $888 - ((8 + 8)/8 + 88)$:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - (99 + 9)/9$</p>

▶ 799 := $((1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1})) - 1$	▶ 802 := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}))$	▶ 805 := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1 + (1 + 11)))$
:= $(2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 2/2$	:= $2 + (2 \times (22 - 2)^2)$	:= $2/2 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2))$
:= $(3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 33/3$	:= $3^{3+3} + (((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3)$	:= $3 + (((3 + 3)^3 + 3)/3) + 3^{3+3}$
:= $((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)) - 4/4$	:= $4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + (4 \times 44))$	:= $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + (4 \times 44))$
:= $(5 \times (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)) - 5/5$	:= $(5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5))$	:= $5 + (5 \times (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5))$
:= $6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + 6/6)$	:= $66 \times (6 + 6) + (66 - 6)/6$	:= $6 + ((66 \times (6 + 6) + 6/6) + 6)$
:= $7 + (((777 + 7/7) + 7) + 7)$	:= $7 + ((77/7 + 777) + 7)$	:= $7 + (777 + 7 + 7 + 7)$
:= $888 - (8/8 + 88)$	:= $888 + (((8 + 8)/8) - 88)$	:= $8 \times 88 + (8888/88)$
:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 99/9$	:= $9/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9)$	:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))$

▶ 800 := $(1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1})$	▶ 803 := $11 \times (1 + (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1)))$	▶ 806 := $1 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1 + (1 + 11))))$
:= $2 \times (22 - 2)^2$	:= $2 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) + 2/2)$	:= $2 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2))$
:= $3^{3+3} + (((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3)$	:= $33/3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3))$	:= $(3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - (3/3 + 3)$
:= $(4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)$	:= $4 + (((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)) - 4/4)$	:= $((44 - 4)/4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4) - 4$
:= $5 \times (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)$	:= $5 + (((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) + 555)$	:= $5 + ((5 \times (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)) + 5/5)$
:= $6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + ((6 + 6)/6))$	:= $66/6 + 66 \times (6 + 6)$	:= $6 + ((66 \times (6 + 6) + ((6 + 6)/6)) + 6)$
:= $7 + (((((7 + 7)/7) + 777) + 7) + 7)$	:= $7 + (((77 + 7)/7 + 777) + 7)$	:= $7 + (((777 + 7/7) + 7) + 7) + 7)$
:= $888 - 88$	:= $88 + (88/8 + 8 \times 88)$	:= $8 + (888 - ((8 + 8)/8 + 88))$
:= $(9 - 9/9) \times (9/9 + 99)$	:= $(9 + 9)/9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9)$	:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + ((9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))$

▶ 801 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}))$	▶ 804 := $1 + (11 \times (1 + (((1 + 11)^{1+1})/(1 + 1))))$	▶ 807 := $(1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (111 - 1))))/(1 + 1 + 1)$
:= $2/2 + (2 \times (22 - 2)^2)$	:= $2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2)$	:= $2 + ((2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2)) + 2/2)$
:= $3 \times ((3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 3))) - 3)$	:= $(3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - (3 + 3)$	:= $(3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 3$
:= $(4 \times 44) + (4/4 + 4)^4$	:= $4 + ((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4))$	:= $4 + (((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)) - 4/4) + 4)$
:= $5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5))$	:= $5 + ((5 \times (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)) - 5/5)$	:= $5 + ((5 \times (5 \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)) + ((5 + 5)/5))$
:= $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 66)$	:= $6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + 6)$	:= $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 66) + 6)$
:= $7 + (((77 - 7)/7) + 777) + 7)$	:= $7 + (((777 - 7/7) + 7) + 7) + 7)$	:= $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + (((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7)$
:= $8/8 + (888 - 88)$	:= $88 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 88)$	:= $8 + (888 - (8/8 + 88))$
:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9$	:= $9 \times 99 + (((99 + 9)/9) - 99)$	:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **808** := $(1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times (((22 - 2)^2 + 2) + 2)$
 := $3/3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 3)$
 := $4 + (((4 \times 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)) + 4)$
 := $5 + (((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) + 555) + 5)$
 := $6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + ((66 - 6)/6))$
 := $7 \times 7 + (777 - (77/7 + 7))$
 := $8 + (888 - 88)$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - (9 + 9)/9$

► **811** := $1 + (11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $22/2 + (2 \times (22 - 2)^2)$
 := $3/3 + (3^3 \times (3^3 + 3))$
 := $44 + (4 \times 4^4 - (4/4 + 4^4))$
 := $5/5 + ((5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5))$
 := $6 + (((66 \times (6 + 6) + 6/6) + 6) + 6)$
 := $77 + ((7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7)) - 7/7)$
 := $888 + (88/8 - 88)$
 := $9/9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)$

► **814** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 \times (111/(1 + 1 + 1)))$
 := $22 + (22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2)$
 := $3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) + 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((44 - 4)/4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4)$
 := $(55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - 55/5$
 := $(66/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66) + 6)$
 := $(7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 \times 88 + ((888 - 8)/8)$
 := $99/9 \times (((9 + 9)/9) - 9) + 9 \times 9)$

► **809** := $((11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}) - 1$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times (((22 - 2)^2 + 2) + 2))$
 := $(3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 3/3$
 := $4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 + (4 \times 44)) + 4)$
 := $(55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - (55/5 + 5)$
 := $6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + (66/6))$
 := $7 + (((77/7 + 777) + 7) + 7)$
 := $8 + ((888 - 88) + 8/8)$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9/9$

► **812** := $1 + 1 + (11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times (((22 - 2)^2 + 2) + 2) + 2)$
 := $3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 3/3)$
 := $44 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4)))$
 := $((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times (555/5 + 5)$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times (((666 - 6)/6) + 6)$
 := $77 + (7 \times (7 \times (7 + 7) + 7))$
 := $888 + ((88 + 8)/8 - 88)$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)$

► **815** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (111/(1 + 1 + 1))))$
 := $22/2 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2))$
 := $3 + (((3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 3/3) + 3)$
 := $4 \times 4 \times 44 + 444/4$
 := $(55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - 5 - 5$
 := $6 + ((66 \times (6 + 6) + (66/6)) + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 + (777 - (77/7))$
 := $8 \times 88 + 888/8$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + ((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **810** := $(11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (2 \times (((22 - 2)^2 + 2) + 2))$
 := $3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)$
 := $(44 - 4)/4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $(5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5)$
 := $6 + ((66 \times (6 + 6) + 6) + 6)$
 := $(7 - 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7)$
 := $(8/8 + 8) \times ((8 + 8)/8 + 88)$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)$

► **813** := $((1 + 1) \times (11 \times (111/(1 + 1 + 1)))) - 1$
 := $2 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) + 22/2)$
 := $3 + (3^3 \times (3^3 + 3))$
 := $44 + ((4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4))) + 4/4)$
 := $(55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - (55 + 5)/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + (666/6 + 666)$
 := $7/7 + ((777 - (7 + 7)) + 7 \times 7)$
 := $888 - (88/8 + 8 \times 8)$
 := $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)$

► **816** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1 + 111))$
 := $2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2 \times (2 + 2))$
 := $3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) + 3)$
 := $4 \times (4 \times (44 - 4) + 44)$
 := $5/5 + ((55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - (5 + 5))$
 := $(6 + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 66)$
 := $7 \times 7 + (((7 - 77)/7) + 777)$
 := $888 - (8 \times 8 + 8)$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times (999/9 - 9)$

<p>► 817 := $1 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1 + 111)))$:= $((22 + 2)^2) + (22^2 - 2)/2$:= $3 + (((3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) + 3/3) + 3)$:= $(4 \times (44 + 4)) + (4/4 + 4)^4$:= $5 + (((5 + 5)/5 + 5) \times (555/5 + 5))$:= $6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - (66/6))$:= $7 + ((7 - 7/7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7))$:= $8/8 + (888 - (8 \times 8 + 8))$:= $9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - ((9 + 9)/9))$</p>	<p>► 820 := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})$:= $22 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 2)$:= $3^3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3/3)$:= $((4 + 4)^4 + 4)/(4/4 + 4)$:= $(55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - 5$:= $6 + (((66 + 66)/6) + 66 \times (6 + 6))$:= $7/7 + (777 - 7 + 7 \times 7)$:= $((88/8 - 8)^8) - 8/8/8$:= $9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + 9/9)$</p>	<p>► 823 := $1111 - ((1 + 1) \times ((1 + 11)^{1+1}))$:= $22 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) + 2/2)$:= $3 + (((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3^3) + 3/3)$:= $4 + (((4 + 4)^4) - 4/4)/(4/4 + 4)$:= $(55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - (5 + 5)/5$:= $6 \times 6 + ((66 \times (6 + 6) - 6) + 6/6)$:= $7 \times 7 + (777 - ((7 + 7 + 7)/7))$:= $888 - (8/8 + 8 \times 8)$:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)$</p>
<p>► 818 := $1 + (1 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - (11 \times (1 + 111))))$:= $22 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 - 2))$:= $3^3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) - 3/3)$:= $4 + (((44 - 4)/4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4) + 4)$:= $(55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - ((5 + 5)/5 + 5)$:= $(6 - (((6 + 6)/6)^{6+6}))/((6/6 - 6))$:= $7 \times 7 + (777 - (7/7 + 7))$:= $8 + ((8/8 + 8) \times ((8 + 8)/8 + 88))$:= $9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) - 9/9)$</p>	<p>► 821 := $1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}))$:= $22 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) - 2/2)$:= $33/3 + (3^3 \times (3^3 + 3))$:= $4 + ((4 \times (44 + 4)) + (4/4 + 4)^4)$:= $5/5 + ((55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - 5)$:= $6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - (6/6 + 6))$:= $7 + ((7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)) + ((7 + 7)/7)^7)$:= $8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) - 88/8$:= $99/9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 824 := $1 + (1111 - ((1 + 1) \times ((1 + 11)^{1+1})))$:= $2 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) + 22)$:= $3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) + 33/3)$:= $4 + (((4 + 4)^4) + 4)/(4/4 + 4)$:= $(55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - 5/5$:= $6 + ((6 - (((6 + 6)/6)^{6+6}))/((6/6 - 6))$:= $7 \times 7 + (777 - ((7 + 7)/7))$:= $888 - 8 \times 8$:= $(9 - 9/9) \times (((999 + 9)/9) - 9)$</p>
<p>► 819 := $11^{1+1+1} - (1 + 1)^{11-1-1}$:= $((22 + 2)^2) + (22^2 + 2)/2$:= $3 \times ((3 \times (3 \times (3^3 + 3))) + 3)$:= $((4 + 4)^4 - 4/4)/(4/4 + 4)$:= $(55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - (5/5 + 5)$:= $(6/6 + 6) \times (666/6 + 6)$:= $7 \times 7 + (777 - 7)$:= $8 + ((888 - 88) + (88/8))$:= $9 + 9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 822 := $(1 + 1) \times (11 + (((1 + 1) \times (11 - 1))^{1+1}))$:= $22 + (2 \times (22 - 2)^2)$:= $3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) + 3^3)$:= $(4 + 4)/4 + (((4 + 4)^4) + 4)/(4/4 + 4)$:= $(5 + 5)/5 + ((55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - 5)$:= $6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - 6)$:= $7 + ((777 - (77/7)) + 7 \times 7)$:= $888 - (((8 + 8)/8) + 8 \times 8)$:= $9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + (99 + 9)/9$</p>	<p>► 825 := $11 \times (1 + ((1 + 1) \times (111/(1 + 1 + 1))))$:= $((2 \times 22)^2) - (2222/2)$:= $33 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3))$:= $44/4 \times ((44 + 4^4)/4)$:= $55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)$:= $6 + ((6/6 + 6) \times (666/6 + 6))$:= $7 \times 7 + (777 - 7/7)$:= $8/8 + (888 - 8 \times 8)$:= $9 + ((9 - 9/9) \times (999/9 - 9))$</p>

► **826** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (1 + 11 \times 111)$
 := $22 + (2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2))$
 := $3/3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3)) + 33)$
 := $((44 \times ((44 + 4^4)/4)) + 4)/4$
 := $5/5 + (55 \times (5 + 5 + 5))$
 := $6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 \times 7 + 777$
 := $888 + (((8 + 8)/8) - 8 \times 8)$
 := $99 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9))$

► **829** := $1 + (1 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - 11 \times 111))$
 := $2/2 + ((2^{2+2} + 2) \times ((2 \times 22) + 2))$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times 33 + 3^{3+3})$
 := $4 + (44/4 \times ((44 + 4^4)/4))$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - 5/5)$
 := $6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + 6/6)$
 := $(77/7 \times (77 - 7/7)) - 7$
 := $8 + (8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) - 88/8)$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 + 99)$

► **832** := $(1 + (1 + 11)) \times ((1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)})$
 := $2 \times ((22 - 2)^2 + 2^{2+2})$
 := $(3^3 - 3/3) \times (33 - 3/3)$
 := $4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4 + 4))$
 := $(5 \times 5 + 5/5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $(6/6 + 6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $7 + ((777 - 7/7) + 7 \times 7)$
 := $8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((999 + 9)/9) - 9)$

► **827** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - 11 \times 111$
 := $2 + (((2 \times 22)^2) - (2222/2))$
 := $3 \times 33 + (3^{3+3} - 3/3)$
 := $(4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4 + 4))) - (4/4 + 4)$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + (55 \times (5 + 5 + 5))$
 := $6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - 6/6)$
 := $7/7 + (777 + 7 \times 7)$
 := $888 + (88/8 - (8 \times 8 + 8))$
 := $99 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9)$

► **830** := $(11 - 1) \times (1 + (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + ((2^{2+2} + 2) \times ((2 \times 22) + 2))$
 := $3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3/3) + 3 \times 33)$
 := $(4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4 + 4))) - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $5 + (55 \times (5 + 5 + 5))$
 := $6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 \times 7 + ((777 - 7) + (77/7))$
 := $8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + (9 \times (9 \times 9 + 9) + (99/9))$

► **833** := $1 + ((1 + (1 + 11)) \times ((1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}))$
 := $22 + ((2 \times (22 - 2)^2) + 22/2)$
 := $(3333 - 3/3)/(3/3 + 3)$
 := $4/4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)))$
 := $5^5/5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5 + 5))$
 := $6 + ((66 \times (6 + 6) - 6/6) + 6 \times 6)$
 := $7 + (777 + 7 \times 7)$
 := $8/8 + 8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9 - 9/9) \times (((999 + 9)/9) - 9))$

► **828** := $1 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - 11 \times 111)$
 := $(2^{2+2} + 2) \times ((2 \times 22) + 2)$
 := $3 \times 33 + 3^{3+3}$
 := $(4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4 + 4))) - 4$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - ((5 + 5)/5))$
 := $6 \times ((66 + 66) + 6)$
 := $7 \times 7 + (((7 + 7)/7) + 777)$
 := $8 + (((88/8 - 8)^8) - 8/8)/8$
 := $99 + 9 \times 9 \times 9$

► **831** := $1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})))$
 := $(2/2 + 2) \times (((22 + 2)^2) - 22)/2$
 := $3 + (3 \times 33 + 3^{3+3})$
 := $(4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4 + 4))) - 4/4$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) + 5/5)$
 := $6 \times 6 + (((6 \times 6)/(6 + 6))^6) + 66$
 := $7 + ((777 - ((7 + 7)/7)) + 7 \times 7)$
 := $8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) - 8/8$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (999/9 - 9)$

► **834** := $(1 + 1) \times ((11 \times (1 + (111/(1 + 1 + 1)))) - 1)$
 := $(22 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)) - 2$
 := $3 + ((3 \times 33 + 3^{3+3}) + 3)$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)))$
 := $5 + (((55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) - 5/5) + 5)$
 := $6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6)$
 := $7 + ((777 + 7 \times 7) + 7/7)$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + 8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)$
 := $(9999 + 9)/((99 + 9)/9)$

► **835** := $1111 - ((1 + 11) \times (1 + (11 + 11)))$
 := $(22 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)) - 2/2$
 := $3 + ((3^3 - 3/3) \times (33 - 3/3))$
 := $4 + ((4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4 + 4))) - 4/4)$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((66 \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6) + 6/6)$
 := $(77 \times 77 - (77 + 7))/7$
 := $888 + (88/8 - 8 \times 8)$
 := $9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) + 99)$

► **838** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (11 \times (111 - 1))$
 := $2 + (22 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2))$
 := $3^3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) + 3/3)$
 := $(4 - 44)/4 + 4 \times (4^4 - 44)$
 := $5 + (((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5 + 5)) + 5^5/5)$
 := $6 + ((6/6 + 6 + 6) \times ((6 + 6)/6)^6)$
 := $((77 \times 77 - (7 + 7))/7) - 7$
 := $8 + (8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) - ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 + 99) + 9/9)$

► **841** := $((((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)) - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $(((((22 + 2/2) + 2) + 2) + 2)^2)$
 := $3^{3+3} + ((333 + 3)/3)$
 := $4 + (((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44) + 4^4)$
 := $(5 \times 5 - 5/5 + 5)^{(5+5)/5}$
 := $(6 \times 6 - (6/6 + 6))^{(6+6)/6}$
 := $((77 \times 77 + 7)/7) - 7$
 := $8 + (8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) + 8/8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((999 + 9)/9)$

► **836** := $(1 + 1) \times (11 \times (1 + (111/(1 + 1 + 1))))$
 := $22 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2)$
 := $3^3 + ((3^3 \times (3^3 + 3)) - 3/3)$
 := $4 + (4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)))$
 := $55/5 + (55 \times (5 + 5 + 5))$
 := $(66/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6) + 6$
 := $77/7 \times (77 - 7/7)$
 := $888 + ((88 + 8)/8 - 8 \times 8)$
 := $9 + ((9 \times 9 \times 9 - 9/9) + 99)$

► **839** := $1 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - (11 \times (111 - 1)))$
 := $((2 - 22) \times (2 - (2 \times 22))) - 2/2$
 := $3^{3+3} + ((333 - 3)/3)$
 := $4444/4 - (4 \times 4 + 4^4)$
 := $((5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 5/5)) - 5/5$
 := $6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + (66/6))$
 := $((77 \times 77 - 7)/7) - 7$
 := $8 + (8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) - 8/8)$
 := $99 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99/9))$

► **842** := $1 + (((((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)) - 1)^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + ((2 - 22) \times (2 - (2 \times 22)))$
 := $3 + (((333 - 3)/3) + 3^{3+3})$
 := $4 \times (4^4 - 44) - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4)$
 := $5 + (((5 \times 5 + 5/5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((66/6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6) + 6)$
 := $((77 \times 77 + 7) + 7)/7 - 7$
 := $8 + (8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) + ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + ((999 + 9 + 9)/9)$

► **837** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (1 + (11 \times (111 - 1)))$
 := $2/2 + (22 \times ((2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2))$
 := $3 \times (3 \times ((3 \times (3^3 + 3)) + 3))$
 := $4^4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44)$
 := $5 + ((5 \times 5 + 5/5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)$
 := $(66 \times 66 + 666)/6$
 := $7 \times 7 + (77/7 + 777)$
 := $8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) - 88/8) + 8)$
 := $9 + (9 \times 9 \times 9 + 99)$

► **840** := $111 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $(2 - 22) \times (2 - (2 \times 22))$
 := $3^{3+3} + 333/3$
 := $4 \times (4^4 - 44) - 4 - 4$
 := $(5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 5/5)$
 := $(6 + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 6)$
 := $(77 \times (77/7)) - 7$
 := $8 + 8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + 999/9$

► **843** := $1 + (1 + (((((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)) - 1)^{1+1})))$
 := $2 + ((((((22 + 2/2) + 2) + 2) + 2)^2))$
 := $33 + (3^3 \times (3^3 + 3))$
 := $4 \times (4^4 - 44) - (4/4 + 4)$
 := $5^5/5 + (((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) - 5 \times 5)$
 := $6 + ((66 \times 66 + 666)/6)$
 := $7 + (77/7 \times (77 - 7/7))$
 := $88/8 + 8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9999 + 9)/((99 + 9)/9))$

▶ 844 := (1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × 111 - 11))	▶ 847 := 11 × (11 × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1))))	▶ 850 := 11 ¹⁺¹ + (11 - 1 - 1) ¹⁺¹⁺¹
:= 2 × ((22 - 2) ² + 22)	:= (2 × 22 ²) - (22/2) ²	:= 2 + (2 × (((22 - 2) ² + 22) + 2))
:= 3 + (((333 + 3)/3) + 3 ³⁺³)	:= 33/3 × (3 × 3 ³ - (3/3 + 3))	:= 3 ³⁺³ + ((33/3) ^{3-3/3})
:= 4 × (4 ⁴ - 44) - 4	:= 4 × (4 ⁴ - 44) - 4/4	:= (4 + 4)/4 + 4 × (4 ⁴ - 44)
:= 5 × 55 + ((5 ⁵ - 5)/5 - 55)	:= ((555 + 555) + 5 ⁵)/5	:= 5 × ((5 × ((5 × 5 + 5) + 5)) - 5)
:= 6 + (((6/6 + 6 + 6) × ((6 + 6)/6) ⁶) + 6)	:= (66/6) × (66/6 + 66)	:= 66 × (6 + 6) + (((6 + 6)/6) ⁶ - 6)
:= (77 × 77 - (7 + 7 + 7))/7	:= 77 × (77/7)	:= (((77 × 77 + 7) + 7) + 7)/7
:= 888 - (88/((8 + 8)/8))	:= 88/8 × (88 - 88/8)	:= 8 + ((8 × (88 + 8 + 8) + ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)
:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 - ((9 + 9)/9)) + 99) + 9)	:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 + 99) + 9/9) + 9)	:= 9 + (((999 + 9)/9) + 9 × 9 × 9)

▶ 845 := (1 + (1 + (1 + 1 + 1))) × ((1 + (1 + 11)) ¹⁺¹)	▶ 848 := 1 + (11 × (11 × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1))))	▶ 851 := (1 + (11 + 11)) × (111/(1 + 1 + 1))
:= 2/2 + (2 × ((22 - 2) ² + 22))	:= 2 × (((22 - 2) ² + 22) + 2)	:= (2 × (22 ² + 2)) - (22/2) ²
:= 333 + ((3 - 3/3) ^{3×3})	:= 3 + (((3 - 3/3) ^{3×3}) + 333)	:= 3 ³⁺³ + ((3 ³⁺³ + 3)/(3 + 3))
:= 4/4 + (4 × (4 ⁴ - 44) - 4)	:= 4 × (4 ⁴ - 44)	:= 4 + (4 × (4 ⁴ - 44) - 4/4)
:= 5 + ((5 + 5 + 5) × (55 + 5/5))	:= (55/5 + 5) × (55 - (5 + 5)/5)	:= 5 × 5 + ((55 × (5 + 5 + 5)) + 5/5)
:= (6/6 + 6 + 6) × (66 - 6/6)	:= ((66 × (66/6 + 66)) + 6)/6	:= 6 + ((6/6 + 6 + 6) × (66 - 6/6))
:= (77 × 77 - (7 + 7))/7	:= (77 × 77 + 7)/7	:= (77/7 × (7/7 + 77)) - 7
:= 88 + (8 × (88 + 8) - (88/8))	:= 8 + (8 × (88 + 8 + 8) + 8)	:= 8 + (8 × (88 + 8 + 8) + 88/8)
:= 9 + (((9 × 9 × 9 - 9/9) + 99) + 9)	:= 9 + ((9 × 9 × 9 + (99/9)) + 99)	:= 9 × 9 × 9 + (999 + 99)/9

▶ 846 := (11 × (11 × (1 + ((1 + 1) × (1 + 1 + 1))))	▶ 849 := ((1 + 1) ¹¹) - (11 × (111 - 1 - 1))	▶ 852 := 11 + (((11 - 1) × (1 + 1 + 1)) - 1) ¹⁺¹)
:= 2 + (2 × ((22 - 2) ² + 22))	:= 2 + ((2 × 22 ²) - (22/2) ²)	:= 2 × ((2 × (222 + 2)) - 22)
:= 3 + ((3 ³ × (3 ³ + 3)) + 33)	:= (33 × 3 ³) - (3 × 3 + 33)	:= (3/3 + 3) × ((3 + 3) ³ - 3)
:= 4 × (4 ⁴ - 44) - (4 + 4)/4	:= 4/4 + 4 × (4 ⁴ - 44)	:= 4 + 4 × (4 ⁴ - 44)
:= 5 + ((5 × 5 - 5/5 + 5) ^{(5+5)/5})	:= 5 × 5 + ((55 × (5 + 5 + 5)) - 5/5)	:= 5 + (((555 + 555) + 5 ⁵)/5)
:= 666 + 6 × (6 × 6 - 6)	:= 6 + (((66 × 66 + 666)/6) + 6)	:= 66 + (66 × (6 + 6) - 6)
:= (77 × 77 - 7)/7	:= ((77 × 77 + 7) + 7)/7	:= 7 + ((77 × 77 - (7 + 7))/7)
:= (8/8 + 8) × ((88 - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)	:= 8 + ((8 × (88 + 8 + 8) + 8/8) + 8)	:= 8 + (888 - (88/((8 + 8)/8)))
:= 9 + ((9 × 9 × 9 + 99) + 9)	:= 9 + (999/9 + 9 × 9 × 9)	:= ((99 + 9)/9) × (9 × 9 - (9/9 + 9))

- **853** := $((1 + 11)^{1+1+1}) / (1 + 1) - 11$
 := $(2 \times (22^2 - 2)) - 222/2$
 := $3/3 + ((3/3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3))$
 := $4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 44) + 4/4)$
 := $5 + ((55/5 + 5) \times (55 - (5 + 5)/5))$
 := $(6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) - 66/6$
 := $7 + ((77 \times 77 - 7)/7)$
 := $888 - ((88/8 + 8 + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - ((99/9 + 9 + 9) + 9)$
- **854** := $1 + (((1 + 11)^{1+1+1}) / (1 + 1) - 11)$
 := $2 + (2 \times ((2 \times (222 + 2)) - 22))$
 := $3^{3+3} + ((3 - 3/3 + 3)^3)$
 := $(4444 - 4)/4 - 4^4$
 := $555 + ((5 \times (55 + 5)) - 5/5)$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times ((666 + 66)/6)$
 := $77 + 777$
 := $88 + (8 \times (88 + 8) - ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 \times 99 - (((9/9 + 9 + 9) + 9) + 9)$
- **855** := $1111 - (1 + 1)^{(1+1) \times (1+1+1)}$
 := $(2 \times 22^2) - (222/2 + 2)$
 := $3 \times 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) - 3$
 := $4444/4 - 4^4$
 := $555 + (5 \times (55 + 5))$
 := $6 \times 6 + ((6/6 + 6) \times (666/6 + 6))$
 := $7 + ((77 \times 77 + 7)/7)$
 := $88 + (8 \times (88 + 8) - 8/8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - ((9 + 9 + 9) + 9)$
- **856** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - ((1 + 11)^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (222 - 2 \times (2 + 2)))$
 := $(3 \times 3^{3+3}) - ((33/3)^3)$
 := $4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 44) + 4)$
 := $5/5 + ((5 \times (55 + 5)) + 555)$
 := $66 \times (6 + 6) + ((6 + 6)/6)^6$
 := $7 + (((77 \times 77 + 7) + 7)/7)$
 := $88 + 8 \times (88 + 8)$
 := $(9 - 9/9) \times ((99 - 9/9) + 9)$
- **857** := $((1 + 1) \times ((11 + 11)^{1+1})) - 111$
 := $(2 \times 22^2) - 222/2$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) - (3/3 + 33)$
 := $4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 44) + 4/4) + 4)$
 := $((5 + 5)/5)^5 + (55 \times (5 + 5 + 5))$
 := $66 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - 6/6)$
 := $((77 \times 77 - 7) + 77)/7$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times (88 + 8) + 88)$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 9 \times 9 + (99/9)) + 99) + 9)$
- **858** := $11 \times (111 - (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)))$
 := $22 \times (2 \times (22 - 2) - 2/2)$
 := $33 \times (3^3 - 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((4444 - 4)/4 - 4^4)$
 := $5^5/5 + (((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) - (5 + 5))$
 := $66 + 66 \times (6 + 6)$
 := $77/7 \times (7/7 + 77)$
 := $88 + (8 \times (88 + 8) + ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 + ((999/9 + 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)$
- **859** := $1 + (11 \times (111 - (11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))))$
 := $2 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 222/2)$
 := $3/3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3/3))$
 := $4 + (4444/4 - 4^4)$
 := $((55/5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5)) - 5$
 := $66 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + 6/6)$
 := $((77 \times 77 + 77) + 7)/7$
 := $8 + ((8 \times (88 + 8 + 8) + 88/8) + 8)$
 := $9 + (((999 + 9)/9) + 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9)$
- **860** := $(1 + 1) \times (((11 + (11 - 1))^{1+1}) - 11)$
 := $(2 - 22) \times (2/2 - (2 \times 22))$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 - 3/3)$
 := $(4/4 + 4) \times ((4 \times 44) - 4)$
 := $5 + ((5 \times (55 + 5)) + 555)$
 := $66 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 + (((77 \times 77 - 7)/7) + 7)$
 := $888 + ((8 - 8 \times 8)/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 \times 99 - (((99 + 99)/9) + 9)$
- **861** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times ((1 + 11)^{1+1})) - 1)$
 := $(2/2 + 2) \times ((22 + 2)^2 - 2)/2$
 := $3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3/3))$
 := $4/4 + ((4/4 + 4) \times ((4 \times 44) - 4))$
 := $5 \times 5 \times 5 + ((555 + 5^5)/5)$
 := $66 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 66)$
 := $7 + (777 + 77)$
 := $888 - (88/8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - 999/9$

► **862** := $((1 + 11)^{1+1+1}) / (1 + 1) - 1 - 1$
 := $2 \times (2 \times 222 - 2) - 22$
 := $3 + ((33 \times (3^3 - 3/3)) + 3/3)$
 := $(4 \times (4^4 - 44 + 4)) - (4 + 4) / 4$
 := $555 + (5^5 - 55) / (5 + 5)$
 := $(6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) - (6 + 6) / 6$
 := $7 + (((77 \times 77 + 7) / 7) + 7)$
 := $888 + ((8 - 88) / 8 - (8 + 8))$
 := $9 \times 99 - (99 / 9 + 9 + 9)$

► **865** := $1 + (((1 + 11)^{1+1+1}) / (1 + 1))$
 := $2/2 + ((22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2)$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3))$
 := $4/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 44 + 4))$
 := $(5 \times (5 \times ((5 \times 5 + 5) + 5))) - 5 - 5$
 := $6/6 + (6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6))$
 := $7 + (77/7 \times (7/7 + 77))$
 := $8/8 + (88 + 8) \times (8/8 + 8)$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times 99 - (9 + 9 + 9))$

► **868** := $1111 - (1 + ((1 + 1) \times 11^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + ((2 \times 2 \times 222) - 22)$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 + 3/3)$
 := $4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 44 + 4))$
 := $5^5/5 + ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) - ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 + (777 + 77 + 7)$
 := $888 - (((88 + 8)/8) + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - ((99 + 99 + 9)/9)$

► **863** := $((1 + 11)^{1+1+1}) / (1 + 1) - 1$
 := $((22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2) - 2/2$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) - (3^3 + 3/3)$
 := $(4 \times (4^4 - 44 + 4)) - 4/4$
 := $5^5/5 + (((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) - 5)$
 := $(6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) - 6/6$
 := $7 + (((77 \times 77 + 7) + 7) / 7) + 7$
 := $888 - (8/8 + 8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - ((9/9 + 9 + 9) + 9)$

► **866** := $1 + (1 + (((1 + 11)^{1+1+1}) / (1 + 1)))$
 := $(2 \times 2 \times 222) - 22$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 3^3) - (3^3 + 3/3))$
 := $(4 + 4) / 4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 44 + 4))$
 := $5 + (((555 + 5^5) / 5) + 5 \times 5 \times 5)$
 := $(6 + 6) / 6 + (6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6))$
 := $7 + (((77 \times 77 + 77) + 7) / 7)$
 := $888 - (88 + 88) / 8$
 := $(9 + 9) / 9 + (9 \times 99 - (9 + 9 + 9))$

► **869** := $11 \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - (1 + 1))$
 := $(2222 - 22^2) / 2$
 := $33/3 + (33 \times (3^3 - 3/3))$
 := $44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) - 44/4$
 := $5 + ((55/5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5))$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) - 6/6)$
 := $77/7 \times ((7 + 7) / 7 + 77)$
 := $888 - (88/8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - ((99 + 99) / 9)$

► **864** := $((1 + 11)^{1+1+1}) / (1 + 1)$
 := $(22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)^2$
 := $3 \times 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3)$
 := $4 \times (4^4 - 44 + 4)$
 := $(55/5 + 5) \times (55 - 5/5)$
 := $6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)$
 := $(77/7 + 7) \times (7 \times 7 - 7/7)$
 := $(88 + 8) \times (8/8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - (9 + 9 + 9)$

► **867** := $1 + (1 + (1 + (((1 + 11)^{1+1+1}) / (1 + 1))))$
 := $2/2 + ((2 \times 2 \times 222) - 22)$
 := $3 + (3 \times 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3))$
 := $4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 44 + 4)) - 4/4)$
 := $555 + (5^5 - 5) / (5 + 5)$
 := $(6 \times 6 / (6 + 6)) + (6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6))$
 := $7 + (((77 \times 77 - 7) / 7) + 7) + 7$
 := $88 + (8 \times (88 + 8) + (88/8))$
 := $9 + (((999/9 + 9 \times 9 \times 9) + 9) + 9)$

► **870** := $1 + (11 \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - (1 + 1)))$
 := $(2 \times (2 \times 222 + 2)) - 22$
 := $3 + ((3 \times 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3)) + 3)$
 := $4^4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 44/4)$
 := $(5 \times (5 \times ((5 \times 5 + 5) + 5))) - 5$
 := $6 + (6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6))$
 := $7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) - (77 + 7) / 7$
 := $888 + ((8 - 88) / 8 - 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - (((99 + 9) / 9) + 9)$

- **871** := $1111 - ((1 + 1) \times (11^{1+1} - 1))$
 := $((((2 \times 22) - 2)^2) - 22)/2$
 := $3 + ((3/3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 + 3/3))$
 := $4 \times 4 + (4444/4 - 4^4)$
 := $5/5 + ((5 \times (5 \times ((5 \times 5 + 5) + 5))) - 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) + 6/6)$
 := $7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) - 77/7$
 := $888 - (8/8 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - (99/9 + 9)$
- **874** := $11 + (((((1 + 11)^{1+1+1})/(1 + 1)) - 1)$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2 \times (222 - (2 + 2))))$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times (3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) + 3))$
 := $44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) - ((4 + 4)/4 + 4)$
 := $(5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)) + (5^5 - 5)/5$
 := $((66 - 6)/6) + (6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6))$
 := $777 + (7 \times (7 + 7) - 7/7)$
 := $888 + (((8 + 8)/8) - (8 + 8))$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times 99 - (9 + 9))$
- **877** := $(111 \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1}) - 11$
 := $(2 \times 2 \times 222) - 22/2$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) - (33/3 + 3)$
 := $4^4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - 4)$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + (5 \times (5 \times ((5 \times 5 + 5) + 5)))$
 := $6 + (((6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) + 6/6) + 6)$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + (777 + 7 \times (7 + 7))$
 := $888 - 88/8$
 := $9 \times 99 + (((9 - 99)/(9 + 9)) - 9)$
- **872** := $(1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \times (111 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (222 - (2 + 2)))$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times (((3 + 3)^3 - 3/3) + 3)$
 := $44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) - 4 - 4$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 555)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 + ((77/7 \times (7/7 + 77)) + 7)$
 := $888 - 8 - 8$
 := $9 \times 99 - (9/9 + 9 + 9)$
- **875** := $11 + (((1 + 11)^{1+1+1})/(1 + 1))$
 := $(2 \times 2 \times 222) - (22/2 + 2)$
 := $33/3 + (3 \times 3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3))$
 := $(4/4 + 4) \times ((4 \times 44) - 4/4)$
 := $5 \times (5 \times ((5 \times 5 + 5) + 5))$
 := $66/6 + (6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6))$
 := $777 + 7 \times (7 + 7)$
 := $888 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + (9 \times 99 - (9 + 9))$
- **878** := $1 + ((111 \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1}) - 11)$
 := $2 \times (((22 - 2/2)^2) - 2)$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) + (((3 - 33)/3) - 3)$
 := $44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $(55 \times (55/5 + 5)) - (5 + 5)/5$
 := $6 + (((6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) + ((6 + 6)/6)) + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) - (77/7))$
 := $888 + (8 - 88)/8$
 := $9 \times 99 - ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)$
- **873** := $1 + ((1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \times (111 - 1 - 1))$
 := $2 + (((((2 \times 22) - 2)^2) - 22)/2)$
 := $3 \times (3 \times (3 \times 33 - 3) + 3)$
 := $4^4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 - (4 + 4))$
 := $5 + (((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) + 5^5/5)$
 := $(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6)$
 := $777 + (7 \times (7 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8/8 + (888 - (8 + 8))$
 := $9 \times 99 - (9 + 9)$
- **876** := $1 + (11 + (((1 + 11)^{1+1+1})/(1 + 1)))$
 := $2 \times ((2 \times (222 - 2)) - 2)$
 := $(3/3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3)^3 + 3)$
 := $44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) - 4$
 := $5/5 + (5 \times (5 \times ((5 \times 5 + 5) + 5)))$
 := $6 + ((6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)) + 6)$
 := $7/7 + (777 + 7 \times (7 + 7))$
 := $888 - (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times 99 + (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - (9 + 9))$
- **879** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 11^{1+1}$
 := $(2 \times (2 \times (222 - 2))) - 2/2$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) - (3 \times 3 + 3)$
 := $44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) - 4/4$
 := $(55 \times (55/5 + 5)) - 5/5$
 := $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6))$
 := $7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $888 - (8/8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - (99 + 9)/9$

► **880** := $11 \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1)$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (222 - 2))$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) - 33/3$
 := $44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$
 := $55 \times (55/5 + 5)$
 := $666 + (6 \times 6 \times 6 - (6 + 6)/6)$
 := $(7/7 + 7) \times (777 - 7)/7$
 := $888 - 8$
 := $9 \times 99 - 99/9$

► **883** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times ((11 + (11 - 1))^{1+1}))$
 := $((((2 \times 22) - 2)^2) + 2)/2$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 3^3) - 33/3)$
 := $4 + (44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) - 4/4)$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (55/5 + 5)) - ((5 + 5)/5))$
 := $6/6 + (666 + 6 \times 6 \times 6)$
 := $7/7 + 7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7)$
 := $888 + (88/8 - (8 + 8))$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)$

► **886** := $(1 + 1) \times (((1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) \times 111) - 1)$
 := $(2 \times 2 \times 222) - 2$
 := $3/3 + ((33 \times 3^3) - (3 + 3))$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 \times (444 - 4/4)$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (55/5 + 5)) + 5/5)$
 := $6 + ((666 - ((6 + 6)/6)) + 6 \times 6 \times 6)$
 := $77/7 + (777 + 7 \times (7 + 7))$
 := $888 - (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))$

► **881** := $1 + (11 \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1))$
 := $((((2 \times 22) - 2)^2) - 2)/2$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) + ((3 - 33)/3)$
 := $4^4 + (4/4 + 4)^4$
 := $5/5 + (55 \times (55/5 + 5))$
 := $666 + (6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6/6)$
 := $7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) - 7/7$
 := $8/8 + 888 - 8$
 := $9 \times 99 - 9/9 - 9$

► **884** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + ((11 + (11 - 1))^{1+1}))$
 := $2 \times (2 \times 222 - 2)$
 := $(3^3 - 3/3) \times (3/3 + 33)$
 := $4 + 44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4)$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (55/5 + 5)) - 5/5)$
 := $666 + (6 \times 6 \times 6 + (6 + 6)/6)$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + 7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7)$
 := $888 - (8/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + (9 \times 99 - 9)$

► **887** := $(111 \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1}) - 1$
 := $(2 \times 2 \times 222) - 2/2$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) - (3/3 + 3)$
 := $((4 + 4) \times 444 - 4)/4$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (55/5 + 5)) + ((5 + 5)/5))$
 := $6 + ((6 \times 6 \times 6 - 6/6) + 666)$
 := $777 + (777 - 7)/7$
 := $888 - 8/8$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **882** := $(1 + 1) \times ((11 + (11 - 1))^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times ((22 - 2/2)^2)$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 3 \times 33 - 3)$
 := $4/4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4^4)$
 := $(5 + 5)/5 + (55 \times (55/5 + 5))$
 := $666 + 6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7)$
 := $888 + (((8 + 8)/8) - 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 - 9$

► **885** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + ((11 + (11 - 1))^{1+1})))$
 := $2 + (((((2 \times 22) - 2)^2) + 2)/2)$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) - (3 + 3)$
 := $4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4^4)$
 := $5 + (55 \times (55/5 + 5))$
 := $(6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 + 66)$
 := $(7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) - 77/7$
 := $8 + (888 - 88/8)$
 := $9 \times 99 + (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - 9)$

► **888** := $111 \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $2 \times 2 \times 222$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) - 3$
 := $(4 + 4) \times 444/4$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((5^5 - (55 + 5))/5)$
 := $6 + (666 + 6 \times 6 \times 6)$
 := $777 + 777/7$
 := 888
 := $9 \times 99 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

► **889** := $1 + (111 \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1})$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times 2 \times 222)$
 := $3/3 + ((33 \times 3^3) - 3)$
 := $((4 + 4) \times 444 + 4)/4$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((5^5 - 55)/5)$
 := $6 + ((666 + 6 \times 6 \times 6) + 6/6)$
 := $7 + 7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7)$
 := $8/8 + 888$
 := $9 \times 99 - (9 + 9)/9$

► **892** := $1 + (11 \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times (2 \times 222 + 2)$
 := $3/3 + (33 \times 3^3)$
 := $4 + (444 + 444)$
 := $5 \times 5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 555)$
 := $6 \times 6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) + ((6 + 6)/6)^6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) - (77/7))$
 := $888 + (8/((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9/9 + 9 \times 99$

► **895** := $((1 + 111) \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1}) - 1$
 := $(2 \times (2 \times (222 + 2))) - 2/2$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + 3/3)$
 := $4 + (44/4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4)$
 := $5^5/5 + (5 \times 55 - 5)$
 := $(6666/6) - 6 \times 6 \times 6$
 := $(7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) - 7/7$
 := $8 + (888 - 8/8)$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((9 \times 9 - 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **890** := $(11 \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}) - 1$
 := $2 + (2 \times 2 \times 222)$
 := $(33 \times 3^3) - 3/3$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 \times (444 + 4/4)$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (55/5 + 5)) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((666 + 6 \times 6 \times 6) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) + 7/7)$
 := $888 + (8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 \times 99 - 9/9$

► **893** := $1 + (1 + (11 \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}))$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times (2 \times 222 + 2))$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 3^3) - 3/3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 444 + 4)/4)$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 - 5)$
 := $666 + (6 \times 6 \times 6 + 66/6)$
 := $77/7 + 7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7)$
 := $8 + (888 - 88/8 + 8)$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + 9 \times 99$

► **896** := $(1 + 111) \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1}$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (222 + 2))$
 := $3 + (((33 \times 3^3) - 3/3) + 3)$
 := $4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4))$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 - 5)$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^{6/6+6})$
 := $7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 + 888$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **891** := $11 \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 + ((2 \times 2 \times 222) + 2/2)$
 := 33×3^3
 := $44/4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 - (5 + 5))$
 := $6 + ((6 - 6/6) \times (666/6 + 66))$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) + ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $888 + (88/8 - 8)$
 := 9×99

► **894** := $1 + (1 + (1 + (11 \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})))$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2 \times 222 + 2))$
 := $3 + (33 \times 3^3)$
 := $4 + ((4 + 4)/4 \times (444 + 4/4))$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 - 5)$
 := $(6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) - 6$
 := $(7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + (888 - ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)$

► **897** := $1 + ((1 + 111) \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1})$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times (2 \times (222 + 2)))$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + 3)$
 := $4 \times 4 + ((4/4 + 4)^4 + 4^4)$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 - 5)$
 := $666/6 + (66 \times (6 + 6) - 6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7)$
 := $8 + (888 + 8/8)$
 := $9 + (9 \times 99 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9))$

- **898** := $((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))^{1+1} - 1 - 1$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2 \times (222 + 2)))$
 := $3 + (((33 \times 3^3) + 3/3) + 3)$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4)))$
 := $5 \times 55 + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5$
 := $(6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7)$
 := $8 + (888 + ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 + (9 \times 99 - ((9 + 9)/9))$
- **899** := $((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))^{1+1} - 1$
 := $22/2 + (2 \times 2 \times 222)$
 := $3 \times 3 + ((33 \times 3^3) - 3/3)$
 := $((4 + 4) \times 444 + 44)/4$
 := $5 \times 55 + (5^5 - 5)/5$
 := $(6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) - 6/6$
 := $777 + (777 + 77)/7$
 := $888 + 88/8$
 := $9 + (9 \times 99 - 9/9)$
- **900** := $((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))^{1+1}$
 := $(2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)^2$
 := $3 \times (3 \times 3 \times 33 + 3)$
 := $4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4)))$
 := $5 \times (5 \times 5 \times 5 + 55)$
 := $6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)$
 := $(77/7 + 7) \times (7/7 + 7 \times 7)$
 := $888 + (88 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + 9 \times 99$
- **901** := $1 + (((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))^{1+1})$
 := $2/2 + ((2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)^2)$
 := $3 \times 3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4))) + 4/4)$
 := $5 \times 55 + (5^5 + 5)/5$
 := $6/6 + (6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6))$
 := $7 + ((7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $888 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
 := $9 + (9 \times 99 + 9/9)$
- **902** := $11 \times (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + ((2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)^2)$
 := $33/3 + (33 \times 3^3)$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - ((444 + 44)/4)$
 := $5 \times 55 + (5^5 + 5 + 5)/5$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + (6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6))$
 := $7 + ((7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) - 7/7)$
 := $8 + ((888 - ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)$
 := $99/9 + 9 \times 99$
- **903** := $(1 + 1)^{11-1} - 11^{1+1}$
 := $2 + (((2 \times (2 + 2) + 22)^2) + 2/2)$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + 3 \times 3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4) \times 444 + 44)/4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 55)$
 := $666/6 + 66 \times (6 + 6)$
 := $7 + (7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7)$
 := $8 + (888 - 8/8 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 + (99 + 9)/9$
- **904** := $1 + ((1 + 1)^{11-1} - 11^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times (2 \times ((222 + 2) + 2))$
 := $3 + (((33 \times 3^3) + 3 \times 3) + 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4))) + 4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 55)$
 := $66 \times (6 + 6) + (666 + 6)/6$
 := $7 + ((7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) + 7/7)$
 := $8 + (888 + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)$
- **905** := $1 + (1 + ((1 + 1)^{11-1} - 11^{1+1}))$
 := $22 + (((((2 \times 22) - 2)^2) + 2)/2)$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + 33/3)$
 := $4 \times 4 + (((4 + 4) \times 444 + 4)/4)$
 := $5 + (5^5/5 + 5 \times 55)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) - 6/6)$
 := $777 + ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 + (888 + 8/8 + 8)$
 := $9 + (((9 \times 9 + 9)/(9 + 9)) + 9 \times 99)$
- **906** := $1 + (1 + (1 + ((1 + 1)^{11-1} - 11^{1+1})))$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2 \times ((222 + 2) + 2)))$
 := $3 + (((33 \times 3^3) + 3 \times 3) + 3)$
 := $4 + (4 \times 4^4 - ((444 + 44)/4))$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times 55)$
 := $6 + (6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6))$
 := $7/7 + (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 777)$
 := $8 + ((888 + ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9 \times 99 - ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$

► **907** := $11 + ((1 + 111) \times (1 + 1)^{1+1+1})$
 := $22/2 + (2 \times (2 \times (222 + 2)))$
 := $3^3 + ((33 \times 3^3) - 33/3)$
 := $4 \times 4 + (44/4 \times (4 - 4/4)^4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times 55)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) + 6/6)$
 := $77/7 + (7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7)$
 := $8 + (888 + 88/8)$
 := $9 + ((9 \times 99 - ((9 + 9)/9)) + 9)$

► **910** := $1 + ((11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1}))$
 := $22 + (2 \times 2 \times 222)$
 := $3/3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + (3 \times (3 + 3)))$
 := $4 \times 4^4 + (((4 - 444)/4) - 4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5/5 + 5 \times 55) + 5)$
 := $(6/6 + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 + 66)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) + 7)$
 := $888 + (88 + 88)/8$
 := $9 + ((9 \times 99 + 9/9) + 9)$

► **913** := $(1 + 1)^{11-1} - 111$
 := $(2^{22/2} - 222)/2$
 := $33 + ((33 \times 3^3) - 33/3)$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - 444/4$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - 555/5$
 := $(66/6) \times (66/6 + 66 + 6)$
 := $77/7 \times (77 - 7/7 + 7)$
 := $8 + ((888 + 8/8 + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((99 + 99)/9)$

► **908** := $((11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1})) - 1$
 := $2 \times ((2 \times ((222 + 2) + 2)) + 2)$
 := $3 + (((33 \times 3^3) + 33/3) + 3)$
 := $44 + (4 \times (4^4 - 44 + 4))$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (555/5 + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $(77 + 7)/7 + (7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7)$
 := $8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 888)$
 := $9 + ((9 \times 99 - 9/9) + 9)$

► **911** := $11 + (((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1))^{1+1})$
 := $22 + ((2 \times 2 \times 222) + 2/2)$
 := $3 \times 3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + 33/3)$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - ((444 + 4 + 4)/4)$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((55 + 5^5)/5)$
 := $66/6 + (6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6))$
 := $7 + (((7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) + 7/7) + 7)$
 := $8 + ((888 - 8/8 + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 + ((99/9) + 9 \times 99)$

► **914** := $1 + ((1 + 1)^{11-1} - 111)$
 := $22 + (2 \times (2 \times 222 + 2))$
 := $3^3 + ((33 \times 3^3) - (3/3 + 3))$
 := $4 \times 4^4 + ((4 - 444)/4)$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 55)$
 := $66 \times (6 + 6) + ((666 + 66)/6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) + (77/7))$
 := $8 + (((888 + ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8) + 8)$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((99 + 99 + 9)/9)$

► **909** := $(11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + (11 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $22 + ((2 \times 2 \times 222) - 2/2)$
 := $3 \times ((3 \times 3 \times 33 + 3) + 3)$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - (444/4 + 4)$
 := $5 + (((5^5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 55) + 5)$
 := $6 + (666/6 + 66 \times (6 + 6))$
 := $7 + (((7 \times ((7 + 7)/7)^7) - 7/7) + 7)$
 := $8 + ((88 + 8 + 8)/8 + 888)$
 := $9 + (9 \times 99 + 9)$

► **912** := $(1 + 1)^{11-1} - (1 + 111)$
 := $2 + ((2 \times 2 \times 222) + 22)$
 := $3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + (3 \times (3 + 3)))$
 := $4 \times ((4^4 - 4 \times (4 + 4)) + 4)$
 := $5 \times 55 + ((55 + 5^5 + 5)/5)$
 := $6 + ((6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) + 6)$
 := $7 + (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 777)$
 := $8 + (888 + 8 + 8)$
 := $9 + (((99 + 9)/9) + 9 \times 99)$

► **915** := $1 + (1 + ((1 + 1)^{11-1} - 111))$
 := $2 + (2^{22/2} - 222)/2$
 := $3^3 + ((33 \times 3^3) - 3)$
 := $4 \times 4^4 + (((4 - 444) + 4)/4)$
 := $(5 + 5 + 5) \times ((55 + 5/5) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((666/6 + 66 \times (6 + 6)) + 6)$
 := $7777/7 - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)$
 := $8 + ((888 + 88/8) + 8)$
 := $999 - (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) + 9 \times 9)$

<p>► 916 := 1 + (1 + (1 + ((1 + 1)¹¹⁻¹ - 111))) := 2 × (22² - (22 + 2 + 2)) := 3³ + (((33 × 3³) - 3) + 3/3) := (4 × (4⁴ - 4 × 4)) - 44 := 5 + (((55 + 5⁵)/5) + 5 × 55) := 6 + ((6/6 + 6) × (((6 + 6)/6)⁶ + 66)) := ((77 × (77 + 7) - 7)/7) - 7 := 8 + (((88 + 8)/8) + 888) + 8 := 999 - (((9 + 9)/9) + 9 × 9)</p>	<p>► 919 := 1 + (((11 - 1 - 1) × (1 + (1 + (11 - 1)¹⁺¹))) := (2 × (22² - (22 + 2))) - 2/2 := 3³ + ((33 × 3³) + 3/3) := 4444/4 - (4 × (44 + 4)) := 5 + ((5 - 5/5)⁵ - (55 + 55)) := 6/6 + (6 × (6 × 6 + 6) + 666) := 7 + (((7 + 7)/7)⁷ + 777) + 7 := 8 + (((888 - 8/8 + 8) + 8) + 8) := 9/9 + (999 - 9 × 9)</p>	<p>► 922 := 11 + (11 + (((11 - 1) × (1 + 1 + 1))¹⁺¹)) := (2 × (22² - 22)) - 2 := 3 + (((33 × 3³) + 3³) + 3/3) := 4 + (((4 - 444)/4) + 4 × 4⁴) + 4 := 55 + ((5⁵ - 5)/(5 + 5) + 555) := 66 + (66 × (6 + 6) + ((6 + 6)/6)⁶) := (77 × (77 + 7) - (7 + 7))/7 := 8 + (((888 + ((8 + 8)/8)) + 8) + 8) + 8 := 9 + (((99 + 99)/9) + 9 × 99)</p>
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<p>► 917 := 1 + (1 + (1 + (1 + ((1 + 1)¹¹⁻¹ - 111)))) := 2 + 2 + (2^{22/2} - 222)/2 := 3³ + ((33 × 3³) - 3/3) := 4 + (4 × 4⁴ - 444/4) := 5 + (((55 + 5⁵ + 5)/5) + 5 × 55) := 666 + (6 × (6 × 6 + 6) - 6/6) := (77 × (77 + 7)/7) - 7 := 8 + (((88 + 8 + 8)/8 + 888) + 8) := 999 - (9/9 + 9 × 9)</p>	<p>► 920 := (11 - 1) × (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)¹⁺¹) := 2 × (22² - (22 + 2)) := 3 + (((33 × 3³) - 3/3) + 3³) := (4 + 4) × (444/4 + 4) := 5⁵/5 + ((5 × (55 + 5)) - 5) := 666 + (6 × (6 × 6 + 6) + ((6 + 6)/6)) := 7 + (77/7 × (77 - 7/7 + 7)) := 8 + ((888 + 8 + 8) + 8) := 9 + (((99/9) + 9 × 99) + 9)</p>	<p>► 923 := 11 + ((1 + 1)¹¹⁻¹ - (1 + 111)) := (2 × (22² - 22)) - 2/2 := 33 + ((33 × 3³) - 3/3) := 44 + (44 × (4 × 4 + 4) - 4/4) := (5 × (55 + 5)) + (5⁵ - 5 - 5)/5 := (6/6 + 6 + 6) × ((66 - 6/6) + 6) := (77 × (77 + 7) - 7)/7 := 8 + (((888 + 88/8) + 8) + 8) := 9 + (((99 + 99 + 9)/9) + 9 × 99)</p>
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<p>► 918 := (11 - 1 - 1) × (1 + (1 + (11 - 1)¹⁺¹)) := 22 + (2 × (2 × (222 + 2))) := 3 × (3 × (3 × 33 + 3)) := 4 + (((4 - 444)/4) + 4 × 4⁴) := 5 + ((5 - 5/5)⁵ - 555/5) := 666 + 6 × (6 × 6 + 6) := ((77 × (77 + 7) + 7)/7) - 7 := 8 + ((88 + 88)/8 + 888) := 999 - 9 × 9</p>	<p>► 921 := 1 + (((11 - 1) × (11 + (11 - 1 - 1)¹⁺¹))) := 2/2 + (2 × (22² - (22 + 2))) := 3 + ((33 × 3³) + 3³) := 4 + ((4 × 4⁴ - 444/4) + 4) := (5 × (55 + 5)) + ((5⁵ + 5)/5 - 5) := 6 + (((666/6 + 66 × (6 + 6)) + 6) + 6) := (77 × (77 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7))/7 := 8 + (((888 + 8/8 + 8) + 8) + 8) := 9 × (9 × 9 + 9) + 999/9</p>	<p>► 924 := 11 + ((1 + 1)¹¹⁻¹ - 111) := 2 × (22² - 22) := 33 + (33 × 3³) := 44 + 44 × (4 × 4 + 4) := (5 × (5 - 5 × 5)) + (5 - 5/5)⁵ := 66 × ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6) := 77 × (77 + 7)/7 := 888 + ((8 × 8 + 8)/((8 + 8)/8)) := 9 × 99 + (99/((9 + 9 + 9)/9))</p>
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► **925** := (11111 - 11)/(1 + 11)
 := 2/2 + (2 × (22² - 22))
 := 3/3 + ((33 × 3³) + 33)
 := 44 + ((4/4 + 4)⁴ + 4⁴)
 := 5 × ((5 × 5 × 5 + 55) + 5)
 := 6/6 + (66 × ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6))
 := (77 × (77 + 7) + 7)/7
 := 888 + 888/(8 + 8 + 8)
 := (((9 + 9)/9)^{9/9+9}) - 99

► **928** := 1 + (1 + ((1 + 11111)/(1 + 11)))
 := 2 × ((22² - 22) + 2)
 := 3 + (((33 × 3³) + 33) + 3/3)
 := 4 × (4⁴ - ((4 × 4 + 4) + 4))
 := ((5 + 5)/5)⁵ × (5 × 5 - 5/5 + 5)
 := ((6 + 6)/6)⁶ + (6 × (6 + 6) × (6 + 6))
 := (77/7 × (7/7 + 77 + 7)) - 7
 := 8 × 8 × (8 + 8) - (88 + 8)
 := 9 + ((999 - 9 × 9) + 9/9)

► **931** := (1 + ((11 - 1) × (1 + 1)¹¹⁻¹)/11
 := (2 × (2 × 222 + 22)) - 2/2
 := 3 + (((33 × 3³) + 33) + 3/3) + 3
 := 4 + ((4 × (4⁴ - 4)) - (4 - 4/4)⁴)
 := 5 + ((5 × (55 + 5)) + (5⁵ + 5)/5)
 := 66 + ((6 × (6 + 6) × (6 + 6)) + 6/6)
 := 7 × (77 + 7 × 7 + 7)
 := 8 + (((888 + 88/8) + 8) + 8) + 8
 := 9 × 99 + ((9 × 9 × 9 - 9)/(9 + 9))

► **926** := (1 + 11111)/(1 + 11)
 := 2 + (2 × (22² - 22))
 := 3 + (((33 × 3³) - 3/3) + 33)
 := 44 + (((4/4 + 4)⁴ + 4⁴) + 4/4)
 := (5 × (55 + 5)) + (5⁵ + 5)/5
 := (6 + 6)/6 + (66 × ((6 + 6)/6 + 6 + 6))
 := ((77 × (77 + 7) + 7) + 7)/7
 := 8 + (((88 + 88)/8 + 888) + 8)
 := 9 + (999 - (9/9 + 9 × 9))

► **929** := ((11 × ((1 + (1 + 11))¹⁺¹)) - 1)/(1 + 1)
 := 2/2 + (2 × 222 + 22²)
 := 3³ + ((33 × 3³) + 33/3)
 := (4 × (4⁴ + 4)) - 444/4
 := 5 + ((5 × (5 - 5 × 5)) + (5 - 5/5)⁵)
 := 66 + ((6 × (6 + 6) × (6 + 6)) - 6/6)
 := 7 + ((77 × (77 + 7) - (7 + 7))/7)
 := 8/8 + (8 × 8 × (8 + 8) - (88 + 8))
 := 99/9 + (999 - 9 × 9)

► **932** := (1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × (11 + (1 + 1) × 111))
 := 2 × (2 × 222 + 22)
 := (3 × 333) - (((3/3 + 3)³) + 3)
 := 4 + (4 × (4⁴ - ((4 × 4 + 4) + 4)))
 := 5⁵/5 + (5⁵ - 55)/(5 + 5)
 := 66 + ((6 × (6 + 6) × (6 + 6)) + ((6 + 6)/6))
 := 7 + ((77 × (77 + 7) + 7)/7)
 := 888 + (88/((8 + 8)/8))
 := 9 × 99 + ((9 × 9 × 9 + 9)/(9 + 9))

► **927** := 1 + ((1 + 11111)/(1 + 11))
 := 2 + ((2 × (22² - 22)) + 2/2)
 := 3 + ((33 × 3³) + 33)
 := (4 × (4⁴ - 4)) - (4 - 4/4)⁴
 := (5 × (55 + 5)) + (5⁵ + 5 + 5)/5
 := 66 + (((6 × 6/(6 + 6))⁶ + 66) + 66)
 := (((77 × (77 + 7) + 7) + 7) + 7)/7
 := (8/8 + 8) × (888/8 - 8)
 := 9 + (999 - 9 × 9)

► **930** := (11 - 1) × (((1 + 1)¹¹⁻¹ - 1)/11)
 := 2 + (2 × 222 + 22²)
 := 3 + (((33 × 3³) + 33) + 3)
 := (4 × (4⁴ + 4)) + ((4 - 444)/4)
 := 5 + ((5 × (55 + 5)) + 5⁵/5)
 := 66 + (6 × (6 + 6) × (6 + 6))
 := 7 + ((77 × (77 + 7) - 7)/7)
 := (8 - 8/8 + 8) × (8 × 8 - ((8 + 8)/8))
 := 9 + (9 × (9 × 9 + 9) + 999/9)

► **933** := 1 + ((1 + 1) × ((1 + 1) × (11 + (1 + 1) × 111)))
 := 2/2 + (2 × (2 × 222 + 22))
 := 3 × 3 + ((33 × 3³) + 33)
 := 4 + ((4 × (4⁴ + 4)) - 444/4)
 := 5⁵/5 + ((5⁵ + 5)/(5 + 5) - 5)
 := 6 × 6 × 6 + (((6 × 6/(6 + 6))⁶ - (6 + 6))
 := 7 + (((77 × (77 + 7) + 7) + 7)/7)
 := 8 × 8 + (888 - (88/8 + 8))
 := 9 + ((99/((9 + 9 + 9)/9)) + 9 × 99)

► **934** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (1 + (1 + (1 + 1111)))$
 := $2 + (2 \times (2 \times 222 + 22))$
 := $3^{3+3} + ((3 + 3)^3 - 33/3)$
 := $(4444 - 4)/4 - (4 \times 44)$
 := $(55 \times (((55 + 5)/5) + 5)) - 5/5$
 := $((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)) - (6 + 6)/6$
 := $(7 \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7)) - 77/7$
 := $8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8) - ((8 + 8)/8 + 88)$
 := $9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^{9/9+9}) - 99$

► **937** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - 1111$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times (22^2 - 2^{2+2}))$
 := $3/3 + ((3 \times 3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3))$
 := $4/4 + (4 \times 4^4 - (44 + 44))$
 := $5^5/5 + (5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6))$
 := $7 + (((77 \times (77 + 7) - 7)/7) + 7)$
 := $8/8 + (8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8) - 88)$
 := $9 + (((999 - 9 \times 9) + 9/9) + 9)$

► **940** := $1 + (1 + (1 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - 1111)))$
 := $2 \times ((22^2 - 2^{2+2}) + 2)$
 := $3/3 + ((3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 33)$
 := $(4 \times (4^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4))) - 4$
 := $5 + (55 \times (((55 + 5)/5) + 5))$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)) - ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $7 + (((77 \times (77 + 7) + 7) + 7)/7) + 7$
 := $8 + ((88/((8 + 8)/8)) + 888)$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((9 \times 99 - 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **935** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (1 + (1 + 1111))$
 := $22/2 + (2 \times (22^2 - 22))$
 := $(3 \times 333) - ((3/3 + 3)^3)$
 := $44/4 \times ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4)$
 := $55 \times (((55 + 5)/5) + 5)$
 := $((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)) - 6/6$
 := $77/7 \times (7/7 + 77 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8) - (8/8 + 88)$
 := $9 + ((999 - (9/9 + 9 \times 9)) + 9)$

► **938** := $1 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - 1111)$
 := $2 + (2 \times (22^2 - 2^{2+2}))$
 := $3 + ((3 \times 333) - ((3/3 + 3)^3))$
 := $4 + ((4444 - 4)/4 - (4 \times 44))$
 := $5^5/5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6))$
 := $7 + (7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7 + 7))$
 := $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8) - 88)$
 := $9 + (((99/9) - 9 \times 9) + 999)$

► **941** := $1111 - (1 + ((1 + (1 + 11))^{1+1}))$
 := $(2 \times (22^2 - 2)) - (22 + 2/2)$
 := $3^{3+3} + ((3 + 3)^3 - (3/3 + 3))$
 := $4/4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4))) - 4)$
 := $5 + ((55 \times (((55 + 5)/5) + 5)) + 5/5)$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)) - 6/6)$
 := $7 + ((7 \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7)) - (77/7))$
 := $8 \times 8 + (888 - 88/8)$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((9 \times 99 + 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **936** := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - (1 + 1111)$
 := $2 \times (22^2 - 2^{2+2})$
 := $(3 \times 3 + 3) \times (3 \times 3^3 - 3)$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - (44 + 44)$
 := $5/5 + (55 \times (((55 + 5)/5) + 5))$
 := $(6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)$
 := $(77 + 7)/7 \times (7/7 + 77)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8) - 88$
 := $9 + ((999 - 9 \times 9) + 9)$

► **939** := $1 + (1 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - 1111))$
 := $((2/2 + 2)^2 + 22)^2 - 22$
 := $(3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 33$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4)$
 := $(5^5 + 5)/5 + (5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) - 6)$
 := $7 + (((77 \times (77 + 7) + 7)/7) + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 + 888 - (88 + 8 + 8)/8$
 := $99 + (999/9 + 9 \times 9 \times 9)$

► **942** := $1111 - ((1 + (1 + 11))^{1+1})$
 := $(2 \times (22^2 - 2)) - 22$
 := $3^{3+3} + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3)$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - ((4 - 4/4)^4 + 4/4)$
 := $5 + ((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 5^5/5)$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6))$
 := $7 + (77/7 \times (7/7 + 77 + 7))$
 := $8 \times 8 + ((8 - 88)/8 + 888)$
 := $(9 \times (99 + 9 + 9)) - 999/9$

► **943** := $1 + (1111 - ((1 + (1 + 11))^{1+1}))$
 := $2/2 + ((2 \times (22^2 - 2)) - 22)$
 := $3/3 + (((3 + 3)^3 - 3) + 3^{3+3})$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - (4 - 4/4)^4$
 := $5 + ((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 5^5/5)$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)) + 6/6)$
 := $7 + ((77 + 7)/7 \times (7/7 + 77))$
 := $8 \times 8 + (888 - (8/8 + 8))$
 := $((9 + 9)/9)^{9/9+9} - 9 \times 9$

► **946** := $(1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - 11)$
 := $(2 \times 22^2) - 22$
 := $3/3 + (3^{3+3} + (3 + 3)^3)$
 := $(44 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4))/(4 + 4)$
 := $55/5 \times (555/5 - 5 \times 5)$
 := $6/6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6 \times 6 \times 6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7))$
 := $88/8 \times (88 - ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $9 \times 9 \times (9 + 9) - (((9 + 9)/9)^9)$

► **949** := $1 + (11 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - 1111))$
 := $2 + (((2 \times 22^2) - 22) + 2/2)$
 := $3 + ((3^{3+3} + (3 + 3)^3) + 3/3)$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - ((44 + 4^4)/4)$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5))$
 := $(6/6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 6/6 + 6)$
 := $7 + ((77/7 \times (7/7 + 77 + 7)) + 7)$
 := $(8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8)) - 88/8$
 := $9999/9 - 9 \times (9 + 9)$

► **944** := $(1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - (1 + 11))$
 := $(2 \times 22^2) - (22 + 2)$
 := $3^{3+3} + ((3 + 3)^3 - 3/3)$
 := $4 \times (4^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4))$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (5 \times 5 + 55)$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)) + ((6 + 6)/6))$
 := $(7/7 + 7) \times (777/7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 + 888 - 8$
 := $999 + ((9 - 999)/(9 + 9))$

► **947** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - 11))$
 := $2/2 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 22)$
 := $3 + ((3^{3+3} - 3/3) + (3 + 3)^3)$
 := $4 + (4 \times 4^4 - (4 - 4/4)^4)$
 := $5 + (((5^5 - 5)/(5 + 5) + 5^5/5) + 5)$
 := $66/6 + ((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6))$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + (7 \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7))$
 := $88/8 + (8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8) - 88)$
 := $9 \times 99 + ((999 + 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **950** := $((1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))^{1+1}) - 11$
 := $(2 \times (22^2 + 2)) - 22$
 := $3 + (((3^{3+3} - 3/3) + (3 + 3)^3) + 3)$
 := $4 + ((44 \times ((4 \times 44) - 4))/(4 + 4))$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5)$
 := $(6 \times 6 - (66/6)) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 6)$
 := $77 \times (7 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7)^7$
 := $8 \times 8 + (888 - ((8 + 8)/8))$
 := $999 + ((9 - 9 \times 99)/(9 + 9))$

► **945** := $((1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - 11)) - 1$
 := $(2 \times 22^2) - (22 + 2/2)$
 := $3^{3+3} + (3 + 3)^3$
 := $4/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4)))$
 := $(5 \times (5 \times (55 + 5))) - 555$
 := $6 \times 6 \times 6 + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6)$
 := $7 \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7)$
 := $8/8 + ((888 - 8) + 8 \times 8)$
 := $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - (9 + 9 + 9)$

► **948** := $11 + (((1 + 1)^{11}) - 1111)$
 := $2 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 22)$
 := $3 + (3^{3+3} + (3 + 3)^3)$
 := $4 + (4 \times (4^4 - (4 \times 4 + 4)))$
 := $5 + (((5^5 + 5)/(5 + 5) + 5^5/5) + 5)$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)) + 6)$
 := $(77 + 7)/7 \times ((7 + 7)/7 + 77)$
 := $8 \times 8 + (888 - (8/((8 + 8)/8)))$
 := $((99 + 9)/9) \times (9 \times 9 - ((9 + 9)/9))$

► **951** := $1 + (((1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))^{1+1}) - 11)$
 := $2/2 + ((2 \times (22^2 + 2)) - 22)$
 := $3 + ((3^{3+3} + (3 + 3)^3) + 3)$
 := $4 + ((4 \times 4^4 - (4 - 4/4)^4) + 4)$
 := $5/5 + ((5 + 5) \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5))$
 := $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6 \times 6 \times 6)$
 := $7 + ((7/7 + 7) \times (777/7 + 7))$
 := $8 \times 8 + (888 - 8/8)$
 := $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - (((99 + 9)/9) + 9)$

<p>► 952 := $(1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1))$:= $2 \times (22^2 - 2 \times (2 + 2))$:= $(3^3 + 3/3) \times (3/3 + 33)$:= $(4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) - 4 - 4$:= $(5 - 5/5) \times (((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5) - 5)$:= $6 \times 66 + (6666 + 6)/(6 + 6)$:= $7 + (7 \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7))$:= $8 \times 8 + 888$:= $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - (99/9 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 955 := $1111 - ((1 + 11) \times (1 + (1 + 11)))$:= $(2 \times 22^2) - (22/2 + 2)$:= $(33 \times 3^3) + ((3/3 + 3)^3)$:= $4 \times 4^4 - ((4^4 + 4)/4 + 4)$:= $5 + ((5 + 5) \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5))$:= $((6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6)^{(6+6)/6} - 6$:= $7 + ((77 + 7)/7 \times ((7 + 7)/7 + 77))$:= $8 \times 8 + (888 - 8 + 88/8)$:= $9/9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - (9 + 9))$</p>	<p>► 958 := $1 + (11 \times (111 - ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11))))$:= $(2 \times (22^2 - (2 + 2))) - 2$:= $3 + ((33 \times 3^3) + ((3/3 + 3)^3))$:= $4 \times 4^4 - (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4)$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (55/5 + 55)$:= $((6 + 6)/6)^{(66-6)/6} - 66$:= $(77 \times 77 + 777)/7$:= $(8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8)) - (8 + 8)/8$:= $9 + (9999/9 - 9 \times (9 + 9))$</p>
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<p>► 953 := $1 + ((1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \times (11^{1+1} - (1 + 1)))$:= $(2 \times (22^2 - 2)) - 22/2$:= $((3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3)) - 3/3$:= $4 + (4 \times 4^4 - ((44 + 4^4)/4))$:= $55 + ((5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 + 5 \times 55)$:= $6 + (((6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)) + (66/6))$:= $7 + ((7 \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7)) + 7/7)$:= $8/8 + (888 + 8 \times 8)$:= $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - (9/9 + 9 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 956 := $1111 - (11 + ((1 + 11)^{1+1}))$:= $2 \times (22^2 - (2 + 2 + 2))$:= $3^{3+3} + ((3 + 3)^3 + 33/3)$:= $(4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) - 4$:= $55 + ((5^5 + 5)/5 + 5 \times 55)$:= $6 + ((6 \times 6 - (66/6)) \times (((6 + 6)/6) + 6 \times 6))$:= $77/7 + (7 \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7))$:= $(88 \times 88 - (88 + 8))/8$:= $(9 + 9)/9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - (9 + 9))$</p>	<p>► 959 := $((1 + 1)^{11}) - ((11 \times (1 + 1 + 1))^{1+1})$:= $2 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 22/2)$:= $((3^3 + 3) \times (33 - 3/3)) - 3/3$:= $4 \times 4^4 - (4^4 + 4)/4$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5 + 5)$:= $(6/6 + 6) \times ((66 - 6/6 + 66) + 6)$:= $77 + 7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7)$:= $(8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8)) - 8/8$:= $999 + ((9 - 9 \times 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))$</p>
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<p>► 954 := $(11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - (1 + (1 + (1 + 1 + 1))))$:= $2 + (2 \times (22^2 - 2 \times (2 + 2)))$:= $(3 + 3) \times ((3 + 3) \times 3^3 - 3)$:= $4 \times 4^4 - (((4^4 + 4) + 4)/4) + 4$:= $5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - (5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)))$:= $666 + 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6)$:= $7 \times 7 + (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 777)$:= $8 \times 8 + (888 + ((8 + 8)/8))$:= $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - (9 + 9)$</p>	<p>► 957 := $11 \times (111 - ((1 + 1) \times (1 + 11)))$:= $(2 \times 22^2) - 22/2$:= $33 \times ((3^3 - 3/3) + 3)$:= $4/4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) - 4)$:= $55/5 \times (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 55)$:= $6 + (((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6) + 6 \times 6 \times 6) + 6$:= $7 + (77 \times (7 + 7) - ((7 + 7)/7)^7)$:= $88/8 \times (88 - 8/8)$:= $99/9 \times (99 - ((99 + 9)/9))$</p>	<p>► 960 := $(1 + 11) \times ((11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1} - 1)$:= $2 \times (22^2 - (2 + 2))$:= $(3^3 + 3) \times (33 - 3/3)$:= $4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)$:= $(5 \times 5 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5$:= $(6 - 66) \times (((6 - 66)/6) - 6)$:= $7/7 + (7 \times (77 + 7 \times 7) + 77)$:= $8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8)$:= $(9 - 9/9) \times (999/9 + 9)$</p>
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<p>► 961 := $(1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))^{1+1}$:= $((2/2 + 2)^2 + 22)^2$:= $((3^3 + 3/3) + 3)^{3-3/3}$:= $4/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4))$:= $((5 \times 5 + 5/5) + 5)^{(5+5)/5}$:= $((6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6)^{(6+6)/6}$:= $(7 \times 7 - (77/7 + 7))^{(7+7)/7}$:= $8/8 + (8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8))$:= $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - 99/9$</p>	<p>► 964 := $(1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - (1 + 1))$:= $2 \times (22^2 - 2)$:= $((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - (33 + 3)$:= $4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4))$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5)$:= $6 + (((6 + 6)/6)^{(66-6)/6}) - 66$:= $7777/7 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)$:= $8 + ((88 \times 88 - (88 + 8))/8)$:= $9/9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9)$</p>	<p>► 967 := $1111 - ((1 + 11)^{1+1})$:= $(2 \times 22^2) - 2/2$:= $((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - 33$:= $((44 \times (44 + 44)) - 4)/4$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 + 5)/5 + 55)$:= $6 + (((6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6)^{(6+6)/6})$:= $77 \times (7 + 7) - 777/7$:= $(88 \times 88 - 8)/8$:= $(9 \times (99 + 9)) + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))$</p>
<p>► 962 := $1 + ((1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))^{1+1})$:= $(2 \times (22^2 - 2)) - 2$:= $(33 \times 3^3) + (((3 + 3)^3 - 3)/3)$:= $(4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4))$:= $(5 \times 5 + 5/5) \times (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5)$:= $6/6 + (((6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6)^{(6+6)/6})$:= $(7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (77/7 + 7)$:= $(8 + 8)/8 + (8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8))$:= $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9/9 - 9$</p>	<p>► 965 := $((1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - 1)) - 1$:= $2/2 + (2 \times (22^2 - 2))$:= $(3 \times 333) - (3/3 + 33)$:= $4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) + 4/4)$:= $5 + ((5 \times 5 + 5) \times ((5 + 5)/5)^5)$:= $66 + ((6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6)) - 6/6)$:= $7 + ((77 \times 77 + 777)/7)$:= $8 + (88/8 \times (88 - 8/8))$:= $(9 + 9)/9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9)$</p>	<p>► 968 := $(1 + 1) \times ((11 + 11)^{1+1})$:= 2×22^2 := $(3/3 + 3) \times ((3^{3+3} - 3)/3)$:= $4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4)) + 4)$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5/5)$:= $(66/6) \times (((66 + 66)/6) + 66)$:= $(7/7 + 7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7)$:= $88 \times (88/8)$:= $99/9 \times (99 - (99/9))$</p>
<p>► 963 := $1 + (1 + ((1 + ((11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)))^{1+1}))$:= $(2 \times (22^2 - 2)) - 2/2$:= $3 \times (333 - (3 \times 3 + 3))$:= $4 + (4 \times 4^4 - (4^4 + 4)/4)$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - ((55 + 5/5) + 5)$:= $6 \times 6 \times 6 \times 6 - 666 \times 6/(6 + 6)$:= $7 + ((7 \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 + 7)) + (77/7))$:= $8 \times 8 + (888 + 88/8)$:= $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9$</p>	<p>► 966 := $(1 + 1) \times (((11 + 11)^{1+1}) - 1)$:= $(2 \times 22^2) - 2$:= $(3 \times 333) - 33$:= $(44 \times 44 - 4)/((4 + 4)/4)$:= $5 + (((5 \times 5 + 5/5) + 5)^{(5+5)/5})$:= $66 + (6 \times ((6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6))$:= $(7 + 7) \times (77 - (7/7 + 7))$:= $(88 \times 88 - (8 + 8))/8$:= $999 - (99/((9 + 9 + 9)/9))$</p>	<p>► 969 := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times ((11 + 11)^{1+1}))$:= $2/2 + (2 \times 22^2)$:= $(3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 3$:= $4 \times 4^4 - (44/4 + 44)$:= $(5 - 5/5)^5 - 55$:= $(6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) - 666/6$:= $(7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 77/7$:= $(88 \times 88 + 8)/8$:= $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$</p>

► **970** := $(1 + 1) \times (1 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + (2 \times 22^2)$
 := $3 + (((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - 33)$
 := $(44 \times 44 + 4)/((4 + 4)/4)$
 := $5/5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - 55)$
 := $((6 - 666)/6) + (6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6 - 6))$
 := $((7 - 77)/7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)$
 := $((88 \times 88 + 8) + 8)/8$
 := $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - (9 + 9)/9$

► **973** := $1 + ((1 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2))$
 := $3/3 + (3^3 \times (33 + 3))$
 := $4 + (4 \times 4^4 - (44/4 + 44))$
 := $5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5/5))$
 := $6/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6)))$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7$
 := $8 + ((88/8 \times (88 - 8/8)) + 8)$
 := $9/9 + (9 \times (99 + 9))$

► **976** := $(1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \times (1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times (22^2 + 2 + 2)$
 := $3 + ((3^3 \times (33 + 3)) + 3/3)$
 := $4 \times ((4^4 - 4 \times 4) + 4)$
 := $5 + (((5 - 5/5)^{5/5+5}) - 5^5)$
 := $((6 + 6)/6 + 6) \times ((666 + 66)/6)$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (77/7))$
 := $88 + 888$
 := $999 - ((99 + 99 + 9)/9)$

► **971** := $1 + ((1 + 1) \times (1 + ((11 + 11)^{1+1})))$
 := $2 + ((2 \times 22^2) + 2/2)$
 := $(3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 3/3$
 := $44/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 \times 4))$
 := $((5 - 5/5)^{5/5+5}) - 5^5$
 := $((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) - 6/6$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - ((7 + 7)/7 + 7)$
 := $88/8 + (8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) - 8))$
 := $(9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9/9$

► **974** := $1 + (1 + ((1 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}))$
 := $2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2))$
 := $3 + ((3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 3/3)$
 := $4 + ((44 \times 44 + 4)/((4 + 4)/4))$
 := $5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - 55)$
 := $(6 + 6)/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6)))$
 := $7/7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7)$
 := $8 + ((88 \times 88 - (8 + 8))/8)$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + (9 \times (99 + 9))$

► **977** := $1 + (1 + 1)^{1+1+1} \times (1 + 11^{1+1})$
 := $2/2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2 + 2))$
 := $3 + (((3^3 \times (33 + 3)) - 3/3) + 3)$
 := $4/4 + (4 \times ((4^4 - 4 \times 4) + 4))$
 := $5 + ((5 - 5/5) \times ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5))$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) - 6/6)$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + ((88 \times 88 + 8)/8)$
 := $999 - ((99 + 99)/9)$

► **972** := $(1 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1}$
 := $2 \times (22^2 + 2)$
 := $3^3 \times (33 + 3)$
 := $4 \times ((4 - 4/4)^{4+4/4})$
 := $(5 - 5/5) \times ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5)$
 := $(6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (7/7 + 7)$
 := $88 + (888 - (8/((8 + 8)/8)))$
 := $9 \times (99 + 9)$

► **975** := $111 + (((1 + 11)^{1+1+1})/(1 + 1))$
 := $2 + ((2 \times (22^2 + 2)) + 2/2)$
 := $3 + (3^3 \times (33 + 3))$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - ((44 + 4/4) + 4)$
 := $5 \times ((5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)) - 55)$
 := $666/6 + (6 \times (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6))$
 := $7 + ((7/7 + 7) \times (((7 + 7)/7)^7 - 7))$
 := $8 + ((88 \times 88 - 8)/8)$
 := $(9 \times (99 + 9)) + ((9 + 9 + 9)/9)$

► **978** := $1111 - (1 + 11 \times (1 + 11))$
 := $2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2 + 2))$
 := $3 + ((3^3 \times (33 + 3)) + 3)$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - ((4 + 4)/4 + 44)$
 := $5 + (((5 - 5/5)^5 - (55 + 5/5)) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6)))$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - (7 + 7)/7$
 := $8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8) + 8)/8)$
 := $999 - (((99 + 9)/9) + 9)$

► **979** := $11 \times (111 - 11 - 11)$
 := $22/2 + (2 \times 22^2)$
 := $(3 \times (333 - 3)) - 33/3$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - (44 + 4/4)$
 := $5 + (((5 - 5/5)^5 - 55) + 5)$
 := $(6666/6) - (66 + 66)$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7/7$
 := $88/8 \times (8/8 + 88)$
 := $999 - (99/9 + 9)$

► **982** := $1 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 + (2 \times ((22^2 + 2 + 2) + 2))$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times (333 - (3 + 3)))$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 44)$
 := $5 + (((5 - 5/5) \times ((5 - (5 + 5)/5)^5)) + 5)$
 := $((6 + 6)/6)^{(66-6)/6} - (6 \times 6 + 6)$
 := $((7 + 7)/7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)$
 := $8 + (((88 \times 88 - (8 + 8))/8) + 8)$
 := $9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) + 9/9)$

► **985** := $1 + (1 + 11) \times (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 + ((2 \times (22^2 + 2)) + 22/2)$
 := $(3 \times 333) - (33/3 + 3)$
 := $4 + ((4 \times 4^4 - 44) + 4/4)$
 := $5 + ((5 \times ((5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)) - 55)) + 5)$
 := $6 + ((6666/6) - (66 + 66))$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8)/8) + 8)$
 := $9 \times 9 \times 9 + (((9 + 9)/9)^{9-9/9})$

► **980** := $1 + 11 \times (111 - 11 - 11)$
 := $2 \times ((22^2 + 2 + 2) + 2)$
 := $(3 \times (333 - (3 + 3))) - 3/3$
 := $4 \times 4^4 - 44$
 := $5 + (5 \times ((5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)) - 55))$
 := $(6 \times 6 - 6/6) \times (((66 + 66)/6) + 6)$
 := $(7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)$
 := $((88 \times 88 + 88) + 8)/8$
 := $9 + ((9 \times (99 + 9)) - 9/9)$

► **983** := $1 + 1 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1)$
 := $22/2 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2))$
 := $33/3 + (3^3 \times (33 + 3))$
 := $4 + 4 \times 4^4 - (44 + 4/4)$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - ((55/5 + 5 \times 5) + 5)$
 := $66/6 + ((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6)))$
 := $((7 + 7 + 7)/7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)$
 := $8 + (((88 \times 88 - 8)/8) + 8)$
 := $99/9 + (9 \times (99 + 9))$

► **986** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1 - 11$
 := $22 + (2 \times (22^2 - 2))$
 := $(3 \times (333 - 3)) - (3/3 + 3)$
 := $4 + (((4 + 4)/4 - 44) + 4 \times 4^4)$
 := $(5555/5) - 5 \times 5 \times 5$
 := $((66/6) + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6)$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7/7)$
 := $8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8) + 8)/8) + 8$
 := $999 - ((99 + 9 + 9)/9)$

► **981** := $(11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1)$
 := $2 + ((2 \times 22^2) + 22/2)$
 := $3 \times (333 - (3 + 3))$
 := $4/4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 44)$
 := $(5555/5) - (5 \times 5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6) + ((6 \times 6/(6 + 6))^6)$
 := $7/7 + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)$
 := $(8/8 + 8) \times ((888 - (8 + 8))/8)$
 := $9 + (9 \times (99 + 9))$

► **984** := $(1 + 11) \times (1 + (11 - 1 - 1)^{1+1})$
 := $2 \times (2 \times (2 + 2) + 22^2)$
 := $3 + (3 \times (333 - (3 + 3)))$
 := $4 + (4 \times 4^4 - 44)$
 := $5 + (((5 - 5/5)^5 - 55) + 5) + 5)$
 := $6 + (((6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - (6 + 6))) + 6)$
 := $77/7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7)$
 := $8 + (888 + 88)$
 := $(9 \times (99 + 9)) + (99 + 9)/9$

► **987** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 - 11$
 := $22 + ((2 \times (22^2 - 2)) + 2/2)$
 := $(3 \times (333 - 3)) - 3$
 := $(4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - (4/4 + 4)$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (((5 + 5)/5)^5 + 5)$
 := $((66 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) - 6)/((6 + 6)/6)$
 := $7 + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)$
 := $8 + (88/8 \times (8/8 + 88))$
 := $999 - (99 + 9)/9$

► **988** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 11$
 := $22 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 2)$
 := $(3 \times 333) - 33/3$
 := $(4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - 4$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (55/5 + 5 \times 5)$
 := $((6 + 6)/6)^{(66-6)/6} - 6 \times 6$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7/7)$
 := $8 + (((88 \times 88 + 88) + 8)/8)$
 := $999 - 99/9$

► **991** := $1 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)$
 := $22 + ((2 \times 22^2) + 2/2)$
 := $3/3 + (3 \times (333 - 3))$
 := $(4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - 4/4$
 := $5 + ((5555/5) - 5 \times 5 \times 5)$
 := $6/6 + ((6 \times (66 - (6 + 6))) + 666)$
 := $77/7 + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)$
 := $888 + (888/8 - 8)$
 := $9/9 + (999 - 9)$

► **994** := $(1 + 1)^{11-1} - (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)$
 := $22 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2))$
 := $((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - (3 + 3)$
 := $(4 + 4)/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4))$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - (5 \times 5 + 5)$
 := $((66 - 6)/6)^{6 \times 6 / (6+6)} - 6$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7)$
 := $8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8) + 8)/8 + 8) + 8$
 := $999 + ((9 - 99)/(9 + 9))$

► **989** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 11$
 := $22 + ((2 \times 22^2) - 2/2)$
 := $(3 \times (333 - 3)) - 3/3$
 := $4/4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - 4)$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 \times 5 + 5) + 5)$
 := $666 + ((6 \times (66 - (6 + 6))) - 6/6)$
 := $7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) + ((7 + 7)/7))$
 := $888 + (8888/88)$
 := $999 - 9/9 - 9$

► **992** := $1 + 1 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)$
 := $2 + ((2 \times 22^2) + 22)$
 := $3 + ((3 \times (333 - 3)) - 3/3)$
 := $4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5$
 := $6 + (((66/6) + 6) \times (((6 + 6)/6)^6 - 6))$
 := $(77 + 7)/7 + (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)$
 := $8 + ((888 + 88) + 8)$
 := $(9 + 9)/9 + (999 - 9)$

► **995** := $(11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1$
 := $22 + ((2 \times (22^2 + 2)) + 2/2)$
 := $(3 \times 333) - (3/3 + 3)$
 := $4 + ((4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - 4/4)$
 := $(5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) - 5$
 := $666 + (6 \times 66 - (66 + 6/6))$
 := $7 + (((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7/7) + 7)$
 := $8 + ((88/8 \times (8/8 + 88)) + 8)$
 := $999 + ((9 - 9 \times 9)/(9 + 9))$

► **990** := $(11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)$
 := $22 + (2 \times 22^2)$
 := $3 \times (333 - 3)$
 := $(4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4)) - (4 + 4)/4$
 := $(5 + 5) \times (5 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5/5)$
 := $6 \times ((66 \times (6 \times 6 - 6))/(6 + 6))$
 := $77/7 \times ((77 - 7/7 + 7) + 7)$
 := $88/8 \times ((8 + 8)/8 + 88)$
 := $999 - 9$

► **993** := $1 + 1 + 1 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)$
 := $2 + (((2 \times 22^2) + 22) + 2/2)$
 := $3 + (3 \times (333 - 3))$
 := $4/4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4))$
 := $(5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 \times 5 + 5/5) + 5)$
 := $((66 \times (6 \times 6 - 6)) + 6)/((6 + 6)/6)$
 := $7 + (((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7/7) + 7)$
 := $8 + (((88 \times 88 + 8)/8) + 8) + 8$
 := $999 + (((9 + 9 + 9)/9) - 9)$

► **996** := $(1 + 1 + 1) \times ((1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1)$
 := $2 + ((2 \times (22^2 + 2)) + 22)$
 := $(3 \times 333) - 3$
 := $4 + (4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4))$
 := $5/5 + ((5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5)) - 5)$
 := $(6 + 6) \times (66/6 + 66 + 6)$
 := $(77 + 7)/7 \times (77 - 7/7 + 7)$
 := $8 \times 8 \times 8 + 88 \times 88/(8 + 8)$
 := $999 - (9 + 9 + 9)/9$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{997} := (11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - (1 + 1 + 1)$$

$$:= ((2/2 + 2)^2 \times 222/2) - 2$$

$$:= ((3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3) - 3$$

$$:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4)) - 44/4$$

$$:= 5 + ((5 - 5/5)^5 - ((5 + 5)/5)^5)$$

$$:= 6 \times 6 + (((6 \times 6 - 6) + 6/6)^{(6+6)/6})$$

$$:= (((77 + 7)^{(7+7)/7}) - 77)/7$$

$$:= 888 + ((888 - (8 + 8))/8)$$

$$:= 999 - (9 + 9)/9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{999} := 111 \times (11 - 1 - 1)$$

$$:= (2/2 + 2)^2 \times 222/2$$

$$:= 3 \times 333$$

$$:= ((4/4 + 4) + 4) \times 444/4$$

$$:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - 5 \times 5$$

$$:= (6 \times 666)/(6 - ((6 + 6)/6))$$

$$:= ((7 + 7)/7 + 7) \times 777/7$$

$$:= 888 + 888/8$$

$$:= 999$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{1000} := (11 - 1)^{1+1+1}$$

$$:= 2 \times (2^{2+2} + 22^2)$$

$$:= (3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3$$

$$:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4)) - 4 - 4$$

$$:= 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5)$$

$$:= ((66 - 6)/6)^{6 \times 6 / (6+6)}$$

$$:= ((77 - 7)/7)^{(7+7+7)/7}$$

$$:= 8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8) - 8 - 8 - 8$$

$$:= 9/9 + 999$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{998} := (11 - 1)^{1+1+1} - 1 - 1$$

$$:= 22 + (2 \times (22^2 + 2 + 2))$$

$$:= (3 \times 333) - 3/3$$

$$:= (4 \times (4^4 - 4)) + (4 - 44)/4$$

$$:= (5 - 5/5)^5 - (5 \times 5 + 5/5)$$

$$:= 666 + (6 \times 66 - ((6 + 6)/6)^6)$$

$$:= 7 + ((7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) + (77/7))$$

$$:= 888 + ((888 - 8)/8)$$

$$:= 999 - 9/9$$